

MPAS-Seaice Model User's Guide

Version: 6.0

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Foreword

MPAS-Seaice is an unstructured-mesh sea-ice model that uses the Modeling for Prediction Across Scales (MPAS) framework, allowing enhanced horizontal resolution in regions of interest. MPAS-Seaice uses many of the methods used in the Los Alamos CICE sea-ice model, but adapted to the Spherical Centroidal Voronoi Tessellation (SCVT) meshes used by the MPAS framework. MPAS-Seaice is one component within the MPAS framework of climate model components that is developed in cooperation between Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) and the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR). A full description and validation of MPAS-Seaice is currently in review with the Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems (JAMES) and is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1194374>.

A history of releases of the sea-ice core within the MPAS version numbering scheme is as follows:

version	date	description
6.0	April 17, 2018	Initial public release of MPAS-Seaice

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Part I

The MPAS Framework

Chapter 1

MPAS Framework Overview

The MPAS Framework provides the foundation for a generalized geophysical fluid dynamics model on unstructured spherical and planar meshes. On top of the framework, implementations specific to the modeling of a particular physical system (e.g., land ice, ocean) are created as MPAS *cores*. To date, MPAS cores for atmosphere (Skamarock et al., 2012), ocean (Ringler et al., 2013; Petersen et al., 2015, 2018), shallow water (Ringler et al., 2011), sea ice (Turner et al., 2018), and land ice (Hoffman et al., 2018) have been implemented. The MPAS design philosophy is to leverage the efforts of developers from the various MPAS cores to provide common framework functionality with minimal effort, allowing MPAS core developers to focus on development of the physics and features relevant to their application.

The framework code includes shared modules for fundamental model operation. Significant capabilities include:

- *Description of model data types.* MPAS uses a handful of fundamental Fortran derived types for basic model functionality. Core-specific model variables are handled through custom groupings of model fields called *pools*, for which custom accessor routines exist. Core-specific variables are easily defined in XML syntax in a *Registry*, and the framework parses the Registry, defines variables, and allocates memory as needed.
- *Description of the mesh specification.* MPAS requires 36 fields to fully describe the mesh used in a simulation. These include the position, area, orientation, and connectivity of all cells, edges, and vertices in the mesh. The mesh specification can flexibly describe both spherical and planar meshes. More details are provided in the next section.
- *Distributed memory parallelization and domain decomposition.* The MPAS Framework provides needed routines for exchanging information between processors in a parallel environment using Message Passing Interface (MPI). This includes halo updates, global reductions, and global broadcasts. MPAS also supports decomposing multiple domain blocks on each processor to, for example, optimize model performance by minimizing transfer of data from disk to memory. Shared memory parallelization through OpenMP is also supported, but the implementation is left up to each core.
- *Parallel input and output capabilities.* MPAS performs parallel input and output of data from and to disk through the commonly used libraries of NetCDF, Parallel NetCDF (pnetcdf), and Parallel Input/Output (PIO) (Dennis et al., 2012). The Registry definitions control which fields can be input and/or output, and a framework *streams* functionality provides easy run-time configuration of what fields are to be written to what file name and at what frequency

through an XML streams file. The MPAS framework includes additional functionality specific to providing a flexible model restart capability.

- *Advanced timekeeping.* MPAS uses a customized version of the timekeeping functionality of the Earth System Modeling Framework (ESMF), which includes a robust set of time and calendar tools used by many Earth System Models (ESMs). This allows explicit definition of model epochs in terms of years, months, days, hours, minutes, seconds, and fractional seconds and can be set to three different calendar types: Gregorian, Gregorian no leap, and 360 day. This flexibility helps enable multi-scale physics and simplifies coupling to ESMs. To manage the complex date/time types that ensue, MPAS framework provides routines for arithmetic of time intervals and the definition of alarm objects for handling events (e.g., when to write output, when the simulation should end).
- *Run-time configurable control of model options.* Model options are configured through *namelist* files that use standard Fortran namelist file format, and input/output are configured through *streams* files that use XML format. Both are completely adjustable at run time.
- *Online, run-time analysis framework.* A system for defining analysis of model states during run time, reducing the need for post-processing and model output.

Additionally, a number of shared operators exist to perform common operations on model data. These include geometric operations (e.g., length, area, and angle operations on the sphere or the plane), interpolation (linear, barycentric, Wachspress, radial basis functions, spline), vector and tensor operations (e.g., cross products, divergence), and vector reconstruction (e.g., interpolating from cell edges to cell centers). Most operators work on both spherical and planar meshes.

Chapter 2

Building MPAS

2.1 Prerequisites

To build MPAS, compatible C and Fortran compilers are required. Additionally, the MPAS software relies on the PIO parallel I/O library to read and write model fields, and the PIO library requires the standard netCDF library as well as the parallel-netCDF library from Argonne National Labs. All libraries must be compiled with the same compilers that will be used to build MPAS. Section 2.2 summarizes the basic procedure of installing the required I/O libraries for MPAS.

In order for the MPAS makefiles to find the PIO, parallel-netCDF, and netCDF include files and libraries, the environment variables `PIO`, `PNETCDF`, and `NETCDF` should be set to the root installation directories of the PIO, parallel-netCDF, and netCDF installations, respectively. Newer versions of the netCDF library use a separate Fortran interface library; the top-level MPAS Makefile attempts to add `-lnetcdf` to the linker flags, but some linkers require that `-lnetcdf` appear before `-lnetcdf`, in which case `-lnetcdf` will need to be manually added just before `-lnetcdf` in the specification of `LIBS` in the top-level Makefile.

An MPI installation such as MPICH or OpenMPI is also required, and there is no option to build a serial version of the MPAS executables. There is currently no support for shared-memory parallelism with OpenMP within the MPAS framework.

2.2 Compiling I/O Libraries

NOTE: It's important to note the MPAS Developers are not responsible for any of the libraries that are used within MPAS. Support for specific libraries should be taken up with the respective developer groups.

Although most recent versions of the I/O libraries should work, the most tested versions of these libraries are: netCDF 4.1.3, parallel-netCDF 1.3.1, and PIO 1.4.1. The netCDF and parallel-netCDF libraries must be installed before building PIO library.

All commands are presented for `csh`, and will not work if pasted into another shell. Please translate them to the appropriate commands in your shell.

2.2.1 netCDF

Version 4.1.3 of the netCDF library may be downloaded from http://www.unidata.ucar.edu/downloads/netcdf/netcdf-4_1_3/index.jsp. Assuming the `gfortran` and `gcc` compilers will be used, the following shell commands are generally sufficient to install netCDF.

```

> setenv FC gfortran
> setenv F77 gfortran
> setenv F90 gfortran
> setenv CC gcc
> ./configure --prefix=XXXXX --disable-dap --disable-netcdf-4 --disable-cxx
--disable-shared --enable-fortran
> make all check
> make install

```

Here, XXXXX should be replaced with the directory that will serve as the root installation directory for netCDF. *Before proceeding to compile PIO the NETCDF_PATH environment variable should be set to the netCDF root installation directory.*

Certain compilers require addition flags in the CPPFLAGS environment variable. Please refer to the netCDF installation instructions for these flags.

2.2.2 parallel-netCDF

Version 1.3.1 of the parallel-netCDF library may be downloaded from <https://trac.mcs.anl.gov/projects/parallel-netcdf/wiki/Download>. Assuming the gfortran and gcc compilers will be used, the following shell commands are generally sufficient to install parallel-netCDF.

```

> setenv MPIF90 mpif90
> setenv MPIF77 mpif90
> setenv MPICC mpicc
> ./configure --prefix=XXXXX
> make
> make install

```

Here, XXXXX should be replaced with the directory that will serve as the root installation directory for parallel-netCDF. *Before proceeding to compile PIO the PNETCDF_PATH environment variable should be set to the parallel-netCDF root installation directory.*

2.2.3 PIO

Instructions for building PIO can be found at <http://www.cesm.ucar.edu/models/pio/>. Please refer to these instructions for building PIO.

After PIO is built, and installed the PIO environment variable needs to be defined to point at the directory PIO is installed into. Older versions of PIO cannot be installed, and the PIO environment variable needs to be set to the directory where PIO was built instead.

2.3 Compiling MPAS

Before compiling MPAS, the NETCDF, PNETCDF, and PIO environment variables must be set to the library installation directories as described in the previous section. A CORE variable also needs to either be defined or passed in during the make process. If CORE is not specified, the build process will fail.

The MPAS code uses only the ‘make’ utility for compilation. Rather than employing a separate configuration step before building the code, all information about compilers, compiler flags, etc.,

is contained in the top-level `Makefile`; each supported combination of compilers (i.e., a configuration) is included in the `Makefile` as a separate make target, and the user selects among these configurations by running `make` with the name of a build target specified on the command-line, e.g.,

```
> make gfortran
```

to build the code using the GNU Fortran and C compilers. Some of the available targets are listed in the table below, and additional targets can be added by simply editing the `Makefile` in the top-level directory.

Target	Fortran compiler	C compiler	MPI wrappers
<code>xlf</code>	<code>xlf90</code>	<code>xlc</code>	<code>mpxlf90 / mpcc</code>
<code>pgi</code>	<code>pgf90</code>	<code>pgcc</code>	<code>mpif90 / mpicc</code>
<code>ifort</code>	<code>ifort</code>	<code>gcc</code>	<code>mpif90 / mpicc</code>
<code>gfortran</code>	<code>gfortran</code>	<code>gcc</code>	<code>mpif90 / mpicc</code>
<code>g95</code>	<code>g95</code>	<code>gcc</code>	<code>mpif90 / mpicc</code>

In order to get a more complete and up-to-date list of available targets, one can use the following command within the top-level of MPAS. **NOTE:** This command is known to not work with Mac OSX.

```
> make -rpn | sed -n -e '/^$/ { n ; /^[^ ]*/:p }' | sed "s/: *.*$/g"
```

The MPAS framework supports multiple *cores* — currently a shallow water model, an ocean model, a non-hydrostatic atmosphere model, a non-hydrostatic atmosphere initialization core, and a land ice core — so the build process must be told which core to build. This is done by either setting the environment variable `CORE` to the name of the model core to build, or by specifying the core to be built explicitly on the command-line when running `make`. For the shallow water core, for example, one may run either

```
> setenv CORE sw
> make gfortran
```

or

```
> make gfortran CORE=sw
```

If the `CORE` environment variable is set and a core is specified on the command-line, the command-line value takes precedence; if no core is specified, either on the command line or via the `CORE` environment variable, the build process will stop with an error message stating such. Assuming compilation is successful, the model executable, named `_${CORE}_model` (e.g., `sw_model`), should be created in the top-level MPAS directory.

In order to get a list of available cores, one can simply run the top-level `Makefile` without setting the `CORE` environment variable, or passing the core via the command-line. An example of the output from this can be seen below.

```
> make
```

```

( make error )
make[1]: Entering directory 'mpas'

Usage: make target CORE=[core] [options]

Example targets:
ifort
gfortran
xlf
pgi

Availabe Cores:
atmosphere
init_atmosphere
landice
ocean
sw

Available Options:
DEBUG=true      - builds debug version. Default is optimized version.
USE_PAPI=true   - builds version using PAPI for timers. Default is off.
TAU=true        - builds version using TAU hooks for profiling. Default is off.

Ensure that NETCDF, PNETCDF, PIO, and PAPI (if USE_PAPI=true) are environment variables
that point to the absolute paths for the libraries.

***** ERROR *****
No CORE specified. Quitting.
***** ERROR *****

make[1]: Leaving directory 'mpas'

```

2.4 Cleaning

To remove all files that were created when the model was built, including the model executable itself, `make` may be run for the 'clean' target:

```
> make clean
```

As with compiling, the core to be cleaned is specified by the `CORE` environment variable, or by specifying a core explicitly on the command-line with `CORE=`.

2.5 Graph partitioning with METIS

Before MPAS can be run in parallel, a mesh decomposition file with an appropriate number of partitions (equal to the number of MPI tasks that will be used) is required in the run directory. A limited number of mesh decomposition files (`graph.info.part.*`) are provided with each test case. In order to create new mesh decomposition files for your desired number of partitions, begin with the provided `graph.info` file and partition with METIS software (<http://glaros.dtc.umn.edu/gkhome/views/metis>). The serial graph partitioning program, METIS (rather than ParMETIS or

hMETIS) should be sufficient for quickly partitioning any SCVT produced by the `grid_gen` mesh generator.

After installing METIS, a `graph.info` file may be partitioned into N partitions by running

```
> gpmetis graph.info N
```

The resulting file, `graph.info.part.N`, can then be copied into the MPAS run directory before running the model with N MPI tasks.

Chapter 3

Grid Description

This chapter provides a brief introduction to the common types of grids used in the MPAS framework.

The MPAS grid system requires the definition of seven elements. These seven elements are composed of two types of *cells*, two types of *lines*, and three types of *points*. These elements are depicted in Figure 3.1 and defined in Table 3.1. These elements can be defined on either the plane or the surface of the sphere. The two types of cells form two meshes, a primal mesh composed of Voronoi regions and a dual mesh composed of Delaunay triangles. Each corner of a primal mesh cell is uniquely associated with the “center” of a dual mesh cell and vice versa. So we define the two mesh as either a primal mesh (composed of cells P_i) or a dual mesh (composed of cells D_v). The center of any primal mesh cell, P_i , is denoted by \mathbf{x}_i and the center of any the dual mesh cell, D_v , is denoted by \mathbf{x}_v . The boundary of a given primal mesh cell P_i is composed of the set of lines that connect the \mathbf{x}_v locations of associated dual mesh cells D_v . Similarly, the boundary of a given dual mesh cell D_v is composed of the set of lines that connect the \mathbf{x}_i locations of the associated primal mesh cells P_i .

As shown in Figure 3.1, a line segment that connects two primal mesh cell centers is uniquely associated with a line segment that connects two dual mesh cell centers. We assume that these two line segments cross and the point of intersection is labeled as \mathbf{x}_e . In addition, we assume that these two line segments are orthogonal as indicated in Figure 3.1. Each \mathbf{x}_e is associated with two distances: d_e measures the distance between the primal mesh cells sharing \mathbf{x}_e and l_e measures the distance between the dual mesh cells sharing \mathbf{x}_e .

Since the two line segments crossing at \mathbf{x}_e are orthogonal, these line segments form a convenient local coordinate system for each edge. At each \mathbf{x}_e location a unit vector \mathbf{n}_e is defined to be parallel to the line connecting primal mesh cells. A second unit vector \mathbf{t}_e is defined such that $\mathbf{t}_e = \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{n}_e$.

In addition to these seven element types, we require the definition of *sets of elements*. In all, eight different types of sets are required and these are defined and explained in Table 3.2 and Figure 3.2. The notation is always of the form of, for example, $i \in CE(e)$, where the LHS indicates the type of element to be gathered (cells) based on the RHS relation to another type of element (edges).

Table 3.3 provides the names of all *elements* and all *sets of elements* as used in the MPAS framework. Elements appear twice in the table when described in the grid file in more than one way, e.g. points are described with both cartesian and latitude/longitude coordinates. An “ncdump -h” of any MPAS grid, output or restart file will contain all variable names shown in second column of Table 3.3.

Table 3.1: Definition of elements used to build the MPAS grid.

<i>Element</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Definition</i>
\mathbf{x}_i	point	location of center of primal-mesh cells
\mathbf{x}_v	point	location of center of dual-mesh cells
\mathbf{x}_e	point	location of edge points where velocity is defined
d_e	line segment	distance between neighboring \mathbf{x}_i locations
l_e	line segment	distance between neighboring \mathbf{x}_v locations
P_i	cell	a cell on the primal-mesh
D_v	cell	a cell on the dual-mesh

Table 3.2: Definition of element groups used to reference connections in the MPAS grid. Examples are provided in Figure 3.2.

<i>Syntax</i>	<i>output</i>
$e \in EC(i)$	set of edges that define the boundary of P_i .
$e \in EV(v)$	set of edges that define the boundary of D_v .
$i \in CE(e)$	two primal-mesh cells that share edge e .
$i \in CV(v)$	set of primal-mesh cells that form the vertices of dual mesh cell D_v .
$v \in VE(e)$	the two dual-mesh cells that share edge e .
$v \in VI(i)$	the set of dual-mesh cells that form the vertices of primal-mesh cell P_i .
$e \in ECP(e)$	edges of cell pair meeting at edge e .
$e \in EVC(v, i)$	edge pair associated with vertex v and mesh cell i .

Table 3.3: Variable names used to describe a MPAS grid.

<i>Element</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Size</i>	<i>Comment</i>
\mathbf{x}_i	{x,y,z}Cell	nCells	cartesian location of \mathbf{x}_i
\mathbf{x}_i	{lon,lat}Cell	nCells	longitude and latitude of \mathbf{x}_i
\mathbf{x}_v	{x,y,z}Vertex	nVertices	cartesian location of \mathbf{x}_v
\mathbf{x}_v	{lon,lat}Vertex	nVertices	longitude and latitude of \mathbf{x}_v
\mathbf{x}_e	{x,y,z}Edge	nEdges	cartesian location of \mathbf{x}_e
\mathbf{x}_e	{lon,lat}Edge	nEdges	longitude and latitude of \mathbf{x}_e
d_e	dcEdge	nEdges	distance between \mathbf{x}_i locations
l_e	dvEdge	nEdges	distance between \mathbf{x}_v locations
$e \in EC(i)$	edgesOnCell	(nEdgesMax,nCells)	edges that define P_i .
$e \in EV(v)$	edgesOnVertex	(3,nCells)	edges that define D_v .
$i \in CE(e)$	cellsOnEdge	(2,nEdges)	primal-mesh cells that share edge e .
$i \in CV(v)$	cellsOnVertex	(3,nVertices)	primal-mesh cells that define D_v .
$v \in VE(e)$	verticesOnEdge	(2,nEdges)	dual-mesh cells that share edge e .
$v \in VI(i)$	verticesOnCell	(nEdgesMax,nCells)	vertices that define P_i .

Figure 3.1: Definition of elements used to build the MPAS grid. Also see Table 3.1.

Figure 3.2: Definition of element groups used to reference connections in the MPAS grid. Also see Table 3.2.

Chapter 4

Configuring Model Input and Output

The reading and writing of model fields in MPAS is handled by user-configurable *streams*. A stream represents a fixed set of model fields, together with dimensions and attributes, that are all written or read together to or from the same file or set of files. Each MPAS model core may define its own set of default streams that it typically uses for reading initial conditions, for writing and reading restart fields, and for writing additional model history fields. Besides these default streams, users may define new streams to, e.g., write certain diagnostic fields at a higher temporal frequency than the usual model history fields.

Streams are defined in XML configuration files that are created at build time for each model core. The name of this XML file is simply ‘streams.’ suffixed with the name of the core. For example, the streams for the *sw* (shallow-water) core are defined in a file named ‘streams.sw’. An XML stream file may further reference other text files that contain lists of the model fields that are read or written in each of the streams defined in the XML stream file.

Changes to the XML stream configuration file will take effect the next time an MPAS core is run; there is no need to re-compile after making modifications to the XML files. As described in the next section, it is therefore possible, e.g., to change the interval at which a stream is written, the template for the filenames associated with a stream, or the set of fields that are written to a stream, without the need to re-compile any code.

Two classes of streams exist in MPAS: *immutable* streams and *mutable* streams. Immutable streams are those for which the set of fields that belong to the stream may not be modified at model run-time; however, it is possible to modify the interval at which the stream is read or written, the filename template describing the files containing the stream on disk, and several other parameters of the stream. In contrast, all aspects of mutable streams, including the set of fields that belong to the stream, may be modified at run-time. The motivation for the creation of two stream classes is the idea that an MPAS core may not function correctly if certain fields are not read in upon model start-up or written to restart files, and it is therefore not reasonable for users to modify this set of required fields at run-time. An MPAS core developer may choose to implement such streams as immutable streams. Since fields may not be added to an immutable stream at run-time, new immutable streams may not be defined at run-time, and the only type of new stream that may be defined at run-time is the mutable stream type.

4.1 XML stream configuration files

The XML stream configuration file for an MPAS core always has a parent XML *element* named *streams*, within which individual streams are defined:

```
<streams>
```

... one or more stream definitions ...

```
</streams>
```

Immutable streams are defined with the `immutable_stream` element, and mutable streams are defined with the `stream` element:

```
<immutable_stream name="initial_conditions"  
    type="input"  
    filename_template="init.nc"  
    input_interval="initial_only"  
>
```

```
<stream name="history"  
    type="output"  
    filename_template="output.$Y-$M-$D.$h.$m.$s.nc"  
    output_interval="6:00:00" >
```

... model fields belonging to this stream ...

```
</stream>
```

As shown in the example stream definitions, above, both classes of stream have the following required attributes:

- **name** — A unique name used to refer to the stream.
- **type** — The type of stream, either "input", "output", "input;output", or "none". A stream may be both an input and an output stream (i.e., "input;output") if, for example, it is read once at model start-up to provide initial conditions and thereafter written periodically to provide model checkpoints. A stream may be defined as neither input nor output (i.e., "none") for the purposes of defining a set of fields for inclusion other streams. Note that, for immutable streams, the type attribute may not be changed at run-time.
- **filename_template** — The template for files that exist or will be created by the stream. The filename template may include any of the following variables, which are expanded based on the simulated time at which files are first created.
 - **\$Y** — Year
 - **\$M** — Month
 - **\$D** — Day of the month
 - **\$d** — Day of the year
 - **\$h** — Hour

- `$m` — Minute
- `$s` — Second

A filename template may include either a relative or an absolute path, in which case MPAS will attempt to create any directories in the path that do not exist, subject to filesystem permissions.

- `input_interval` — For streams that have type `"input"` or `"input;output"`, the interval, beginning at the model initial time, at which the stream will be read. Possible values include a time interval specification in the format `"YYYY-MM-DD_hh:mm:ss"`; the value `"initial_only"`, which specifies that the stream is read only once at the model initial time; or the value `"none"`, which specifies that the stream is not read during a model run.
- `output_interval` — For streams that have type `"output"` or `"input;output"`, the interval, beginning at the model initial time, at which the stream will be written. Possible values include a time interval specification in the format `"YYYY-MM-DD_hh:mm:ss"`; the value `"initial_only"`, which specifies that the stream is written only once at the model initial time; or the value `"none"`, which specifies that the stream is not written during a model run.

Finally, the set of fields that belong to a mutable stream may be specified with any combination of the following elements. Note that, for immutable streams, no fields are specified at run-time in the XML configuration file.

- `var` — Associates the specified variable with the stream. The variable may be any of those defined in an MPAS core's Registry.xml file, but may not include individual constituent arrays from a `var_array`.
- `var_array` — Associates all constituent variables in a `var_array`, defined in an MPAS core's Registry.xml file, with the stream.
- `var_struct` — Associates all variables in a `var_struct`, defined in an MPAS core's Registry.xml file, with the stream.
- `stream` — Associates all explicitly associated fields in the specified stream with the stream; streams are not recursively included.
- `file` — Associates all variables listed in the specified text file, with one field per line, with the stream.

4.2 Optional stream attributes

Besides the required attributes described in the preceding section, several additional, optional attributes may be added to the definition of a stream.

- `filename_interval` — The interval between the timestamps used in the construction of the names of files associated with a stream. Possible values include a time interval specification in the format `"YYYY-MM-DD_hh:mm:ss"`; the value `"none"`, indicating that only one file containing all times is associated with the stream; the value `"input_interval"` that, for input type streams, indicates that each time to be read from the stream will come from a unique file; or the value `"output_interval"` that, for output type streams, indicates that each time to

be written to the stream will go to a unique file whose name is based on the timestamp of the data being written. The default value is "input_interval" for input type streams and "output_interval" for output type streams. For streams of type "input;output", the default filename interval is "input_interval" if the input interval is an interval (i.e., not "initial_only"), or "output_interval" otherwise. Refer to Section 4.3.1 for an example of the use of the filename_interval attribute.

- **reference_time** — A time that is an integral number of filename intervals from the timestamp of any file associated with the stream. The default value is the start time of the model simulation. Refer to Section 4.3.3 for an example of the use of the reference_time attribute.
- **clobber_mode** — Specifies how a stream should handle attempts to write to a file that already exists. Possible values for the mode include:
 - "overwrite" — The stream is allowed to overwrite records in existing files and to append new records to existing files; records not explicitly written to are left untouched.
 - "truncate" or "replace_files" — The stream is allowed to overwrite existing files, which are first truncated to remove any existing records; this is equivalent to replacing any existing files with newly created files of the same name.
 - "append" — The stream is only allowed to append new records to existing files; existing records may not be overwritten.
 - "never_modify" — The stream is not allowed to modify existing files in any way.

The default clobber mode for streams is "never_modify". Refer to Section 4.3.2 for an example of the use of the clobber_mode attribute.

- **precision** — The precision with which real-valued fields will be written or read in a stream. Possible values include "single" for 4-byte real values, "double" for 8-byte real values, or "native", which specifies that real-valued fields will be written or read in whatever precision the MPAS core was compiled. The default value is "native". Refer to Section 4.3.1 for an example of the use of the precision attribute.
- **packages** — A list of packages attached to the stream. A stream will be active (i.e., read or written) only if at least one of the packages attached to it is active, or if no packages at all are attached. Package names are provided as a semi-colon-separated list. Note that packages may only be defined in an MPAS core's Registry.xml file at build time. By default, no packages are attached to a stream.
- **io_type** — The underlying library and file format that will be used to read or write a stream. Possible values include:
 - "pnetcdf" — Read/write the stream with classic large-file NetCDF files (CDF-2) using the ANL Parallel-NetCDF library.
 - "pnetcdf,cdf5" — Read/write the stream with large-variable files (CDF-5) using the ANL Parallel-NetCDF library.
 - "netcdf" — Read/write the stream with classic large-file NetCDF files (CDF-2) using the Unidata serial NetCDF library.
 - "netcdf4" — Read/write the stream with HDF-5 files using the Unidata parallel NetCDF-4 library.

Note that the PIO library must have been built with support for the selected `io_type`. By default, all input and output streams are read and written using the "pnetcdf" option.

4.3 Stream definition examples

This section provides several example streams that make use of the optional stream attributes described in Section 4.2. All examples are of output streams, since it is more likely that a user will need to write additional fields than to read additional fields, which a model would need to be aware of; however, the concepts that are illustrated here translate directly to input streams as well.

4.3.1 Example: a single-precision output stream with one month of data per file

In this example, the optional attribute specification `filename_interval="01-00_00:00:00"` is added to force a new output file to be created for the stream every month. Note that the general format for time interval specifications is `YYYY-MM-DD.hh:mm:ss`, where any leading terms can be omitted; in this case, the year part of the interval is omitted. To reduce the file size, the specification `precision="single"` is also added to force real-valued fields to be written as 4-byte floating-point values, rather than the default of 8 bytes.

```
<stream name="diagnostics"
  type="output"
  filename_template="diagnostics.$Y-$M.nc"
  filename_interval="01-00_00:00:00"
  precision="single"
  output_interval="6:00:00" >

  <var name="u10"/>
  <var name="v10"/>
  <var name="t2"/>
  <var name="q2"/>

</stream>
```

The only fields that will be written to this stream are the hypothetical 10-m diagnosed wind components, the 2-m temperature, and the 2-m specific humidity variables. Also, note that the filename template only includes the year and month from the model valid time; this can be problematic when the simulation starts in the middle of a month, and a solution for this problem is illustrated in the example of Section 4.3.3.

4.3.2 Example: appending records to existing output files

By default, streams will never modify existing files whose filenames match the name of a file that would otherwise be written during the course of a simulation. However, when restarting a simulation that is expected to add more records to existing output files, it can be useful to instruct the MPAS I/O system to append these records, thereby modifying existing files. This may be accomplished with the `clobber_mode` attribute.

```

<stream name="diagnostics"
  type="output"
  filename_template="diagnostics.$Y-$M.nc"
  filename_interval="01-00_00:00:00"
  precision="single"
  clobber_mode="append"
  output_interval="6:00:00" >

  <var name="u10"/>
  <var name="v10"/>
  <var name="t2"/>
  <var name="q2"/>

</stream>

```

In general, if MPAS were to attempt to write a record at a time that already existed in an output file, a `clobber_mode` of ‘append’ would not permit the write to take place, since this would modify existing data; in ‘append’ mode, only new records may be added. However, due to a peculiarity in the implementation of the ‘append’ clobber mode, it may be possible for an output file to contain duplicate times. This can happen when the first record that is appended to an existing file has a timestamp not matching any in the file, after which, any record that is written — regardless of whether its timestamp matches one already in the file — will be appended to the end of the file. This situation may arise, for example, when restarting a model simulation with a shorter `output_interval` than was used in the original model simulation with an MPAS core that does not write the first output time for restart runs.

4.3.3 Example: referencing filename intervals to a time other than the start time

The example stream of the previous sections creates a new file each month during the simulation, and the filenames contain only the year and month of the timestamp when the file was created. If a simulation begins at 00 UTC on the first day of a month, then each file in the diagnostic stream will contain only output times that fall within the month in the filename. However, if a simulation were to begin in the middle of a month — for example, the month of June, 2014 — the first diagnostics output file would have a filename of ‘diagnostics.2014-06.nc’, but rather than containing only output fields valid in June, it would contain all fields written between the middle of June and the middle of July, at which point one month of simulation would have elapsed, and a new output file, ‘diagnostics.2014-07.nc’, would be created.

In order to ensure that the file ‘diagnostics.2014-06.nc’ contained only data from June 2014, the `reference_time` attribute may be added such that the day, hour, minute, and second in the date and time represent the first day of the month at 00 UTC. In this example, the year and month of the reference time are not important, since the purpose of the reference time here is to describe to MPAS that the monthly filename interval begins (i.e., is referenced to) the first day of the month.

```

<stream name="diagnostics"
  type="output"
  filename_template="diagnostics.$Y-$M.nc"

```

```
filename_interval="01-00_00:00:00"  
reference_time="2014-01-01_00:00:00"  
precision="single"  
clobber_mode="append"  
output_interval="6:00:00" >
```

```
<var name="u10"/>  
<var name="v10"/>  
<var name="t2"/>  
<var name="q2"/>
```

```
</stream>
```

In general, the components of a timestamp, `YYYY-MM-DD_hh:mm:ss`, that are less significant than (i.e., to the right of) those contained in a filename template are important in a `reference_time`. For example, with a `filename_template` that contained only the year, the month component of the `reference_time` would become important to identify the month of the year on which the yearly basis for filenames would begin.

Chapter 5

Visualization

This chapter discusses visualization tools that may be used by all cores.

5.1 ParaView

ParaView may be used to visualize MPAS initialization, output, and restart files. It includes a reader that was specifically designed to read MPAS NetCDF files, including Cartesian and spherical domains. At this time, only cell-centered quantities may be plotted with ParaView. Variables located at edges and vertices must be interpolated to cell centers for visualization.

ParaView is freely available for download at <http://www.paraview.org>. Binary installations are available for Windows, Mac, and Linux, as well as source code files and tutorials. From the ParaView website:

ParaView is an open-source, multi-platform data analysis and visualization application. ParaView users can quickly build visualizations to analyze their data using qualitative and quantitative techniques. The data exploration can be done interactively in 3D or programmatically using ParaView's batch processing capabilities. ParaView was developed to analyze extremely large datasets using distributed memory computing resources. It can be run on supercomputers to analyze datasets of terascale as well as on laptops for smaller data.

To visualize an MPAS cell-centered variable in ParaView, open the file and choose **MPAS NetCDF (Unstructured)** as the file format. In the lower left Object Inspector panel, choose your variables of interest (Figure 5.1). For large data sets, loading fewer variables will result in less wait time. Options are available for latitude-longitude projections, vertical level, etc. Click the 'Apply' button to load the data set. In the toolbars at the top, choose the variable to plot from the pull-down menu, and 'Surface' for the type of visualization. The color bar button displays a color bar, and the color scale editor button allows the user to manually change the color bar type and extents. The Filters menu provides computational tools for interactive data manipulation. Movies, in avi format or as individual frames, may be conveniently created with the **Save Animation** tool in the File menu.

Paraview may be used to view the grid from any MPAS NetCDF file by choosing **Wireframe** or **Surface With Edges** from the visualization-type pull-down menu (Figure 5.2). This produces a view of the Delaunay triangulation, which is the dual mesh to the primal Voronoi cell grid (Figure 3.1). Paraview plots all variables by interpolating colors between each corner of the Delaunay triangles. These corners are the cell-center locations of the primal grid.

Figure 5.1: Example of ParaView to view an MPAS NetCDF file.

Figure 5.2: Example of visualizing the dual mesh from an MPAS NetCDF file.

Part II

MPAS-Seaice

Chapter 6

Model Description

A full description and validation of the physics in MPAS-Seaice can be found at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1194374>.

6.1 Velocity Solver

6.1.1 Overview

MPAS-Seaice uses a ‘B’ Arakawa type grid (Arakawa and Lamb, 1977) with both components of velocity defined at cell vertices and sea-ice concentration, volume and other tracers defined at cell centers (see Chapter 3). The velocity components at a given MPAS vertex are defined as eastwards (u) and northwards (v), irrespective of the orientation of edges joining that vertex. Such a definition, however, would result in a convergence of v components at the geographic North Pole and strong metric terms in the velocity solution. Consequently, in addition, these definitions of u and v are rotated so that their pole lies on the geographical equator at 0° longitude.

To prognose sea-ice velocity MPAS-Seaice solves the same sea-ice momentum equation as CICE (Hibler III, 1979; Hunke and Dukowicz, 1997):

$$m \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \boldsymbol{\tau}_a + \boldsymbol{\tau}_w - \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times m f \mathbf{u} - m g \nabla H_o. \quad (6.1)$$

Here m is the mass of snow and ice per unit area, \mathbf{u} is the sea-ice velocity, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the ice internal stress tensor, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_a$ and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_w$ are the horizontal stresses due to atmospheric winds and ocean currents respectively, $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ is the unit vector normal to the Earth surface, f is the Coriolis parameter, g is the acceleration due to gravity and H_o is the ocean surface height. The second to last term represents the Coriolis force and the last term represents the force due to the ocean surface tilt. Only the divergence of internal stress and ocean surface tilt terms depend on horizontal differential operators. During coupled simulations the ocean model provides the ocean surface tilt term, whereas in non-coupled simulations MPAS-Seaice assumes that the ocean currents are in geostrophic balance so that

$$m g \nabla H_o = m f \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{u}_o \quad (6.2)$$

where \mathbf{u}_o is the ocean surface velocity. Consequently, only the divergence of internal stress depends on the properties of the horizontal grid employed, and only adaptations to this stress term are required to adapt the velocity solver of CICE to MPAS meshes. The other terms in the momentum equation are solved in an identical way to CICE.

Determination of the divergence of the internal stress can be broken down into three stages:

1. The strain rate tensor is determined from the velocity field.
2. The stress tensor at a point is determined, through a constitutive relation, from the strain rate tensor at that point.
3. The divergence of this stress tensor is calculated.

As in CICE an Elastic-Viscous-Plastic (EVP) rheology (Hunke and Dukowicz, 1997) is used for the constitutive relation. This step does not depend on the details of the horizontal mesh and MPAS-Seaice uses the same formulation as CICE. Two schemes to calculate the strain rate tensor and the divergence of internal stress on MPAS meshes are implemented in MPAS-Seaice. A variational scheme is based on that used in CICE (Hunke and Dukowicz, 2002), whereas a weak scheme uses the line integral forms of the symmetric gradient and divergence operators. These schemes are described in the following sections.

6.1.2 Variational Scheme

MPAS-Seaice implements a variational scheme for calculating the divergence of stress based on that of Hunke and Dukowicz (2002) but adapted for arbitrarily shaped and sided convex polygons. This scheme is based on the fact that over the entire domain, Ω , and ignoring boundary effects, the total work done by the internal stress is equal to the dissipation of mechanical energy:

$$\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{u} \cdot (\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}) dA = - \int_{\Omega} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{11} \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_{11} + 2\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{12} \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_{12} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{22} \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_{22}) dA. \quad (6.3)$$

Here $\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$ is the strain rate tensor and the integrals are area integrals over the whole model domain. The work done over the whole domain can be split into a sum over the contribution to the work done from each cell on the dual Delaunay mesh. Each dual cell on the dual mesh consists of a triangle surrounding a single vertex point where the discretized velocity is defined. Equation 6.3 can then be written as

$$\sum_i^{n_d} \int_i \mathbf{u} \cdot (\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}) dA = D(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n_d}) \quad (6.4)$$

where the left-side sum is over the n_d cells of the dual mesh, the integral is an area integral over each dual cell, and the dissipation of mechanical energy has been written as a function of the discretized velocity components. Writing the two components of the divergence of stress as $F_u = (\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma})_u$ and $F_v = (\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma})_v$, then

$$\sum_i^{n_d} \int_i (u F_u + v F_v) dA = D(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n_d}). \quad (6.5)$$

If it is assumed that within the dual cell the velocity is constant, it follows that

$$\sum_i^{n_d} (u_i F_{ui} + v_i F_{vi}) A_{ui} = D(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n_d}) \quad (6.6)$$

where A_{ui} is the area of the dual mesh cell. The variation of these expressions with respect to the u component of the discretized velocity at a particular vertex point j is given by

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial u_j} \sum_i^{n_d} (u_i F_{ui} + v_i F_{vi}) A_{ui} = \frac{\partial}{\partial u_j} D(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n_d}) \quad (6.7)$$

Assuming F_u and F_v are not functions of velocity,

$$F_{u_j} = \frac{1}{A_{u_j}} \frac{\partial}{\partial u_j} D(u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n_d}). \quad (6.8)$$

F_v is obtained in a similar way by taking the variation of D with respect to v_j . The dissipation of mechanical energy, D , can be split into three terms:

$$D = D_1 + D_2 + D_3 \quad (6.9)$$

with

$$D_1 = - \int \sigma_{11} \dot{\epsilon}_{11} dA, \quad D_2 = - \int 2\sigma_{12} \dot{\epsilon}_{12} dA, \quad D_3 = - \int \sigma_{22} \dot{\epsilon}_{22} dA. \quad (6.10)$$

The contribution to F_u and F_v from D_1 will be calculated. Similar contributions come from D_2 and D_3 . Using the expression for $\dot{\epsilon}_{11}$ in terms of the velocity components and latitude ϕ , D_1 becomes

$$D_1 = - \int \sigma_{11} \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - \frac{v \tan \phi}{r} \right] dA \quad (6.11)$$

where x and y are locally Cartesian coordinates, with x in the rotated due eastwards direction and y in the rotated due northwards direction, ϕ is the latitude, and r is the radius of the Earth. The second term in $\dot{\epsilon}$ accounts for the metric effects of the curved domain (Batchelor, 1967). The integral can be broken up into a sum over the n_p cells in the primary mesh:

$$D_1 = - \sum_k^{n_p} \int_k \sigma_{11} \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - \frac{v \tan \phi}{r} \right] dA \quad (6.12)$$

where the integral is over the interior area of the k th cell. To perform this integral a set of basis functions, \mathcal{W}_l , is used to represent functions within a cell of the primary mesh. If a function, ψ , has a value of ψ_l at vertex l of a cell, then the value of the function at a position (x, y) within the cell can be approximated as

$$\psi(x, y) = \sum_l^{n_v} \psi_l \mathcal{W}_l(x, y) \quad (6.13)$$

where the sum is over the n_v vertices of the cell in the primary mesh. Using those basis functions, equation 6.12 can be written as

$$D_1 = - \sum_k^{n_p} \int_k \left[\sum_l^{n_v} \sigma_{11l} \mathcal{W}_l \cdot \sum_m^{n_v} \left(u_m \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}_m}{\partial x} - \frac{\tan \phi}{r} v_m \mathcal{W}_m \right) \right] dA \quad (6.14)$$

where the derivative with respect to x has been taken inside the summation. Rearranging

$$D_1 = - \sum_k^{n_p} \sum_l^{n_v} \sum_m^{n_v} \sigma_{11l} \left(u_m \int_k \mathcal{W}_l \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}_m}{\partial x} dA - \frac{\tan \phi}{r} v_m \int_k \mathcal{W}_l \mathcal{W}_m dA \right). \quad (6.15)$$

In moving the integral, it has been assumed that ϕ , the latitude, is constant in the cell. The terms involving integrals are now only a function of the geometry of the mesh and can be calculated once during the initialization phase of the model run. Defining

$$\mathcal{S}_{lm}^x = \int_k \mathcal{W}_l \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}_m}{\partial x} dA \quad (6.16)$$

and

$$\mathcal{T}_{lm} = \int_k \mathcal{W}_l \mathcal{W}_m dA. \quad (6.17)$$

then

$$D_1 = - \sum_k^{n_p} \sum_l^{n_v} \sum_m^{n_v} \sigma_{11l} \left(u_m \mathcal{S}_{lm}^x - \frac{\tan \phi}{r} v_m \mathcal{T}_{lm} \right). \quad (6.18)$$

Taking the variation with respect to a discretized velocity component at a particular vertex point, j , as in equation 6.8, now gives us the contribution from D_1 to the components of the divergence of stress tensor at that velocity point:

$$(\nabla \cdot \sigma)_{u_j}^{D_1} = \frac{\delta D_1}{\delta u_j} = - \sum_k^{n_p} \sum_l^{n_v} \sigma_{11l} \mathcal{S}_{lj}^x \quad (6.19)$$

$$(\nabla \cdot \sigma)_{v_j}^{D_1} = \frac{\delta D_1}{\delta v_j} = \sum_k^{n_p} \sum_l^{n_v} \sigma_{11l} \frac{\tan \phi}{r} \mathcal{T}_{lj} \quad (6.20)$$

Only cells that border the vertex point j contribute to the k sum over cells. The total divergence of stress at the point j is then the sum from the contributions from D_1 , D_2 , and D_3 :

$$(\nabla \cdot \sigma)_{u_j} = (\nabla \cdot \sigma)_{u_j}^{D_1} + (\nabla \cdot \sigma)_{u_j}^{D_2} + (\nabla \cdot \sigma)_{u_j}^{D_3} \quad (6.21)$$

$$(\nabla \cdot \sigma)_{v_j} = (\nabla \cdot \sigma)_{v_j}^{D_1} + (\nabla \cdot \sigma)_{v_j}^{D_2} + (\nabla \cdot \sigma)_{v_j}^{D_3}. \quad (6.22)$$

The stress for each cell at its vertices now needs to be determined. As in the formulation in CICE, each cell has its own values of the stress at its vertices, so each vertex has several values of the stress, each corresponding to a different surrounding cell. The stresses are calculated from the strain rate tensor at each vertex using the constitutive relation. Including metric effects (Batchelor, 1967) the strain rate tensor is given by:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{11} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - \frac{v \tan \phi}{r} \quad (6.23)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{22} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \quad (6.24)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{12} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{u \tan \phi}{2r}. \quad (6.25)$$

The strain rate tensor at cell vertex l is then given by

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{11l} = \sum_m^{n_v} u_m \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}_m}{\partial x} \Big|_l - \frac{v_l \tan \phi_l}{r} \quad (6.26)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{22l} = \sum_m^{n_v} v_m \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}_m}{\partial y} \Big|_l \quad (6.27)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{12l} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_m^{n_v} u_m \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}_m}{\partial y} \Big|_l + \sum_m^{n_v} v_m \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}_m}{\partial x} \Big|_l \right) + \frac{u_l \tan \phi_l}{2r} \quad (6.28)$$

The derivatives of the basis functions are taken at cell vertex l .

In MPAS-Seaice two options for the choice of basis functions, \mathcal{W}_l are provided: Wachspress basis functions and Piece-Wise Linear (PWL) basis functions. Both basis functions have a value

Figure 6.1: Contour integration lines used by the weak scheme. (a): Strain rate at cell centers (*circle*) are calculated from line integrals around primary mesh cells (*solid line*). (b): Divergence of stress at cell vertices (*square*) are calculated from line integrals around the dual mesh cells (*solid line*). Directions of normal vectors used in the integrals are shown for both figures.

of one on vertex l and zero on the other vertices of a cell, and are linear on the cell boundaries. The Wachspress basis functions are smooth rational polynomials in the cell interior (Dasgupta, 2003). The integrals of the Wachspress basis function within a cell are performed using the eighth order quadrature rules of Dunavant (1985). PWL basis functions divide the polygonal cell into sub-triangles and use a linear basis within each sub-triangle (Bailey et al., 2008). To divide the polygonal cell into sub-triangles, a point is chosen within the cell and sub-triangles formed using this point and two adjacent vertices. The central point in the cell, \mathbf{x}_c , is chosen as

$$\mathbf{x}_c = \sum_i^{n_v} \alpha_i \mathbf{x}_i \quad (6.29)$$

where the sum is over the n_v vertices of the cell each with position \mathbf{x}_i . The simplest choice for the α_i is to set them all equal to the inverse of the number of cell vertices, $1/n_v$. For quadrilateral meshes the Wachspress basis functions reduce to the bilinear basis functions used in CICE.

6.1.3 Weak Scheme

For the weak scheme line integrals around cells in the primary and dual meshes are used to calculate the strain rate tensor and the divergence of stress, respectively. To determine the strain rate tensor the following vector identity is used:

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{v}) = (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} + (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) \mathbf{v} \quad (6.30)$$

and from the divergence theorem:

$$\int_{\Omega} [\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{v})] \partial \Omega = \oint_S [\mathbf{n} \cdot (\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{v})] \partial S = \oint_S [(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{u}) \mathbf{v}] \partial S \quad (6.31)$$

where \mathbf{n} is a normal vector to the surface S and \otimes is the tensor product. If equation 6.30 is integrated over Ω , using equation 6.31

$$\int_{\Omega} [(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{v} + (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u})\mathbf{v}] \partial\Omega = \oint_S [(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{u})\mathbf{v}] \partial S \quad (6.32)$$

If \mathbf{u} is chosen as constant then $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}$ vanishes as does the second term in equation 6.32. Taking, also, \mathbf{u} sequentially as the cartesian unit vectors spanning Ω and summing the results

$$\int_{\Omega} [\nabla\mathbf{v}] \partial\Omega = \oint_S [\mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{v}] \partial S \quad (6.33)$$

The symmetric version of this operator is then obtained as:

$$\int_{\Omega} [\nabla_S\mathbf{v}] \partial\Omega = \oint_S [\mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{n}] \partial S \quad (6.34)$$

The strain rate at a point is then obtained from the limit

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \nabla_S\mathbf{v} = \lim_{A \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{A} \oint \frac{1}{2} [\mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{n}] dl \quad (6.35)$$

where the integral is around a closed loop with area A and normal vector \mathbf{n} , and \mathbf{v} is the sea-ice velocity. To determine the strain rate tensor at the centers of the primary mesh, this integration is taken around the edges of the cells in the primary mesh. First the cell is projected onto a flat tangent plane perpendicular to the vector joining the center of the sphere to the cell center. The sea ice velocity at a cell edge is taken as the average of the values on the two vertices forming that edge projected onto the tangent plane:

$$\dot{\epsilon}' = \frac{1}{A} \sum_i^{n_e} \frac{1}{2} [\mathbf{n}_i \otimes \mathbf{v}_i + \mathbf{v}_i \otimes \mathbf{n}_i] l_i \quad (6.36)$$

Here, A is the area of the primary cell, the summation is over the n_e edges of the primary cell, \mathbf{n}_i is the normal vector to the edge i that lies in the tangent plane, \mathbf{v}_i is the edge velocity and l_i is the length of edge i . The tangential projection of the velocity is used and metric terms are accounted for separately. The full strain rate tensor including these metric terms is (Batchelor, 1967):

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{11} = \dot{\epsilon}'_{11} - \frac{v \tan \phi}{r} \quad (6.37)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{22} = \dot{\epsilon}'_{22} \quad (6.38)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{12} = \dot{\epsilon}'_{12} + \frac{u \tan \phi}{2r} \quad (6.39)$$

where the prime symbol signifies a strain rate without metric terms. The stress, which is determined from the strain rate tensor using the constitutive relation, is now defined on cell centers. To find its divergence the divergence theorem is used:

$$\iint \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} dA = \oint [\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n}] dl \quad (6.40)$$

or

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \lim_{A \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{A} \oint [\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n}] dl \quad (6.41)$$

for the divergence of stress at a point. The divergence of internal stress is determined at primary cell vertices (where the velocity is defined and momentum equation solved) by performing a sum around the edges of the dual mesh on a tangent projected plane, tangential to the primary cell vertex. The vertices of the dual mesh are the cell centers of the primary mesh where the strain rate has been determined. The divergence of stress at primary cell vertices is then given by

$$(\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma})' = \frac{1}{A_d} \sum_i^{n_c} [\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i \cdot \mathbf{n}_i] l_i \quad (6.42)$$

where A_d is the area of the dual mesh cell, the sum is over the n_c vertices of the dual mesh, l_i is the length of the i edge of the dual mesh, and \mathbf{n}_i is a normal vector to the i edge on the projected plane. As before, this gives a result without taking into account metric effects of the mesh. With those effects the divergence of stress is:

$$(\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma})_u = (\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma})'_u - \frac{2\sigma_{12} \tan \phi}{r} \quad (6.43)$$

$$(\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma})_v = (\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma})'_v + \frac{(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22}) \tan \phi}{r} \quad (6.44)$$

where the components of $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ are approximated as the average of the values on the dual mesh vertices.

6.2 Transport

6.2.1 Overview

To transport sea ice fractional area and various tracers, MPAS-Seaice uses an incremental remapping (IR) algorithm similar to that described by [Dukowicz and Baumgardner \(2000\)](#), [Lipscomb and Hunke \(2004\)](#) (henceforth LH04) and [Lipscomb and Ringler \(2005\)](#) (henceforth LR05). The LH04 scheme was designed for structured quadrilateral meshes and is implemented in CICE ([Hunke et al., 2015](#)). The LR05 scheme was implemented on a structured SCVT global mesh consisting of quasi-regular hexagons and 12 pentagons.

For MPAS-Seaice the IR scheme was generalized to work on either the standard MPAS mesh (hexagons and other n-gons of varying sizes, with a vertex degree of 3 as in LR05) or a quadrilateral mesh (with a vertex degree of 4 as in LH04 and CICE). Since MPAS meshes are unstructured, the IR scheme had to be rewritten from scratch. Most of the code is mesh-agnostic, but a small amount of code is specific to quad meshes as noted below.

Here we review the conceptual framework of incremental remapping as in ([Hunke et al., 2015](#)) and describe features specific to the MPAS-Seaice implementation. IR is designed to solve equations of the form

$$\frac{\partial m}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}m) \quad (6.45)$$

$$\frac{\partial(mT_1)}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}mT_1), \quad (6.46)$$

$$\frac{\partial(mT_1T_2)}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}mT_1T_2), \quad (6.47)$$

$$\frac{\partial(mT_1T_2T_3)}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u}mT_1T_2T_3), \quad (6.48)$$

where $\mathbf{u} = (x, y)$ is the horizontal velocity, m is mass or a mass-like field (such as density or fractional sea ice concentration), and T_1 , T_2 and T_3 are tracers. These equations describe conservation of

quantities such as mass and internal energy under horizontal transport. Sources and sinks of mass and tracers (e.g., ice growth and melting) are treated separately from transport.

In MPAS-Seaice, the fractional ice area in each thickness category is a mass-like field whose transport is described by (6.45). (Henceforth, “area” refers to fractional ice area unless stated otherwise.) Ice and snow thickness, among other fields, are type 1 tracers obeying equations of the form (6.46), and the ice and snow enthalpy in each vertical layer are type 2 tracers obeying equations like (6.47), with ice or snow thickness as their parent tracer. When run with advanced options (e.g., active melt ponds and biogeochemistry), MPAS-Seaice advects tracers up to type 3. Thus, the mass-like field is the “parent field” for type 1 tracers; type 1 tracers are parents of type 2; and type 2 tracers are parents of type 3.

Incremental remapping has several desirable properties for sea ice modeling:

- It is conservative to within machine roundoff.
- It preserves tracer monotonicity. That is, transport produces no new local extrema in fields like ice thickness or internal energy.
- The reconstructed mass and tracer fields vary linearly in x and y . This means that remapping is second-order accurate in space, except where gradients are limited locally to preserve monotonicity.
- There are economies of scale. Transporting a single field is fairly expensive, but additional tracers have a low marginal cost, especially when all tracers are transported with a single velocity field as in CICE and MPAS-Seaice.

The time step is limited by the requirement that trajectories projected backward from vertices are confined to the cells sharing the vertex (i.e., 3 cells for the standard MPAS mesh and 4 for the quad mesh). This is what is meant by incremental as opposed to general remapping. This requirement leads to a CFL-like condition,

$$\frac{\max(|\mathbf{u}|\Delta t)}{\Delta x} \leq 1, \quad (6.49)$$

where Δx is the grid spacing and Δt is the time step. For highly divergent velocity fields, the maximum time step may have to be reduced by a factor of 2 to ensure that trajectories do not cross.

The IR algorithm consists of the following steps:

- Given mean values of the ice area and tracer fields in each grid cell and thickness category, construct linear approximations of these fields. Limit the field gradients to preserve monotonicity.
- Given ice velocities at grid cell vertices, identify departure regions for the transport across each cell edge. Divide these departure regions into triangles and compute the coordinates of the triangle vertices.
- Integrate the area and tracer fields over the departure triangles to obtain the area, volume, and other conserved quantities transported across each cell edge.
- Given these transports, update the area and tracers.

Since all fields are transported by the same velocity field, the second step is done only once per time step. The other steps are repeated for each field.

With advanced physics and biogeochemistry (BGC) options, MPAS-Seaice can be configured to include up to ~ 40 tracer fields, each of which is advected in every thickness category, and many of which are defined in each vertical ice or snow layer. In order to accommodate different tracer combinations and make it easy to add new tracers, the tracer fields are organized in a linked list that depends on which physics and BGC packages are active. The list is arranged with fractional ice area first, followed by the type 1 tracers, type 2 tracers, and finally type 3 tracers. In this way, values computed for parent tracers are always available when needed for computations involving child tracers.

We next describe the IR algorithm in detail, pointing out features that are new in MPAS-Seaice.

6.2.2 Reconstructing area and tracer fields

The fractional ice area and all tracers are reconstructed in each grid cell (quadrilaterals, hexagons or other n -gons) as functions of $\mathbf{r} = (x, y)$ in a cell-based coordinate system. On a sphere, \mathbf{r} lies in a local plane that is tangent to the sphere at the cell center. The state variable for ice area, denoted as \bar{a} , should be recovered as the mean value when integrated over the cell:

$$\int_A a(x, y) dA = \bar{a} A_C, \quad (6.50)$$

where A_C is the grid cell area. Equation 6.50 is satisfied if $a(\mathbf{r})$ has the form

$$a(\mathbf{r}) = \bar{a} + \alpha_a \nabla a \cdot (\mathbf{r} - \bar{\mathbf{r}}), \quad (6.51)$$

where ∇a is a cell-centered gradient, α_a is a coefficient between 0 and 1 that enforces monotonicity, and $\bar{\mathbf{r}}$ is the cell centroid:

$$\bar{\mathbf{r}} = \frac{1}{A_C} \int_A \mathbf{r} dA. \quad (6.52)$$

Similarly, tracer means should be recovered when integrated over a cell:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_A a(\mathbf{r}) T_1(\mathbf{r}) dA &= \bar{a} \bar{T}_1 A_C, \\ \int_A a(\mathbf{r}) T_1(\mathbf{r}) T_2(\mathbf{r}) dA &= \bar{a} \bar{T}_1 \bar{T}_2 A_C, \\ \int_A a(\mathbf{r}) T_1(\mathbf{r}) T_2(\mathbf{r}) T_3(\mathbf{r}) dA &= \bar{a} \bar{T}_1 \bar{T}_2 \bar{T}_3 A_C. \end{aligned} \quad (6.53)$$

These equations are satisfied when the tracers are reconstructed as

$$\begin{aligned} T_1(\mathbf{r}) &= \bar{T}_1 + \alpha_{T1} \nabla T_1 \cdot (\mathbf{r} - \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_1), \\ T_2(\mathbf{r}) &= \bar{T}_2 + \alpha_{T2} \nabla T_2 \cdot (\mathbf{r} - \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_2), \\ T_3(\mathbf{r}) &= \bar{T}_3 + \alpha_{T3} \nabla T_3 \cdot (\mathbf{r} - \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_3), \end{aligned} \quad (6.54)$$

where the tracer barycenter coordinates $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_n$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_1 &= \frac{1}{\bar{a} A_C} \int_A \mathbf{r} a dA, \\ \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_2 &= \frac{1}{\bar{a} \bar{T}_1 A_C} \int_A \mathbf{r} a T_1 dA, \\ \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_3 &= \frac{1}{\bar{a} \bar{T}_1 \bar{T}_2 A_C} \int_A \mathbf{r} a T_1 T_2 dA. \end{aligned} \quad (6.55)$$

Figure 6.2: (a): Schematic showing transport across a cell edge on a standard MPAS mesh with 3 edges meeting at each vertex. The letters C , E and V denote cell centers, edges and vertices, respectively. Points $D1$ and $D2$ are backward trajectories, and the departure region is shaded. (b): Schematic showing transport across a cell edge on a quadrilateral MPAS mesh with 4 edges meeting at each vertex.

The integrals in (6.55) can be evaluated by applying quadrature rules for linear, quadratic and cubic polynomials as described in Section 6.2.4.

Monotonicity is enforced by van Leer limiting (van Leer, 1979). The reconstructed area and tracers are evaluated at cell vertices, and the coefficients α are reduced as needed so that the reconstructed values lie within the range of the mean values in the cell and its neighbors. When $\alpha = 1$, the reconstruction is second-order accurate in space. When $\alpha = 0$, the reconstruction reduces locally to first-order.

6.2.3 Locating departure triangles

The next step is to identify the departure region associated with fluxes across each cell edge, and to divide the departure region into triangles. Figure 6.2a illustrates the geometry for the standard MPAS mesh. The edge has vertices $V1$ and $V2$. Each edge is oriented such that one adjacent cell ($C1$) is defined to lie in the left half-plane and the other ($C2$) in the right half-plane. The departure points $D1$ and $D2$ are found by projecting velocities backward from $V1$ and $V2$. The shaded departure region is a quadrilateral containing all the ice transported across the edge in one time step. In addition to $C1$ and $C2$, the departure region can include side cells $C3$ and $C4$. The side cells share edges $E1$ to $E4$ and vertices $V3$ to $V6$ with the central cells $C1$ and $C2$.

The edges and vertices in Figure 6.2a are defined in a coordinate system lying in the local tangent plane at the midpoint of the main edge, halfway between $V1$ and $V2$. These coordinates are pre-computed at initialization. During each time step, departure triangles are found by locating $D1$ and $D2$ in this coordinate system, and then looping through the edges to identify any intersections of line segment $\overline{D1D2}$ (i.e., the segment joining $D1$ and $D2$) with the various edges. If $\overline{D1D2}$ intersects the main edge, then the departure region consists of two triangles (one each in $C1$ and $C2$) rather than a quadrilateral (as shown in the figure). If $\overline{D1D2}$ intersects any of edges $E1$ to $E4$, the departure region includes triangles in side cells.

Each departure triangle lies in a single grid cell, and there are at most four such triangles. There are two triangles in the central cells (either one each in $C1$ and $C2$, or a quadrilateral that can be split into two triangles), and up to two triangles in side cells. The triangle vertices are a combination of cell vertices ($V1$ and $V2$), departure points ($D1$ and $D2$), and intersection points (points where $\overline{D12}$ crosses an edge).

Figure 6.2b shows the geometry for a quadrilateral mesh. In this figure the departure region consists of two triangles, but it could also be a quadrilateral as in Figure 6.2a. For the quad mesh there are two additional side cells ($C5$ and $C6$), edges ($E5$ and $E6$) and vertices ($V7$ and $V8$). The search algorithm is designed such that the code used to find departure triangles for the standard mesh is also applied to the quad mesh. For quad meshes only, there is additional logic to find intersection points and triangles associated with the extra edges and cells. This is the only mesh-specific code in the run-time IR code. For the quad mesh there are at most six departure triangles: two in the central cells and one in each of the four side cells. If the edges meet at right angles as shown in the figure, the maximum is five triangles, but this is not a mesh requirement.

Once triangle vertices have been found in edge-based coordinates, they are transformed to cell-based coordinates, i.e., coordinates in the local tangent plane of the cell containing each triangle. (Coefficients for these transformations are computed at initialization.) Triangle areas are computed as

$$A_T = \frac{1}{2} |(x_2 - x_1)(y_3 - y_1) - (y_2 - y_1)(x_3 - x_1)|. \quad (6.56)$$

6.2.4 Integrating the transport

Next, ice area and area-tracer products are integrated in each triangle. The integrals have the form (6.50) for area and (6.53) for tracers. Since each field is a linear function of (x, y) as in (6.51) and (6.54), the area-tracer products are quadratic, cubic and quartic polynomials, respectively, for tracers of type 1, 2 and 3.

The integrals can be evaluated exactly by summing over values at quadrature points in each triangle. Polynomials of quadratic or lower order are integrated using the formula

$$I = \frac{A_T}{3} \sum_{i=1}^3 f(\mathbf{x}'_i). \quad (6.57)$$

The quadrature points are located at $\mathbf{x}'_i = (\mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{x}_i)/2$, where \mathbf{x}_0 is the triangle midpoint and \mathbf{x}_i are the three vertices. The products involving type-2 and type-3 tracers are cubic and quadratic polynomials, which can be evaluated using a similar formula with 6 quadrature points:

$$I = A_T \left[w_1 \sum_{i=1}^3 f(\mathbf{x}_{1i}) + w_2 \sum_{i=1}^3 f(\mathbf{x}_{2i}) \right], \quad (6.58)$$

where \mathbf{x}_{1i} and \mathbf{x}_{2i} are two sets of three quadrature points, arranged symmetrically on trisecting medians of the triangle, and w_1 and w_2 are weighting factors. Coefficients and weighting factors for these and other symmetric quadrature rules for triangles were computed by Dunavant (1985). These integrals are computed for each triangle and summed over edges to give fluxes of ice area and area-tracer products across each edge.

6.2.5 Updating area and tracer fields

The area transported across edge k for a given cell can be denoted as Δa_k , and the area-tracer products as $\Delta(aT_1)_k$, $\Delta(aT_1T_2)_k$ and $\Delta(aT_1T_2T_3)_k$. The new ice area at time $n + 1$ is given by

$$a^{n+1} = a^n + \frac{1}{A_C} \sum_k \pm \Delta a_k, \quad (6.59)$$

where the sum is taken over cell edges k , with a positive sign denoting transport into a cell and a negative sign denoting outward transport. The new tracers are given by

$$\begin{aligned} T_1^{n+1} &= \frac{a^n T_1^n + \frac{1}{A_C} \sum_k \pm \Delta(aT_1)_k}{a^{n+1}}, \\ T_2^{n+1} &= \frac{a^n T_1^n T_2^n + \frac{1}{A_C} \sum_k \pm \Delta(aT_1T_2)_k}{a^{n+1} T_1^{n+1}}, \\ T_3^{n+1} &= \frac{a^n T_1^n T_2^n T_3^n + \frac{1}{A_C} \sum_k \pm \Delta(aT_1T_2T_3)_k}{a^{n+1} T_1^{n+1} T_2^{n+1}}. \end{aligned} \quad (6.60)$$

Dukowicz and Baumgardner (2000) showed that (6.60) satisfies tracer monotonicity, since the new-time tracer values are area-weighted averages of old-time values.

6.3 Column Physics

This version of MPAS-Seaice uses an early version of the Icepack library for column physics and biogeochemistry. Full documentation for Icepack can be found at <https://github.com/CICE-Consortium/Icepack>. Icepack includes sophisticated vertical physics and biogeochemical schemes, which include vertical thermodynamics schemes (Bitz and Lipscomb, 1999; Turner et al., 2013; Turner and Hunke, 2015), several melt-pond parameterizations (Flocco et al., 2010; Holland et al., 2012a; Hunke et al., 2013), a delta-Eddington radiation scheme (Briegleb and Light, 2007; Holland et al., 2012a), schemes for transport in thickness space (Lipscomb, 2001), and representations of mechanical redistribution (Lipscomb et al., 2007).

6.4 Forcing

The MPAS framework includes a forcing module designed to perform time interpolation of forcing data. MPAS-Seaice currently implements a single forcing option which repeats the methods used by Hunke et al. (2013). Air temperature, air specific humidity and air velocity at 10 m height and six-hourly frequency are taken from the Coordinated Ocean-ice Reference Experiments (CORE) Corrected Inter-Annual Forcing Version 2.0 (Large and Yeager, 2009; Griffies et al., 2009). Monthly climatologies of precipitation (Griffies et al., 2009) and cloudiness (Röske, 2001) are also used. Downwelling shortwave radiation is calculated from the monthly climatology of cloudiness using the AOMIP shortwave forcing formula (Hunke et al., 2015). Downwelling longwave radiation is calculated according to Rosati and Miyakoda (1988). Oceanic inputs, consisting of sea surface salinity, initial sea surface temperature, currents, sea-surface slope and deep ocean heat flux, come from monthly mean output of 20 years of a Community Climate System Model (CCSM) climate run (b30.009, Collins et al., 2006). All input forcing fields are interpolated linearly in time, although the MPAS forcing functionality can be easily extended to allow interpolation in time with arbitrary order.

6.5 Biogeochemistry

There are two options for modeling biogeochemistry in sea ice: 1) a skeletal layer or bottom layer model (skl-model) that assumes biology and biogeochemical molecules are restricted to a single layer at the base of the sea ice; and 2) a vertically resolved model (zbgc) that allows for biogeochemical processes throughout the ice column. The two models may be run with the same suite of biogeochemical tracers and use the same set of nonlinear coupled equations to determine the biochemical reaction terms for the tracers at each vertical grid level. In the case of the skeletal layer model this is a single layer, while for zbgc there are `nBioLayers`+1 vertical layers. The primary difference between the two schemes is in the vertical transport assumptions for each biogeochemical tracer. This includes the parameterizations of fluxes between ocean and ice.

For both models, there are configuration variables that, in part, specify the complexity of the ecosystem. In `Registry.xml` these are 1) `nAlgae`, the number of algal species; 2) `nDOC`, the number of dissolved organic carbon groups, 3) `nDIC`, the number of dissolved inorganic carbon groups, 4) `nDON`, the number of dissolved organic nitrogen groups, 5) `nParticulateIron`, the number of particulate iron groups; and 6) `nDissolvedIron`, the number of dissolved iron groups. The current version of the biochemistry has parameters for up to 3 algal species (diatoms, small phytoplankton and *Phaeocystis* sp, respectively), 2 dissolved organic carbon (DOC) tracers (polysaccharids and lipids, respectively), 0 dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) tracers, 1 dissolved organic nitrogen (DON) tracer (proteins/amino acids), 1 particulate iron tracer and 1 dissolved iron tracer. However the carbon, DOC and DIC, tracers are not fully implented in this version and should not be used out of the box. Note also that for tracers with multiple species/groups, the order is important. For example, specifying `nALG= 1` will compute reaction terms using parameters specific to ice diatoms.

In addition to specifying the group size, individual biogeochemical tracer groups must also be set as true in `namelist.seaice`. These includes the nutrients: nitrate (`config_use_nitrate`), silicate (`config_use_silicate`), ammonium (`config_use_ammonium`), and dissolved iron (`config_use_iron`); the dimethylsulphide group: DMS, DMSPp, DMSPd (`config_use_DMS`); carbon: DOC and DIC (`config_use_carbon`); DON (`config_use_DON`); humic material (`config_use_humics`); a non-adsorptive passive tracer (`config_use_nonreactive`); and particulate and dissolved iron (`config_use_iron`).

Biogeochemical upper ocean concentrations are initialized in the subroutine `colpkg_init_ocean_conc` in `ice.colpkg.F90` using a default set of fixed values unless coupled to the ocean biogeochemistry. In coupled ice-ocean biogeochemical simulations, ocean surface concentrations for diatoms, small plankton, *Phaeocystis* sp, nitrate, silicate, ammonium, and dissolved iron are passed to the sea ice biogeochemistry. The sea ice computes return fluxes based on the local brine fluxes, and/or ice growth and melt rates.

6.5.1 Skeletal Layer BGC

In the skeletal layer model, ice algal biogeochemistry is modelled as a single layer of reactive tracers attached to the sea ice bottom. This assumption has greater validity in the Arctic than in the Southern Ocean where internal and freeboard communitites are common. To use skl-bgc, set the following `namelist.seaice` configuration options to true: `config_use_brine`, `config_use_column_biogeochemistry`, `config_use_skeletal_biogeochemistry`.

Skeletal tracers (T_b) are ice area (a_i) conserved and, for each thickness category n , satisfy the horizontal transport equation:

$$\frac{\partial(T_{bn}a_{in})}{\partial t} + \Delta \cdot (T_{bn}a_{in}\mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (6.61)$$

for horizontal velocity \mathbf{u} .

In addition, the column biogeochemistry solves a coupled set of reaction equations which define transformations between biogeochemical tracers and computes fluxes between the ice and ocean:

$$\frac{\partial T_b}{\partial t} = w_b \frac{\Delta T_b}{\Delta z} + R_b(T_j : j = 1, \dots, N_b) \quad (6.62)$$

where R_b represents the nonlinear biochemical reaction terms (described in section 6.5.9) and Δz is a length scale representing the molecular sublayer of the ice-ocean interface. Its value is absorbed in the piston velocity parameters. The piston velocity w_b depends on the particular tracer and the flux formulation. There are two types of ice-ocean tracer flux formulations: 1) ‘Jin2006’ modelled after the growth rate dependent piston velocity of Jin et al. (2006) and 2) ‘constant’ which sets the piston velocity to a constant (Elliott et al. (2012)). The formulation is chosen in `namelist.seaice` by setting `config_skeletal_bgc_flux_type` equal to ‘Jin2006’ or ‘constant’.

The default parameterization, ‘Jin2006’, assumes the piston velocity is a function of ice growth and melt rates. All tracers (algae included) flux with the same piston velocity during ice thickness growth, $dh_i/dt > 0$:

$$w_b = -p_g \left| m_1 + m_2 \frac{dh_i}{dt} - m_3 \left(\frac{dh_i}{dt} \right)^2 \right| \quad (6.63)$$

with parameters m_1 , m_2 , m_3 and p_g defined in `skl_biogeochemistry` in `ice_algae.F90`. For ice melt, $dh_i/dt < 0$, all tracers with the exception of ice algae flux with

$$w_b = p_m \left| m_2 \frac{dh}{dt} - m_3 \left(\frac{dh}{dt} \right)^2 \right| \quad (6.64)$$

with p_m defined in `skl_biogeochemistry`. The ‘Jin2006’ formulation also requires that for both expressions, $|w_b| \leq 0.9h_{sk}/\Delta t$ where $h_{sk} = 0.03 m$ is the skeletal layer thickness. The concentration difference at the ice-ocean boundary for each tracer, ΔT_b , depends on the sign of w_b . For growing ice, $w_b < 0$, $\Delta T_b = T_b/h_{sk} - T_{io}$, where T_{io} is the ocean concentration of tracer i . For melting ice, $w_b > 0$, $\Delta T_b = T_b/h_{sk}$.

In ‘Jin2006’, the algal tracer (N_a) responds to ice melt in the same manner as the other tracers (6.64). However, during ice growth, the skeletal algal concentration remains fixed unless the ice algal brine concentration is less than the ocean algal concentration (N_o). In this case, the ocean seeds the sea ice according to

$$w_b \frac{\Delta N_a}{\Delta z} = \frac{N_o h_{sk} / \phi_{sk} - N_a}{\Delta t} \quad (6.65)$$

where $\phi_{sk} = 0.3$ is the skeletal layer porosity.

The ‘constant’ formulation uses a fixed piston velocity for positive ice growth rates for all tracers except N_a . As in ‘Jin2006’, congelation ice growth seeds the sea ice algal population according to (6.65) when $N_a < N_o h_{sk} / \phi_{sk}$. For bottom ice melt, all tracers follow the prescription

$$w_b \frac{\Delta T_b}{\Delta z} = \begin{cases} T_b |dh_i/dt| / h_{sk} & \text{if } |dh_i/dt| \Delta t / h_{sk} < 1 \\ T_b / \Delta t & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (6.66)$$

A detailed description of the biogeochemistry reaction terms is given in section 6.5.9.

6.5.2 Vertical “Z” BGC

In order to solve the vertically resolved biogeochemistry, set the following configuration options in `namelist.seaice` to true: a) `config_use_brine`, b) `config_use_vertical_tracers`, and c) `config_use_vertical_biochemistry`.

- a) `config_use_brine` true, turns on the dynamic brine fraction tracer, f_b , (see section 6.5.6) which defines the vertical domain of the biogeochemical tracers. z-Tracer horizontal transport is conserved on ice volume \times brine height fraction.
- b) `config_use_vertical_tracers` true, indicates use of vertically resolved biogeochemical and z-aerosol tracers. This flag alone turns on the vertical transport scheme but not the biochemistry.
- c) `config_use_vertical_biochemistry` true, turns on the biochemistry for the vertically resolved tracers and automatically turns on the algal nitrogen. If false, algal nitrogen is not transported and any other biogeochemical tracers in use is transported as a passive tracer. This is appropriate for the black carbon and dust aerosols specified by `config_use_zaerosols` true.

In addition, a halodynamics scheme must also be on. The default thermo-halodynamics is mushy layer `config_thermodynamics_type` set to 2. An alternative uses Bitz and Lipscomb (1999)’s thermodynamics (`config_thermodynamics_type` set to 1) and `config_use_vertical_salinity` true (referred to as “zsalinity”).

Vertically resolved z-tracer bulk concentrations (T_{zb}) are brine volume fraction conserved and thus depend on both the ice volume (v_i) and the brine height fraction tracer (f_b). These tracers follow the conservation equations for multiply dependent tracers:

$$\frac{\partial(T_{zbn}v_{in}f_{bn})}{\partial t} + \Delta \cdot (T_{zbn}v_{in}f_{bn}\mathbf{u}) = 0. \quad (6.67)$$

The following sections describe the vertical biological grid, the vertical transport equation for mobile tracers, the partitioning of tracers into mobile and stationary fractions and the biochemical reaction equations.

6.5.3 Bio grid

The bio grid is a vertical grid used for solving the brine height variable ($h_b = f_b h_i$) and discretizing the vertical transport equations of biogeochemical tracers. The grid is non-dimensional and takes the value zero at the brine surface and one at the ice-ocean interface. The number of grid levels is specified during Registry.xml by setting the variable `nBioLayers` integer (n_b).

Ice tracers and microstructural properties defined on the bio grid are referenced in two ways: as 1) $n_b + 2$ `bgrid` points and 2) $n_b + 1$ `igrid` points. For both `bgrid` and `igrid`, the first and last points reference the brine surface and the ice-ocean interface and so take the values 0 and 1, respectively. For `bgrid`, the interior points $[2, n_b + 1]$ are spaced at $1/n_b$ intervals beginning with `bgrid(2) = 1/(2n_b)`. The `igrid` interior points $[2, n_b]$ are also equidistant with the same spacing, but physically coincide with points midway between those of the `bgrid`.

Transport along the interface bio grid

Purely mobile biogeochemical tracers are tracers which move with the brine and thus, in the absence of biochemical reactions, evolve in a manner like salinity. In the vertical tracer transport of purely

mobile tracers, the flux conserved quantity is the bulk tracer concentration multiplied by the ice thickness, i.e. $C = h\phi[c]$, where h is the ice thickness, ϕ is the porosity, and $[c]$ is the tracer concentration in the brine. ϕ , $[c]$ and C are defined on the interface bio grid (igrid):

$$\text{igrid}(k) = \Delta(k-1) \quad \text{for } k = 1 : n_b + 1 \quad (6.68)$$

and $\Delta = 1/n_b$

The biogeochemical module solves the equation:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left\{ \left(\frac{v}{h} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi} - \frac{\tilde{D}}{h^2\phi^2} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \right) C + \frac{\tilde{D}}{h^2\phi} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \right\} + h\phi R([c]) \quad (6.69)$$

where $D_{in} = \tilde{D}/h^2 = (D + \phi D_m)/h^2$ (Jeffery et al. (2011)) and $R([c])$ is the nonlinear biogeochemical interaction term.

Solutions to (6.69) are found using a flux-corrected and positive definite finite element Galerkin discretization. Details are in section 6.5.10.

6.5.4 Splitting tracers: config_mobility_type

In addition to purely mobile tracers such as nitrate, some biogeochemical tracers also adsorb or otherwise adhere to the ice crystals. These tracers exist in both the mobile and stationary phase and their total brine concentration is a sum $c_m + c_s$ where c_m is the mobile fraction transported by (6.69) and c_s remains vertically fixed during ice growth/melt and brine motion. The primary algal group, discussed below, are a notable exception.

In order to model the transfer between these fractions, we assume that tracers adhere to the crystals with a time-constant of τ_{ret} , and release with a time constant τ_{rel} , i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial c_m}{\partial t} &= -\frac{c_m}{\tau_{ret}} + \frac{c_s}{\tau_{rel}} \\ \frac{\partial c_s}{\partial t} &= \frac{c_m}{\tau_{ret}} - \frac{c_s}{\tau_{rel}} \end{aligned} \quad (6.70)$$

We use the exponential form of these equations:

$$\begin{aligned} c_m^{t+dt} &= c_m^t \exp\left(\left\{-\frac{dt}{\tau_{ret}}\right\}\right) + c_s^t \left(1 - \exp\left[-\left\{\frac{dt}{\tau_{rel}}\right\}\right]\right) \\ c_s^{t+dt} &= c_s^t \exp\left(\left\{-\frac{dt}{\tau_{rel}}\right\}\right) + c_m^t \left(1 - \exp\left[-\left\{\frac{dt}{\tau_{rel}}\right\}\right]\right) \end{aligned}$$

The time constants are functions of the ice growth and melt rates (dh/dt). All tracers except algal nitrogen diatoms follow the simple case: when $dh/dt \geq 0$, then $\tau_{rel} \rightarrow \infty$ and τ_{ret} is finite. For $dh/dt < 0$, then $\tau_{ret} \rightarrow \infty$ and τ_{rel} is finite. In other words, ice growth promotes transitions to the stationary phase and ice melt enables transitions to the mobile phase.

The adsorption of tracers is also bound by a saturation concentration which is determined from geometric properties of the ice crystals (assumed to be spheres), and the size and shape of the adsorbing particle (prolate spheroids) (Johnson et al. (1995)). When the stationary concentration reaches or exceeds the saturation concentration, adsorption stops and the additional material remains in the mobile phase.

Table 6.1: Types of Mobile and Stationary Transitions

<code>config_mobility_type</code>	τ_{ret}	τ_{rel}	Description
-1	∞	0	entirely in the mobile phase
0	min	max	retention dominated
1	max	min	release dominated
0.5	min	min	equal but rapid exchange
2	max	max	equal but slow exchange

Diatoms are somewhat unique in that they have the ability to move independently. Although we do not model motility in an advective sense, we assume that diatoms, the first algal nitrogen group, actively maintain their relative position within the ice, i.e. bottom (interior, upper) algae remain in the bottom (interior, upper) ice, unless melt rates exceed a threshold. The configuration parameter `config_algal_maximum_velocity` sets this threshold.

6.5.5 Mobile and Stationary Phases

There are 5 possible mobility types indicated by the set $\{-1, 0, 0.5, 1, 2\}$ which assigns a combination of a fast and slow timescale to the release and retention of tracers. In `namelist.seaice`, the parameters beginning `config_mobility_type_` specify the vertical transport behavior of each biogeochemical in the code and `config_long_mobile_to_stationary_time` and `config_rapid_mobile_to_stationary_time` define the maximum (slow) and minimum (fast) timescales (rates). For a mobility type of -1, the tracer remains solely in the mobile phase throughout the simulation. This is the default for nitrate and silicate. For mobility types of 0, the tracer has maximal rates (i.e. minimum timescale) of retention and slow rates (i.e. maximum timescale) of release back to the mobile phase. For a value of 1, the tracer has slow rates in the retention phase and fast release to mobility. For a mobility type of 0.5, minimum timescales are used for both transitions, and for a value of 2, maximal timescales are used. Table 6.1 summarizes the transition types.

The fraction of a given tracer in the mobile phase is independent of ice depth and stored in the tracer variable `zbgc_frac`. The horizontal transport of this tracer is conserved on brine volume fraction and so is dependent on two tracers: brine height fraction (f_b) and ice volume (v_{in}) (6.67). The tracer, `zbgc_frac`, is initialized to 1 during new ice formation because all z-tracers are assumed to be initially in the purely mobile phase. As the ice melts, z-tracers return to the mobile phase. Very large release timescales will prevent this transition and could result in an unphysically large accumulation during the melt season.

6.5.6 Brine Fraction Tracer

The brine height, h_b , is the distance from the ice-ocean interface to the brine surface. It is the vertical domain for all ice biogeochemical tracers and aerosols. When `config_use_brine` is set true in `namelist.seaice` the position of the brine surface relative moves relative to the ice surface. Physically, this occurs when the ice is permeable and there is a nonzero pressure head: the difference between the brine height and the equilibrium sea surface. Brine height motion is computed in `ice.brine.F90` from thermodynamic variables and the ice microstructural state deduced from internal bulk salinities and temperature. This tracer is required for the transport of vertically resolved biogeochemical tracers.

Vertical transport processes are, generally, a result of the brine motion. Therefore the vertical transport equations for biogeochemical tracers will be defined only where brine is present. This region, from the ice-ocean interface to the brine height, defines the domain of the vertical bio-grid (section 6.5.3). The ice microstructural state, determined in `ice_brine.F90`, is computed from sea ice salinities and temperatures linearly interpolated to the bio-grid. When $h_b > h_i$, the upper surface brine is assumed to have the same temperature as the ice surface.

Brine height is transported horizontally as the fraction $f_b = h_b/h_i$, a volume conserved tracer. Note that unlike the sea ice porosity, brine height fraction may be greater than 1 when $h_b > h_i$.

Changes to h_b occur from ice and snow melt, ice bottom boundary changes, and from pressure adjustments. The computation of h_b at $t + \Delta t$ is a two step process. First, h_b is updated from changes in ice and snow thickness (h_s), i.e.

$$h'_b = h_b(t) + \Delta h_b|_{h_i, h_s} \quad . \quad (6.71)$$

Second, pressure driven adjustments arising from meltwater flushing and snow loading are applied to h'_b . Brine flow due to pressure forces are governed by Darcy's equation:

$$w = -\frac{\Pi^* \bar{\rho} g h_p}{\mu h_i} \quad (6.72)$$

where μ is the viscosity and g is the gravitational acceleration. The vertical component of the net permeability tensor Π^* is computed as

$$\Pi^* = \left(\frac{1}{h} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\Delta z_i}{\Pi_i} \right)^{-1} \quad (6.73)$$

where the sea ice is composed of N vertical layers with i th layer thickness Δz_i and permeability Π_i . The average sea ice density is $\bar{\rho}$. The hydraulic head is $h_p = h_b - h_{sl}$ where h_{sl} is the sea level given by

$$h_{sl} = \frac{\bar{\rho}}{\rho_w} h_i + \frac{\rho_s}{\rho_w} h_s \quad . \quad (6.74)$$

where ρ_s is the snow density and ρ_w is the density of water. Assuming constant h_i and h_s during Darcy flow, the rate of change of h_b is

$$\frac{\partial h_b}{\partial t} = -w h_p \quad (6.75)$$

where $w_o = \Pi^* \bar{\rho} g / (h_i \mu \phi_{top})$ and ϕ_{top} is the upper surface porosity. When the Darcy flow is downward into the ice ($w_o < 0$), the ϕ_{top} equals the sea ice porosity in the uppermost layer. However, when the flow is upwards into the snow, then ϕ_{top} equals the snow porosity `phi_snow` specified in the namelist `config_snow_porosity_at_ice_surface`. If a negative number is specified, then the default value is used: `phi_snow = 1 - \rho_s / \rho_w`.

Since h_{sl} remains relatively unchanged during Darcy flow, (6.75) has the approximate solution

$$h_b(t + \Delta t) \approx h_{sl}(t + \Delta t) + [h'_b - h_{sl}(t + \Delta t)] \exp \{-w \Delta t\} \quad (6.76)$$

The contribution $\Delta h_b|_{h_i, h_s}$ arises from snow and ice melt and bottom ice changes. Since the ice and brine bottom boundaries coincide, changes in the ice bottom from growth or melt, $(\Delta h_i)_{bot}$, equal the bottom brine boundary changes. The surface contribution from ice and snow melt,

however, is opposite in sign. The ice contribution is as follows. If $h_i > h_b$ and the ice surface is melting, ie. $(\Delta h_i)_{top} < 0$, then meltwater increases the brine height:

$$(\Delta h_b)_{top} = \frac{\rho_i}{\rho_o} \cdot \begin{cases} -(\Delta h_i)_{top} & \text{if } |(\Delta h_i)_{top}| < h_i - h_b \\ h_i - h_b & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (6.77)$$

For snow melt ($\Delta h_s < 0$), it is assumed that all snow meltwater contributes a source of surface brine. The total change from snow melt and ice thickness changes is

$$\Delta h_b|_{h_i, h_s} = (\Delta h_b)_{top} - (\Delta h_i)_{bot} - \frac{\rho_s}{\rho_o} \Delta h_s. \quad (6.78)$$

The above brine height calculation is used only when h_i and h_b exceed a minimum thickness, `thinS`, specified in `ice_zbgc_shared`. Otherwise

$$h_b(t + \Delta t) = h_b(t) + \Delta h_i \quad (6.79)$$

provided that $|h_{sl} - h_b| \leq 0.001$. This formulation ensures small Darcy velocities when h_b first exceeds `thinS`.

6.5.7 Standard Aerosols

The standard aerosol scheme was developed in CCSM4 and its impacts described by [Holland et al. \(2012b\)](#). Briefly, aerosols deposited on the ice gradually work their way through until the ice melts and they are passed into the ocean. They are defined as ice and snow volume tracers, with the snow and ice each having two tracers for each aerosol species, one in the surface scattering layer (delta-Eddington SSL) and one in the snow or ice interior below the SSL.

Rather than updating aerosols for each change to ice/snow thickness due to evaporation, melting, snow-ice formation, etc., during the thermodynamics calculation, these changes are deduced from the ice diagnostic variables (`melts`, `meltb`, `snoice`, etc) in `ice_aerosol.F90`. Three processes change the volume of ice or snow but do not change the total amount of aerosol, thus causing the aerosol concentration (the value of the tracer itself) to change: evaporation, snow deposition and basal ice growth. Basal and lateral melting remove all aerosols in the melted portion. Surface ice and snow melt leave a significant fraction of the aerosols behind, but they do scavenge some fraction given by the parameter `kscav` = [0.03, 0.2, 0.02, 0.02, 0.01, 0.01]. Scavenging also applies to snow-ice formation. When sea ice ridges, a fraction of the snow on the ridging ice is thrown into the ocean, and any aerosols in that fraction are also lost to the ocean.

As upper SSL or interior layers disappear from the snow or ice, aerosols are transferred to the next lower layer, or into the ocean when no ice remains. The atmospheric flux `faero_atm` contains the rates of aerosol deposition for each species, while `faero_ocn` has the rate at which the aerosols are transferred to the ocean.

The aerosol tracer flag `config_use_aerosols` must be set to true in `namelist.seaice`, and the number of aerosol species, `nAerosols`, is set in `Registry.xml`. The following output variables may be added to `streams.seaice`: `snowScatteringAerosol`, `snowBodyAerosol`, `iceScatteringAerosol`, and `iceBodyAerosol`.

6.5.8 Z-Aerosols

MPAS-Seaice offers an alternate scheme for aerosols in sea ice using the brine motion based transport scheme of the biogeochemical tracers. All vertically resolved biogeochemical tracers (z-tracers),

including zaerosols, have the potential to be atmospherically deposited onto the snow or ice, scavenged during snow melt, and passed into the brine. The mobile fraction (section 6.5.5) is then transported via brine drainage processes (6.69) while a stationary fraction (section 6.5.5) adheres to the ice crystals. Snow deposition and the process of scavenging aerosols during snow melt is consistent with the default aerosol scheme, though parameters have been generalized to accommodate potential atmospheric deposition for all z-tracers. For an example, see the scavenging parameter `kscavz` for z-tracers defined in `ice_zbgc_shared`.

Within the snow, z-tracers are defined as concentrations in the snow surface layer (h_{ssl}) and the snow interior ($h_s - h_{ssl}$). The total snow content of z-tracers per ice area per grid cell area, C_{snow} is

$$C_{snow} = C_{ssl}h_{ssl} + C_{sint}(h_s - h_{ssl}) \quad (6.80)$$

One major difference in how the two schemes model snow aerosol transport is that the fraction scavenged from snow melt in the z-tracer scheme is not immediately fluxed into the ocean, but rather, enters the ice as a source of low salinity but potentially tracer rich brine. The snow melt source is included as a surface flux condition in `ice_algae.F90`.

All the z-aerosols are nonreactive with the exception of the dust aerosols. We assume that a small fraction of the dust flux into the ice has soluble iron which is passed to the dissolved iron tracer (see `config_solubility_of_Fe_in_dust` and `config_ratio_Fe_to_dust` in `namelist.seaice`). The remaining dust passes through the ice without reactions.

To use z-aerosols, set `config_use_zaerosols` to true in `namelist.seaice` and choose up to 6 z-aerosol species `nAerosols` in `Registry.xml`. Note, the default tracers `config_use_aerosols` must be false. In addition, `config_use_brine` and `config_use_vertical_tracers` z-tracers and the brine height tracer must also be true. In addition, to turn on the radiative coupling between the aerosols and the Delta-Eddington radiative scheme, `config_shortwave_type` must equal `dEdd` and `config_use_shortwave_bioabsorption` must be true.

6.5.9 Biogeochemical Reactions

The biogeochemical reaction terms for each biogeochemical tracer (see table 6.2 for tracer definitions) are defined in `ice_algae.F90` in the subroutine `algal_dyn`. The same set of equations is used for the bottom layer model (when `config_use_skeletal_biochemistry` is true) and the multi-layer biogeochemical model (when `config_use_vertical_biochemistry` and `config_use_vertical_tracers` are true).

The biochemical reaction term for each algal species has the form:

$$\Delta N/dt = R_N = \mu(1 - f_{graze} - f_{res}) - M_{ort} \quad (6.81)$$

where μ is the algal growth rate, M_{ort} is a mortality loss, f_{graze} is the fraction of algal growth that is lost to predatory grazing, and f_{res} is the fraction of algal growth lost to respiration. Algal mortality is temperature dependent and limited by a maximum loss rate fraction (l_{max}):

$$M_{ort} = \min(l_{max}[N], m_{pre} \exp\{m_T(T - T_{max})\}[N]) \quad (6.82)$$

Note, $[\dots]$ denotes brine concentration.

Table 6.2: Biogeochemical Tracers

Text Variable	Variable in code	flag config_use_	Description	units
N(1)	Nin(1)	vertical_biochemistry ^c	diatom	mmol N/m^3
N(2)	Nin(2)	vertical_biochemistry ^c	small phytoplankton	mmol N/m^3
N(3)	Nin(3)	vertical_biochemistry ^c	<i>Phaeocystis sp</i>	mmol N/m^3
DOC(1)	DOCin(1)	carbon	polysaccharids	mmol C/m^3
DOC(2)	DOCin(2)	carbon	lipids	mmol C/m^3
DON	DONin(1)	DON	proteins	mmol N/m^3
fed	Fedin(1)	iron	dissolved iron	$\mu\text{mol } Fe/m^3$
fep	Fepin(1)	iron	particulate iron	$\mu\text{mol } Fe/m^3$
NO ₃	Nitin	nitrate	NO ₃	mmol N/m^3
NH ₄	Amin	ammonium	NH ₄	mmol N/m^3
SiO ₃	Silin	silicate	SiO ₃	mmol Si/m^3
DMSPp	DMSPpin	DMS	particulate DMSP	mmol S/m^3
DMSPd	DMSPdin	DMS	dissolved DMSP	mmol S/m^3
DMS	DMSin	DMS	DMS	mmol S/m^3
PON	PON ^a	nonreactive	passive mobile tracer	mmol N/m^3
hum	hum ^{ab}	humics	passive sticky tracer	mmol $/m^3$
BC(1)	zaero(1) ^a	zaerosols	black carbon species 1	kg $/m^3$
BC(2)	zaero(2) ^a	zaerosols	black carbon species 2	kg $/m^3$
dust(1)	zaero(3) ^a	zaerosols	dust species 1	kg $/m^3$
dust(2)	zaero(4) ^a	zaerosols	dust species 2	kg $/m^3$
dust(3)	zaero(5) ^a	zaerosols	dust species 3	kg $/m^3$
dust(4)	zaero(6) ^a	zaerosols	dust species 4	kg $/m^3$

^a not modified in `algal_dyn`

^b may be in C or N units depending on the ocean concentration

^c `skeletal_biochemistry` when using the `skl-model`

Nitrate and ammonium reaction terms are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta\text{NO}_3/dt &= R_{\text{NO}_3} = [\text{NH}_4]k_{\text{nit}} - U_{\text{NO}_3}^{\text{tot}} \\
\Delta\text{NH}_4/dt &= R_{\text{NH}_4} = -[\text{NH}_4]k_{\text{nit}} - U_{\text{NH}_4}^{\text{tot}} + (f_{ng}f_{graze}(1 - f_{gs}) + f_{res})\mu^{\text{tot}} \\
&\quad + f_{nm}M_{ort} \\
&= -[\text{NH}_4]k_{\text{nit}} - U_{\text{NH}_4}^{\text{tot}} + N_{remin}
\end{aligned} \tag{6.83}$$

where the uptake U^{tot} and algal growth μ^{tot} are accumulated totals for all algal species. k_{nit} is the nitrification rate and f_{ng} and f_{nm} are the fractions of grazing and algal mortality that are remineralized to ammonium and f_{gs} is the fraction of grazing spilled or lost. Algal growth and nutrient uptake terms are described below in more detail.

Dissolved organic nitrogen satisfies the equation

$$\Delta\text{DON}/dt = R_{\text{DON}} = f_{dg}f_{gs}f_{graze}\mu^{\text{tot}} - [\text{DON}]k_{nb} \tag{6.84}$$

With a loss from bacterial degradation (rate k_{nb}) and a gain from spilled grazing that does not enter the NH_4 pool.

A term Z_{oo} closes the nitrogen cycle by summing all the excess nitrogen removed as zooplankton/bacteria in a timestep. This term is not a true tracer, i.e. not advected horizontally with the ice motion, but provides a diagnostic comparison of the amount of N removed biogeochemically from the ice N - NO_3 - NH_4 -DON cycle at each timestep.

$$Z_{oo} = [(1 - f_{ng}(1 - f_{gs}) - f_{dg}f_{gs})f_{graze}\mu^{tot}dt + (1 - f_{nm})M_{ort}dt + [\text{DON}]k_{nb}dt$$

Dissolved organic carbon may be divided into polysaccharids and lipids. Parameters are two dimensional (indicated by superscript i) with index 1 corresponding to polysaccharids and index 2 appropriate for lipids. The DOC^i equation is:

$$\Delta\text{DOC}^i/dt = R_{\text{DOC}} = f_{cg}^i f_{ng}\mu^{tot} + R_{c:n}^i M_{ort} - [\text{DOC}]k_{cb}^i \quad (6.85)$$

Silicate has no biochemical source terms within the ice and is lost only through algal uptake:

$$\Delta\text{SiO}_3/dt = R_{\text{SiO}_3} = -U_{\text{SiO}_3}^{tot} \quad (6.86)$$

Dissolved iron has algal uptake and remineralization pathways. In addition, fed may be converted to or released from the particulate iron pool depending on the dissolved iron (fed) to polysaccharid ($\text{DOC}(1)$) concentration ratio. If this ratio exceeds a maximum value $r_{fed:doc}^{max}$ then the change in concentration for dissolved and particulate iron is

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{fe} \text{fed}/dt &= -[\text{fed}]/\tau_{fe} \\ \Delta_{fe} \text{fep}/dt &= [\text{fed}]/\tau_{fe} \end{aligned} \quad (6.87)$$

For values less than $r_{fed:doc}^{max}$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{fe} \text{fed}/dt &= [\text{fep}]/\tau_{fe} \\ \Delta_{fe} \text{fep}/dt &= -[\text{fep}]/\tau_{fe} \end{aligned} \quad (6.88)$$

Very long timescales τ_{fe} will remove this source/sink term. Since carbon is not yet fully implemented, the default value is currently set at 3065 days to turn off this dependency. 61-65 days is a more realistic option (Parekh et al. (2004)).

The full equation for fed including uptake and remineralization is

$$\Delta\text{fed}/dt = R_{\text{fed}} = -U_{\text{fed}}^{tot} + f_{fa}R_{fe:n}N_{remin} + \Delta_{fe} \text{fed}/dt \quad (6.89)$$

Particulate iron also includes a source term from algal mortality and grazing that is not immediately bioavailable. The full equation for fep is

$$\Delta\text{fep}/dt = R_{\text{fep}} = R_{fe:n}[Z_{oo}/dt + (1 - f_{fa})]N_{remin} + \Delta_{fe} \text{fep}/dt \quad (6.90)$$

The sulfur cycle includes DMS and dissolved DMSP (DMSPd). Particulate DMSP is assumed to be proportional to the algal concentration, i.e. $\text{DMSPp} = R_{s:n}^i N^i$ for algal species i . For DMSP and DMS,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\text{DMSPd}/dt &= R_{\text{DMSPd}} = R_{s:n}[f_{sr}f_{res}\mu^{tot} + f_{nm}M_{ort}] - [\text{DMSPd}]/\tau_{dmsp} \\ \Delta\text{DMS}/dt &= R_{\text{DMS}} = y_{dms}[\text{DMSPd}]/\tau_{dmsp} - [\text{DMS}]/\tau_{dms} \end{aligned} \quad (6.91)$$

See Table 6.3 for a more complete list and description of biogeochemical parameters.

Algal Growth and Nutrient Uptake

Nutrient limitation terms are defined, in the simplest ecosystem, for NO_3 . If the appropriate tracer flags are true, then limitation terms may also be found for NH_4 , SiO_3 , and fed

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{NO}_{3lim} &= \frac{[\text{NO}_3]}{[\text{NO}_3] + K_{\text{NO}_3}} \\
 \text{NH}_{4lim} &= \frac{[\text{NH}_4]}{[\text{NH}_4] + K_{\text{NH}_4}} \\
 N_{lim} &= \min(1, \text{NO}_{3lim} + \text{NH}_{4lim}) \\
 \text{SiO}_{3lim} &= \frac{[\text{SiO}_3]}{[\text{SiO}_3] + K_{\text{SiO}_3}} \\
 \text{fed}_{lim} &= \frac{[\text{fed}]}{[\text{fed}] + K_{\text{fed}}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{6.92}$$

Light limitation L_{lim} is defined in the following way: $I_{sw}(z)$ (in W/m^2) is the shortwave radiation at the ice level and the optical depth is proportional to the chlorophyll concentration, $op_{dep} = chlabs[\text{Chla}]$. If ($op_{dep} > op_{min}$) then

$$I_{avg} = I_{sw}(1 - \exp(-op_{dep}))/op_{dep}$$

otherwise $I_{avg} = I_{sw}$.

$$L_{lim} = (1 - \exp(-\alpha \cdot I_{avg})) \exp(-\beta \cdot I_{avg}) \tag{6.93}$$

The maximal algal growth rate before limitation is

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mu_o &= \mu_{max} \exp(\mu_T \Delta T) f_{sal}[\text{N}] \\
 \mu' &= \min(L_{lim}, N_{lim}, \text{SiO}_{3lim}, \text{fed}_{lim}) \mu_o
 \end{aligned} \tag{6.94}$$

where μ' is the initial estimate of algal growth rate for a given algal species and ΔT is the difference between the local temperature and the maximum (in this case $T_{max} = 0^\circ\text{C}$).

The initial estimate of the uptake rate for silicate and iron is

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{U}_{\text{SiO}_3} &= R_{si:n} \mu' \\
 \tilde{U}_{\text{fed}} &= R_{fe:n} \mu'
 \end{aligned} \tag{6.95}$$

For nitrogen uptake, we assume that ammonium is preferentially acquired by algae. To determine the nitrogen uptake needed for each algal growth rate of μ , first determine the potential uptake rate of ammonium:

$$U'_{\text{NH}_4} = \text{NH}_{4lim} \mu_o \tag{6.96}$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{U}_{\text{NH}_4} &= \min(\mu', U'_{\text{NH}_4}) \\
 \tilde{U}_{\text{NO}_3} &= \mu' - \tilde{U}_{\text{NH}_4}
 \end{aligned} \tag{6.97}$$

We require that each rate not exceed a maximum loss rate l_{max}/dt . This is particularly important when multiple species are present. In this case, the accumulated uptake rate for each nutrient is found and the fraction (fU^i) of uptake due to algal species i is saved. Then the total uptake rate is compared with the maximum loss condition. For example, the net uptake of nitrate when there are three algal species is

$$\tilde{U}_{\text{NO}_3}^{\text{tot}} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \tilde{U}_{\text{NO}_3}^i .$$

Then the uptake fraction for species i and the adjusted total uptake is

$$\begin{aligned} fU_{\text{NO}_3}^i &= \frac{\tilde{U}_{\text{NO}_3}^i}{\tilde{U}_{\text{NO}_3}^{\text{tot}}} \\ U_{\text{NO}_3}^{\text{tot}} &= \min(\tilde{U}_{\text{NO}_3}^{\text{tot}}, l_{max}[\text{NO}_3]/dt) \end{aligned} \quad (6.98)$$

Now, for each algal species the nitrate uptake is

$$U_{\text{NO}_3}^i = fU_{\text{NO}_3}^i U_{\text{NO}_3}^{\text{tot}} \quad (6.99)$$

Similar expressions are found for all potentially limiting nutrients. Then the true growth rate for each algal species i is

$$\mu^i = \min(U_{\text{SiO}_3}^i/R_{si:n}, U_{\text{NO}_3}^i + U_{\text{NH}_4}^i, U_{\text{fed}}^i/R_{fe:n}) \quad (6.100)$$

Preferential ammonium uptake is assumed once again and the remaining nitrogen is taken from the nitrate pool.

BGC Tuning Parameters

Biogeochemical tuning parameters are specified as namelist options in **namelist.seaice**. Table 6.3 provides a list of parameters used in the above reaction equations, their representation in subroutine `algal_dyn`, a short description and units.

6.5.10 Flux-Corrected, Positive Definite Transport Scheme

Numerical solution of the vertical tracer transport equation is accomplished using the finite element Galerkin discretization. Multiply (6.69) by “w” and integrate by parts

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_h \left[w \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \left(- \left[\frac{v}{h} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi} \right] C + \frac{D_{in}}{\phi^2} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} C - \frac{D_{in}}{\phi} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \right) \right] dx \\ + & w \left(- \left[\frac{1}{h} \frac{dh_b}{dt} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi} \right] C + \frac{D_{in}}{\phi^2} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} C - \frac{D_{in}}{\phi} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \right) \Big|_{\text{bot}} + w \left[\frac{1}{h} \frac{dh_t}{dt} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi} \right] C \Big|_{\text{top}} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6.101)$$

The bottom boundary condition indicated by $|_{\text{bot}}$ satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} & -w \left(- \left[\frac{1}{h} \frac{dh_b}{dt} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi} \right] C + \frac{D_{in}}{\phi^2} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} C - \frac{D_{in}}{\phi} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \right) \Big|_{\text{bot}} = \\ & w \left[\frac{1}{h} \frac{dh_b}{dt} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi_{N+1}} \right] (C_{N+2} \text{ or } C_{N+1}) - w \frac{D_{in}}{\phi_{N+1}(\Delta h + g_o)} (C_{N+1} - C_{N+2}) \end{aligned} \quad (6.102)$$

Table 6.3: Biogeochemical Reaction Parameters in subroutine: algal_dyn

Text Variable	Variable in code	Description	units
f_{graze}	fr_graze(1:3)	fraction of growth grazed	1
f_{res}	fr_resp	fraction of growth respired	1
l_{max}	max_loss	maximum tracer loss fraction	1
m_{pre}	mort_pre(1:3)	maximum mortality rate	day ⁻¹
m_T	mort_Tdep(1:3)	mortality temperature decay	°C ⁻¹
T_{max}	T_max	maximum brine temperature	°C
k_{nitr}	k_nitrif	nitrification rate	day ⁻¹
f_{ng}	fr_graze_e	fraction of grazing excreted	1
f_{gs}	fr_graze_s	fraction of grazing spilled	1
f_{nm}	fr_mort2min	fraction of mortality to NH ₄	1
f_{dg}	f_don	frac. spilled grazing to DON	1
k_{nb}	kn_bac	bacterial degradation of DON	day ⁻¹
f_{cg}	f_doc(1:3)	fraction of mortality to DOC	1
$R_{c:n}^c$	R_C2N(1:3)	algal carbon to nitrogen ratio	mol/mol
k_{cb}	k_bac1:3 ^a	bacterial degradation of DOC	day ⁻¹
τ_{fe}	t_iron_conv	conversion time pFe ↔ dFe	day
$r_{fed:doc}^{max}$	max_dfe_doc1	max ratio of dFe to saccharids	nM Fe/ μ M C
f_{fa}	fr_dFe	fraction of remin. N to dFe	1
$R_{fe:n}$	R_Fe2N(1:3)	algal Fe to N ratio	mmol/mol
$R_{s:n}$	R_S2N(1:3)	algal S to N ratio	mol/mol
f_{sr}	fr_resp_s	resp. loss as DMSPd	1
τ_{dmisp}	t_sk_conv	Stefels rate	day
τ_{dms}	t_sk_ox	DMS oxidation rate	day
y_{dms}	y_sk_DMS	yield for DMS conversion	1
K_{NO_3}	K_Nit(1:3)	NO ₃ half saturation constant	mmol/m ³
K_{NH_4}	K_Am(1:3)	NH ₄ half saturation constant	mmol/m ⁻³
K_{SiO_3}	K_Sil(1:3)	silicate half saturation constant	mmol/m ⁻³
K_{fed}	K_Fe(1:3)	iron half saturation constant	μ mol/m ⁻³
op_{min}	op_dep_min	boundary for light attenuation	1
$chlabs$	chlabs(1:3)	light absorption length per chla conc.	1/m/(mg/m ³)
α	alpha2max_low(1:3)	light limitation factor	m ² /W
β	beta2max(1:3)	light inhibition factor	m ² /W
μ_{max}	mu_max(1:3)	maximum algal growth rate	day ⁻¹
μ_T	grow_Tdep(1:3)	temperature growth factor	day ⁻¹
f_{sal}	fsal	salinity growth factor	1
$R_{si:n}$	R_Si2N(1:3)	algal silicate to nitrogen	mol/mol

^a only (1:2) of DOC and DOC parameters have physical meaning

where $C_{N+2} = h\phi_{N+1}[c]_{ocean}$ and $w = 1$ at the bottom boundary and the top. The component C_{N+2} or C_{N+1} depends on the sign of the advection boundary term. If $dh_b + w_f/\phi > 0$ then use C_{N+2} otherwise C_{N+1} .

Define basis functions as linear piecewise, with two nodes (boundary nodes) in each element.

Then for $i > 1$ and $i < N + 1$

$$w_i(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & x < x_{i-1} \\ (x - x_{i-1})/\Delta & x_{i-1} < x \leq x_i \\ 1 - (x - x_i)/\Delta & x_i \leq x < x_{i+1} \\ 0, & x \geq x_{i+1} \end{cases} \quad (6.103)$$

For $i = 1$

$$w_1(x) = \begin{cases} 1 - x/\Delta & x < x_2 \\ 0, & x \geq x_2 \end{cases} \quad (6.104)$$

and $i = N + 1$

$$w_{N+1}(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x < x_N \\ (x - x_N)/\Delta & x \geq x_N \end{cases} \quad (6.105)$$

Now assume a form

$$C_h = \sum_j^{N+1} c_j w_j \quad (6.106)$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \int_h C_h dx &= c_1 \int_0^{x_2} \left(1 - \frac{x}{\Delta}\right) dx + c_{N+1} \int_{x_N}^{x_{N+1}} \frac{x - x_N}{\Delta} dx \\ &+ \sum_{j=2}^N c_j \left\{ \int_{x_{j-1}}^{x_j} \frac{x - x_{j-1}}{\Delta} dx + \int_{x_j}^{x_{j+1}} \left[1 - \frac{(x - x_j)}{\Delta}\right] dx \right\} \\ &= \Delta \left[\frac{c_1}{2} + \frac{c_{N+1}}{2} + \sum_{j=2}^N c_j \right] \end{aligned} \quad (6.107)$$

Now this approximate solution form is substituted into the variational equation with $w = w_h \in \{w_j\}$

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \int_h \left[w_h \frac{\partial C_h}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial w_h}{\partial x} \left(\left[-\frac{v}{h} - \frac{w_f}{h\phi} + \frac{D_{in}}{\phi^2} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \right] C_h - \frac{D_{in}}{\phi} \frac{\partial C_h}{\partial x} \right) \right] dx \\ &+ w_h \left(- \left[\frac{1}{h} \frac{dh_b}{dt} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi} \right] C_h + \frac{D_{in}}{\phi^2} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} C - \frac{D_{in}}{\phi} \frac{\partial C_h}{\partial x} \right) \Big|_{bot} + w_h \left[\frac{1}{h} \frac{dh_t}{dt} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi} \right] C_h \Big|_{top} \end{aligned}$$

The result is a linear matrix equation

$$M_{jk} \frac{\partial C_k(t)}{\partial t} = [K_{jk} + S_{jk}] C_k(t) + q_{in} \quad (6.108)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{jk} &= \int_h w_j(x)w_k(x)dx \\
K_{jk} &= \left[-\frac{v}{h} - \frac{w_f}{h\phi} + \frac{D_{in}}{\phi^2} \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \right] \int_h \frac{\partial w_j}{\partial x} w_k dx \\
&\quad - w_j \left(-\left[\frac{v}{h} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi_k} \right] w_k + \frac{D_{in}}{\phi^2} \frac{\partial\phi_k}{\partial x} w_k - \frac{D_{in}}{\phi_k} \frac{\partial w_k}{\partial x} \right) \Big|_{bot} \\
&= -V_k \int_h \frac{\partial w_j}{\partial x} w_k dx - w_j \left(-V_k w_k - \frac{D_{in}}{\phi_k} \frac{\partial w_k}{\partial x} \right) \Big|_{bot} \\
S_{jk} &= -\frac{D_{in}}{\phi_k} \int_h \frac{\partial w_j}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{\partial w_k}{\partial x} dx \\
q_{in} &= -VC_t w_j(x)|_t
\end{aligned} \tag{6.109}$$

And $C_{N+2} = h\phi_{N+1}[c]_{ocean}$

For the top condition q_{in} is applied to the upper value C_2 when $VC_t < 0$, i.e. q_{in} is a source.

Compute the M_{jk} integrals:

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{jj} &= \int_{x_{j-1}}^{x_j} \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^2}{\Delta^2} dx + \int_{x_j}^{x_{j+1}} \left[1 - \frac{(x-x_j)}{\Delta} \right]^2 dx = \frac{2\Delta}{3} \quad \text{for } 1 < j < N+1 \\
M_{11} &= \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \left[1 - \frac{(x-x_2)}{\Delta} \right]^2 dx = \frac{\Delta}{3} \\
M_{N+1,N+1} &= \int_{x_N}^{x_{N+1}} \frac{(x-x_N)^2}{\Delta^2} dx = \frac{\Delta}{3}
\end{aligned}$$

Off diagonal components:

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{j,j+1} &= \int_{x_j}^{x_{j+1}} \left[1 - \frac{(x-x_j)}{\Delta} \right] \left[\frac{x-x_j}{\Delta} \right] dx = \frac{\Delta}{6} \quad \text{for } j < N+1 \\
M_{j,j-1} &= \int_{x_{j-1}}^{x_j} \left[\frac{x-x_{j-1}}{\Delta} \right] \left[1 - \frac{(x-x_{j-1})}{\Delta} \right] dx = \frac{\Delta}{6} \quad \text{for } j > 1
\end{aligned} \tag{6.110}$$

Compute the K_{jk} integrals:

$$\begin{aligned}
K_{jj} &= k'_{jj} \left[\int_{x_{j-1}}^{x_j} \frac{\partial w_j}{\partial x} w_j dx + \int_{x_j}^{x_{j+1}} \frac{\partial w_j}{\partial x} w_j dx \right] \\
&= \frac{1}{2} + -\frac{1}{2} = 0 \quad \text{for } 1 < j < N+1 \\
K_{11} &= -\frac{k'_{11}}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{v}{h} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi} \right] \\
K_{N+1,N+1} &= \frac{k'_{N+1,N+1}}{2} + \min \left[0, \left(\frac{1}{h} \frac{dh_b}{dt} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi_{N+1}} \right) \right] - \frac{D_{in}}{\phi_{N+1}(g_o/h)} \\
&= \left[-\frac{v}{h} - \frac{w_f}{h\phi} + \frac{D_{in}}{\phi^2} \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \right] \frac{1}{2} + \min \left[0, \left(\frac{1}{h} \frac{dh_b}{dt} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi_{N+1}} \right) \right] - \frac{D_{in}}{\phi_{N+1}(g_o/h)}
\end{aligned}$$

Off diagonal components:

$$\begin{aligned}
K_{j(j+1)} &= k'_{j(j+1)} \int_{x_j}^{x_{j+1}} \frac{\partial w_j}{\partial x} w_{j+1} dx = -k'_{j(j+1)} \int_{x_j}^{x_{j+1}} \frac{(x - x_j)}{\Delta^2} dx \\
&= -\frac{k'_{j(j+1)} \Delta^2}{2} = -\frac{k'_{j(j+1)}}{2} = p5 * \left[\frac{v}{h} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi} - \frac{D_{in}}{\phi^2} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \right]_{(j+1)} \quad \text{for } j < N + 1 \\
K_{j(j-1)} &= k'_{j(j-1)} \int_{x_{j-1}}^{x_j} \frac{\partial w_j}{\partial x} w_{j-1} dx = k'_{j(j-1)} \int_{x_{j-1}}^{x_j} \left[1 - \frac{(x - x_{j-1})}{\Delta^2} \right] dx \\
&= \frac{k'_{j(j-1)} \Delta^2}{2} = \frac{k'_{j(j-1)}}{2} = -p5 * \left[\frac{v}{h} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi} - \frac{D_{in}}{\phi^2} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \right]_{(j-1)} \quad \text{for } j > 1 \quad (6.111)
\end{aligned}$$

for $K_{N+1,N}$, there's a boundary contribution .

$$K_{N+1,N} = \frac{k'_{N+1(N)}}{2} - \frac{D_N}{\Delta \phi_N} \quad (6.112)$$

Note. The bottom condition works if $C_{bot} = h\phi_{N+2}[c]_{ocean}$, ϕ^2 is $\phi_{N+1}\phi_{N+2}$ and

$$\left. \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \right|_{bot} = \frac{\phi_{N+2} - \phi_N}{2\Delta} \quad (6.113)$$

Then the $D_{N+1}/\phi_{N+1}/\Delta$ cancels properly with the porosity gradient. In general

$$\left. \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \right|_k = \frac{\phi_{k+2} - \phi_k}{2\Delta} \quad (6.114)$$

When evaluating the integrals for the diffusion term, we will assume that D/ϕ is constant in an element. For $D_{in}/i\phi$ defined on interface points, $D_1 = 0$ for $j = 2, \dots, N$ $D_j/b\phi_j = (D_{in}(j) + D_{in}(j+1))/(i\phi_j + i\phi_{j+1})$. Then the above integrals will be modified as follows:

Compute the S_{jk} integrals:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{jj} &= - \left[\frac{D_{j-1}}{b\phi_{j-1}} \int_{x_{j-1}}^{x_j} \left(\frac{\partial w_j}{\partial x} \right)^2 dx + \frac{D_j}{b\phi_j} \int_{x_j}^{x_{j+1}} \left(\frac{\partial w_j}{\partial x} \right)^2 dx \right] \\
&= -\frac{1}{\Delta} \left[\frac{D_{j-1}}{b\phi_{j-1}} + \frac{D_j}{b\phi_j} \right] \quad \text{for } 1 < j < N + 1 \\
S_{11} &= \frac{s'_{11}}{\Delta} = 0 \\
S_{N+1,N+1} &= \frac{s'_{N+1,N+1}}{\Delta} = -\frac{(D_N)}{b\phi_N \Delta} \quad (6.115)
\end{aligned}$$

Compute the off-diagonal components of S_{jk} :

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{j(j+1)} &= s'_{j(j+1)} \int_{x_j}^{x_{j+1}} \frac{\partial w_j}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w_{j+1}}{\partial x} dx = -\frac{s'_{j(j+1)}}{\Delta} = \frac{D_j}{b\phi_j \Delta} \quad \text{for } j < N + 1 \\
S_{j(j-1)} &= s'_{j(j-1)} \int_{x_{j-1}}^{x_j} \frac{\partial w_j}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w_{j-1}}{\partial x} dx = -\frac{s'_{j(j-1)}}{\Delta} = \frac{D_{j-1}}{b\phi_{j-1} \Delta} \quad \text{for } j > 1 \quad (6.116)
\end{aligned}$$

We assume that $D/\phi^2\partial\phi/\partial x$ is constant in the element i . If D/ϕ_j is constant, and $\partial\phi/\partial x$ is constant then both the Darcy and D terms go as ϕ^{-1} . Then $\phi = (\phi_j - \phi_{j-1})(x - x_j)/\Delta + \phi_j$ and $m = (\phi_j - \phi_{j-1})/\Delta$ and $b = \phi_j - mx_j$.

The first integral contribution to the Darcy term is:

$$\begin{aligned}
K_{jj}^1 &= \frac{-1}{\Delta^2} \left(\frac{w_f}{h} - \frac{D}{\phi} \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \right) \int_{x_{j-1}}^j (x - x_{j-1}) \frac{1}{mx + b} dx \\
&= - \left(\frac{w_f}{h} - \frac{D}{\phi} \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \right) \frac{1}{\Delta^2} \left[\int_{x_{j-1}}^j \frac{x}{mx + b} dx - x_{j-1} \int_{x_{j-1}}^j \frac{1}{mx + b} dx \right] \\
&= - \left(\frac{w_f}{h} - \frac{D}{\phi} \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \right) \frac{1}{\Delta^2} \left[\frac{mx - b \log(b + mx)}{m^2} - x_{j-1} \frac{\log(b + mx)}{m} \right]_{x_{j-1}}^{x_j} \\
&= - \left(\frac{w_f}{h} - \frac{D}{\phi} \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \right) \frac{1}{\Delta_\phi} \left[1 + \log \left(\frac{\phi_j}{\phi_{j-1}} \right) - \frac{\phi_j}{\Delta_{\phi_j}} \log \left(\frac{\phi_j}{\phi_{j-1}} \right) \right] \\
&= - \left(\frac{w_f}{h} - \frac{D}{\phi} \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \right) \frac{1}{\Delta_\phi} \left[1 + \frac{\phi_{j-1}}{\Delta_\phi} \log \left(\frac{\phi_j}{\phi_{j-1}} \right) \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{6.117}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
K_{jj}^2 &= \left(\frac{w_f}{h} - \frac{D}{\phi} \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \right) \frac{1}{\Delta} \int_{x_j}^{x_{j+1}} \left[1 - \frac{(x - x_j)}{\Delta} \right] \frac{1}{mx + b} dx \\
&= \left(\frac{w_f}{h} - \frac{D}{\phi} \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \right) \frac{1}{\Delta} \left[\frac{(b + m(x_j + \Delta)) \log(b + mx) - mx}{\Delta m^2} \right]_{x_j}^{x_{j+1}} \\
&= \left(\frac{w_f}{h} - \frac{D}{\phi} \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \right) \frac{1}{\Delta_\phi} \left[1 - \frac{\phi_{j+1}}{\Delta_\phi} \log \left(\frac{\phi_{j+1}}{\phi_j} \right) \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{6.118}$$

Now $m = (\phi_{j+1} - \phi_j)/\Delta$ and $b = \phi_{j+1} - mx_{j+1}$.

Source terms $q_{bot} = q_{N+1}$ and $q_{top} = q_1$ (both positive)

$$\begin{aligned}
q_{bot} &= \max \left[0, \left(\frac{1}{h} \frac{dh_b}{dt} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi_{N+1}} \right) \right] C|_{bot} + \frac{D_{in}}{\phi_{N+1}(g_o/h)} C|_{bot} \\
C|_{bot} &= \phi_{N+1}[c]_{ocean}
\end{aligned} \tag{6.119}$$

where g_o is not zero.

$$\begin{aligned}
q_{in} &= - \min \left[0, \left(\frac{1}{h} \frac{dh_t}{dt} + \frac{w_f}{h\phi} \right) C|_{top} \right] \\
C|_{top} &= h[c]_o \phi_{min}
\end{aligned} \tag{6.120}$$

Calculating the low order solution: 1) Find the lumped mass matrix $M_l = diag\{m_i\}$

$$\begin{aligned}
m_j &= \sum_i m_{ji} = m_{j(j+1)} + m_{j(j-1)} + m_{jj} \\
&= \frac{\Delta}{6} + \frac{\Delta}{6} + \frac{2\Delta}{3} = \Delta \quad \text{for } 1 < j < N + 1 \\
m_1 &= m_{11} + m_{12} = \frac{\Delta}{3} + \frac{\Delta}{6} = \frac{\Delta}{2} \\
m_{N+1} &= m_{N+1,N} + m_{N+1,N+1} = \frac{\Delta}{6} + \frac{\Delta}{3} = \frac{\Delta}{2}
\end{aligned} \tag{6.121}$$

2) Define artificial diffusion D_a

$$\begin{aligned} d_{j,(j+1)} &= \max\{-k_{j(j+1)}, 0, -k_{(j+1)j}\} = d_{(j+1)j} \\ d_{jj} &= -\sum_{i \neq j} d_{ji} \end{aligned} \quad (6.122)$$

3) Add artificial diffusion to K : $L = K + D_a$. 4) Solve for the low order predictor solution:

$$(M_l - \Delta t[L + S])C^{n+1} = M_l C^n + \Delta t q \quad (6.123)$$

Conservations terms for the low order solution are:

$$\begin{aligned} \int [C^{n+1} - C^n] w(x) dx &= \Delta \left[\frac{c_1^{n+1} - c_1^n}{2} + \frac{c_{N+1}^{n+1} - c_{N+1}^n}{2} + \sum_{j=2}^N (c_j^{n+1} - c_j^n) \right] \\ &= \Delta t [q_{bot} + q_{in} + (K_{N+1,N+1} + K_{N,N+1})C_{N+1}^{n+1} + (K_{1,1} + K_{2,1})C_1^{n+1}] \end{aligned}$$

Now add the antidiffusive flux: 1) compute the F matrix using the low order solution c^{n+1} . Diagonal components are zero. For $i \neq j$

$$f_{ij} = m_{ij} \left[\frac{\Delta c_i}{\Delta t} - \frac{\Delta c_j}{\Delta t} + d_{ij}(c_i^{n+1} - c_j^{n+1}) \right] \quad (6.124)$$

Chapter 7

Standalone Simulations

7.1 Input Data

Input data for simple standalone simulations and for the MPAS-Seaice testing system are available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1219191>. The data consists of model domain grid files and forcing data for two different domains: a quasi-uniform 120 km resolution mesh, and a quasi-uniform 240 km resolution mesh. Included files for the quasi-uniform 120 km domain are:

Filename	Description
LYq_monthly.nc	Monthly climatology atmospheric forcing file.
LYq_six_hourly.2000.nc	Six hourly Atmospheric forcing file.
culled_graph.info.part.16	Grid partition file for 16 processors.
culled_graph.info.part.32	Grid partition file for 32 processors.
get_domain.py	Script to set up MPAS-Seaice run directory.
mpas_seaice_domain_manifest	Contents of this directory.
oceanmixed_ice_depth_QU120km.nc	Ocean forcing file.
seaice_QU_120km.nc	Grid file for the quasi-uniform 120 km domain
snicar_optics_5bnd_mam_c140303_mpas_seaice.nc	
standard_optics_mpas_seaice.nc	

7.2 Standard Configurations

Several standard configurations (namelist and streams files) are available in the MPAS repository at `MPAS/testing_and_setup/seaice/configurations/`. The `standard_physics` is the standard configuration for testing and exercises the standard physics configuration. All configurations:

Configuration	Description
<code>standard_physics</code>	A standard physics configuration without BGC
<code>standard_physics_single_cell</code>	As <code>standard_physics</code> but with a single cell.
<code>standard_bgc</code>	

7.3 Quick start simulation

Successful building of MPAS-Seaice (see chapter 2 for building instructions) can be demonstrated by running a simple simulation with the test data described in section 7.1. To run the model with

the quasi-uniform 120 km domain and the `standard_physics` configuration:

1. Create a run directory and execute the `get_domain.py` script from the `domain_QU120km` directory of the input data. This create symbolic links with the correct names to the grid and forcing data.
2. Copy the streams and namelist files from the `standard_physics` directory of the sea-ice configurations directory (see section 7.2) of the MPAS repository to the run directory.
3. Execute the `seaice_model` MPAS-Seaice executable from the run directory. The model should run and generate a log file called `log.seaice.0000.out`.

7.4 Testing

MPAS-Seaice includes a simple testing system located in the MPAS repository at `MPAS/testing_and_setup/seaice/testing/`. Three test types (found at `MPAS/testing_and_setup/seaice/testing/tests/`) are currently implemented:

1. **Regression:** This test compares the output of two different versions of MPAS-Seaice and checks that they produce bit-for-bit identical results. Typically, this is used to ensure developments do not unintentionally change results by comparing model versions from before and after the changes.
2. **Parallelism:** This test compares a single version of the model for model runs using different numbers of processors, and checks that using different numbers of processors does not change the model answer.
3. **Restartability:** This tests that restarting does not produce different results than if a restart was not performed.

These tests can be run against different domains and different configurations. These combinations are defined in a test suite xml file found at `MPAS/testing_and_setup/seaice/testing/testsuites/`. The default testsuite is the `testsuite.standard.xml` test suite which uses the quasi-uniform 120km domain with the `standard_physics` configuration. A BGC test suite is also included that uses the quasi-uniform 240km domain and the `standard_bgc` configuration.

To run the default testsuite:

1. Set the `MPAS_SEAICE_DOMAINS_DIR` environment variable to the location of the input data described in section 7.1.
2. Create a test directory. From that directory run the MPAS-Seaice test script: `MPAS/testing_and_setup/seaice/testing/test_mpas-seaice.py -d dev_repo -b base_repo` where `dev_repo` and `base_repo` are the locations of the two MPAS repositories (with compiled model binary) to be compared in the regression test. Other tests (parallelism and restartability) only test the `dev_repo` repository. The `-t` option allows testsuites other than the default (`testsuite.standard.xml`) to be used.

Chapter 8

Namelist options

Embedded links point to more detailed namelist information in the appendix.

8.1 `seaice_model`

Namelist parameters for the `seaice_model` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_dt	Length of model time-step.
config_calendar_type	Selection of the type of calendar that should be used in the simulation.
config_start_time	Timestamp describing the initial time of the simulation. If it is set to 'file', the initial time is read from <code>restart_timestamp</code> .
config_stop_time	Timestamp describing the final time of the simulation. If it is set to 'none' the final time is determined from <code>config_start_time</code> and <code>config_run_duration</code> .
config_run_duration	Timestamp describing the length of the simulation. If it is set to 'none' the duration is determined from <code>config_start_time</code> and <code>config_stop_time</code> . <code>config_run_duration</code> overrides inconsistent values of <code>config_stop_time</code> .
config_num_halos	Determines the number of halo cells extending from a blocks owned cells (Called the 0-Halo). The default of 3 is the minimum that can be used with monotonic advection.

8.2 `io`

Namelist parameters for the `io` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_pio_num_iotasks	Integer specifying how many IO tasks should be used within the PIO library. A value of 0 causes all MPI tasks to also be IO tasks. IO tasks are required to write contiguous blocks of data to a file.
config_pio_stride	Integer specifying the stride of each IO task.
config_write_output_on_startup	If true write the output streams to disk after model initialization but before time stepping.
config_test_case_diag	If true output test case diagnostics.
config_test_case_diag_type	Test case diagnostic type.
config_full_abort_write	If true write the abort stream to disk after a critical error for the entire domain, not just failing block.

8.3 decomposition

Namelist parameters for the `decomposition` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_block_decomp_file_prefix	Defines the prefix for the block decomposition file. Can include a path. The number of blocks is appended to the end of the prefix at run-time.
config_number_of_blocks	Determines the number of blocks a simulation should be run with. If it is set to 0, the number of blocks is the same as the number of MPI tasks at run-time.
config_explicit_proc_decomp	Determines if an explicit processor decomposition should be used. This is only useful if multiple blocks per processor are used.
config_proc_decomp_file_prefix	Defines the prefix for the processor decomposition file. This file is only read if <code>config_explicit_proc_decomp</code> is true. The number of processors is appended to the end of the prefix at run-time.
config_use_halo_exch	Determines if time integration halo exchanges are performed.
config_aggregate_halo_exch	Determines if aggregated halo exchanges are used in some places.
config_reuse_halo_exch	Determines if halo exchange lists are reused.
config_load_balance_timers	Determines if mpi barriers are used and timed before halo exchanges.

8.4 restart

Namelist parameters for the `restart` namelist group.

Name	Description
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Name	Description (Continued)
config_do_restart	Determines if the initial conditions should be read from a restart file, or an input file.
config_restart_timestamp_name	Path to the filename for restart timestamps to be read and written from.
config_do_restart_hbrine	Restart the brine height tracer needed for vertical bgc
config_do_restart_zsalinity	Restart the z-salinity tracer
config_do_restart_bgc	Restart the ice biogeochemistry

8.5 dimensions

Namelist parameters for the `dimensions` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_nCategories	The number of ice thickness categories to use.
config_nIceLayers	The number of ice layers in the vertical direction to use.
config_nSnowLayers	The number of snow layers in the vertical direction to use.

8.6 initialize

Namelist parameters for the `initialize` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_initial_condition_type	Initial condition type for sea ice state.
config_initial_ice_area	Sea ice concentration at initialization.
config_initial_ice_volume	Sea ice volume at initialization.
config_initial_snow_volume	Sea ice snow volume at initialization.
config_initial_latitude_north	Minimum latitude limit for initial northern hemisphere sea ice extent.
config_initial_latitude_south	Maximum latitude limit for initial southern hemisphere sea ice extent.
config_initial_velocity_type	Initial condition type for sea ice velocity.
config_initial_uvelocity	Sea ice velocity in the U direction at initialization. ???Geo or native???
config_initial_vvelocity	Sea ice velocity in the V direction at initialization. ???Geo or native???
config_calculate_coriolis	If True calculate the Coriolis parameter at initialization from the latitude.

8.7 use_sections

Namelist parameters for the `use_sections` namelist group.

Name	Description
<code>config_use_velocity_solver</code>	If true calculate the sea ice velocity.
<code>config_use_advection</code>	If true perform advection of the sea ice.
<code>config_use_forcing</code>	If true calculate input forcing fields.
<code>config_use_column_package</code>	If true perform calculations from the column physics package.

8.8 forcing

Namelist parameters for the `forcing` namelist group.

Name	Description
<code>config_atmospheric_forcing_type</code>	Atmospheric forcing type.
<code>config_forcing_start_time</code>	Forcing time to use at the simulation start time
<code>config_forcing_cycle_start</code>	Start time for the forcing cycle.
<code>config_forcing_cycle_duration</code>	Duration of the forcing cycle.
<code>config_forcing_precipitation_units</code>	Forcing input precipitation units.
<code>config_forcing_sst_type</code>	Sea surface temperature ocean forcing type.
<code>config_update_ocean_fluxes</code>	MISSING
<code>config_include_pond_freshwater_feedback</code>	Reduce the ocean fresh water flux by the pond fresh water flux for coupling.

8.9 unit_test

Namelist parameters for the `unit_test` namelist group.

Name	Description
<code>config_perform_unit_test</code>	If true perform a unit test.
<code>config_unit_test_type</code>	Unit test type.
<code>config_unit_test_subtype</code>	Unit test subtype.
<code>config_use_test_ice_shelf</code>	If true test add a test ice shelf to the ice shelf mask.
<code>config_testing_system_test</code>	If true initialize variables that will fail the testing system tests.

8.10 velocity_solver

Namelist parameters for the `velocity_solver` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_dynamics_subcycle_number	The number of dynamics subcycles to perform per thermodynamic time step (<code>config_dt</code>)
config_rotate_cartesian_grid	Rotate the velocity directions from geographic so their pole lies on the equator.
config_include_metric_terms	Include metric terms due to Earth curvature in velocity solver horizontal operators.
config_elastic_subcycle_number	The number of elastic EVP subcycles to perform per dynamics time step.
config_stress_divergence_scheme	Choice of stress divergence scheme to use in the velocity solver.
config_variational_basis	Type of basis functions to use with the variational stress divergence scheme.
config_wachspres_integration_type	Type of integration to perform with the Wachspres variational stress divergence scheme.
config_wachspres_integration_order	Order of integration for Wachspres basis integrations.
config_revised_evp	If true use the revised EVP rheology (Bouillon et al., Ocean Modelling)
config_use_air_stress	If true include the air stress term in the velocity solver calculations.
config_use_ocean_stress	If true include the ocean stress term in the velocity solver calculations.
config_use_surface_tilt	If true include the sea surface tilt stress term in the velocity solver calculations.
config_geostrophic_surface_tilt	If true calculate the sea surface tilt stress assuming currents are geostrophic.

8.11 advection

Namelist parameters for the `advection` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_advection_type	Type of advection scheme (upwind or incremental remapping).
config_monotonic	If true then fluxes are limited to produce a monotonic advection scheme.
config_conservation_check	If true test the advection results for tracer conservation (incremental remap only).

Name	Description (Continued)
config_monotonicity_check	If true test the advection results for monotonicity (incremental remap only).
config_recover_tracer_means_-check	If true compare mass*tracer products for incremental remapping with analytical values.

8.12 [column_package](#)

Namelist parameters for the `column_package` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_use_column_shortwave	Run the shortwave radiation column physics calculation.
config_use_column_vertical_-thermodynamics	Run the vertical thermodynamics column physics calculation.
config_use_column_-biogeochemistry	Use biological and chemical tracers in the ice
config_use_column_itd_-thermodynamics	Run the ice thickness distribution thermodynamics column physics calculation.
config_use_column_ridging	Run the ridging column physics calculation.

8.13 [column_tracers](#)

Namelist parameters for the `column_tracers` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_use_ice_age	If true use the ice age tracer.
config_use_first_year_ice	If true use the first year ice tracer.
config_use_level_ice	If true use the level ice tracers.
config_use_cesm_meltponds	If true use the cesm meltponds tracers.
config_use_level_meltponds	If true use the level ice meltponds tracers.
config_use_topo_meltponds	If true use the topo meltpond tracers.
config_use_aerosols	Carry aerosols in the ice (NCAR scheme)

8.14 [biogeochemistry](#)

Namelist parameters for the `biogeochemistry` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_use_brine	Use the brine height tracer
config_use_vertical_zsalinity	Use z-salinity (with Bitz and Lipscomb 1999 thermodynamics)
config_use_vertical_biochemistry	Turn on the reaction terms for vertical biological tracers
config_use_shortwave_- bioabsorption	Permit radiative transfer calculations that include dynamic chlorophyll and aerosols if active
config_use_vertical_tracers	Allow vertically resolved biological and chemical tracers
config_use_skeletal_biochemistry	Use the bottom 1-layer biogeochemistry
config_use_nitrate	Use the nitrate tracer
config_use_carbon	Use dissolved organic and inorganic carbon tracers
config_use_chlorophyll	Use the chlorophyll tracer (currently not implemented!)
config_use_ammonium	Use the ammonium tracer
config_use_silicate	Use the silicate tracer
config_use_DMS	Use DMS/DMSPd/DMSPp species
config_use_nonreactive	Use a non-reactive nitrate tracer
config_use_humics	Use the humic matter tracer
config_use_DON	Use dissolved organic nitrogen (proteins and amino acids)
config_use_iron	Use particulate and dissolved iron tracers
config_use_modal_aerosols	Aerosols are consistent with the CAM modal aerosol scheme
config_use_z_aerosols	Aerosols in the ice use the z-aerosol scheme
config_skeletal_bgc_flux_type	Determines the ocean-ice fluxes of biogeochemistry for the bottom1-layer model: in Jin2006, the piston velocity is a function of ice growth/melt rate, in default, the piston velocity is constant
config_scale_initial_vertical_bgc	initialize the vertical ice biogeochemistry profile to scale with the salinity restart/initial profile
config_biogrid_bottom_- molecular_sublayer	Sets the value of the ice/ocean molecular sublayer for the vertical biogeochemistry model
config_biogrid_top_molecular_- sublayer	Sets the value of the ice surface molecular sublayer for the vertical biogeochemistry model
config_bio_gravity_drainage_- length_scale	positive real number less than 1
config_zsalinity_molecular_- sublayer	Sets the ice/ocean molecular sublayer for the z-salinity model
config_zsalinity_gravity_- drainage_scale	Sets the gravity drainage length scale in the z-salinity model
config_snow_porosity_at_ice_- surface	Specifies the snow porosity (volume of air/total volume) at the ice surface
config_new_ice_fraction_biotracer	Fraction of biological tracer retained as new sea ice is formed from ocean water
config_fraction_biotracer_in_frazil	Factor multiplying the ocean concentration of a biological tracer in new frazil ice
config_ratio_Si_to_N_diatoms	Sets the ratio of silicate to nitrogen in diatoms
config_ratio_Si_to_N_small_- plankton	Sets the ratio of silicate to nitrogen in small plankton
config_ratio_Si_to_N_phaeocystis	Sets the ratio of silicate to nitrogen in phaeocystis
config_ratio_S_to_N_diatoms	Sets the ratio of sulfur to nitrogen in diatoms
config_ratio_S_to_N_small_- plankton	Sets the ratio of sulfur to nitrogen in small plankton
config_ratio_S_to_N_phaeocystis	Sets the ratio of sulfur to nitrogen in phaeocystis
config_ratio_Fe_to_C_diatoms	Sets the ratio of iron to carbon in diatoms
config_ratio_Fe_to_C_small_- plankton	Sets the ratio of iron to carbon in small plankton

Name	Description (Continued)
config_ratio_Fe_to_C_phaeocystis	Sets the ratio of iron to carbon in phaeocystis
config_ratio_Fe_to_N_diatoms	Sets the ratio of iron to nitrogen in diatoms
config_ratio_Fe_to_N_small-plankton	Sets the ratio of iron to nitrogen in small plankton
config_ratio_Fe_to_N_phaeocystis	Sets the ratio of iron to nitrogen in phaeocystis
config_ratio_Fe_to_DON	Sets the ratio of iron to dissolved organic nitrogen
config_ratio_Fe_to_DOC-saccharids	Sets the ratio of iron to poly/saccharid carbon
config_ratio_Fe_to_DOC_lipids	Sets the ratio of iron to lipid carbon
config_respiration_fraction_of-growth	Fraction of algal growth that is lost due to respiration
config_rapid_mobile_to-stationary_time	Rapid adsorption timescale
config_long_mobile_to-stationary_time	Slow adsorption timescale
config_algal_maximum_velocity	Maximum speed at which diatoms can move
config_ratio_Fe_to_dust	Mass ratio of iron in dust
config_solubility_of_Fe_in_dust	Fraction of iron that is soluble
config_chla_absorptivity_of-diatoms	Absorptivity of chlorophyll in diatoms
config_chla_absorptivity_of-small_plankton	Absorptivity of chlorophyll in small plankton
config_chla_absorptivity_of-phaeocystis	Absorptivity of chlorophyll in phaeocystis
config_light_attenuation_diatoms	Controls the ability of diatoms to utilize light
config_light_attenuation-small_plankton	Controls the ability of small plankton to utilize light
config_light_attenuation-phaeocystis	Controls the ability of phaeocystis to utilize light
config_light_inhibition_diatoms	Controls the strength of light inhibition to growth for diatoms
config_light_inhibition_small-plankton	Controls the strength of light inhibition to growth for small plankton
config_light_inhibition-phaeocystis	Controls the strength of light inhibition to growth for phaeocystis
config_maximum_growth_rate-diatoms	Maximum growth rate for diatoms
config_maximum_growth_rate-small_plankton	Maximum growth rate for small plankton
config_maximum_growth_rate-phaeocystis	Maximum growth rate for phaeocystis
config_temperature_growth-diatoms	Controls the temperature dependence of growth for diatoms
config_temperature_growth-small_plankton	Controls the temperature dependence of growth for small plankton
config_temperature_growth-phaeocystis	Controls the temperature dependence of growth for phaeocystis
config_grazed_fraction_diatoms	Fraction of diatom biomass grazed
config_grazed_fraction_small-plankton	Fraction of small plankton biomass grazed
config_grazed_fraction-phaeocystis	Fraction of phaeocystis biomass grazed

Name	Description (Continued)
config_mortality_diatoms	Mortality rate of diatoms
config_mortality_small_plankton	Mortality rate of small plankton
config_mortality_phaeocystis	Mortality rate of phaeocystis
config_temperature_mortality_- diatoms	Temperature dependence of diatom mortality rate
config_temperature_mortality_- small_plankton	Temperature dependence of small plankton mortality rate
config_temperature_mortality_- phaeocystis	Temperature dependence of phaeocystis mortality rate
config_exudation_diatoms	Rate diatoms exude DOC
config_exudation_small_plankton	Rate small plankton exude DOC
config_exudation_phaeocystis	Rate phaeocystis exude DOC
config_nitrate_saturation_- diatoms	Nitrate half saturation for diatom growth
config_nitrate_saturation_- small_plankton	Nitrate half saturation for small plankton growth
config_nitrate_saturation_- phaeocystis	Nitrate half saturation for phaeocystis growth
config_ammonium_saturation_- diatoms	Ammonium half saturation for diatom growth
config_ammonium_saturation_- small_plankton	Ammonium half saturation for small plankton growth
config_ammonium_saturation_- phaeocystis	Ammonium half saturation for phaeocystis growth
config_silicate_saturation_- diatoms	Silicate half saturation for diatom growth
config_silicate_saturation_- small_plankton	Silicate half saturation for small plankton growth
config_silicate_saturation_- phaeocystis	Silicate half saturation for phaeocystis growth
config_iron_saturation_diatoms	Iron half saturation for diatom growth
config_iron_saturation_small_- plankton	Iron half saturation for small plankton growth
config_iron_saturation_- phaeocystis	Iron half saturation for phaeocystis growth
config_fraction_spilled_to_DON	Fraction of spilled grazing to proteins
config_degradation_of_DON	Bacterial degradation of DON
config_fraction_DON_ammonium	Fraction of remineralized DON converted to ammonium
config_fraction_loss_to_saccharids	Fraction of mortality to poly/saccharids
config_fraction_loss_to_lipids	Fraction of mortality to lipids
config_fraction_exudation_to_- saccharids	Fraction of exudation to poly/saccharids
config_fraction_exudation_to_- lipids	Fraction of exudation to lipids
config_remineralization_- saccharids	Bacterial degradation rate of poly/saccharids
config_remineralization_lipids	Bacterial degradation rate of lipids
config_maximum_brine_- temperature	Maximum brine temperature
config_salinity_dependence_of_- growth	Salinity limitation factor

Name	Description (Continued)
config_minimum_optical_depth	Minimum optical depth above which light attenuates
config_slopped_grazing_fraction	Fraction of grazing spilled or slopped
config_excreted_fraction	Fraction of assimilation excreted
config_fraction_mortality_to-ammonium	Fraction of mortality to ammonium
config_fraction_iron-remineralized	Fraction of remineralized iron
config_nitrification_rate	Nitrification rate
config_desorption_loss-particulate_iron	Desorption rate of particulate iron to dissolved iron
config_maximum_loss_fraction	Maximum uptake fraction in a single timestep
config_maximum_ratio_iron-to_saccharids	Optimal ratio of dissolved iron to poly/saccharids in the brine
config_respiration_loss_to-DMSPd	Fraction of respiration loss as DMSPd
config_DMSP_to_DMS-conversion_fraction	Fraction of conversion to DMS given high yield
config_DMSP_to_DMS-conversion_time	Stefels conversion time
config_DMS_oxidation_time	DMS oxidation time
config_mobility_type_diatoms	Transport type of diatoms
config_mobility_type_small-plankton	Transport type of small plankton
config_mobility_type_phaeocystis	Transport type of phaeocystis
config_mobility_type_nitrate	Transport type of nitrate
config_mobility_type_ammonium	Transport type of ammonium
config_mobility_type_silicate	Transport type of silicate
config_mobility_type_DMSPp	Transport type of particulate DMSP
config_mobility_type_DMSPd	Transport type of dissolved DMSP
config_mobility_type_humics	Transport type of humics
config_mobility_type_saccharids	Transport type of poly/saccharids
config_mobility_type_lipids	Transport type of lipids
config_mobility_type_proteins	Transport type of proteins
config_mobility_type-dissolved_iron	Transport type of dissolved iron
config_mobility_type-particulate_iron	Transport type of particulate iron
config_mobility_type_black-carbon1	Transport type of black carbon 1 pool
config_mobility_type_black-carbon2	Transport type of black carbon 1 pool
config_mobility_type_dust1	Transport type of dust pool 1
config_mobility_type_dust2	Transport type of dust pool 2
config_mobility_type_dust3	Transport type of dust pool 3
config_mobility_type_dust4	Transport type of dust pool 4
config_ratio_C_to_N_diatoms	Algal carbon to nitrogen mole ratio for diatoms
config_ratio_C_to_N_small-plankton	Algal carbon to nitrogen mole ratio for small plankton
config_ratio_C_to_N_phaeocystis	Algal carbon to nitrogen mole ratio for phaeocystis
config_ratio_chla_to_N_diatoms	Algal chlorophyll to nitrogen ratio for diatoms

Name	Description (Continued)
config_ratio_chla_to_N_small_plankton	Algal chlorophyll to nitrogen ratio for small plankton
config_ratio_chla_to_N_phaeocystis	Algal chlorophyll to nitrogen ratio for phaeocystis
config_scales_absorption_diatoms	Scales absorbed radiation for diatoms
config_scales_absorption_small_plankton	Scales absorbed radiation for small plankton
config_scales_absorption_phaeocystis	Scales absorbed radiation for phaeocystis
config_ratio_C_to_N_proteins	Ratio of carbon to nitrogen in proteins

8.15 [shortwave](#)

Namelist parameters for the `shortwave` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_shortwave_type	Shortwave radiation method.
config_albedo_type	Albedo parameterization type.
config_visible_ice_albedo	Visible ice albedo for ice thickness greater than <code>config_variable_albedo_thickness_limit</code> .
config_infrared_ice_albedo	Near-IR ice albedo for ice thickness greater than <code>config_variable_albedo_thickness_limit</code> .
config_visible_snow_albedo	Visible cold snow albedo.
config_infrared_snow_albedo	Near-IR cold snow albedo.
config_variable_albedo_thickness_limit	Ice thickness above which the ice albedo is constant.
config_ice_shortwave_tuning_parameter	Sea ice tuning parameter; +1 for 1sig increase in albedo.
config_pond_shortwave_tuning_parameter	Ponded ice tuning parameter; +1 for 1sig increase in albedo.
config_snow_shortwave_tuning_parameter	Snow tuning parameter; +1 for .01 change in broadband albedo.
config_temp_change_snow_grain_radius_change	Change in temperature for non-melt to melt snow grain radius change.
config_max_melting_snow_grain_radius	Maximum melting snow grain radius.
config_algae_absorption_coefficient	Algae absorption coefficient for 0.5 m thick layer.

8.16 [meltponds](#)

Namelist parameters for the `meltponds` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_snow_to_ice_-transition_depth	Snow depth for transition to bare sea ice.
config_pond_refreezing_type	Pond refreezing parameterization.
config_pond_flushing_timescale	Alter e-folding time scale for flushing.?????
config_min_meltwater_-retained_fraction	Minimum retained fraction of meltwater.
config_max_meltwater_-retained_fraction	Maximum retained fraction of meltwater.
config_pond_depth_to_-fraction_ratio	Ratio of pond depth to pond fraction.
config_snow_on_pond_ice_-tapering_parameter	Tapering parameter for snow on pond ice.
config_critical_pond_ice_thickness	Critical parameter for pond ice thickness.

8.17 thermodynamics

Namelist parameters for the `thermodynamics` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_thermodynamics_type	Vertical themodynamics type.
config_heat_conductivity_type	Thermal conductivity type for BL99 thermodynamics. Options are Maykut and Untersteiner 1971 form (with Wettlaufer 1991 constants), or Pringle et al JGR 2007 'bubbly brine'
config_rapid_mode_channel_-radius	Channel radius for rapid gravity drainage mode.
config_rapid_mode_critical_Ra	Critical Rayleigh number for rapid gravity drainage mode.
config_rapid_mode_aspect_ratio	Aspect ratio for rapid gravity drainage mode (larger=wider).
config_slow_mode_drainage_-strength	Slow gravity drainage mode drainage strength.
config_slow_mode_critical_-porosity	Liquid fraction porosity cutoff for slow gravity drainage mode.
config_congelation_ice_porosity	Liquid fraction of congelation ice.

8.18 itd

Namelist parameters for the `itd` namelist group.

Name	Description
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Name	Description (Continued)
config_itd_conversion_type	Type of ice thickness distribution conversions.
config_category_bounds_type	Type of ice thickness category bounds.

8.19 [ridging](#)

Namelist parameters for the `ridging` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_ice_strength_formulation	Type of ice strength formulation.
config_ridging_participation_function	Type of ridging participation function.
config_ridging_redistribution_function	Type of ridging redistribution function.
config_ridging_efolding_scale	E-folding scale of ridged ice (<code>krdg_redist = 1</code>)
config_ratio_ridging_work_to_PE	Ratio of ridging work to PE change in ridging (<code>kstrength = 1</code>)

8.20 [atmosphere](#)

Namelist parameters for the `atmosphere` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_atmos_boundary_method	Atmosphere boundary method.
config_calc_surface_stresses	If true calculate wind stress components.
config_calc_surface_temperature	If true calculate surface temperature. If false surface temperature is computed elsewhere and atmos-ice fluxes are provided.
config_use_form_drag	If true calculate form drag.
config_use_high_frequency_coupling	If true use high frequency coupling.
config_boundary_layer_iteration_number	Number of iterations for boundary layer calculations

8.21 [ocean](#)

Namelist parameters for the `ocean` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_use_ocean_mixed_layer	If true use an ocean mixed layer.
config_min_friction_velocity	Minimum friction velocity for ice-ocean heat flux.
config_ocean_heat_transfer_type	Transfer coefficient type for ice-ocean heat flux.
config_sea_freezing_temperature_type	Form of ocean freezing temperature.
config_ocean_surface_type	Type of coupled ocean surface: (MPAS-O:'free'), (SOM:'non-free')
config_couple_biogeochemistry_fields	MISSING

8.22 [diagnostics](#)

Namelist parameters for the `diagnostics` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_check_state	If true perform a check at runtime of the model state.

8.23 [AM_highFrequencyOutput](#)

Namelist parameters for the `AM_highFrequencyOutput` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_enable	If true, ocean analysis member <code>highFrequencyOutput</code> is called.
config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_compute_interval	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_output_stream	Name of the stream that the <code>highFrequencyOutput</code> analysis member should be tied to.
config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_compute_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_write_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

8.24 [AM_temperatures](#)

Namelist parameters for the `AM_temperatures` namelist group.

Name	Description
<code>config_AM_temperatures.enable</code>	If true, ocean analysis member temperatures is called.
<code>config_AM_temperatures.-compute_interval</code>	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
<code>config_AM_temperatures.-output_stream</code>	Name of the stream that the temperatures analysis member should be tied to.
<code>config_AM_temperatures.-compute_on_startup</code>	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
<code>config_AM_temperatures.-write_on_startup</code>	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

8.25 `AM_regionalStatistics`

Namelist parameters for the `AM_regionalStatistics` namelist group.

Name	Description
<code>config_AM_regionalStatistics.-enable</code>	If true, ocean analysis member regionalStatistics is called.
<code>config_AM_regionalStatistics.-compute_interval</code>	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
<code>config_AM_regionalStatistics.-output_stream</code>	Name of the stream that the regionalStatistics analysis member should be tied to.
<code>config_AM_regionalStatistics.-compute_on_startup</code>	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
<code>config_AM_regionalStatistics.-write_on_startup</code>	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.
<code>config_AM_regionalStatistics.-ice_extent_limit</code>	sea-ice fraction limit for ice extent.

8.26 `AM_ridgingDiagnostics`

Namelist parameters for the `AM_ridgingDiagnostics` namelist group.

Name	Description
<code>config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics.-enable</code>	If true, ocean analysis member ridgingDiagnostics is called.
<code>config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics.-compute_interval</code>	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
<code>config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics.-output_stream</code>	Name of the stream that the ridgingDiagnostics analysis member should be tied to.

Name	Description (Continued)
config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics_-compute_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics_-write_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

8.27 [AM_conservationCheck](#)

Namelist parameters for the `AM_conservationCheck` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_AM_conservationCheck_-enable	If true, ocean analysis member conservationCheck is called.
config_AM_conservationCheck_-compute_interval	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
config_AM_conservationCheck_-output_stream	Name of the stream that the conservationCheck analysis member should be tied to.
config_AM_conservationCheck_-compute_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
config_AM_conservationCheck_-write_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.
config_AM_conservationCheck_-write_to_logfile	Logical flag determining if the conservation check is written to the log file.

8.28 [AM_geographicalVectors](#)

Namelist parameters for the `AM_geographicalVectors` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_AM_geographicalVectors_enable	If true, ocean analysis member geographicalVectors is called.
config_AM_geographicalVectors_compute_interval	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
config_AM_geographicalVectors_output_stream	Name of the stream that the geographicalVectors analysis member should be tied to.
config_AM_geographicalVectors_compute_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
config_AM_geographicalVectors_write_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

8.29 AM_loadBalance

Namelist parameters for the `AM_loadBalance` namelist group.

Name	Description
<code>config_AM_loadBalance_enable</code>	If true, ocean analysis member loadBalance is called.
<code>config_AM_loadBalance.-compute_interval</code>	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
<code>config_AM_loadBalance.-output_stream</code>	Name of the stream that the loadBalance analysis member should be tied to.
<code>config_AM_loadBalance.-compute_on_startup</code>	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
<code>config_AM_loadBalance.write.-on_startup</code>	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.
<code>config_AM_loadBalance.nProcs</code>	Number of processors to output results for

8.30 AM_maximumIcePresence

Namelist parameters for the `AM_maximumIcePresence` namelist group.

Name	Description
<code>config_AM_maximumIcePresence_enable</code>	If true, ocean analysis member maximumIcePresence is called.
<code>config_AM_maximumIcePresence_compute_interval</code>	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
<code>config_AM_maximumIcePresence_output_stream</code>	Name of the stream that the maximumIcePresence analysis member should be tied to.
<code>config_AM_maximumIcePresence_compute_on_startup</code>	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
<code>config_AM_maximumIcePresence_write_on_startup</code>	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.
<code>config_AM_maximumIcePresence_start_time</code>	Time to start accumulating ice domain

8.31 AM_miscellaneous

Namelist parameters for the `AM_miscellaneous` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_AM_miscellaneous_enable	If true, ocean analysis member miscellaneous is called.
config_AM_miscellaneous.-compute_interval	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
config_AM_miscellaneous.-output_stream	Name of the stream that the miscellaneous analysis member should be tied to.
config_AM_miscellaneous.-compute_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
config_AM_miscellaneous.-write_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

8.32 [AM_areaVariables](#)

Namelist parameters for the `AM_areaVariables` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_AM_areaVariables_enable	If true, ocean analysis member areaVariables is called.
config_AM_areaVariables.-compute_interval	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
config_AM_areaVariables.-output_stream	Name of the stream that the areaVariables analysis member should be tied to.
config_AM_areaVariables.-compute_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
config_AM_areaVariables.-write_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

8.33 [AM_pondDiagnostics](#)

Namelist parameters for the `AM_pondDiagnostics` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_AM_pondDiagnostics.-enable	If true, ocean analysis member pondDiagnostics is called.
config_AM_pondDiagnostics.-compute_interval	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
config_AM_pondDiagnostics.-output_stream	Name of the stream that the pondDiagnostics analysis member should be tied to.
config_AM_pondDiagnostics.-compute_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
config_AM_pondDiagnostics.-write_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

8.34 `AM_unitConversion`

Namelist parameters for the `AM_unitConversion` namelist group.

Name	Description
<code>config_AM_unitConversion.-enable</code>	If true, ocean analysis member <code>unitConversion</code> is called.
<code>config_AM_unitConversion.-compute_interval</code>	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
<code>config_AM_unitConversion.-output_stream</code>	Name of the stream that the <code>unitConversion</code> analysis member should be tied to.
<code>config_AM_unitConversion.-compute_on_startup</code>	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
<code>config_AM_unitConversion.-write_on_startup</code>	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

8.35 `AM_pointwiseStats`

Namelist parameters for the `AM_pointwiseStats` namelist group.

Name	Description
<code>config_AM_pointwiseStats.enable</code>	If true, ocean analysis member <code>pointwiseStats</code> is called.
<code>config_AM_pointwiseStats.-compute_interval</code>	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
<code>config_AM_pointwiseStats.-output_stream</code>	Name of the stream that the <code>pointwiseStats</code> analysis member should be tied to.
<code>config_AM_pointwiseStats.-compute_on_startup</code>	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
<code>config_AM_pointwiseStats.-write_on_startup</code>	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

8.36 `AM_iceShelves`

Name	Description
config_AM_iceShelves_enable	If true, ocean analysis member iceShelves is called.
config_AM_iceShelves_compute_interval	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
config_AM_iceShelves_output_stream	Name of the stream that the iceShelves analysis member should be tied to.
config_AM_iceShelves_compute_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
config_AM_iceShelves_write_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

8.37 [AM_icePresent](#)

Name	Description
config_AM_icePresent_enable	If true, ocean analysis member icePresent is called.
config_AM_icePresent_compute_interval	Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.
config_AM_icePresent_output_stream	Name of the stream that the icePresent analysis member should be tied to.
config_AM_icePresent_compute_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.
config_AM_icePresent_write_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

8.38 [AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily](#)

Namelist parameters for the `AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_enable	If true, ocean analysis member time series stats is called.
config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_compute_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up. You likely want this off for this (time series) analysis member because it will accumulate any state prior to time stepping (double counting the last time step).
config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_write_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member output occurs on start-up.
config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_compute_interval	Interval that determines frequency of computation for the time series stats analysis member.

Name	Description (Continued)
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Daily_output_stream	Name of stream the time series stats analysis member will operate on.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Daily_restart_stream	Name of the restart stream the time series stats analysis member will use to initialize itself if restart is enabled.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Daily_operation	An operation describing the statistic to apply to the time series for all variables in the output stream, reducing the time dimension.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Daily_reference_times	A list of absolute times describing when to start accumulating statistics. Each time indicates the start of one time window (time series statistic) per variable, in the output stream (i.e., provide four start times if you want quarterly climatologies, only one time is needed for monthly or daily averages, etc.)
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Daily_duration_intervals	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing how long to accumulate statistics in a time window for each repetition (repeat_interval). It has to match the number of start time tokens in reference_times.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Daily_repeat_intervals	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing the accumulation statistic temporal periodicity (time between beginning to accumulate again after it started - duration_interval describes when to stop after starting/restarting). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Daily_reset_intervals	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing the statistic reset periodicity (how often to reset/clear/zero the accumulation). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Daily_backward_output_offset	Backward offset for filename timestamps when writing the output stream

8.39 [AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly](#)

Namelist parameters for the `AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Monthly_enable	If true, ocean analysis member time series stats is called.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Monthly_compute_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up. You likely want this off for this (time series) analysis member because it will accumulate any state prior to time stepping (double counting the last time step).
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Monthly_write_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member output occurs on start-up.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Monthly_compute_interval	Interval that determines frequency of computation for the time series stats analysis member.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Monthly_output_stream	Name of stream the time series stats analysis member will operate on.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Monthly_restart_stream	Name of the restart stream the time series stats analysis member will use to initialize itself if restart is enabled.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Monthly_operation	An operation describing the statistic to apply to the time series for all variables in the output stream, reducing the time dimension.

Name	Description (Continued)
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Monthly_reference_times	A list of absolute times describing when to start accumulating statistics. Each time indicates the start of one time window (time series statistic) per variable, in the output stream (i.e., provide four start times if you want quarterly climatologies, only one time is needed for monthly or daily averages, etc.)
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Monthly_duration_intervals	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing how long to accumulate statistics in a time window for each repetition (repeat_interval). It has to match the number of start time tokens in reference_times.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Monthly_repeat_intervals	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing the accumulation statistic temporal periodicity (time between beginning to accumulate again after it started - duration_interval describes when to stop after starting/restarting). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Monthly_reset_intervals	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing the statistic reset periodicity (how often to reset/clear/zero the accumulation). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Monthly_backward_output_offset	Backward offset for filename timestamps when writing the output stream

8.40 [AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology](#)

Namelist parameters for the `AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Climatology_enable	If true, ocean analysis member time series stats is called.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Climatology_compute_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up. You likely want this off for this (time series) analysis member because it will accumulate any state prior to time stepping (double counting the last time step).
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Climatology_write_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member output occurs on start-up.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Climatology_compute_interval	Interval that determines frequency of computation for the time series stats analysis member.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Climatology_output_stream	Name of stream the time series stats analysis member will operate on.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Climatology_restart_stream	Name of the restart stream the time series stats analysis member will use to initialize itself if restart is enabled.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Climatology_operation	An operation describing the statistic to apply to the time series for all variables in the output stream, reducing the time dimension.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Climatology_reference_times	A list of absolute times describing when to start accumulating statistics. Each time indicates the start of one time window (time series statistic) per variable, in the output stream (i.e., provide four start times if you want quarterly climatologies, only one time is needed for monthly or daily averages, etc.)

Name	Description (Continued)
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Climatology_duration_intervals	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing how long to accumulate statistics in a time window for each repetition (repeat_interval). It has to match the number of start time tokens in reference_times.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Climatology_repeat_intervals	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing the accumulation statistic temporal periodicity (time between beginning to accumulate again after it started - duration_interval describes when to stop after starting/restarting). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Climatology_reset_intervals	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing the statistic reset periodicity (how often to reset/clear/zero the accumulation). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Climatology_backward_output_offset	Backward offset for filename timestamps when writing the output stream

8.41 [AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom](#)

Namelist parameters for the `AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom` namelist group.

Name	Description
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Custom_enable	If true, ocean analysis member time series stats is called.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Custom_compute_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up. You likely want this off for this (time series) analysis member because it will accumulate any state prior to time stepping (double counting the last time step).
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Custom_write_on_startup	Logical flag determining if an analysis member output occurs on start-up.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Custom_compute_interval	Interval that determines frequency of computation for the time series stats analysis member.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Custom_output_stream	Name of stream the time series stats analysis member will operate on.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Custom_restart_stream	Name of the restart stream the time series stats analysis member will use to initialize itself if restart is enabled.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Custom_operation	An operation describing the statistic to apply to the time series for all variables in the output stream, reducing the time dimension.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Custom_reference_times	A list of absolute times describing when to start accumulating statistics. Each time indicates the start of one time window (time series statistic) per variable, in the output stream (i.e., provide four start times if you want quarterly climatologies, only one time is needed for monthly or daily averages, etc.)
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Custom_duration_intervals	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing how long to accumulate statistics in a time window for each repetition (repeat_interval). It has to match the number of start time tokens in reference_times.

Name	Description (Continued)
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Custom_repeat_intervals	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing the accumulation statistic temporal periodicity (time between beginning to accumulate again after it started - duration_interval describes when to stop after starting/restarting). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Custom_reset_intervals	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing the statistic reset periodicity (how often to reset/clear/zero the accumulation). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.
config_AM_timeSeriesStats-Custom_backward_output_offset	Backward offset for filename timestamps when writing the output stream

Chapter 9

Dimensions

Name	Units	Description
nCells	MISSING	The number of polygons in the primary grid.
nEdges	MISSING	The number of edge midpoints in either the primary or dual grid.
maxEdges	MISSING	The largest number of edges any polygon within the grid has.
maxEdges2	MISSING	Two times the largest number of edges any polygon within the grid has.
nVertices	MISSING	The total number of cells in the dual grid. Also the number of corners in the primary grid.
ONE	MISSING	The number one as a dimension.
TWO	MISSING	The number two as a dimension.
R3	MISSING	The number three as a dimension.
FIFTEEN	MISSING	The number fifteen as a dimension.
TWENTYONE	MISSING	The number twenty one as a dimension.
vertexDegree	MISSING	The number of cells or edges touching each vertex.
nCategories	MISSING	The number of ice thickness categories.
nIceLayers	MISSING	The number of ice layers in the vertical direction.
nSnowLayers	MISSING	The number of snow layers in the vertical direction.
nHemispheres	MISSING	The number of hemispheres (global, north, south).
nQuadPoints	MISSING	MISSING
nTriPerEdgeRemap	MISSING	MISSING
maxCellsPerEdgeRemap	MISSING	MISSING
maxEdgesPerEdgeRemap	MISSING	MISSING
maxVerticesPerEdgeRemap	MISSING	MISSING
nIceLayersP1	MISSING	The number of ice layers in the vertical direction plus one.
nCategoriesP1	MISSING	The number of ice thickness categories plus one.
nAerosols	MISSING	Number of aerosol species carried in the ice (NCAR scheme)
nSpectralIntervals	MISSING	Number of spectral intervals in the radiation calculation
nBioLayers	MISSING	Number of levels in the biological grid
nBioLayersP1	MISSING	Number of levels in the interface biological grid
nBioLayersP2	MISSING	Number of levels in the biological grid plus two
nBioLayersP3	MISSING	Number of biological levels in the ice and snow
maxAlgaeType	MISSING	Maximum number of ice algal types
maxDOCType	MISSING	Maximum number of dissolved organic carbon groups
maxDICType	MISSING	Maximum number of dissolved inorganic carbon groups
maxDONType	MISSING	Maximum number of dissolved organic nitrogen groups
maxIronType	MISSING	Maximum number of dissolved or particulate iron groups
maxBCType	MISSING	Maximum number of black carbon species carried in the ice

Name	Units	Description (Continued)
maxDustType	MISSING	Maximum number of dust species carried in the ice
maxAerosolType	MISSING	Total maximum number of aerosols carried in the ice
nModal1	MISSING	Specifies the second dimension of the modal aerosol optical parameter matrix
nModal2	MISSING	Specifies the third dimension of the modal aerosol optical parameter matrix
nAlgae	MISSING	Number of algal species in use
nDOC	MISSING	Number of dissolved organic carbon groups in use
nDIC	MISSING	Number of dissolved inorganic carbon groups in use
nDON	MISSING	Number of dissolved organic nitrogen groups in use
nParticulateIron	MISSING	Number of particulate iron species in use
nDissolvedIron	MISSING	Number of dissolved iron species in use
nzAerosols	MISSING	Number of aerosol species carried in the ice
nShortwaveBio	MISSING	Number of levels in the radiation calculation with biological species
nAlgaeLayers	MISSING	Total number of algal layers including two for snow plus the interface grid
nAlgaeIceLayers	MISSING	Total number of algal layers in the ice
nAlgaeSnowLayers	MISSING	Total number of algal layers in the snow
nDOCLayers	MISSING	Total number of DOC layers including two for snow plus the interface grid
nDOCIceLayers	MISSING	Total number of DOC layers in the ice
nDOCSnowLayers	MISSING	Total number of DOC layers in the snow
nDICLayers	MISSING	Total number of DIC layers including two for snow plus the interface grid
nDICIceLayers	MISSING	Total number of DIC layers in the ice
nDICSnowLayers	MISSING	Total number of DIC layers in the snow
nDONLayers	MISSING	Total number of DON layers including two for snow plus the interface grid
nDONIceLayers	MISSING	Total number of DON layers in the ice
nDONSnowLayers	MISSING	Total number of DON layers in the snow
nParticulateIronLayers	MISSING	Total number of particulate iron layers including two for snow plus the interface grid
nPartIronIceLayers	MISSING	Total number of particulate iron layers in the ice
nPartIronSnowLayers	MISSING	Total number of particulate iron layers in the snow
nDissolvedIronLayers	MISSING	Total number of dissolved iron layers including two for snow plus the interface grid
nDisIronIceLayers	MISSING	Total number of dissolved iron layers in the ice
nDisIronSnowLayers	MISSING	Total number of dissolved iron layers in the snow
nzAerosolsLayers	MISSING	Total number of z-aerosol layers including two for snow plus the interface grid
nzAerosolsSnowLayers	MISSING	Total number of z-aerosol layers in the snow
nzAerosolsIceLayers	MISSING	Total number of z-aerosol layers in the ice
nZBGCTracers	MISSING	Maximum number of distinct biological or chemical tracer types
nRegions	MISSING	The number of regions defined for analysis.
nPoints	unitless	The number of points for AM_pointwiseStats
nPointGroups	unitless	The number of points groups
maxPointsInGroup	unitless	The maximum number of points in any group.
nForcingGroupsMax	MISSING	The maximum number of forcing groups defined in the core.
nProcs	MISSING	MISSING
nMonths	MISSING	MISSING

Chapter 10

Variable definitions

Embedded links point to more detailed variable information in the appendix.

10.1 [mesh](#)

Name	Description
latCell	Latitude location of cell centers in radians.
lonCell	Longitude location of cell centers in radians.
xCell	X Coordinate in cartesian space of cell centers.
yCell	Y Coordinate in cartesian space of cell centers.
zCell	Z Coordinate in cartesian space of cell centers.
indexToCellID	List of global cell IDs.
latEdge	Latitude location of edge midpoints in radians.
lonEdge	Longitude location of edge midpoints in radians.
xEdge	X Coordinate in cartesian space of edge midpoints.
yEdge	Y Coordinate in cartesian space of edge midpoints.
zEdge	Z Coordinate in cartesian space of edge midpoints.
indexToEdgeID	List of global edge IDs.
latVertex	Latitude location of vertices in radians.
lonVertex	Longitude location of vertices in radians.
xVertex	X Coordinate in cartesian space of vertices.
yVertex	Y Coordinate in cartesian space of vertices.
zVertex	Z Coordinate in cartesian space of vertices.
indexToVertexID	List of global vertex IDs.
cellsOnEdge	List of cells that straddle each edge.
nEdgesOnCell	Number of edges that border each cell.
nEdgesOnEdge	Number of edges that surround each of the cells that straddle each edge. These edges are used to reconstruct the tangential velocities.
edgesOnCell	List of edges that border each cell.
edgesOnEdge	List of edges that border each of the cells that straddle each edge.
dvEdge	Length of each edge, computed as the distance between verticesOnEdge.
dcEdge	Length of each edge, computed as the distance between cellsOnEdge.

Name	Description (Continued)
areaCell	Area of each cell in the primary grid.
areaTriangle	Area of each cell (triangle) in the dual grid.
edgeNormalVectors	Normal unit vector defined at an edge.
cellTangentPlane	The two vectors that define a tangent plane at a cell center.
localVerticalUnitVectors	Unit surface normal vectors defined at cell centers.
cellsOnCell	List of cells that neighbor each cell.
verticesOnCell	List of vertices that border each cell.
verticesOnEdge	List of vertices that straddle each edge.
edgesOnVertex	List of edges that share a vertex as an endpoint.
cellsOnVertex	List of cells that share a vertex.
kiteAreasOnVertex	Area of the portions of each dual cell that are part of each cellsOnVertex.
fVertex	Coriolis parameter at vertices.
coeffs_reconstruct	Coefficients to reconstruct velocity vectors at cells centers.
itimestep	MISSING

10.2 tracers

Name	Description
iceAreaCategory	MISSING
iceVolumeCategory	MISSING
snowVolumeCategory	MISSING
surfaceTemperature	MISSING
iceEnthalpy	MISSING
iceSalinity	MISSING
snowEnthalpy	MISSING
iceAge	MISSING
firstYearIceArea	MISSING
levelIceArea	MISSING
levelIceVolume	MISSING
pondArea	MISSING
pondDepth	MISSING
pondLidThickness	MISSING
snowScatteringAerosol	MISSING
snowBodyAerosol	MISSING
iceScatteringAerosol	MISSING
iceBodyAerosol	MISSING
brineFraction	MISSING
mobileFraction	MISSING
skeletalAlgaeConc	MISSING
skeletalDOCConc	MISSING
skeletalDICConc	MISSING
skeletalDONConc	MISSING
skeletalNitrateConc	MISSING
skeletalSilicateConc	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
skeletalAmmoniumConc	MISSING
skeletalDMSConc	MISSING
skeletalDMSPpConc	MISSING
skeletalDMSPdConc	MISSING
skeletalNonreactiveConc	MISSING
skeletalHumicsConc	MISSING
skeletalParticulateIronConc	MISSING
skeletalDissolvedIronConc	MISSING
verticalAlgaeConc	MISSING
verticalDOCConc	MISSING
verticalDICConc	MISSING
verticalDONConc	MISSING
verticalNitrateConc	MISSING
verticalSilicateConc	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumConc	MISSING
verticalDMSConc	MISSING
verticalDMSPpConc	MISSING
verticalDMSPdConc	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveConc	MISSING
verticalHumicsConc	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronConc	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronConc	MISSING
verticalAlgaeSnow	MISSING
verticalDOCSnow	MISSING
verticalDICSnow	MISSING
verticalDONSnow	MISSING
verticalNitrateSnow	MISSING
verticalSilicateSnow	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumSnow	MISSING
verticalDMSSnow	MISSING
verticalDMSPpSnow	MISSING
verticalDMSPdSnow	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveSnow	MISSING
verticalHumicsSnow	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronSnow	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronSnow	MISSING
verticalAlgaeIce	MISSING
verticalDOCIce	MISSING
verticalDICIce	MISSING
verticalDONIce	MISSING
verticalNitrateIce	MISSING
verticalSilicateIce	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumIce	MISSING
verticalDMSIce	MISSING
verticalDMSPpIce	MISSING
verticalDMSPdIce	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveIce	MISSING
verticalHumicsIce	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronIce	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronIce	MISSING
verticalAerosolsConc	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
verticalAerosolsSnow	MISSING
verticalAerosolsIce	MISSING
verticalSalinity	MISSING

10.3 tracers_aggregate

Name	Description
iceAreaCell	MISSING
iceVolumeCell	MISSING
snowVolumeCell	MISSING
surfaceTemperatureCell	MISSING
iceEnthalpyCell	MISSING
iceSalinityCell	MISSING
snowEnthalpyCell	MISSING
iceAgeCell	MISSING
firstYearIceAreaCell	MISSING
levelIceAreaCell	MISSING
levelIceVolumeCell	MISSING
pondAreaCell	MISSING
pondDepthCell	MISSING
pondLidThicknessCell	MISSING
snowScatteringAerosolCell	MISSING
snowBodyAerosolCell	MISSING
iceScatteringAerosolCell	MISSING
iceBodyAerosolCell	MISSING
brineFractionCell	Grid cell average ratio of brine height to ice thickness
skeletalAlgaeConcCell	MISSING
skeletalDOCConcCell	MISSING
skeletalDICConcCell	MISSING
skeletalDONConcCell	MISSING
skeletalNitrateConcCell	MISSING
skeletalSilicateConcCell	MISSING
skeletalAmmoniumConcCell	MISSING
skeletalDMSConcCell	MISSING
skeletalDMSPpConcCell	MISSING
skeletalDMSPdConcCell	MISSING
skeletalNonreactiveConcCell	MISSING
skeletalHumicsConcCell	MISSING
skeletalParticulateIronConcCell	MISSING
skeletalDissolvedIronConcCell	MISSING
verticalAlgaeConcCell	MISSING
verticalDOCConcCell	MISSING
verticalDICConcCell	MISSING
verticalDONConcCell	MISSING
verticalNitrateConcCell	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
verticalSilicateConcCell	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumConcCell	MISSING
verticalDMSConcCell	MISSING
verticalDMSPpConcCell	MISSING
verticalDMSPdConcCell	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveConcCell	MISSING
verticalHumicsConcCell	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronConcCell	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronConcCell	MISSING
verticalAlgaeSnowCell	MISSING
verticalDOCSnowCell	MISSING
verticalDICSnowCell	MISSING
verticalDONSnowCell	MISSING
verticalNitrateSnowCell	MISSING
verticalSilicateSnowCell	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumSnowCell	MISSING
verticalDMSSnowCell	MISSING
verticalDMSPpSnowCell	MISSING
verticalDMSPdSnowCell	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveSnowCell	MISSING
verticalHumicsSnowCell	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronSnowCell	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronSnowCell	MISSING
verticalAlgaeIceCell	Cell average algal nitrogen for each type and ice bio-grid layer
verticalDOCIceCell	Cell average dissolved organic carbon for each type and ice bio-grid layer
verticalDICIceCell	Cell average dissolved inorganic carbon for each type and ice bio-grid layer
verticalDONIceCell	Cell average dissolved organic nitrogen for each type and ice bio-grid layer
verticalNitrateIceCell	Cell average nitrate for each ice bio-grid layer
verticalSilicateIceCell	Cell average silicate for each ice bio-grid layer
verticalAmmoniumIceCell	Cell average ammonium for each ice bio-grid layer
verticalDMSIceCell	Cell average DMS for each ice bio-grid layer
verticalDMSPpIceCell	Cell average particulate DMSP for each ice bio-grid layer
verticalDMSPdIceCell	Cell average dissolved DMSP for each ice bio-grid layer
verticalNonreactiveIceCell	Cell average nonreactive nitrate for each ice bio-grid layer
verticalHumicsIceCell	Cell average humic carbon for each ice bio-grid layer
verticalParticulateIronIceCell	Cell average particulate iron for each type and ice bio-grid layer
verticalDissolvedIronIceCell	Cell average dissolved iron for each type and ice bio-grid layer
verticalAerosolsSnowCell	Cell average aerosol for each type and snow bio-grid layer
verticalAerosolsIceCell	Cell average aerosol for each type and ice bio-grid layer
verticalAerosolsConcCell	MISSING
verticalSalinityCell	MISSING

10.4 `icestate`

Name	Description
<code>iceAreaCellInitial</code>	MISSING
<code>iceAreaCategoryInitial</code>	MISSING
<code>iceVolumeCategoryInitial</code>	MISSING
<code>iceThicknessCategoryInitial</code>	MISSING
<code>snowVolumeCategoryInitial</code>	MISSING
<code>openWaterArea</code>	MISSING
<code>iceAreaVertex</code>	MISSING
<code>totalMassCell</code>	MISSING
<code>totalMassVertex</code>	MISSING

10.5 `tracer_tendencies`

Name	Description
<code>iceAreaCategoryTend</code>	MISSING
<code>iceVolumeCategoryTend</code>	MISSING
<code>snowVolumeCategoryTend</code>	MISSING
<code>surfaceTemperatureTend</code>	MISSING
<code>iceEnthalpyTend</code>	MISSING
<code>iceSalinityTend</code>	MISSING
<code>snowEnthalpyTend</code>	MISSING

10.6 `tracer_masks`

Name	Description
<code>iceAreaCategoryMask</code>	MISSING
<code>iceVolumeCategoryMask</code>	MISSING
<code>snowVolumeCategoryMask</code>	MISSING
<code>surfaceTemperatureMask</code>	MISSING
<code>iceEnthalpyMask</code>	MISSING
<code>iceSalinityMask</code>	MISSING
<code>snowEnthalpyMask</code>	MISSING
<code>iceAgeMask</code>	MISSING
<code>firstYearIceAreaMask</code>	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
levelIceAreaMask	MISSING
levelIceVolumeMask	MISSING
pondAreaMask	MISSING
pondDepthMask	MISSING
pondLidThicknessMask	MISSING
snowScatteringAerosolMask	MISSING
snowBodyAerosolMask	MISSING
iceScatteringAerosolMask	MISSING
iceBodyAerosolMask	MISSING
brineFractionMask	MISSING
mobileFractionMask	MISSING
skeletalAlgaeConcMask	MISSING
skeletalDOCConcMask	MISSING
skeletalDICConcMask	MISSING
skeletalDONConcMask	MISSING
skeletalNitrateConcMask	MISSING
skeletalSilicateConcMask	MISSING
skeletalAmmoniumConcMask	MISSING
skeletalDMSConcMask	MISSING
skeletalDMSPpConcMask	MISSING
skeletalDMSPdConcMask	MISSING
skeletalNonreactiveConcMask	MISSING
skeletalHumicsConcMask	MISSING
skeletalParticulateIronConcMask	MISSING
skeletalDissolvedIronConcMask	MISSING
verticalAlgaeSnowMask	MISSING
verticalDOCSnowMask	MISSING
verticalDICSnowMask	MISSING
verticalDONSnowMask	MISSING
verticalNitrateSnowMask	MISSING
verticalSilicateSnowMask	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumSnowMask	MISSING
verticalDMSSnowMask	MISSING
verticalDMSPpSnowMask	MISSING
verticalDMSPdSnowMask	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveSnowMask	MISSING
verticalHumicsSnowMask	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronSnowMask	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronSnowMask	MISSING
verticalAlgaeIceMask	MISSING
verticalDOCIceMask	MISSING
verticalDICIceMask	MISSING
verticalDONIceMask	MISSING
verticalNitrateIceMask	MISSING
verticalSilicateIceMask	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumIceMask	MISSING
verticalDMSIceMask	MISSING
verticalDMSPpIceMask	MISSING
verticalDMSPdIceMask	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveIceMask	MISSING
verticalHumicsIceMask	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
verticalParticulateIronIceMask	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronIceMask	MISSING
verticalAerosolsSnowMask	MISSING
verticalAerosolsIceMask	MISSING
verticalSalinityMask	MISSING

10.7 `tracer_edge_fluxes`

Name	Description
iceAreaCategoryEdgeFlux	MISSING
iceVolumeCategoryEdgeFlux	MISSING
snowVolumeCategoryEdgeFlux	MISSING
surfaceTemperatureEdgeFlux	MISSING
iceEnthalpyEdgeFlux	MISSING
iceSalinityEdgeFlux	MISSING
snowEnthalpyEdgeFlux	MISSING
iceAgeEdgeFlux	MISSING
firstYearIceAreaEdgeFlux	MISSING
levelIceAreaEdgeFlux	MISSING
levelIceVolumeEdgeFlux	MISSING
pondAreaEdgeFlux	MISSING
pondDepthEdgeFlux	MISSING
pondLidThicknessEdgeFlux	MISSING
snowScatteringAerosolEdgeFlux	MISSING
snowBodyAerosolEdgeFlux	MISSING
iceScatteringAerosolEdgeFlux	MISSING
iceBodyAerosolEdgeFlux	MISSING
brineFractionEdgeFlux	MISSING
mobileFractionEdgeFlux	MISSING
skeletalAlgaeConcEdgeFlux	MISSING
skeletalDOCConcEdgeFlux	MISSING
skeletalDICConcEdgeFlux	MISSING
skeletalDONConcEdgeFlux	MISSING
skeletalNitrateConcEdgeFlux	MISSING
skeletalSilicateConcEdgeFlux	MISSING
skeletalAmmoniumConcEdgeFlux	MISSING
skeletalDMSConcEdgeFlux	MISSING
skeletalDMSPPConcEdgeFlux	MISSING
skeletalDMSPDConcEdgeFlux	MISSING
skeletalNonreactiveConcEdgeFlux	MISSING
skeletalHumicsConcEdgeFlux	MISSING
skeletalParticulateIronConcEdge-Flux	MISSING
skeletalDissolvedIronConcEdge-Flux	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
verticalAlgaeSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalDOCsSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalDICsSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalDONsSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalNitrateSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalSilicateSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalDMSSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalDMSPpSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalDMSPdSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalHumicsSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalAlgaeIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalDOCIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalDICIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalDONIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalNitrateIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalSilicateIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalDMSIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalDMSPpIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalDMSPdIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalHumicsIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalAerosolsSnowEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalAerosolsIceEdgeFlux	MISSING
verticalSalinityEdgeFlux	MISSING

10.8 [tracer_products](#)

Name	Description
iceAreaCategoryProduct	MISSING
iceVolumeCategoryProduct	MISSING
snowVolumeCategoryProduct	MISSING
surfaceTemperatureProduct	MISSING
iceEnthalpyProduct	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
iceSalinityProduct	MISSING
snowEnthalpyProduct	MISSING
iceAgeProduct	MISSING
firstYearIceAreaProduct	MISSING
levelIceAreaProduct	MISSING
levelIceVolumeProduct	MISSING
pondAreaProduct	MISSING
pondDepthProduct	MISSING
pondLidThicknessProduct	MISSING
snowScatteringAerosolProduct	MISSING
snowBodyAerosolProduct	MISSING
iceScatteringAerosolProduct	MISSING
iceBodyAerosolProduct	MISSING
brineFractionProduct	MISSING
mobileFractionProduct	MISSING
skeletalAlgaeConcProduct	MISSING
skeletalDOCConcProduct	MISSING
skeletalDICConcProduct	MISSING
skeletalDONConcProduct	MISSING
skeletalNitrateConcProduct	MISSING
skeletalSilicateConcProduct	MISSING
skeletalAmmoniumConcProduct	MISSING
skeletalDMSConcProduct	MISSING
skeletalDMSPpConcProduct	MISSING
skeletalDMSPdConcProduct	MISSING
skeletalNonreactiveConcProduct	MISSING
skeletalHumicsConcProduct	MISSING
skeletalParticulateIronConc-Product	MISSING
skeletalDissolvedIronConc-Product	MISSING
verticalAlgaeSnowProduct	MISSING
verticalDOCSnowProduct	MISSING
verticalDICSnowProduct	MISSING
verticalDONSnowProduct	MISSING
verticalNitrateSnowProduct	MISSING
verticalSilicateSnowProduct	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumSnowProduct	MISSING
verticalDMSSnowProduct	MISSING
verticalDMSPpSnowProduct	MISSING
verticalDMSPdSnowProduct	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveSnowProduct	MISSING
verticalHumicsSnowProduct	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronSnow-Product	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronSnow-Product	MISSING
verticalAlgaeIceProduct	MISSING
verticalDOCIceProduct	MISSING
verticalDICIceProduct	MISSING
verticalDONIceProduct	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
verticalNitrateIceProduct	MISSING
verticalSilicateIceProduct	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumIceProduct	MISSING
verticalDMSIceProduct	MISSING
verticalDMSPpIceProduct	MISSING
verticalDMSPdIceProduct	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveIceProduct	MISSING
verticalHumicsIceProduct	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronIceProduct	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronIceProduct	MISSING
verticalAerosolsSnowProduct	MISSING
verticalAerosolsIceProduct	MISSING
verticalSalinityProduct	MISSING

10.9 tracer_triangles

Name	Description
iceAreaCategoryTriangle	MISSING
iceVolumeCategoryTriangle	MISSING
snowVolumeCategoryTriangle	MISSING
surfaceTemperatureTriangle	MISSING
iceEnthalpyTriangle	MISSING
iceSalinityTriangle	MISSING
snowEnthalpyTriangle	MISSING
iceAgeTriangle	MISSING
firstYearIceAreaTriangle	MISSING
levelIceAreaTriangle	MISSING
levelIceVolumeTriangle	MISSING
pondAreaTriangle	MISSING
pondDepthTriangle	MISSING
pondLidThicknessTriangle	MISSING
snowScatteringAerosolTriangle	MISSING
snowBodyAerosolTriangle	MISSING
iceScatteringAerosolTriangle	MISSING
iceBodyAerosolTriangle	MISSING
brineFractionTriangle	MISSING
mobileFractionTriangle	MISSING
skeletalAlgaeConcTriangle	MISSING
skeletalDOCConcTriangle	MISSING
skeletalDICConcTriangle	MISSING
skeletalDONConcTriangle	MISSING
skeletalNitrateConcTriangle	MISSING
skeletalSilicateConcTriangle	MISSING
skeletalAmmoniumConcTriangle	MISSING
skeletalDMSConcTriangle	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
skeletalDMSPpConcTriangle	MISSING
skeletalDMSPdConcTriangle	MISSING
skeletalNonreactiveConcTriangle	MISSING
skeletalHumicsConcTriangle	MISSING
skeletalParticulateIronConcTriangle	MISSING
skeletalDissolvedIronConcTriangle	MISSING
verticalAlgaeSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalDOCSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalDICSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalDONSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalNitrateSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalSilicateSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalDMSSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalDMSPpSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalDMSPdSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalHumicsSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalAlgaeIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalDOCIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalDICIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalDONIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalNitrateIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalSilicateIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalDMSIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalDMSPpIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalDMSPdIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalHumicsIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalAerosolsSnowTriangle	MISSING
verticalAerosolsIceTriangle	MISSING
verticalSalinityTriangle	MISSING

10.10 `tracer_barycenter`

Name	Description
iceAreaCategoryBarycenterx	MISSING
iceAreaCategoryBarycentery	MISSING
iceVolumeCategoryBarycenterx	MISSING
iceVolumeCategoryBarycentery	MISSING
snowVolumeCategoryBarycenterx	MISSING
snowVolumeCategoryBarycentery	MISSING
surfaceTemperatureBarycenterx	MISSING
surfaceTemperatureBarycentery	MISSING
iceEnthalpyBarycenterx	MISSING
iceEnthalpyBarycentery	MISSING
iceSalinityBarycenterx	MISSING
iceSalinityBarycentery	MISSING
snowEnthalpyBarycenterx	MISSING
snowEnthalpyBarycentery	MISSING
iceAgeBarycenterx	MISSING
iceAgeBarycentery	MISSING
firstYearIceAreaBarycenterx	MISSING
firstYearIceAreaBarycentery	MISSING
levelIceAreaBarycenterx	MISSING
levelIceAreaBarycentery	MISSING
levelIceVolumeBarycenterx	MISSING
levelIceVolumeBarycentery	MISSING
pondAreaBarycenterx	MISSING
pondAreaBarycentery	MISSING
pondDepthBarycenterx	MISSING
pondDepthBarycentery	MISSING
pondLidThicknessBarycenterx	MISSING
pondLidThicknessBarycentery	MISSING
snowScatteringAerosol-Barycenterx	MISSING
snowScatteringAerosol-Barycentery	MISSING
snowBodyAerosolBarycenterx	MISSING
snowBodyAerosolBarycentery	MISSING
iceScatteringAerosolBarycenterx	MISSING
iceScatteringAerosolBarycentery	MISSING
iceBodyAerosolBarycenterx	MISSING
iceBodyAerosolBarycentery	MISSING
brineFractionBarycenterx	MISSING
brineFractionBarycentery	MISSING
mobileFractionBarycenterx	MISSING
mobileFractionBarycentery	MISSING
skeletalAlgaeConcBarycenterx	MISSING
skeletalAlgaeConcBarycentery	MISSING
skeletalDOCConcBarycenterx	MISSING
skeletalDOCConcBarycentery	MISSING
skeletalDICConcBarycenterx	MISSING
skeletalDICConcBarycentery	MISSING
skeletalDONConcBarycenterx	MISSING
skeletalDONConcBarycentery	MISSING
skeletalNitrateConcBarycenterx	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
skeletalNitrateConcBarycentery	MISSING
skeletalSilicateConcBarycenterx	MISSING
skeletalSilicateConcBarycentery	MISSING
skeletalAmmoniumConc-Barycenterx	MISSING
skeletalAmmoniumConc-Barycentery	MISSING
skeletalDMSConcBarycenterx	MISSING
skeletalDMSConcBarycentery	MISSING
skeletalDMSPpConcBarycenterx	MISSING
skeletalDMSPpConcBarycentery	MISSING
skeletalDMSPdConcBarycenterx	MISSING
skeletalDMSPdConcBarycentery	MISSING
skeletalNonreactiveConc-Barycenterx	MISSING
skeletalNonreactiveConc-Barycentery	MISSING
skeletalHumicsConcBarycenterx	MISSING
skeletalHumicsConcBarycentery	MISSING
skeletalParticulateIronConc-Barycenterx	MISSING
skeletalParticulateIronConc-Barycentery	MISSING
skeletalDissolvedIronConc-Barycenterx	MISSING
skeletalDissolvedIronConc-Barycentery	MISSING
verticalAlgaeSnowBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalAlgaeSnowBarycentery	MISSING
verticalDOCSnowBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalDOCSnowBarycentery	MISSING
verticalDICSnowBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalDICSnowBarycentery	MISSING
verticalDONSnowBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalDONSnowBarycentery	MISSING
verticalNitrateSnowBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalNitrateSnowBarycentery	MISSING
verticalSilicateSnowBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalSilicateSnowBarycentery	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumSnow-Barycenterx	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumSnow-Barycentery	MISSING
verticalDMSSnowBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalDMSSnowBarycentery	MISSING
verticalDMSPpSnowBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalDMSPpSnowBarycentery	MISSING
verticalDMSPdSnowBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalDMSPdSnowBarycentery	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveSnow-Barycenterx	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
verticalNonreactiveSnow-Barycenterx	MISSING
verticalHumicsSnowBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalHumicsSnowBarycentery	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronSnow-Barycenterx	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronSnow-Barycentery	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronSnow-Barycenterx	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronSnow-Barycentery	MISSING
verticalAlgaeIceBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalAlgaeIceBarycentery	MISSING
verticalDOCIceBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalDOCIceBarycentery	MISSING
verticalDICIceBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalDICIceBarycentery	MISSING
verticalDONIceBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalDONIceBarycentery	MISSING
verticalNitrateIceBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalNitrateIceBarycentery	MISSING
verticalSilicateIceBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalSilicateIceBarycentery	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumIceBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumIceBarycentery	MISSING
verticalDMSIceBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalDMSIceBarycentery	MISSING
verticalDMSPpIceBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalDMSPpIceBarycentery	MISSING
verticalDMSPdIceBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalDMSPdIceBarycentery	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveIceBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveIceBarycentery	MISSING
verticalHumicsIceBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalHumicsIceBarycentery	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronIce-Barycenterx	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronIce-Barycentery	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronIce-Barycenterx	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronIce-Barycentery	MISSING
verticalAerosolsSnowBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalAerosolsSnowBarycentery	MISSING
verticalAerosolsIceBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalAerosolsIceBarycentery	MISSING
verticalSalinityBarycenterx	MISSING
verticalSalinityBarycentery	MISSING

10.11 tracer_reconstruction

Name	Description
iceAreaCategoryCenter	MISSING
iceAreaCategoryGradx	MISSING
iceAreaCategoryGrady	MISSING
iceVolumeCategoryCenter	MISSING
iceVolumeCategoryGradx	MISSING
iceVolumeCategoryGrady	MISSING
snowVolumeCategoryCenter	MISSING
snowVolumeCategoryGradx	MISSING
snowVolumeCategoryGrady	MISSING
surfaceTemperatureCenter	MISSING
surfaceTemperatureGradx	MISSING
surfaceTemperatureGrady	MISSING
iceEnthalpyCenter	MISSING
iceEnthalpyGradx	MISSING
iceEnthalpyGrady	MISSING
iceSalinityCenter	MISSING
iceSalinityGradx	MISSING
iceSalinityGrady	MISSING
snowEnthalpyCenter	MISSING
snowEnthalpyGradx	MISSING
snowEnthalpyGrady	MISSING
iceAgeCenter	MISSING
iceAgeGradx	MISSING
iceAgeGrady	MISSING
firstYearIceAreaCenter	MISSING
firstYearIceAreaGradx	MISSING
firstYearIceAreaGrady	MISSING
levelIceAreaCenter	MISSING
levelIceAreaGradx	MISSING
levelIceAreaGrady	MISSING
levelIceVolumeCenter	MISSING
levelIceVolumeGradx	MISSING
levelIceVolumeGrady	MISSING
pondAreaCenter	MISSING
pondAreaGradx	MISSING
pondAreaGrady	MISSING
pondDepthCenter	MISSING
pondDepthGradx	MISSING
pondDepthGrady	MISSING
pondLidThicknessCenter	MISSING
pondLidThicknessGradx	MISSING
pondLidThicknessGrady	MISSING
snowScatteringAerosolCenter	MISSING
snowScatteringAerosolGradx	MISSING
snowScatteringAerosolGrady	MISSING
snowBodyAerosolCenter	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
snowBodyAerosolGradx	MISSING
snowBodyAerosolGrady	MISSING
iceScatteringAerosolCenter	MISSING
iceScatteringAerosolGradx	MISSING
iceScatteringAerosolGrady	MISSING
iceBodyAerosolCenter	MISSING
iceBodyAerosolGradx	MISSING
iceBodyAerosolGrady	MISSING
brineFractionCenter	MISSING
brineFractionGradx	MISSING
brineFractionGrady	MISSING
mobileFractionCenter	MISSING
mobileFractionGradx	MISSING
mobileFractionGrady	MISSING
skeletalAlgaeConcCenter	MISSING
skeletalAlgaeConcGradx	MISSING
skeletalAlgaeConcGrady	MISSING
skeletalDOCConcCenter	MISSING
skeletalDOCConcGradx	MISSING
skeletalDOCConcGrady	MISSING
skeletalDICConcCenter	MISSING
skeletalDICConcGradx	MISSING
skeletalDICConcGrady	MISSING
skeletalDONConcCenter	MISSING
skeletalDONConcGradx	MISSING
skeletalDONConcGrady	MISSING
skeletalNitrateConcCenter	MISSING
skeletalNitrateConcGradx	MISSING
skeletalNitrateConcGrady	MISSING
skeletalSilicateConcCenter	MISSING
skeletalSilicateConcGradx	MISSING
skeletalSilicateConcGrady	MISSING
skeletalAmmoniumConcCenter	MISSING
skeletalAmmoniumConcGradx	MISSING
skeletalAmmoniumConcGrady	MISSING
skeletalDMSConcCenter	MISSING
skeletalDMSConcGradx	MISSING
skeletalDMSConcGrady	MISSING
skeletalDMSPpConcCenter	MISSING
skeletalDMSPpConcGradx	MISSING
skeletalDMSPpConcGrady	MISSING
skeletalDMSPdConcCenter	MISSING
skeletalDMSPdConcGradx	MISSING
skeletalDMSPdConcGrady	MISSING
skeletalNonreactiveConcCenter	MISSING
skeletalNonreactiveConcGradx	MISSING
skeletalNonreactiveConcGrady	MISSING
skeletalHumicsConcCenter	MISSING
skeletalHumicsConcGradx	MISSING
skeletalHumicsConcGrady	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
skeletalParticulateIronConcCenter	MISSING
skeletalParticulateIronConcGradx	MISSING
skeletalParticulateIronConcGrady	MISSING
skeletalDissolvedIronConcCenter	MISSING
skeletalDissolvedIronConcGradx	MISSING
skeletalDissolvedIronConcGrady	MISSING
verticalAlgaeSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalAlgaeSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalAlgaeSnowGrady	MISSING
verticalDOCSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalDOCSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalDOCSnowGrady	MISSING
verticalDICSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalDICSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalDICSnowGrady	MISSING
verticalDONSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalDONSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalDONSnowGrady	MISSING
verticalNitrateSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalNitrateSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalNitrateSnowGrady	MISSING
verticalSilicateSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalSilicateSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalSilicateSnowGrady	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumSnowGrady	MISSING
verticalDMSSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalDMSSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalDMSSnowGrady	MISSING
verticalDMSPpSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalDMSPpSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalDMSPpSnowGrady	MISSING
verticalDMSPdSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalDMSPdSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalDMSPdSnowGrady	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveSnowGrady	MISSING
verticalHumicsSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalHumicsSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalHumicsSnowGrady	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronSnowGrady	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
verticalDissolvedIronSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronSnowGrady	MISSING
verticalAlgaeIceCenter	MISSING
verticalAlgaeIceGradx	MISSING
verticalAlgaeIceGrady	MISSING
verticalDOCIceCenter	MISSING
verticalDOCIceGradx	MISSING
verticalDOCIceGrady	MISSING
verticalDICIceCenter	MISSING
verticalDICIceGradx	MISSING
verticalDICIceGrady	MISSING
verticalDONIceCenter	MISSING
verticalDONIceGradx	MISSING
verticalDONIceGrady	MISSING
verticalNitrateIceCenter	MISSING
verticalNitrateIceGradx	MISSING
verticalNitrateIceGrady	MISSING
verticalSilicateIceCenter	MISSING
verticalSilicateIceGradx	MISSING
verticalSilicateIceGrady	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumIceCenter	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumIceGradx	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumIceGrady	MISSING
verticalDMSIceCenter	MISSING
verticalDMSIceGradx	MISSING
verticalDMSIceGrady	MISSING
verticalDMSPpIceCenter	MISSING
verticalDMSPpIceGradx	MISSING
verticalDMSPpIceGrady	MISSING
verticalDMSPdIceCenter	MISSING
verticalDMSPdIceGradx	MISSING
verticalDMSPdIceGrady	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveIceCenter	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveIceGradx	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveIceGrady	MISSING
verticalHumicsIceCenter	MISSING
verticalHumicsIceGradx	MISSING
verticalHumicsIceGrady	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronIceCenter	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronIceGradx	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronIceGrady	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronIceCenter	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronIceGradx	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronIceGrady	MISSING
verticalAerosolsSnowCenter	MISSING
verticalAerosolsSnowGradx	MISSING
verticalAerosolsSnowGrady	MISSING
verticalAerosolsIceCenter	MISSING
verticalAerosolsIceGradx	MISSING
verticalAerosolsIceGrady	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
verticalSalinityCenter	MISSING
verticalSalinityGradx	MISSING
verticalSalinityGrady	MISSING

10.12 `tracer_conservation`

Name	Description
iceAreaCategoryCons	MISSING
iceVolumeCategoryCons	MISSING
snowVolumeCategoryCons	MISSING
surfaceTemperatureCons	MISSING
iceEnthalpyCons	MISSING
iceSalinityCons	MISSING
snowEnthalpyCons	MISSING
iceAgeCons	MISSING
firstYearIceAreaCons	MISSING
levelIceAreaCons	MISSING
levelIceVolumeCons	MISSING
pondAreaCons	MISSING
pondDepthCons	MISSING
pondLidThicknessCons	MISSING
snowScatteringAerosolCons	MISSING
snowBodyAerosolCons	MISSING
iceScatteringAerosolCons	MISSING
iceBodyAerosolCons	MISSING
brineFractionCons	MISSING
mobileFractionCons	MISSING
skeletalAlgaeConcCons	MISSING
skeletalDOCConcCons	MISSING
skeletalDICConcCons	MISSING
skeletalDONConcCons	MISSING
skeletalNitrateConcCons	MISSING
skeletalSilicateConcCons	MISSING
skeletalAmmoniumConcCons	MISSING
skeletalDMSConcCons	MISSING
skeletalDMSPpConcCons	MISSING
skeletalDMSPdConcCons	MISSING
skeletalNonreactiveConcCons	MISSING
skeletalHumicsConcCons	MISSING
skeletalParticulateIronConcCons	MISSING
skeletalDissolvedIronConcCons	MISSING
verticalAlgaeSnowCons	MISSING
verticalDOCSnowCons	MISSING
verticalDICSnowCons	MISSING
verticalDONSnowCons	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
verticalNitrateSnowCons	MISSING
verticalSilicateSnowCons	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumSnowCons	MISSING
verticalDMSSnowCons	MISSING
verticalDMSPpSnowCons	MISSING
verticalDMSPdSnowCons	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveSnowCons	MISSING
verticalHumicsSnowCons	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronSnowCons	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronSnowCons	MISSING
verticalAlgaeIceCons	MISSING
verticalDOCIceCons	MISSING
verticalDICIceCons	MISSING
verticalDONIceCons	MISSING
verticalNitrateIceCons	MISSING
verticalSilicateIceCons	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumIceCons	MISSING
verticalDMSIceCons	MISSING
verticalDMSPpIceCons	MISSING
verticalDMSPdIceCons	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveIceCons	MISSING
verticalHumicsIceCons	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronIceCons	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronIceCons	MISSING
verticalAerosolsSnowCons	MISSING
verticalAerosolsIceCons	MISSING
verticalSalinityCons	MISSING

10.13 `tracer_monotonicity`

Name	Description
iceAreaCategoryLocalMin	MISSING
iceAreaCategoryLocalMax	MISSING
iceVolumeCategoryLocalMin	MISSING
iceVolumeCategoryLocalMax	MISSING
snowVolumeCategoryLocalMin	MISSING
snowVolumeCategoryLocalMax	MISSING
surfaceTemperatureLocalMin	MISSING
surfaceTemperatureLocalMax	MISSING
iceEnthalpyLocalMin	MISSING
iceEnthalpyLocalMax	MISSING
iceSalinityLocalMin	MISSING
iceSalinityLocalMax	MISSING
snowEnthalpyLocalMin	MISSING
snowEnthalpyLocalMax	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
iceAgeLocalMin	MISSING
iceAgeLocalMax	MISSING
firstYearIceAreaLocalMin	MISSING
firstYearIceAreaLocalMax	MISSING
levelIceAreaLocalMin	MISSING
levelIceAreaLocalMax	MISSING
levelIceVolumeLocalMin	MISSING
levelIceVolumeLocalMax	MISSING
pondAreaLocalMin	MISSING
pondAreaLocalMax	MISSING
pondDepthLocalMin	MISSING
pondDepthLocalMax	MISSING
pondLidThicknessLocalMin	MISSING
pondLidThicknessLocalMax	MISSING
snowScatteringAerosolLocalMin	MISSING
snowScatteringAerosolLocalMax	MISSING
snowBodyAerosolLocalMin	MISSING
snowBodyAerosolLocalMax	MISSING
iceScatteringAerosolLocalMin	MISSING
iceScatteringAerosolLocalMax	MISSING
iceBodyAerosolLocalMin	MISSING
iceBodyAerosolLocalMax	MISSING
brineFractionLocalMin	MISSING
brineFractionLocalMax	MISSING
mobileFractionLocalMin	MISSING
mobileFractionLocalMax	MISSING
skeletalAlgaeConcLocalMin	MISSING
skeletalAlgaeConcLocalMax	MISSING
skeletalDOCConcLocalMin	MISSING
skeletalDOCConcLocalMax	MISSING
skeletalDICConcLocalMin	MISSING
skeletalDICConcLocalMax	MISSING
skeletalDONConcLocalMin	MISSING
skeletalDONConcLocalMax	MISSING
skeletalNitrateConcLocalMin	MISSING
skeletalNitrateConcLocalMax	MISSING
skeletalSilicateConcLocalMin	MISSING
skeletalSilicateConcLocalMax	MISSING
skeletalAmmoniumConcLocalMin	MISSING
skeletalAmmoniumConcLocalMax	MISSING
skeletalDMSConcLocalMin	MISSING
skeletalDMSConcLocalMax	MISSING
skeletalDMSPpConcLocalMin	MISSING
skeletalDMSPpConcLocalMax	MISSING
skeletalDMSPdConcLocalMin	MISSING
skeletalDMSPdConcLocalMax	MISSING
skeletalNonreactiveConcLocalMin	MISSING
skeletalNonreactiveConcLocalMax	MISSING
skeletalHumicsConcLocalMin	MISSING
skeletalHumicsConcLocalMax	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
skeletalParticulateIronConcLocal-Min	MISSING
skeletalParticulateIronConcLocal-Max	MISSING
skeletalDissolvedIronConcLocal-Min	MISSING
skeletalDissolvedIronConcLocal-Max	MISSING
verticalAlgaeSnowLocalMin	MISSING
verticalAlgaeSnowLocalMax	MISSING
verticalDOCSnowLocalMin	MISSING
verticalDOCSnowLocalMax	MISSING
verticalDICSnowLocalMin	MISSING
verticalDICSnowLocalMax	MISSING
verticalDONSnowLocalMin	MISSING
verticalDONSnowLocalMax	MISSING
verticalNitrateSnowLocalMin	MISSING
verticalNitrateSnowLocalMax	MISSING
verticalSilicateSnowLocalMin	MISSING
verticalSilicateSnowLocalMax	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumSnowLocalMin	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumSnowLocal-Max	MISSING
verticalDMSSnowLocalMin	MISSING
verticalDMSSnowLocalMax	MISSING
verticalDMSPpSnowLocalMin	MISSING
verticalDMSPpSnowLocalMax	MISSING
verticalDMSPdSnowLocalMin	MISSING
verticalDMSPdSnowLocalMax	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveSnowLocalMin	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveSnowLocal-Max	MISSING
verticalHumicsSnowLocalMin	MISSING
verticalHumicsSnowLocalMax	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronSnowLocal-Min	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronSnowLocal-Max	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronSnowLocal-Min	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronSnowLocal-Max	MISSING
verticalAlgaeIceLocalMin	MISSING
verticalAlgaeIceLocalMax	MISSING
verticalDOCIceLocalMin	MISSING
verticalDOCIceLocalMax	MISSING
verticalDICIceLocalMin	MISSING
verticalDICIceLocalMax	MISSING
verticalDONIceLocalMin	MISSING
verticalDONIceLocalMax	MISSING
verticalNitrateIceLocalMin	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
verticalNitrateIceLocalMax	MISSING
verticalSilicateIceLocalMin	MISSING
verticalSilicateIceLocalMax	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumIceLocalMin	MISSING
verticalAmmoniumIceLocalMax	MISSING
verticalDMSIceLocalMin	MISSING
verticalDMSIceLocalMax	MISSING
verticalDMSPpIceLocalMin	MISSING
verticalDMSPpIceLocalMax	MISSING
verticalDMSPdIceLocalMin	MISSING
verticalDMSPdIceLocalMax	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveIceLocalMin	MISSING
verticalNonreactiveIceLocalMax	MISSING
verticalHumicsIceLocalMin	MISSING
verticalHumicsIceLocalMax	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronIceLocal- Min	MISSING
verticalParticulateIronIceLocal- Max	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronIceLocalMin	MISSING
verticalDissolvedIronIceLocalMax	MISSING
verticalAerosolsSnowLocalMin	MISSING
verticalAerosolsSnowLocalMax	MISSING
verticalAerosolsIceLocalMin	MISSING
verticalAerosolsIceLocalMax	MISSING
verticalSalinityLocalMin	MISSING
verticalSalinityLocalMax	MISSING

10.14 rotated_mesh

Name	Description
xCellRotate	MISSING
yCellRotate	MISSING
zCellRotate	MISSING
xVertexRotate	MISSING
yVertexRotate	MISSING
zVertexRotate	MISSING
xEdgeRotate	MISSING
yEdgeRotate	MISSING
zEdgeRotate	MISSING

10.15 incremental_remap

Name	Description
xTriangle	MISSING
yTriangle	MISSING
iCellTriangle	MISSING
triangleArea	MISSING
departurePoint	MISSING
remapEdge	MISSING
cellsOnEdgeRemap	MISSING
edgesOnEdgeRemap	MISSING
xVertexOnCell	MISSING
yVertexOnCell	MISSING
xVertexOnEdge	MISSING
yVertexOnEdge	MISSING
transCellToGlobal	MISSING
transGlobalToCell	MISSING
transVertexToGlobal	MISSING
transGlobalToVertex	MISSING
transEdgeToGlobal	MISSING
transGlobalToEdge	MISSING
minLengthEdgesOnVertex	MISSING
xAvgCell	MISSING
yAvgCell	MISSING
xxAvgCell	MISSING
xyAvgCell	MISSING
yyAvgCell	MISSING
xxxAvgCell	MISSING
xxyAvgCell	MISSING
xyyAvgCell	MISSING
yyyAvgCell	MISSING
xxxxAvgCell	MISSING
xxxyAvgCell	MISSING
xxyyAvgCell	MISSING
xyyyAvgCell	MISSING
yyyyAvgCell	MISSING
maskEdge	MISSING
maskCell	MISSING
maskCategoryCell	MISSING
workCategoryCell	MISSING

10.16 forcing

Name	Description
nForcingGroupCounter	MISSING
forcingGroupNames	MISSING
forcingGroupRestartTimes	MISSING

10.17 `atmos_coupling`

Name	Description
airLevelHeight	MISSING
airPotentialTemperature	MISSING
airTemperature	MISSING
airSpecificHumidity	MISSING
airDensity	MISSING
shortwaveVisibleDirectDown	MISSING
shortwaveVisibleDiffuseDown	MISSING
shortwaveIRDirectDown	MISSING
shortwaveIRDiffuseDown	MISSING
longwaveDown	MISSING
rainfallRate	MISSING
snowfallRate	MISSING
uAirVelocity	MISSING
vAirVelocity	MISSING
atmosReferenceSpeed10m	MISSING
atmosReferenceTemperature2m	MISSING
atmosReferenceHumidity2m	MISSING

10.18 `atmos_forcing`

Name	Description
windSpeed	MISSING
uAirStress	MISSING
vAirStress	MISSING
shortwaveDown	MISSING
cloudFraction	MISSING
sensibleTransferCoefficient	MISSING
latentTransferCoefficient	MISSING

10.19 alternative_atmos_forcing

Name	Description
latentHeatFluxCouple	MISSING
sensibleHeatFluxCouple	MISSING
surfaceHeatFluxCouple	MISSING
surfaceConductiveFluxCouple	MISSING
airStressForcingU	MISSING
airStressForcingV	MISSING

10.20 ocean_coupling

Name	Description
seaSurfaceTemperature	MISSING
seaSurfaceSalinity	MISSING
seaFreezingTemperature	MISSING
freezingMeltingPotential	MISSING
uOceanVelocity	MISSING
vOceanVelocity	MISSING
seaSurfaceTiltU	MISSING
seaSurfaceTiltV	MISSING
oceanMixedLayerDepth	MISSING
oceanHeatFluxConvergence	MISSING
landIceMask	MISSING
landIceMaskVertex	MISSING

10.21 boundary

Name	Description
interiorVertex	MISSING
interiorCell	MISSING
interiorEdge	MISSING
blockIDout	MISSING

10.22 velocity_solver

Name	Description
dynamicsTimeStep	MISSING
elasticTimeStep	MISSING
uVelocity	MISSING
vVelocity	MISSING
uVelocityInitial	MISSING
vVelocityInitial	MISSING
edgeVelocity	MISSING
normalVectorEdge	MISSING
solveStress	MISSING
solveVelocity	MISSING
solveVelocityPrevious	MISSING
icePressure	MISSING
stressDivergenceU	MISSING
stressDivergenceV	MISSING
airStressCellU	MISSING
airStressCellV	MISSING
airStressVertexU	MISSING
airStressVertexV	MISSING
uOceanVelocityVertex	MISSING
vOceanVelocityVertex	MISSING
oceanStressU	MISSING
oceanStressV	MISSING
oceanStressCoeff	MISSING
oceanStressCellU	MISSING
oceanStressCellV	MISSING
seaSurfaceTiltVertexU	MISSING
seaSurfaceTiltVertexV	MISSING
surfaceTiltForceU	MISSING
surfaceTiltForceV	MISSING
totalMassVertexfVertex	MISSING
divergence	MISSING
shear	MISSING
dynamicallyLockedCellsMask	MISSING

10.23 velocity_weak

Name	Description
normalVectorPolygon	MISSING
normalVectorTriangle	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
latCellRotated	MISSING
latVertexRotated	MISSING
strain11weak	MISSING
strain22weak	MISSING
strain12weak	MISSING
stress11weak	MISSING
stress22weak	MISSING
stress12weak	MISSING
principalStress1Weak	MISSING
principalStress2Weak	MISSING
replacementPressureWeak	MISSING

10.24 velocity_variational

Name	Description
strain11var	MISSING
strain22var	MISSING
strain12var	MISSING
stress11var	MISSING
stress22var	MISSING
stress12var	MISSING
tanLatVertexRotatedOverRadius	MISSING
cellVerticesAtVertex	MISSING
basisIntegralsU	MISSING
basisIntegralsV	MISSING
basisIntegralsMetric	MISSING
basisGradientU	MISSING
basisGradientV	MISSING
principalStress1Var	MISSING
principalStress2Var	MISSING
replacementPressureVar	MISSING

10.25 ridging

Name	Description
ridgeConvergence	MISSING
ridgeShear	MISSING
areaLossRidge	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
areaGainRidge	MISSING
iceVolumeRidged	MISSING
openingRateRidge	MISSING
ridgeParticipationFunction	MISSING
ratioRidgeThicknessToIce	MISSING
fractionNewRidgeArea	MISSING
fractionNewRidgeVolume	MISSING
areaLossRidgeCategory	MISSING
areaGainRidgeCategory	MISSING
iceVolumeRidgedCategory	MISSING
raftingIceArea	MISSING
raftingIceVolume	MISSING

10.26 melt_growth_rates

Name	Description
lateralIceMeltFraction	MISSING
surfaceIceMelt	MISSING
surfaceIceMeltCategory	MISSING
basalIceMelt	MISSING
basalIceMeltCategory	MISSING
lateralIceMelt	MISSING
snowMelt	MISSING
snowMeltCategory	MISSING
congelation	MISSING
congelationCategory	MISSING
snowiceFormation	MISSING
snowiceFormationCategory	MISSING
snowThicknessChange	MISSING
snowThicknessChangeCategory	MISSING
frazilFormation	MISSING
frazilGrowthDiagnostic	MISSING

10.27 atmos_fluxes

Name	Description
surfaceHeatFlux	MISSING
surfaceHeatFluxCategory	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
surfaceConductiveFlux	MISSING
surfaceConductiveFluxCategory	MISSING
longwaveUp	MISSING
sensibleHeatFlux	MISSING
sensibleHeatFluxCategory	MISSING
latentHeatFlux	MISSING
latentHeatFluxCategory	MISSING
evaporativeWaterFlux	MISSING

10.28 ocean_fluxes

Name	Description
oceanFreshWaterFlux	MISSING
oceanSaltFlux	MISSING
oceanHeatFlux	MISSING
oceanShortwaveFlux	MISSING
oceanFreshWaterFluxArea	MISSING
oceanSaltFluxArea	MISSING
oceanHeatFluxArea	MISSING
oceanShortwaveFluxArea	MISSING
oceanHeatFluxIceBottom	MISSING

10.29 ocean_atmosphere

Name	Description
airStressOceanU	MISSING
airStressOceanV	MISSING
atmosReferenceTemperature2m-Ocean	MISSING
atmosReferenceHumidity2mOcean	MISSING
albedoVisibleDirectOcean	MISSING
albedoVisibleDiffuseOcean	MISSING
albedoIRDirectOcean	MISSING
albedoIRDiffuseOcean	MISSING
longwaveUpOcean	MISSING
sensibleHeatFluxOcean	MISSING
latentHeatFluxOcean	MISSING
evaporativeWaterFluxOcean	MISSING

10.30 shortwave

Name	Description
dayOfNextShortwaveCalculation	MISSING
solarZenithAngleCosine	MISSING
albedoVisibleDirectCategory	MISSING
albedoVisibleDiffuseCategory	MISSING
albedoIRDirectCategory	MISSING
albedoIRDiffuseCategory	MISSING
albedoVisibleDirectCell	MISSING
albedoVisibleDiffuseCell	MISSING
albedoIRDirectCell	MISSING
albedoIRDiffuseCell	MISSING
albedoVisibleDirectArea	MISSING
albedoVisibleDiffuseArea	MISSING
albedoIRDirectArea	MISSING
albedoIRDiffuseArea	MISSING
shortwaveScalingFactor	MISSING
surfaceShortwaveFlux	MISSING
interiorShortwaveFlux	MISSING
penetratingShortwaveFlux	MISSING
shortwaveLayerPenetration	MISSING
absorbedShortwaveFlux	MISSING
absorbedShortwaveSnowLayer	MISSING
absorbedShortwaveIceLayer	MISSING
bareIceAlbedoCategory	MISSING
snowAlbedoCategory	MISSING
pondAlbedoCategory	MISSING
bareIceAlbedoCell	MISSING
snowAlbedoCell	MISSING
pondAlbedoCell	MISSING
effectivePondAreaCategory	MISSING
effectivePondAreaCell	MISSING
snowFractionCategory	MISSING

10.31 drag

Name	Description
airOceanDragCoefficientRatio	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
oceanDragCoefficient	MISSING
oceanDragCoefficientSkin	MISSING
oceanDragCoefficientFloe	MISSING
oceanDragCoefficientKeel	MISSING
airDragCoefficient	MISSING
airDragCoefficientSkin	MISSING
airDragCoefficientFloe	MISSING
airDragCoefficientPond	MISSING
airDragCoefficientRidge	MISSING
dragFreeboard	MISSING
dragIceSnowDraft	MISSING
dragRidgeHeight	MISSING
dragRidgeSeparation	MISSING
dragKeelDepth	MISSING
dragKeelSeparation	MISSING
dragFloeLength	MISSING
dragFloeSeparation	MISSING

10.32 ponds

Name	Description
pondFreshWaterFlux	MISSING
pondSnowDepthDifference	MISSING
pondLidMeltFluxFraction	MISSING

10.33 aerosols

Name	Description
atmosAerosolFlux	MISSING
oceanAerosolFlux	MISSING
aerosolMassExtinctionCross-Section	MISSING
aerosolSingleScatterAlbedo	MISSING
aerosolAsymmetryParameter	MISSING
modalMassExtinctionCross-Section	MISSING
modalSingleScatterAlbedo	MISSING
modalAsymmetryParameter	MISSING
modalBCabsorptionParameter	MISSING

10.34 biogeochemistry

Name	Description
newlyFormedIce	MISSING
rayleighCriteriaReal	MISSING
atmosBioFluxes	MISSING
atmosIceBioFluxes	MISSING
snowIceBioFluxes	MISSING
atmosBlackCarbonFlux	MISSING
atmosDustFlux	MISSING
oceanBioFluxes	Tracers are ordered: diatom nitrogen, smallPlankton nitrogen, phaeocystis nitrogen, nitrate, polysaccharid carbon, lipid carbon, ammonium, silicate, DMSPp, DMSPd, DMS, Nonreactive nitrate, Protein nitrogen, dissolved iron in umol/m ² /s, particulate iron in umol/m ² /s, humic carbon, black carbon1 in mg/m ² /s, black carbon2 in mg/m ² /s, dust1 in mg/m ² /s, dust2 in mg/m ² /s, dust3 in mg/m ² /s, dust4 in mg/m ² /s
oceanBioConcentrations	Tracers are ordered: diatom nitrogen, smallPlankton nitrogen, phaeocystis nitrogen, nitrate, polysaccharid carbon, lipid carbon, ammonium, silicate, DMSPp, DMSPd, DMS, Nonreactive nitrate, Protein nitrogen, dissolved iron in umol/m ³ , particulate iron in umol/m ³ , humic carbon, black carbon1 in mg/m ³ , black carbon2 in mg/m ³ , dust1 in mg/m ³ , dust2 in mg/m ³ , dust3 in mg/m ³ , dust4 in mg/m ³
oceanAlgaeConc	MISSING
oceanDOCConc	MISSING
oceanDICConc	MISSING
oceanDONConc	MISSING
oceanNitrateConc	MISSING
oceanSilicateConc	MISSING
oceanAmmoniumConc	MISSING
oceanDMSConc	MISSING
oceanDMSPConc	MISSING
oceanHumicsConc	MISSING
oceanParticulateIronConc	MISSING
oceanDissolvedIronConc	MISSING
oceanZAerosolConc	MISSING
oceanAlgaeFlux	MISSING
oceanDOCFlux	MISSING
oceanDICFlux	MISSING
oceanDONFlux	MISSING
oceanNitrateFlux	MISSING
oceanSilicateFlux	MISSING
oceanAmmoniumFlux	MISSING
oceanDMSFlux	MISSING
oceanDMSPpFlux	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
oceanDMSPdFlux	MISSING
oceanHumicsFlux	MISSING
oceanParticulateIronFlux	MISSING
oceanDissolvedIronFlux	MISSING
oceanDustIronFlux	MISSING
bioTracerShortwave	MISSING
bioPorosity	MISSING
bioTemperature	MISSING
bioShortwaveFlux	Shortwave radiative flux on the vertical biology grid per category
bioShortwaveFluxCell	Averaged cell shortwave radiative flux on the vertical biology grid
bioDiffusivity	MISSING
bioPermeability	MISSING
zSalinityFlux	MISSING
zSalinityGDFlux	MISSING
zSalinityFluxCat	MISSING
zSalinityGDFluxCat	MISSING
darcyVelocityBio	MISSING
brineTopChange	MISSING
brineBottomChange	MISSING
zSalinityIceDensity	MISSING
peakVerticalAlgalConc	MISSING
netSpecificAlgalGrowthRate	Specific algal growth rate per grid cell
verticalNitrogenLosses	MISSING
netNitrateUptake	Total rate of nitrate uptake by algae weighted by ice area
netAmmoniumUptake	Total rate of ammonium uptake by algae weighted by ice area
primaryProduction	Average total primary production in a grid cell
totalSkeletalAlgae	MISSING
totalVerticalBiologyIce	Tracers are ordered: diatom nitrogen, smallPlankton nitrogen, phaeocystis nitrogen, nitrate, polysaccharid carbon, lipid carbon, ammonium, silicate, DMSPp, DMSPd, DMS, Nonreactive nitrate, Protein nitrogen, dissolved iron in umol/m2, particulate iron in umol/m2, humic carbon, black carbon1 in mg/m2, black carbon2 in mg/m2,dust1 in mg/m2, dust2 in mg/m2, dust3 in mg/m2, dust4 in mg/m2
totalVerticalBiologySnow	Tracers are ordered: diatom nitrogen, smallPlankton nitrogen, phaeocystis nitrogen, nitrate, polysaccharid carbon, lipid carbon, ammonium, silicate, DMSPp, DMSPd, DMS, Nonreactive nitrate, Protein nitrogen, dissolved iron in umol/m2, particulate iron in umol/m2, humic carbon, black carbon1 in mg/m2, black carbon2 in mg/m2,dust1 in mg/m2, dust2 in mg/m2, dust3 in mg/m2, dust4 in mg/m2
totalVerticalSalinity	MISSING
totalChlorophyll	Ice integrated chlorophyll concentration per cell
totalNitrate	Ice integrated nitrate concentration per cell
netBrineHeight	Cell average brine height
biologyGrid	MISSING
interfaceBiologyGrid	MISSING
verticalGrid	MISSING
interfaceGrid	MISSING
verticalShortwaveGrid	MISSING
carbonToNitrogenRatioAlgae	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
carbonToNitrogenRatioDON	MISSING

10.35 **initial**

Name	Description
initialSalinityProfile	MISSING
initialMeltingTemperatureProfile	MISSING
categoryThicknessLimits	MISSING

10.36 **regions**

Name	Description
regionCellMasks	MISSING
regionVertexMasks	MISSING
regionNames	MISSING

10.37 **diagnostics**

Name	Description
xtime	MISSING
simulationStartTime	MISSING
daysSinceStartOfSim	MISSING
meltOnset	MISSING
freezeOnset	MISSING
iceAreaTendencyTransport	MISSING
iceVolumeTendencyTransport	MISSING
iceAgeTendencyTransport	MISSING
iceAreaTendencyThermodynamics	MISSING
iceVolumeTendency- Thermodynamics	MISSING
iceAgeTendencyThermodynamics	MISSING
freezingMeltingPotentialInitial	MISSING

Name	Description (Continued)
timeAverageTestVariable	MISSING

10.38 [testing_system_test](#)

Name	Description
testArrayRegression	MISSING
testArrayParallelism	MISSING
testArrayRestartability	MISSING

10.39 [pointLocations](#)

Name	Description
pointCellGlobalID	List of global cell IDs in point set.
pointCellLocalID	List of local cell IDs in point set.
indexToPointCellLocalID	Index to list of local cell IDs in point set.
pointVertexGlobalID	List of global vertex IDs in point set.
pointVertexLocalID	List of local vertex IDs in point set.
indexToPointVertexLocalID	Index to list of local vertex IDs in point set.
pointNames	The names of each point.
pointGroupNames	The names of each point group.
nPointsInGroup	The number of points in each point group.
pointsInGroup	The indices of each point in a each group.
xPoint	X Coordinate in cartesian space of point locations.
yPoint	Y Coordinate in cartesian space of point locations.
zPoint	Z Coordinate in cartesian space of point locations.
latPoint	Latitude of point locations.
lonPoint	Longitude of point locations.

10.40 [highFrequencyOutputAM](#)

Name	Description
iceAreaCellCategory1	area of ice in category 1

10.41 [temperaturesAM](#)

Name	Description
iceTemperature	Ice layer temperature
snowTemperature	snow layer temperature

10.42 [regionalStatisticsAM](#)

Name	Description
uVelocityCell	U ice velocity on cells
vVelocityCell	V ice velocity on cells
totalIceArea	Total sea-ice area by region
totalIceExtent	Total sea-ice extent by region
totalIceVolume	Total sea-ice volume by region
totalSnowVolume	Total snow volume by region
totalKineticEnergy	Total kinetic energy by region
rmsIceSpeed	RMS ice speed by region
averageAlbedo	Average albedo by region
maximumIceVolume	Maximum sea-ice volume by region
maximumIceVolumeLocked	Maximum sea-ice volume by region for dynamically locked cells
maximumIceVolumeNotLocked	Maximum sea-ice volume by region for non-dynamically locked cells
maximumIcePressure	Maximum sea-ice pressure by region
maximumIceSpeed	Maximum sea-ice speed by region

10.43 [ridgingDiagnosticsAM](#)

Name	Description
levelIceAreaAverage	level ice cell fraction
ridgedIceAreaAverage	ridged ice cell fraction
levelIceVolumeAverage	level ice cell volume
ridgedIceVolumeAverage	ridged ice cell volume

10.44 conservationCheckAM

Name	Description
performConservationPrecompute	MISSING

10.45 conservationCheckEnergyAM

Name	Description
initialEnergy	Total initial energy of ice and snow
finalEnergy	Total final energy of ice and snow
energyChange	Total energy change of ice and snow during time step
netEnergyFlux	Net energy flux to ice
absoluteEnergyError	Absolute energy conservation error
relativeEnergyError	Relative energy conservation error
accumulatedSurfaceHeatFlux	MISSING
accumulatedOceanHeatFlux	MISSING
accumulatedFreezingPotential	MISSING
accumulatedSnowfallHeat	MISSING
accumulatedLatentHeat	MISSING

10.46 conservationCheckMassAM

Name	Description
initialMass	Total initial mass of ice and snow
finalMass	Total final mass of ice and snow
massChange	Total mass change of ice and snow during time step
netMassFlux	Net mass flux to ice
absoluteMassError	Absolute mass conservation error
relativeMassError	Relative mass conservation error
accumulatedRainfallRate	MISSING
accumulatedSnowfallRate	MISSING
accumulatedEvaporation	MISSING
accumulatedFreshWater	MISSING
accumulatedFrazilWater	MISSING

10.47 conservationCheckSaltAM

Name	Description
initialSalt	Total initial salt of ice and snow
finalSalt	Total final salt of ice and snow
saltChange	Total salt change of ice and snow during time step
netSaltFlux	Net salt flux to ice
absoluteSaltError	Absolute salt conservation error
relativeSaltError	Relative salt conservation error
accumulatedOceanSaltFlux	MISSING
accumulatedFrazilSaltFlux	MISSING

10.48 geographicalVectorsAM

Name	Description
uVelocityGeo	True eastwards ice velocity
vVelocityGeo	True northwards ice velocity
stressDivergenceUGeo	True eastwards stress divergence
stressDivergenceVGeo	True northwards stress divergence
airStressVertexUGeo	True eastwards sea ice-air stress
airStressVertexVGeo	True northwards sea ice-air stress
oceanStressUGeo	True eastwards sea ice-ocean stress
oceanStressVGeo	True northwards sea ice-ocean stress
surfaceTiltForceUGeo	True eastwards sea surface tilt stress
surfaceTiltForceVGeo	True northwards sea surface tilt stress
uOceanVelocityVertexGeo	True eastwards ocean velocity
vOceanVelocityVertexGeo	True northwards ocean velocity

10.49 loadBalanceAM

Name	Description
nCellsProcWithSeaIce	Number of cells with sea ice present per processor
nCellsProc	Number of cells per processor

10.50 [maximumIcePresenceAM](#)

Name	Description
maximumIcePresence	Maximum extent of sea-ice for the simulation divided by months

10.51 [miscellaneousAM](#)

Name	Description
bulkSalinity	Bulk salinity of ice in a cell
broadbandAlbedo	snow/sea ice broadband albedo
coriolisStressVertexU	Coriolis stress in U direction
coriolisStressVertexV	Coriolis stress in V direction

10.52 [areaVariablesAM](#)

Name	Description
snowfallRateInitialArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
rainfallRateInitialArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
absorbedShortwaveFluxInitialArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
latentHeatFluxInitialArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
sensibleHeatFluxInitialArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
longwaveUpInitialArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
evaporativeWaterFluxInitialArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
surfaceHeatFluxInitialArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
surfaceConductiveFluxInitialArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
surfaceHeatFluxCategoryInitialArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
surfaceConductiveFluxCategoryInitialArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
latentHeatFluxCategoryInitialArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
sensibleHeatFluxCategoryInitialArea	DESCRIPTION HERE

10.53 [pondDiagnosticsAM](#)

Name	Description
meltPondArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
meltPondAreaFinalArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
meltPondDepth	DESCRIPTION HERE
meltPondDepthFinalArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
meltPondLidThickness	DESCRIPTION HERE
meltPondLidThicknessFinalArea	DESCRIPTION HERE
meltPondDepthCategory	DESCRIPTION HERE

10.54 [iceShelvesAM](#)

Name	Description
iceAreaOverIceShelves	Total ice area present where ice shelves exist

10.55 [icePresentAM](#)

Name	Description
icePresent	1.0 if ice present, 0.0 if ice not present

10.56 [timeSeriesStatsAM](#)

Name	Description
timeSeriesStatsOneString	MISSING
timeSeriesStatsOneInteger	MISSING
timeSeriesStatsOneReal	MISSING

Part III

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Part IV

Appendices

Appendix A

Namelist options

Embedded links point to information in chapter 8

A.1 [seaice_model](#)

A.1.1 [config_dt](#)

Type:	real
Units:	Seconds
Default Value:	3600.0
Possible Values:	Any positive real number.

Table A.1: config_dt: Length of model time-step.

A.1.2 [config_calendar_type](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	gregorian_noleap
Possible Values:	'gregorian', 'gregorian_noleap'

Table A.2: config_calendar_type: Selection of the type of calendar that should be used in the simulation.

A.1.3 [config_start_time](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	2000-01-01_00:00:00
Possible Values:	'YYYY-MM-DD_HH:MM:SS' or 'file'

Table A.3: `config_start_time`: Timestamp describing the initial time of the simulation. If it is set to 'file', the initial time is read from `restart_timestamp`.

A.1.4 `config_stop_time`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	none
Possible Values:	'YYYY-MM-DD_HH:MM:SS' or 'none'

Table A.4: `config_stop_time`: Timestamp describing the final time of the simulation. If it is set to 'none' the final time is determined from `config_start_time` and `config_run_duration`.

A.1.5 `config_run_duration`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	00-00-01_00:00:00
Possible Values:	"YYYY-MM-DD_HH:MM:SS" or 'none'

Table A.5: `config_run_duration`: Timestamp describing the length of the simulation. If it is set to 'none' the duration is determined from `config_start_time` and `config_stop_time`. `config_run_duration` overrides inconsistent values of `config_stop_time`.

A.1.6 `config_num_halos`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	2
Possible Values:	Any positive integer value.

Table A.6: `config_num_halos`: Determines the number of halo cells extending from a blocks owned cells (Called the 0-Halo). The default of 3 is the minimum that can be used with monotonic advection.

A.2 io

A.2.1 `config_pio_num_iotasks`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0
Possible Values:	Any positive integer value greater than or equal to 0.

Table A.7: `config_pio_num_iotasks`: Integer specifying how many IO tasks should be used within the PIO library. A value of 0 causes all MPI tasks to also be IO tasks. IO tasks are required to write contiguous blocks of data to a file.

A.2.2 `config_pio_stride`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1
Possible Values:	Any positive integer value greater than 0.

Table A.8: `config_pio_stride`: Integer specifying the stride of each IO task.

A.2.3 `config_write_output_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.9: `config_write_output_on_startup`: If true write the output streams to disk after model initialization but before time stepping.

A.2.4 `config_test_case_diag`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.10: `config_test_case_diag`: If true output test case diagnostics.

A.2.5 `config_test_case_diag_type`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	none
Possible Values:	'global_velocity', 'square_advection' or 'advection'

Table A.11: `config_test_case_diag_type`: Test case diagnostic type.

A.2.6 `config_full_abort_write`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.12: `config_full_abort_write`: If true write the abort stream to disk after a critical error for the entire domain, not just failing block.

A.3 decomposition

A.3.1 `config_block_decomp_file_prefix`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	graphs/graph.info.part.
Possible Values:	Any path/prefix to a block decomposition file.

Table A.13: `config_block_decomp_file_prefix`: Defines the prefix for the block decomposition file. Can include a path. The number of blocks is appended to the end of the prefix at run-time.

A.3.2 `config_number_of_blocks`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0
Possible Values:	Any integer greater than or equal to 0.

Table A.14: `config_number_of_blocks`: Determines the number of blocks a simulation should be run with. If it is set to 0, the number of blocks is the same as the number of MPI tasks at run-time.

A.3.3 `config_explicit_proc_decomp`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.15: `config_explicit_proc_decomp`: Determines if an explicit processor decomposition should be used. This is only useful if multiple blocks per processor are used.

A.3.4 `config_proc_decomp_file_prefix`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	graphs/graph.info.part.
Possible Values:	Any path/prefix to a processor decomposition file.

Table A.16: `config_proc_decomp_file_prefix`: Defines the prefix for the processor decomposition file. This file is only read if `config_explicit_proc_decomp` is true. The number of processors is appended to the end of the prefix at run-time.

A.3.5 `config_use_halo_exch`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	.true. or .false.

Table A.17: `config_use_halo_exch`: Determines if time integration halo exchanges are performed.

A.3.6 `config_aggregate_halo_exch`

Type:	logical
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Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	.true. or .false.

Table A.18: `config_aggregate_halo_exch`: Determines if aggregated halo exchanges are used in some places.

A.3.7 `config_reuse_halo_exch`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	.true. or .false.

Table A.19: `config_reuse_halo_exch`: Determines if halo exchange lists are reused.

A.3.8 `config_load_balance_timers`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	.true. or .false.

Table A.20: `config_load_balance_timers`: Determines if mpi barriers are used and timed before halo exchanges.

A.4 `restart`

A.4.1 `config_do_restart`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.21: `config_do_restart`: Determines if the initial conditions should be read from a restart file, or an input file.

A.4.2 `config_restart_timestamp_name`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	restart_timestamp
Possible Values:	Path to a file.

Table A.22: `config_restart_timestamp_name`: Path to the filename for restart timestamps to be read and written from.

A.4.3 `config_do_restart_hbrine`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.23: `config_do_restart_hbrine`: Restart the brine height tracer needed for vertical bgc

A.4.4 `config_do_restart_zsalinity`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	false

Table A.24: `config_do_restart_zsalinity`: Restart the z-salinity tracer

A.4.5 `config_do_restart_bgc`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.25: `config_do_restart_bgc`: Restart the ice biogeochemistry

A.5 dimensions

A.5.1 config_nCategories

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	5
Possible Values:	Any positive integer.

Table A.26: config_nCategories: The number of ice thickness categories to use.

A.5.2 config_nIceLayers

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	7
Possible Values:	Any positive integer.

Table A.27: config_nIceLayers: The number of ice layers in the vertical direction to use.

A.5.3 config_nSnowLayers

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1
Possible Values:	Any positive integer.

Table A.28: config_nSnowLayers: The number of snow layers in the vertical direction to use.

A.6 initialize

A.6.1 config_initial_condition_type

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	cice_default
Possible Values:	'restart', 'uniform', 'circle', 'square' or 'uniform_interior'

Table A.29: config_initial_condition_type: Initial condition type for sea ice state.

A.6.2 `config_initial_ice_area`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	A real number between 0.0 and 1.0 inclusive.

Table A.30: `config_initial_ice_area`: Sea ice concentration at initialization.

A.6.3 `config_initial_ice_volume`

Type:	real
Units:	m
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	Any positive real number.

Table A.31: `config_initial_ice_volume`: Sea ice volume at initialization.

A.6.4 `config_initial_snow_volume`

Type:	real
Units:	m
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	Any positive real number.

Table A.32: `config_initial_snow_volume`: Sea ice snow volume at initialization.

A.6.5 `config_initial_latitude_north`

Type:	real
Units:	degrees latitude
Default Value:	70.0
Possible Values:	Any real number.

Table A.33: `config_initial_latitude_north`: Minimum latitude limit for initial northern hemisphere sea ice extent.

A.6.6 `config_initial_latitude_south`

Type:	real
Units:	degrees latitude
Default Value:	-60.0
Possible Values:	Any real number.

Table A.34: `config_initial_latitude_south`: Maximum latitude limit for initial southern hemisphere sea ice extent.

A.6.7 `config_initial_velocity_type`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	uniform
Possible Values:	'uniform', 'ocean', 'random', 'special', or 'none'

Table A.35: `config_initial_velocity_type`: Initial condition type for sea ice velocity.

A.6.8 `config_initial_uvelocity`

Type:	real
Units:	m s^{-2}
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	Any real number.

Table A.36: `config_initial_uvelocity`: Sea ice velocity in the U direction at initialization. ???Geo or native???

A.6.9 `config_initial_vvelocity`

Type:	real
Units:	m s^{-2}
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	Any real number.

Table A.37: `config_initial_vvelocity`: Sea ice velocity in the V direction at initialization. ???Geo or native???

A.6.10 `config_calculate_coriolis`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or .false

Table A.38: `config_calculate_coriolis`: If True calculate the Coriolis parameter at initialization from the latitude.

A.7 `use_sections`

A.7.1 `config_use_velocity_solver`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or .false

Table A.39: `config_use_velocity_solver`: If true calculate the sea ice velocity.

A.7.2 `config_use_advection`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or .false

Table A.40: `config_use_advection`: If true perform advection of the sea ice.

A.7.3 `config_use_forcing`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or .false

Table A.41: `config_use_forcing`: If true calculate input forcing fields.

A.7.4 `config_use_column_package`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or .false

Table A.42: `config_use_column_package`: If true perform calculations from the column physics package.

A.8 forcing

A.8.1 `config_atmospheric_forcing_type`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	CORE
Possible Values:	'CORE'

Table A.43: `config_atmospheric_forcing_type`: Atmospheric forcing type.

A.8.2 `config_forcing_start_time`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	2000-01-01_00:00:00
Possible Values:	'YYYY-MM-DD_HH:MM:SS'

Table A.44: `config_forcing_start_time`: Forcing time to use at the simulation start time

A.8.3 `config_forcing_cycle_start`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	2000-01-01_00:00:00
Possible Values:	'YYYY-MM-DD_HH:MM:SS'

Table A.45: `config_forcing_cycle_start`: Start time for the forcing cycle.

A.8.4 [config_forcing_cycle_duration](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	2-00-00_00:00:00
Possible Values:	'YYYY-MM-DD_HH:MM:SS'

Table A.46: config_forcing_cycle_duration: Duration of the forcing cycle.

A.8.5 [config_forcing_precipitation_units](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	mm_per_sec
Possible Values:	'mm_per_month', 'mm_per_day', or 'mm_per_sec'

Table A.47: config_forcing_precipitation_units: Forcing input precipitation units.

A.8.6 [config_forcing_sst_type](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	ncar
Possible Values:	'ncar'

Table A.48: config_forcing_sst_type: Sea surface temperature ocean forcing type.

A.8.7 [config_update_ocean_fluxes](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.49: config_update_ocean_fluxes: **MISSING**

A.8.8 [config_include_pond_freshwater_feedback](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.50: `config_include_pond_freshwater_feedback`: Reduce the ocean fresh water flux by the pond fresh water flux for coupling.

A.9 unit_test

A.9.1 config_perform_unit_test

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.51: `config_perform_unit_test`: If true perform a unit test.

A.9.2 config_unit_test_type

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	MISSING
Possible Values:	'strain rate operator', 'stress divergence operator', or 'constitutive relationship'

Table A.52: `config_unit_test_type`: Unit test type.

A.9.3 config_unit_test_subtype

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	MISSING
Possible Values:	('strain rate operator'): 'all', 'zero', 'zonal', 'meridonal', 'solid_body', 'sinusoidal1', or 'sinusoidal2', (stress divergence operator): 'all', 'zero', 'const11', 'const22', 'const12', 'test1', 'test2', 'test3', or 'test4'

Table A.53: `config_unit_test_subtype`: Unit test subtype.

A.9.4 `config_use_test_ice_shelf`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.54: `config_use_test_ice_shelf`: If true test add a test ice shelf to the ice shelf mask.

A.9.5 `config_testing_system_test`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.55: `config_testing_system_test`: If true initialize variables that will fail the testing system tests.

A.10 `velocity_solver`

A.10.1 `config_dynamics_subcycle_number`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1
Possible Values:	Any positive integer.

Table A.56: `config_dynamics_subcycle_number`: The number of dynamics subcycles to perform per thermodynamic time step (`config_dt`)

A.10.2 `config_rotate_cartesian_grid`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or. false.

Table A.57: `config_rotate_cartesian_grid`: Rotate the velocity directions from geographic so their pole lies on the equator.

A.10.3 `config_include_metric_terms`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or. false.

Table A.58: `config_include_metric_terms`: Include metric terms due to Earth curvature in velocity solver horizontal operators.

A.10.4 `config_elastic_subcycle_number`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	120
Possible Values:	Any positive integer.

Table A.59: `config_elastic_subcycle_number`: The number of elastic EVP subcycles to perform per dynamics time step.

A.10.5 `config_stress_divergence_scheme`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	variational
Possible Values:	'weak' or 'variational'

Table A.60: `config_stress_divergence_scheme`: Choice of stress divergence scheme to use in the velocity solver.

A.10.6 `config_variational_basis`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless

Default Value:	wachspress
Possible Values:	'wachspress' or 'pwl'

Table A.61: `config_variational_basis`: Type of basis functions to use with the variational stress divergence scheme.

A.10.7 `config_wachspress_integration_type`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dunavant
Possible Values:	'trapezoidal', 'dunavant' or 'fekete'

Table A.62: `config_wachspress_integration_type`: Type of integration to perform with the Wachspress variational stress divergence scheme.

A.10.8 `config_wachspress_integration_order`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	8
Possible Values:	'trapezoidal': any positive integer, 'dunavant':1-10,12, 'fekete':1-6,8,9

Table A.63: `config_wachspress_integration_order`: Order of integration for Wachspress basis integrations.

A.10.9 `config_revised_evp`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or. false.

Table A.64: `config_revised_evp`: If true use the revised EVP rheology (Bouillon et al., Ocean Modelling)

A.10.10 `config_use_air_stress`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or. false.

Table A.65: `config_use_air_stress`: If true include the air stress term in the velocity solver calculations.

A.10.11 `config_use_ocean_stress`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or. false.

Table A.66: `config_use_ocean_stress`: If true include the ocean stress term in the velocity solver calculations.

A.10.12 `config_use_surface_tilt`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or. false.

Table A.67: `config_use_surface_tilt`: If true include the sea surface tilt stress term in the velocity solver calculations.

A.10.13 `config_geostrophic_surface_tilt`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or. false.

Table A.68: `config_geostrophic_surface_tilt`: If true calculate the sea surface tilt stress assuming currents are geostrophic.

A.11 advection

A.11.1 config_advection_type

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	incremental_remap
Possible Values:	'upwind' and 'incremental_remap'

Table A.69: config_advection_type: Type of advection scheme (upwind or incremental remapping).

A.11.2 config_monotonic

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true and false

Table A.70: config_monotonic: If true then fluxes are limited to produce a monotonic advection scheme.

A.11.3 config_conservation_check

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.71: config_conservation_check: If true test the advection results for tracer conservation (incremental remap only).

A.11.4 config_monotonicity_check

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.72: config_monotonicity_check: If true test the advection results for monotonicity (incremental remap only).

A.11.5 [config_recover_tracer_means_check](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.73: config_recover_tracer_means_check: If true compare mass*tracer products for incremental remapping with analytical values.

A.12 [column_package](#)

A.12.1 [config_use_column_shortwave](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.74: config_use_column_shortwave: Run the shortwave radiation column physics calculation.

A.12.2 [config_use_column_vertical_thermodynamics](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.75: config_use_column_vertical_thermodynamics: Run the vertical thermodynamics column physics calculation.

A.12.3 [config_use_column_biogeochemistry](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.76: config_use_column_biogeochemistry: Use biological and chemical tracers in the ice

A.12.4 `config_use_column_itd_thermodynamics`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.77: `config_use_column_itd_thermodynamics`: Run the ice thickness distribution thermodynamics column physics calculation.

A.12.5 `config_use_column_ridging`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.78: `config_use_column_ridging`: Run the ridging column physics calculation.

A.13 `column tracers`

A.13.1 `config_use_ice_age`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_iage</code>

Table A.79: `config_use_ice_age`: If true use the ice age tracer.

A.13.2 `config_use_first_year_ice`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_FY</code>

Table A.80: config_use_first_year_ice: If true use the first year ice tracer.

A.13.3 [config_use_level_ice](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	tr_lvl

Table A.81: config_use_level_ice: If true use the level ice tracers.

A.13.4 [config_use_cesm_meltponds](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	tr_pond_cesm

Table A.82: config_use_cesm_meltponds: If true use the cesm meltponds tracers.

A.13.5 [config_use_level_meltponds](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	tr_pond_lvl

Table A.83: config_use_level_meltponds: If true use the level ice meltponds tracers.

A.13.6 [config_use_topo_meltponds](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false

Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_pond_topo</code>

Table A.84: `config_use_topo_meltponds`: If true use the topo meltpond tracers.

A.13.7 `config_use_aerosols`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_aero</code>

Table A.85: `config_use_aerosols`: Carry aerosols in the ice (NCAR scheme)

A.14 `biogeochemistry`

A.14.1 `config_use_brine`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_brine</code>

Table A.86: `config_use_brine`: Use the brine height tracer

A.14.2 `config_use_vertical_zsalinity`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_bgc_S</code>

Table A.87: `config_use_vertical_zsalinity`: Use z-salinity (with Bitz and Lipscomb 1999 thermodynamics)

A.14.3 `config_use_vertical_biochemistry`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	TRBGCZ

Table A.88: `config_use_vertical_biochemistry`: Turn on the reaction terms for vertical biological tracers

A.14.4 `config_use_shortwave_bioabsorption`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	dEdd_algae

Table A.89: `config_use_shortwave_bioabsorption`: Permit radiative transfer calculations that include dynamic chlorophyll and aerosols if active

A.14.5 `config_use_vertical_tracers`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	z_tracers

Table A.90: `config_use_vertical_tracers`: Allow vertically resolved biological and chemical tracers

A.14.6 `config_use_skeletal_biochemistry`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	TRBGCS

Table A.91: `config_use_skeletal_biochemistry`: Use the bottom 1-layer biogeochemistry

A.14.7 `config_use_nitrate`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_bgc_Nit</code>

Table A.92: `config_use_nitrate`: Use the nitrate tracer

A.14.8 `config_use_carbon`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_bgc_C</code>

Table A.93: `config_use_carbon`: Use dissolved organic and inorganic carbon tracers

A.14.9 `config_use_chlorophyll`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_bgc_chl</code>

Table A.94: `config_use_chlorophyll`: Use the chlorophyll tracer (currently not implemented!)

A.14.10 `config_use_ammonium`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_bgc_Am</code>

Table A.95: `config_use_ammonium`: Use the ammonium tracer

A.14.11 `config_use_silicate`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_bgc_Sil</code>

Table A.96: `config_use_silicate`: Use the silicate tracer

A.14.12 `config_use_DMS`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_bgc_DMS</code>

Table A.97: `config_use_DMS`: Use DMS/DMSPd/DMSPp species

A.14.13 `config_use_nonreactive`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_bgc_PON</code>

Table A.98: `config_use_nonreactive`: Use a non-reactive nitrate tracer

A.14.14 `config_use_humics`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_bgc_hum</code>

Table A.99: `config_use_humics`: Use the humic matter tracer

A.14.15 `config_use_DON`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_bgc_DON</code>

Table A.100: `config_use_DON`: Use dissolved organic nitrogen (proteins and amino acids)

A.14.16 `config_use_iron`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_bgc_Fe</code>

Table A.101: `config_use_iron`: Use particulate and dissolved iron tracers

A.14.17 `config_use_modal_aerosols`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>modal_aero</code>

Table A.102: `config_use_modal_aerosols`: Aerosols are consistent with the CAM modal aerosol scheme

A.14.18 `config_use_zaerosols`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>tr_zaero</code>

Table A.103: config_use_zaerosols: Aerosols in the ice use the z-aerosol scheme

A.14.19 [config_skeletal_bgc_flux_type](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	Jin2006
Possible Values:	Jin2006 or default
Icepack name:	<code>bgc_flux_type</code>

Table A.104: config_skeletal_bgc_flux_type: Determines the ocean-ice fluxes of biogeochemistry for the bottom1-layer model: in Jin2006, the piston velocity is a function of ice growth/melt rate, in default, the piston velocity is constant

A.14.20 [config_scale_initial_vertical_bgc](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>scale_bgc</code>

Table A.105: config_scale_initial_vertical_bgc: initialize the vertical ice biogeochemistry profile to scale with the salinity restart/initial profile

A.14.21 [config_biogrid_bottom_molecular_sublayer](#)

Type:	real
Units:	m
Default Value:	0.006
Possible Values:	positive real number less than 1
Icepack name:	<code>grid_o</code>

Table A.106: config_biogrid_bottom_molecular_sublayer: Sets the value of the ice/ocean molecular sublayer for the vertical biogeochemistry model

A.14.22 [config_biogrid_top_molecular_sublayer](#)

Type:	real
Units:	m
Default Value:	0.006
Possible Values:	positive real number less than 1
Icepack name:	grid_o_t

Table A.107: config.biogrid_top_molecular_sublayer: Sets the value of the ice surface molecular sublayer for the vertical biogeochemistry model

A.14.23 [config_bio_gravity_drainage_length_scale](#)

Type:	real
Units:	m
Default Value:	0.024
Possible Values:	Sets the gravity drainage length scale in the biological transport model
Icepack name:	l_sk

Table A.108: config_bio_gravity_drainage_length_scale: positive real number less than 1

A.14.24 [config_zsalinity_molecular_sublayer](#)

Type:	real
Units:	m
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	zero or positive real number less than 1
Icepack name:	grid_oS

Table A.109: config_zsalinity_molecular_sublayer: Sets the ice/ocean molecular sublayer for the z-salinity model

A.14.25 [config_zsalinity_gravity_drainage_scale](#)

Type:	real
Units:	m
Default Value:	0.028
Possible Values:	positive real number less than 1
Icepack name:	l_skS

Table A.110: config_zsalinity_gravity_drainage_scale: Sets the gravity drainage length scale in the z-salinity model

A.14.26 `config_snow_porosity_at_ice_surface`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	-0.3
Possible Values:	real between 0 and 1 or negative. If negative, compute porosity from snow density
Icepack name:	<code>phi_snow</code>

Table A.111: `config_snow_porosity_at_ice_surface`: Specifies the snow porosity (volume of air/total volume) at the ice surface

A.14.27 `config_new_ice_fraction_biotracer`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.80
Possible Values:	positive real number less than or equal to 1
Icepack name:	<code>initbio_frac</code>

Table A.112: `config_new_ice_fraction_biotracer`: Fraction of biological tracer retained as new sea ice is formed from ocean water

A.14.28 `config_fraction_biotracer_in_frazil`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.80
Possible Values:	positive real number
Icepack name:	<code>frazil_scav</code>

Table A.113: `config_fraction_biotracer_in_frazil`: Factor multiplying the ocean concentration of a biological tracer in new frazil ice

A.14.29 `config_ratio_Si_to_N_diatoms`

Type:	real
Units:	mol silicate/mol nitrogen

Default Value:	1.80
Possible Values:	positive real of order 1.8
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_Si2N_diatoms</code>

Table A.114: `config_ratio_Si_to_N_diatoms`: Sets the ratio of silicate to nitrogen in diatoms

A.14.30 `config_ratio_Si_to_N_small_plankton`

Type:	real
Units:	mol silicate/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	0.00
Possible Values:	0
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_Si2N_sp</code>

Table A.115: `config_ratio_Si_to_N_small_plankton`: Sets the ratio of silicate to nitrogen in small plankton

A.14.31 `config_ratio_Si_to_N_phaeocystis`

Type:	real
Units:	mol silicate/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	0.00
Possible Values:	0
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_Si2N_phaeo</code>

Table A.116: `config_ratio_Si_to_N_phaeocystis`: Sets the ratio of silicate to nitrogen in phaeocystis

A.14.32 `config_ratio_S_to_N_diatoms`

Type:	real
Units:	mol Sulfur/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	0.03
Possible Values:	order of 0.03
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_S2N_diatoms</code>

Table A.117: `config_ratio_S_to_N_diatoms`: Sets the ratio of sulfur to nitrogen in diatoms

A.14.33 [config_ratio_S_to_N_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mol sulfur/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	0.03
Possible Values:	order of 0.03
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_S2N_sp</code>

Table A.118: `config_ratio_S_to_N_small_plankton`: Sets the ratio of sulfur to nitrogen in small plankton

A.14.34 [config_ratio_S_to_N_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mol sulfur/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	0.03
Possible Values:	order of 0.03
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_S2N_phaeo</code>

Table A.119: `config_ratio_S_to_N_phaeocystis`: Sets the ratio of sulfur to nitrogen in phaeocystis

A.14.35 [config_ratio_Fe_to_C_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol iron/mol Carbon
Default Value:	0.0033
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_Fe2C_diatoms</code>

Table A.120: `config_ratio_Fe_to_C_diatoms`: Sets the ratio of iron to carbon in diatoms

A.14.36 [config_ratio_Fe_to_C_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol iron/mol carbon
Default Value:	0.0033
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_Fe2C_sp</code>

Table A.121: `config_ratio_Fe_to_C_small_plankton`: Sets the ratio of iron to carbon in small plankton

A.14.37 [config_ratio_Fe_to_C_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol iron/mol carbon
Default Value:	0.1
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_Fe2C_phaeo</code>

Table A.122: `config_ratio_Fe_to_C_phaeocystis`: Sets the ratio of iron to carbon in phaeocystis

A.14.38 [config_ratio_Fe_to_N_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol iron/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	0.023
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_Fe2N_diatoms</code>

Table A.123: `config_ratio_Fe_to_N_diatoms`: Sets the ratio of iron to nitrogen in diatoms

A.14.39 [config_ratio_Fe_to_N_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol iron/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	0.023
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_Fe2N_sp</code>

Table A.124: `config_ratio_Fe_to_N_small_plankton`: Sets the ratio of iron to nitrogen in small plankton

A.14.40 [config_ratio_Fe_to_N_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol iron/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	0.7
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_Fe2N_phaeo</code>

Table A.125: `config_ratio_Fe_to_N_phaeocystis`: Sets the ratio of iron to nitrogen in phaeocystis

A.14.41 `config_ratio_Fe_to_DON`

Type:	real
Units:	mmol iron/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	0.023
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_Fe2DON</code>

Table A.126: `config_ratio_Fe_to_DON`: Sets the ratio of iron to dissolved organic nitrogen

A.14.42 `config_ratio_Fe_to_DOC_saccharids`

Type:	real
Units:	mmol iron/mol carbon
Default Value:	0.1
Possible Values:	positive real number
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_Fe2DOC_s</code>

Table A.127: `config_ratio_Fe_to_DOC_saccharids`: Sets the ratio of iron to poly/saccharid carbon

A.14.43 `config_ratio_Fe_to_DOC_lipids`

Type:	real
Units:	mmol iron/mol carbon
Default Value:	0.033
Possible Values:	positive real number
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_Fe2DOC_l</code>

Table A.128: `config_ratio_Fe_to_DOC_lipids`: Sets the ratio of iron to lipid carbon

A.14.44 `config_respiration_fraction_of_growth`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.05

Possible Values:	positive real less than one
Icepack name:	<code>fr_resp</code>

Table A.129: `config_respiration_fraction_of_growth`: Fraction of algal growth that is lost due to respiration

A.14.45 `config_rapid_mobile_to_stationary_time`

Type:	real
Units:	seconds
Default Value:	5200.0
Possible Values:	zero or positive real number
Icepack name:	<code>tau_min</code>

Table A.130: `config_rapid_mobile_to_stationary_time`: Rapid adsorption timescale

A.14.46 `config_long_mobile_to_stationary_time`

Type:	real
Units:	seconds
Default Value:	173000.0
Possible Values:	zero or positive real number
Icepack name:	<code>tau_max</code>

Table A.131: `config_long_mobile_to_stationary_time`: Slow adsorption timescale

A.14.47 `config_algal_maximum_velocity`

Type:	real
Units:	m/s
Default Value:	0.0000000111
Possible Values:	zero or positive real number
Icepack name:	<code>algal_vel</code>

Table A.132: `config_algal_maximum_velocity`: Maximum speed at which diatoms can move

A.14.48 `config_ratio_Fe_to_dust`

Type:	real
Units:	mg iron/g dust
Default Value:	0.035
Possible Values:	zero or positive real number
Icepack name:	R_dFe2dust

Table A.133: config_ratio_Fe_to_dust: Mass ratio of iron in dust

A.14.49 [config_solubility_of_Fe_in_dust](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.005
Possible Values:	real number between and including zero and one
Icepack name:	dustFe_sol

Table A.134: config_solubility_of_Fe_in_dust: Fraction of iron that is soluble

A.14.50 [config_chla_absorptivity_of_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/m/(mg chla/m ³)
Default Value:	0.03
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	chlabs_diatoms

Table A.135: config_chla_absorptivity_of_diatoms: Absorptivity of chlorophyll in diatoms

A.14.51 [config_chla_absorptivity_of_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/m/(mg chla/m ³)
Default Value:	0.01
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	chlabs_sp

Table A.136: config_chla_absorptivity_of_small_plankton: Absorptivity of chlorophyll in small plankton

A.14.52 `config_chla_absorptivity_of_phaeocystis`

Type:	real
Units:	1/m/(mg chla/m ³)
Default Value:	0.05
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	chlabs_phaeo

Table A.137: `config_chla_absorptivity_of_phaeocystis`: Absorptivity of chlorophyll in phaeocystis

A.14.53 `config_light_attenuation_diatoms`

Type:	real
Units:	1/(W/m ²)
Default Value:	0.8
Possible Values:	positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	alpha2max_low_diatoms

Table A.138: `config_light_attenuation_diatoms`: Controls the ability of diatoms to utilize light

A.14.54 `config_light_attenuation_small_plankton`

Type:	real
Units:	1/(W/m ²)
Default Value:	0.67
Possible Values:	positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	alpha2max_low_sp

Table A.139: `config_light_attenuation_small_plankton`: Controls the ability of small plankton to utilize light

A.14.55 `config_light_attenuation_phaeocystis`

Type:	real
Units:	1/(W/m ²)
Default Value:	0.67
Possible Values:	positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	alpha2max_low_phaeo

Table A.140: `config_light_attenuation_phaeocystis`: Controls the ability of phaeocystis to utilize light

A.14.56 `config_light_inhibition_diatoms`

Type:	real
Units:	1/(W/m ²)
Default Value:	0.018
Possible Values:	positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	<code>beta2max_diatoms</code>

Table A.141: `config_light_inhibition_diatoms`: Controls the strength of light inhibition to growth for diatoms

A.14.57 `config_light_inhibition_small_plankton`

Type:	real
Units:	1/(W/m ²)
Default Value:	0.0025
Possible Values:	positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	<code>beta2max_sp</code>

Table A.142: `config_light_inhibition_small_plankton`: Controls the strength of light inhibition to growth for small plankton

A.14.58 `config_light_inhibition_phaeocystis`

Type:	real
Units:	1/(W/m ²)
Default Value:	0.01
Possible Values:	positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	<code>beta2max_phaeo</code>

Table A.143: `config_light_inhibition_phaeocystis`: Controls the strength of light inhibition to growth for phaeocystis

A.14.59 `config_maximum_growth_rate_diatoms`

Type:	real
Units:	1/day
Default Value:	1.44

Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	mu_max_diatoms

Table A.144: config_maximum_growth_rate_diatoms: Maximum growth rate for diatoms

A.14.60 [config_maximum_growth_rate_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/day
Default Value:	0.851
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	mu_max_sp

Table A.145: config_maximum_growth_rate_small_plankton: Maximum growth rate for small plankton

A.14.61 [config_maximum_growth_rate_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/day
Default Value:	0.851
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	mu_max_phaeo

Table A.146: config_maximum_growth_rate_phaeocystis: Maximum growth rate for phaeocystis

A.14.62 [config_temperature_growth_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/C
Default Value:	0.06
Possible Values:	positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	grow_Tdep_diatoms

Table A.147: config_temperature_growth_diatoms: Controls the temperature dependence of growth for diatoms

A.14.63 [config_temperature_growth_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/C
Default Value:	0.06
Possible Values:	positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	grow_Tdep_sp

Table A.148: config_temperature_growth_small_plankton: Controls the temperature dependence of growth for small plankton

A.14.64 [config_temperature_growth_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/C
Default Value:	0.06
Possible Values:	positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	grow_Tdep_phaeo

Table A.149: config_temperature_growth_phaeocystis: Controls the temperature dependence of growth for phaeocystis

A.14.65 [config_grazed_fraction_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	fr_graze_diatoms

Table A.150: config_grazed_fraction_diatoms: Fraction of diatom biomass grazed

A.14.66 [config_grazed_fraction_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.1
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	fr_graze_sp

Table A.151: config_grazed_fraction_small_plankton: Fraction of small plankton biomass grazed

A.14.67 `config_grazed_fraction_phaeocystis`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.1
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	<code>fr_graze_phaeo</code>

Table A.152: `config_grazed_fraction_phaeocystis`: Fraction of phaeocystis biomass grazed

A.14.68 `config_mortality_diatoms`

Type:	real
Units:	1/day
Default Value:	0.007
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	<code>mort_pre_diatoms</code>

Table A.153: `config_mortality_diatoms`: Mortality rate of diatoms

A.14.69 `config_mortality_small_plankton`

Type:	real
Units:	1/day
Default Value:	0.007
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	<code>mort_pre_sp</code>

Table A.154: `config_mortality_small_plankton`: Mortality rate of small plankton

A.14.70 `config_mortality_phaeocystis`

Type:	real
Units:	1/day
Default Value:	0.007
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	<code>mort_pre_phaeo</code>

Table A.155: `config_mortality_phaeocystis`: Mortality rate of phaeocystis

A.14.71 [config_temperature_mortality_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/C
Default Value:	0.03
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	mort_Tdep_diatoms

Table A.156: config_temperature_mortality_diatoms: Temperature dependence of diatom mortality rate

A.14.72 [config_temperature_mortality_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/C
Default Value:	0.03
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	mort_Tdep_sp

Table A.157: config_temperature_mortality_small_plankton: Temperature dependence of small plankton mortality rate

A.14.73 [config_temperature_mortality_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/C
Default Value:	0.03
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	mort_Tdep_phaeo

Table A.158: config_temperature_mortality_phaeocystis: Temperature dependence of phaeocystis mortality rate

A.14.74 [config_exudation_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/day
Default Value:	0.0

Possible Values:	zero or positive real
Icepack name:	<code>k_exude_diatoms</code>

Table A.159: `config_exudation_diatoms`: Rate diatoms exude DOC

A.14.75 [config_exudation_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/day
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	zero or positive real
Icepack name:	<code>k_exude_sp</code>

Table A.160: `config_exudation_small_plankton`: Rate small plankton exude DOC

A.14.76 [config_exudation_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/day
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	zero or positive real
Icepack name:	<code>k_exude_phaeo</code>

Table A.161: `config_exudation_phaeocystis`: Rate phaeocystis exude DOC

A.14.77 [config_nitrate_saturation_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol nitrogen/m ³
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	<code>K_Nit_diatoms</code>

Table A.162: `config_nitrate_saturation_diatoms`: Nitrate half saturation for diatom growth

A.14.78 [config_nitrate_saturation_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
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Units:	mmol nitrogen/m ³
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	K_Nit_sp

Table A.163: config_nitrate_saturation_small_plankton: Nitrate half saturation for small plankton growth

A.14.79 [config_nitrate_saturation_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol nitrogen/m ³
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	K_Nit_phaeo

Table A.164: config_nitrate_saturation_phaeocystis: Nitrate half saturation for phaeocystis growth

A.14.80 [config_ammonium_saturation_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol nitrogen/m ³
Default Value:	0.3
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	K_Am_diatoms

Table A.165: config_ammonium_saturation_diatoms: Ammonium half saturation for diatom growth

A.14.81 [config_ammonium_saturation_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol nitrogen/m ³
Default Value:	0.3
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	K_Am_sp

Table A.166: config_ammonium_saturation_small_plankton: Ammonium half saturation for small plankton growth

A.14.82 [config_ammonium_saturation_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol nitrogen/m ³
Default Value:	0.3
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	K_Am_phaeo

Table A.167: config_ammonium_saturation_phaeocystis: Ammonium half saturation for phaeocystis growth

A.14.83 [config_silicate_saturation_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol Si/m ³
Default Value:	4.0
Possible Values:	zero or positive real
Icepack name:	K_Sil_diatoms

Table A.168: config_silicate_saturation_diatoms: Silicate half saturation for diatom growth

A.14.84 [config_silicate_saturation_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol Si/m ³
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	zero or positive real
Icepack name:	K_Sil_sp

Table A.169: config_silicate_saturation_small_plankton: Silicate half saturation for small plankton growth

A.14.85 [config_silicate_saturation_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol Si/m ³
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	zero or positive real
Icepack name:	K_Sil_phaeo

Table A.170: config_silicate_saturation_phaeocystis: Silicate half saturation for phaeocystis growth

A.14.86 [config_iron_saturation_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	umol iron/m ³
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	K_Fe_diatoms

Table A.171: config_iron_saturation_diatoms: Iron half saturation for diatom growth

A.14.87 [config_iron_saturation_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	umol iron/m ³
Default Value:	0.2
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	K_Fe_sp

Table A.172: config_iron_saturation_small_plankton: Iron half saturation for small plankton growth

A.14.88 [config_iron_saturation_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	umol iron/m ³
Default Value:	0.1
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	K_Fe_phaeo

Table A.173: config_iron_saturation_phaeocystis: Iron half saturation for phaeocystis growth

A.14.89 [config_fraction_spilled_to_DON](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.6
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than or equal to 1
Icepack name:	f_don_protein

Table A.174: config_fraction_spilled_to_DON: Fraction of spilled grazing to proteins

A.14.90 [config_degredation_of_DON](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/day
Default Value:	0.03
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	<code>kn_bac_protein</code>

Table A.175: `config_degredation_of_DON`: Bacterial degradation of DON

A.14.91 [config_fraction_DON_ammonium](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.25
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than or equal to 1
Icepack name:	<code>f_don_Am_protein</code>

Table A.176: `config_fraction_DON_ammonium`: Fraction of remineralized DON converted to ammonium

A.14.92 [config_fraction_loss_to_saccharids](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.4
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	<code>f_doc_s</code>

Table A.177: `config_fraction_loss_to_saccharids`: Fraction of mortality to poly/saccharids

A.14.93 [config_fraction_loss_to_lipids](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.4
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	<code>f_doc_l</code>

Table A.178: config_fraction_loss_to_lipids: Fraction of mortality to lipids

A.14.94 [config_fraction_exudation_to_saccharids](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than or equal to 1
Icepack name:	f_exude_s

Table A.179: config_fraction_exudation_to_saccharids: Fracton of exudation to poly/saccharids

A.14.95 [config_fraction_exudation_to_lipids](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than or equal to 1
Icepack name:	f_exude_l

Table A.180: config_fraction_exudation_to_lipids: Fraction of exudation to lipids

A.14.96 [config_remineralization_saccharids](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/day
Default Value:	0.03
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	k_bac_s

Table A.181: config_remineralization_saccharids: Bacterial degredaton rate of poly/saccarids

A.14.97 [config_remineralization_lipids](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/day
Default Value:	0.03

Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	k_bac_1

Table A.182: config_remineralization_lipids: Bacterial degradation rate of lipids

A.14.98 [config_maximum_brine_temperature](#)

Type:	real
Units:	C
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	T_max

Table A.183: config_maximum_brine_temperature: Maximum brine temperature

A.14.99 [config_salinity_dependence_of_growth](#)

Type:	real
Units:	ppt
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	fsal

Table A.184: config_salinity_dependence_of_growth: Salinity limitation factor

A.14.100 [config_minimum_optical_depth](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.1
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	op_dep_min

Table A.185: config_minimum_optical_depth: Minimum optical depth above which light attenuates

A.14.101 [config_sloped_grazing_fraction](#)

Type:	real
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Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.5
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	<code>fr_graze_s</code>

Table A.186: `config_slopped_grazing_fraction`: Fraction of grazing spilled or slopped

A.14.102 [config_excreted_fraction](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.5
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	<code>fr_graze_e</code>

Table A.187: `config_excreted_fraction`: Fraction of assimilation excreted

A.14.103 [config_fraction_mortality_to_ammonium](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.5
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	<code>fr_mort2min</code>

Table A.188: `config_fraction_mortality_to_ammonium`: Fraction of mortality to ammonium

A.14.104 [config_fraction_iron_remineralized](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.3
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than or equal to 1
Icepack name:	<code>fr_dFe</code>

Table A.189: `config_fraction_iron_remineralized`: Fraction of remineralized iron

A.14.105 [config_nitrification_rate](#)

Type:	real
Units:	1/day
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	zero or positive real
Icepack name:	<code>k_nitrif</code>

Table A.190: `config_nitrification_rate`: Nitrification rate

A.14.106 [config_desorption_loss_particulate_iron](#)

Type:	real
Units:	day
Default Value:	3065.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	<code>t_iron_conv</code>

Table A.191: `config_desorption_loss_particulate_iron`: Desorption rate of particulate iron to dissolved iron

A.14.107 [config_maximum_loss_fraction](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.9
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than 1
Icepack name:	<code>max_loss</code>

Table A.192: `config_maximum_loss_fraction`: Maximum uptake fraction in a single timestep

A.14.108 [config_maximum_ratio_iron_to_saccharids](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.2
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	<code>max_dfe_doc1</code>

Table A.193: `config_maximum_ratio_iron_to_saccharids`: Optimal ratio of dissolved iron to poly/saccharids in the brine

A.14.109 [config_respiration_loss_to_DMSPd](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.75
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than or equal to 1
Icepack name:	fr_resp_s

Table A.194: config_respiration_loss_to_DMSPd: Fraction of respiration loss as DMSPd

A.14.110 [config_DMSP_to_DMS_conversion_fraction](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.5
Possible Values:	zero or positive real less than or equal to 1
Icepack name:	y_sk_conv

Table A.195: config_DMSP_to_DMS_conversion_fraction: Fraction of conversion to DMS given high yield

A.14.111 [config_DMSP_to_DMS_conversion_time](#)

Type:	real
Units:	day
Default Value:	3.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	t_sk_conv

Table A.196: config_DMSP_to_DMS_conversion_time: Stefels conversion time

A.14.112 [config_DMS_oxidation_time](#)

Type:	real
Units:	day
Default Value:	10.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	t_sk_ox

Table A.197: config_DMS_oxidation_time: DMS oxidation time

A.14.113 [config_mobility_type_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	algaltype_diatoms

Table A.198: config_mobility_type_diatoms: Transport type of diatoms

A.14.114 [config_mobility_type_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.5
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	algaltype_sp

Table A.199: config_mobility_type_small_plankton: Transport type of small plankton

A.14.115 [config_mobility_type_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.5
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	algaltype_phaeo

Table A.200: config_mobility_type_phaeocystis: Transport type of phaeocystis

A.14.116 [config_mobility_type_nitrate](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	-1.0
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	nitratetype

Table A.201: config_mobility_type_nitrate: Transport type of nitrate

A.14.117 [config_mobility_type_ammonium](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	ammoniumtype

Table A.202: config_mobility_type_ammonium: Transport type of ammonium

A.14.118 [config_mobility_type_silicate](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	-1.0
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	silicatetype

Table A.203: config_mobility_type_silicate: Transport type of silicate

A.14.119 [config_mobility_type_DMSPp](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless

Default Value:	0.5
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	dmsptype

Table A.204: config_mobility_type_DMSPp: Transport type of particulate DMSP

A.14.120 [config_mobility_type_DMSPd](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	-1.0
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	dmspdtype

Table A.205: config_mobility_type_DMSPd: Transport type of dissolved DMSP

A.14.121 [config_mobility_type_humics](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	humtypes

Table A.206: config_mobility_type_humics: Transport type of humics

A.14.122 [config_mobility_type_saccharids](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.5
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange

Icepack name:	doctype_s
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Table A.207: config_mobility_type_saccharids: Transport type of poly/saccharids

A.14.123 [config_mobility_type_lipids](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.5
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	doctype_1

Table A.208: config_mobility_type_lipids: Transport type of lipids

A.14.124 [config_mobility_type_proteins](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.5
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	dontype_protein

Table A.209: config_mobility_type_proteins: Transport type of proteins

A.14.125 [config_mobility_type_dissolved_iron](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.5
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	fedtype_1

Table A.210: config_mobility_type_dissolved_iron: Transport type of dissolved iron

A.14.126 [config_mobility_type_particulate_iron](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.5
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	feptype_1

Table A.211: config_mobility_type_particulate_iron: Transport type of particulate iron

A.14.127 [config_mobility_type_black_carbon1](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	zaerotype_bc1

Table A.212: config_mobility_type_black_carbon1: Transport type of black carbon 1 pool

A.14.128 [config_mobility_type_black_carbon2](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	zaerotype_bc2

Table A.213: config_mobility_type_black_carbon2: Transport type of black carbon 1 pool

A.14.129 [config_mobility_type_dust1](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepak name:	zaerotype_dust1

Table A.214: config_mobility_type_dust1: Transport type of dust pool 1

A.14.130 [config_mobility_type_dust2](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepak name:	zaerotype_dust2

Table A.215: config_mobility_type_dust2: Transport type of dust pool 2

A.14.131 [config_mobility_type_dust3](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepak name:	zaerotype_dust3

Table A.216: config_mobility_type_dust3: Transport type of dust pool 3

A.14.132 [config_mobility_type_dust4](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1.0

Possible Values:	-1 = entirely in the mobile phase; 0 = retention dominated; 1 = release dominated; 0.5 = equal but rapid exchange; 2 = equal but slow exchange
Icepack name:	zaerotype_dust4

Table A.217: config_mobility_type_dust4: Transport type of dust pool 4

A.14.133 [config_ratio_C_to_N_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mol carbon/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	7.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	ratio_C2N_diatoms

Table A.218: config_ratio_C_to_N_diatoms: Algal carbon to nitrogen mole ratio for diatoms

A.14.134 [config_ratio_C_to_N_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mol carbon/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	7.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	ratio_C2N_sp

Table A.219: config_ratio_C_to_N_small_plankton: Algal carbon to nitrogen mole ratio for small plankton

A.14.135 [config_ratio_C_to_N_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mol carbon/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	7.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	ratio_C2N_phaeo

Table A.220: config_ratio_C_to_N_phaeocystis: Algal carbon to nitrogen mole ratio for phaeocystis

A.14.136 [config_ratio_chla_to_N_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	g chla/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	2.1
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_chl2N_diatoms</code>

Table A.221: config_ratio_chla_to_N_diatoms: Algal chlorophyll to nitrogen ratio for diatoms

A.14.137 [config_ratio_chla_to_N_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	g chla/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	1.1
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_chl2N_sp</code>

Table A.222: config_ratio_chla_to_N_small_plankton: Algal chlorophyll to nitrogen ratio for small plankton

A.14.138 [config_ratio_chla_to_N_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	g chla/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	0.84
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	<code>ratio_chl2N_phaeo</code>

Table A.223: config_ratio_chla_to_N_phaeocystis: Algal chlorophyll to nitrogen ratio for phaeocystis

A.14.139 [config_scales_absorption_diatoms](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	2.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	<code>F_abs_chl_diatoms</code>

Table A.224: config_scales_absorption_diatoms: Scales absorbed radiation for diatoms

A.14.140 [config_scales_absorption_small_plankton](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	4.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	F_abs_chl_sp

Table A.225: config_scales_absorption_small_plankton: Scales absorbed radiation for small plankton

A.14.141 [config_scales_absorption_phaeocystis](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	5.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	F_abs_chl_phaeo

Table A.226: config_scales_absorption_phaeocystis: Scales absorbed radiation for phaeocystis

A.14.142 [config_ratio_C_to_N_proteins](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mol carbon/mol nitrogen
Default Value:	7.0
Possible Values:	positive real
Icepack name:	ratio_C2N_proteins

Table A.227: config_ratio_C_to_N_proteins: Ratio of carbon to nitrogen in proteins

A.15 [shortwave](#)

A.15.1 [config_shortwave_type](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dEdd
Possible Values:	'ccsm3' or 'dEdd'

Icepack name:	<code>shortwave</code>
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Table A.228: `config_shortwave_type`: Shortwave radiation method.

A.15.2 `config_albedo_type`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	<code>ccsm3</code>
Possible Values:	' <code>ccsm3</code> ' or ' <code>constant</code> '
Icepack name:	<code>albedo_type</code>

Table A.229: `config_albedo_type`: Albedo parameterization type.

A.15.3 `config_visible_ice_albedo`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.78
Possible Values:	Any real number between 0 and 1.
Icepack name:	<code>albicev</code>

Table A.230: `config_visible_ice_albedo`: Visible ice albedo for ice thickness greater than `config_variable_albedo_thickness_limit`.

A.15.4 `config_infrared_ice_albedo`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.36
Possible Values:	Any real number between 0 and 1.
Icepack name:	<code>albicev</code>

Table A.231: `config_infrared_ice_albedo`: Near-IR ice albedo for ice thickness greater than `config_variable_albedo_thickness_limit`.

A.15.5 `config_visible_snow_albedo`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.98
Possible Values:	Any real number between 0 and 1.
Icepack name:	albsnowv

Table A.232: config_visible_snow_albedo: Visible cold snow albedo.

A.15.6 [config_infrared_snow_albedo](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.70
Possible Values:	Any real number between 0 and 1.
Icepack name:	albsnowi

Table A.233: config_infrared_snow_albedo: Near-IR cold snow albedo.

A.15.7 [config_variable_albedo_thickness_limit](#)

Type:	real
Units:	m
Default Value:	0.3
Possible Values:	Any positive real number.
Icepack name:	ahmax

Table A.234: config_variable_albedo_thickness_limit: Ice thickness above which the ice albedo is constant.

A.15.8 [config_ice_shortwave_tuning_parameter](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	MISSING
Icepack name:	R_ice

Table A.235: config_ice_shortwave_tuning_parameter: Sea ice tuning parameter; +1 for 1sig increase in albedo.

A.15.9 [config_pond_shortwave_tuning_parameter](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	MISSING
Icepack name:	R_pnd

Table A.236: config_pond_shortwave_tuning_parameter: Poned ice tuning parameter; +1 for 1sig increase in albedo.

A.15.10 [config_snow_shortwave_tuning_parameter](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Default Value:	1.5
Possible Values:	MISSING
Icepack name:	R_snw

Table A.237: config_snow_shortwave_tuning_parameter: Snow tuning parameter; +1 for .01 change in broadband albedo.

A.15.11 [config_temp_change_snow_grain_radius_change](#)

Type:	real
Units:	C
Default Value:	1.5
Possible Values:	MISSING
Icepack name:	dT_mlt

Table A.238: config_temp_change_snow_grain_radius_change: Change in temperture for non-melt to melt snow grain radius change.

A.15.12 [config_max_melting_snow_grain_radius](#)

Type:	real
Units:	10e - 6 m
Default Value:	1500.0

Possible Values:	MISSING
Icepack name:	rsnw_mlt

Table A.239: config_max_melting_snow_grain_radius: Maximum melting snow grain radius.

A.15.13 [config_algae_absorption_coefficient](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Default Value:	0.6
Possible Values:	MISSING
Icepack name:	kalg

Table A.240: config_algae_absorption_coefficient: Algae absorption coefficient for 0.5 m thick layer.

A.16 [meltponds](#)

A.16.1 [config_snow_to_ice_transition_depth](#)

Type:	real
Units:	m
Default Value:	0.0
Possible Values:	MISSING
Icepack name:	hs0

Table A.241: config_snow_to_ice_transition_depth: Snow depth for transition to bare sea ice.

A.16.2 [config_pond_refreezing_type](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	hlid
Possible Values:	'cesm' or 'hlid'
Icepack name:	frzpond

Table A.242: config_pond_refreezing_type: Pond refreezing parameterization.

A.16.3 [config_pond_flushing_timescale](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Default Value:	1.0e-3
Possible Values:	MISSING
Icepack name:	dpscale

Table A.243: config_pond_flushing_timescale: Alter e-folding time scale for flushing.?????

A.16.4 [config_min_meltwater_retained_fraction](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.15
Possible Values:	Any real number between 0 and 1
Icepack name:	rfracmin

Table A.244: config_min_meltwater_retained_fraction: Minimum retained fraction of meltwater.

A.16.5 [config_max_meltwater_retained_fraction](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	Any real number between 0 and 1
Icepack name:	rfracmax

Table A.245: config_max_meltwater_retained_fraction: Maximum retained fraction of meltwater.

A.16.6 [config_pond_depth_to_fraction_ratio](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.8
Possible Values:	MISSING
Icepack name:	pndaspect

Table A.246: config_pond_depth_to_fraction_ratio: Ratio of pond depth to pond fraction.

A.16.7 [config_snow_on_pond_ice_tapering_parameter](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Default Value:	0.03
Possible Values:	MISSING
Icepack name:	hs1

Table A.247: config_snow_on_pond_ice_tapering_parameter: Tapering parameter for snow on pond ice.

A.16.8 [config_critical_pond_ice_thickness](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Default Value:	0.01
Possible Values:	MISSING
Icepack name:	hp1

Table A.248: config_critical_pond_ice_thickness: Critical parameter for pond ice thickness.

A.17 [thermodynamics](#)

A.17.1 [config_thermodynamics_type](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	mushy
Possible Values:	'zero layer', 'BL99', or 'mushy'
Icepack name:	ktherm

Table A.249: config_thermodynamics_type: Vertical thermodynamics type.

A.17.2 [config_heat_conductivity_type](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	bubbly
Possible Values:	'MU71' or 'bubbly'
Icepack name:	conduct

Table A.250: `config.heat_conductivity_type`: Thermal conductivity type for BL99 thermodynamics. Options are Maykut and Untersteiner 1971 form (with Wettlaufer 1991 constants), or Pringle et al JGR 2007 'bubbly brine'

A.17.3 `config_rapid_mode_channel_radius`

Type:	real
Units:	m
Default Value:	0.5e-3
Possible Values:	Any positive real number.
Icepack name:	<code>a_rapid_mode</code>

Table A.251: `config_rapid_mode_channel_radius`: Channel radius for rapid gravity drainage mode.

A.17.4 `config_rapid_model_critical_Ra`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	10.0
Possible Values:	Any positive real number.
Icepack name:	<code>Rac_rapid_mode</code>

Table A.252: `config_rapid_model_critical_Ra`: Critical Rayleigh number for rapid gravity drainage mode.

A.17.5 `config_rapid_mode_aspect_ratio`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1.0
Possible Values:	Any positive real number.
Icepack name:	<code>aspect_rapid_mode</code>

Table A.253: `config_rapid_mode_aspect_ratio`: Aspect ratio for rapid gravity drainage mode (larger=wider).

A.17.6 `config_slow_mode_drainage_strength`

Type:	real
Units:	$\text{m s}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
Default Value:	-5.0e-8
Possible Values:	Any negative real number.
Icepack name:	dSdt_slow_mode

Table A.254: config_slow_mode_drainage_strength: Slow gravity drainage mode drainage strength.

A.17.7 [config_slow_mode_critical_porosity](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.05
Possible Values:	Any real number between 0 and 1.
Icepack name:	phi_c_slow_mode

Table A.255: config_slow_mode_critical_porosity: Liquid fraction porosity cutoff for slow gravity drainage mode.

A.17.8 [config_congelation_ice_porosity](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.85
Possible Values:	Any real number between 0 and 1.
Icepack name:	phi_i_mushy

Table A.256: config_congelation_ice_porosity: Liquid fraction of congelation ice.

A.18 [itd](#)

A.18.1 [config_itd_conversion_type](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	linear remap
Possible Values:	'delta function' or 'linear remap'
Icepack name:	kitd

Table A.257: config_itd_conversion_type: Type of ice thickness distribution conversions.

A.18.2 `config_category_bounds_type`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	original
Possible Values:	'single category', 'original', 'new', 'WMO', or 'asymptotic'
Icepack name:	kcatbound

Table A.258: `config_category_bounds_type`: Type of ice thickness category bounds.

A.19 `ridging`

A.19.1 `config_ice_strength_formulation`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	Rothrock75
Possible Values:	'Hibler79' or 'Rothrock75'
Icepack name:	kstrength

Table A.259: `config_ice_strength_formulation`: Type of ice strength formulation.

A.19.2 `config_ridging_participation_function`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	exponential
Possible Values:	'Thorndike75' or 'exponential'
Icepack name:	krdg_partic

Table A.260: `config_ridging_participation_function`: Type of ridging participation function.

A.19.3 `config_ridging_redistribution_function`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	exponential
Possible Values:	'Hibler80' or 'exponential'

Icepack name:	<code>krdg_redist</code>
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Table A.261: `config_ridging_redistribution_function`: Type of ridging redistribution function.

A.19.4 `config_ridging_efolding_scale`

Type:	real
Units:	$m^0 5$
Default Value:	3.0
Possible Values:	MISSING
Icepack name:	<code>mu_rdg</code>

Table A.262: `config_ridging_efolding_scale`: E-folding scale of ridged ice (`krdg_redist = 1`)

A.19.5 `config_ratio_ridging_work_to_PE`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	17.0
Possible Values:	MISSING
Icepack name:	<code>Cf</code>

Table A.263: `config_ratio_ridging_work_to_PE`: Ratio of ridging work to PE change in ridging (`kstrength = 1`)

A.20 `atmosphere`

A.20.1 `config_atmos_boundary_method`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	<code>ccsm3</code>
Possible Values:	<code>'ccsm3'</code> or <code>'constant'</code>
Icepack name:	<code>atmbndy</code>

Table A.264: `config_atmos_boundary_method`: Atmosphere boundary method.

A.20.2 `config_calc_surface_stresses`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>calc_strair</code>

Table A.265: `config_calc_surface_stresses`: If true calculate wind stress components.

A.20.3 `config_calc_surface_temperature`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>calc_Tsfc</code>

Table A.266: `config_calc_surface_temperature`: If true calculate surface temperature. If false surface temperature is computed elsewhere and `atmos-ice` fluxes are provided.

A.20.4 `config_use_form_drag`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>formdrag</code>

Table A.267: `config_use_form_drag`: If true calculate form drag.

A.20.5 `config_use_high_frequency_coupling`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>highfreq</code>

Table A.268: `config_use_high_frequency_coupling`: If true use high frequency coupling.

A.20.6 `config_boundary_layer_iteration_number`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	5
Possible Values:	Any positive integer.
Icepack name:	<code>natmiter</code>

Table A.269: `config_boundary_layer_iteration_number`: Number of iterations for boundary layer calculations

A.21 `ocean`

A.21.1 `config_use_ocean_mixed_layer`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false
Icepack name:	<code>oceanmixed_ice</code>

Table A.270: `config_use_ocean_mixed_layer`: If true use an ocean mixed layer.

A.21.2 `config_min_friction_velocity`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Default Value:	0.0005
Possible Values:	MISSING
Icepack name:	<code>ustar_min</code>

Table A.271: `config_min_friction_velocity`: Minimum friction velocity for ice-ocean heat flux.

A.21.3 `config_ocean_heat_transfer_type`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	constant

Possible Values:	'constant' or 'Cdn.ocn'
Icepack name:	fbot_xfer_type

Table A.272: config_ocean_heat_transfer_type: Transfer coefficient type for ice-ocean heat flux.

A.21.4 config_sea_freezing_temperature_type

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	mushy
Possible Values:	'mushy', 'linear_salt', or DEFAULT
Icepack name:	tfrz_option

Table A.273: config_sea_freezing_temperature_type: Form of ocean freezing temperature.

A.21.5 config_ocean_surface_type

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	free
Possible Values:	'free' or 'non-free'

Table A.274: config_ocean_surface_type: Type of coupled ocean surface: (MPAS-O:'free'), (SOM:'non-free')

A.21.6 config_couple_biogeochemistry_fields

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.275: config_couple_biogeochemistry_fields: **MISSING**

A.22 diagnostics

A.22.1 config_check_state

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.276: `config_check_state`: If true perform a check at runtime of the model state.

A.23 AM_highFrequencyOutput

A.23.1 `config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_enable`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.277: `config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_enable`: If true, ocean analysis member `highFrequencyOutput` is called.

A.23.2 `config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	<code>output_interval</code>
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.278: `config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_compute_interval`: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.23.3 `config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_output_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	<code>highFrequencyOutput</code>
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.279: `config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_output_stream`: Name of the stream that the `highFrequencyOutput` analysis member should be tied to.

A.23.4 [config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_compute_on_startup](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.280: config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_compute_on_startup: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.23.5 [config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_write_on_startup](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.281: config_AM_highFrequencyOutput_write_on_startup: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.24 [AM_temperatures](#)

A.24.1 [config_AM_temperatures_enable](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.282: config_AM_temperatures_enable: If true, ocean analysis member temperatures is called.

A.24.2 [config_AM_temperatures_compute_interval](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dt
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.283: config_AM_temperatures_compute_interval: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.24.3 `config_AM_temperatures_output_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	output
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.284: `config_AM_temperatures_output_stream`: Name of the stream that the temperatures analysis member should be tied to.

A.24.4 `config_AM_temperatures_compute_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.285: `config_AM_temperatures_compute_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.24.5 `config_AM_temperatures_write_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.286: `config_AM_temperatures_write_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.25 `AM_regionalStatistics`

A.25.1 `config_AM_regionalStatistics_enable`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.287: `config_AM_regionalStatistics_enable`: If true, ocean analysis member `regionalStatistics` is called.

A.25.2 `config_AM_regionalStatistics_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	<code>output_interval</code>
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.288: `config_AM_regionalStatistics_compute_interval`: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.25.3 `config_AM_regionalStatistics_output_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	<code>regionalStatisticsOutput</code>
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.289: `config_AM_regionalStatistics_output_stream`: Name of the stream that the regional-Statistics analysis member should be tied to.

A.25.4 `config_AM_regionalStatistics_compute_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.290: `config_AM_regionalStatistics_compute_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.25.5 `config_AM_regionalStatistics_write_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless

Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.291: `config_AM_regionalStatistics_write_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.25.6 `config_AM_regionalStatistics_ice_extent_limit`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	0.15
Possible Values:	real value between 0 and 1

Table A.292: `config_AM_regionalStatistics_ice_extent_limit`: sea-ice fraction limit for ice extent.

A.26 `AM_ridgingDiagnostics`

A.26.1 `config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics_enable`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.293: `config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics_enable`: If true, ocean analysis member `ridgingDiagnostics` is called.

A.26.2 `config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dt
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.294: `config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics_compute_interval`: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.26.3 [config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics_output_stream](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	output
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.295: config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics_output_stream: Name of the stream that the ridging-Diagnostics analysis member should be tied to.

A.26.4 [config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics_compute_on_startup](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.296: config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics_compute_on_startup: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.26.5 [config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics_write_on_startup](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.297: config_AM_ridgingDiagnostics_write_on_startup: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.27 [AM_conservationCheck](#)

A.27.1 [config_AM_conservationCheck_enable](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.298: config_AM_conservationCheck_enable: If true, ocean analysis member conservationCheck is called.

A.27.2 [config_AM_conservationCheck_compute_interval](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dt
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.299: `config_AM_conservationCheck_compute_interval`: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.27.3 [config_AM_conservationCheck_output_stream](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	conservationCheckOutput
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.300: `config_AM_conservationCheck_output_stream`: Name of the stream that the `conservationCheck` analysis member should be tied to.

A.27.4 [config_AM_conservationCheck_compute_on_startup](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.301: `config_AM_conservationCheck_compute_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.27.5 [config_AM_conservationCheck_write_on_startup](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.302: `config_AM_conservationCheck_write_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.27.6 `config_AM_conservationCheck_write_to_logfile`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.303: `config_AM_conservationCheck_write_to_logfile`: Logical flag determining if the conservation check is written to the log file.

A.28 `AM_geographicalVectors`

A.28.1 `config_AM_geographicalVectors_enable`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.304: `config_AM_geographicalVectors_enable`: If true, ocean analysis member `geographicalVectors` is called.

A.28.2 `config_AM_geographicalVectors_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dt
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.305: `config_AM_geographicalVectors_compute_interval`: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.28.3 `config_AM_geographicalVectors_output_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	output
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.306: `config_AM_geographicalVectors_output_stream`: Name of the stream that the `geographicalVectors` analysis member should be tied to.

A.28.4 `config_AM_geographicalVectors_compute_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.307: `config_AM_geographicalVectors_compute_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.28.5 `config_AM_geographicalVectors_write_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.308: `config_AM_geographicalVectors_write_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.29 `AM_loadBalance`

A.29.1 `config_AM_loadBalance_enable`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.309: `config_AM_loadBalance_enable`: If true, ocean analysis member `loadBalance` is called.

A.29.2 `config_AM_loadBalance_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	output_interval
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.310: config_AM_loadBalance_compute_interval: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.29.3 [config_AM_loadBalance_output_stream](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	loadBalanceOutput
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.311: config_AM_loadBalance_output_stream: Name of the stream that the loadBalance analysis member should be tied to.

A.29.4 [config_AM_loadBalance_compute_on_startup](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.312: config_AM_loadBalance_compute_on_startup: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.29.5 [config_AM_loadBalance_write_on_startup](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.313: config_AM_loadBalance_write_on_startup: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.29.6 `config_AM_loadBalance_nProcs`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	32
Possible Values:	Any positive integer

Table A.314: `config_AM_loadBalance_nProcs`: Number of processors to output results for

A.30 `AM_maximumIcePresence`

A.30.1 `config_AM_maximumIcePresence_enable`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.315: `config_AM_maximumIcePresence_enable`: If true, ocean analysis member `maximumIcePresence` is called.

A.30.2 `config_AM_maximumIcePresence_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dt
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.316: `config_AM_maximumIcePresence_compute_interval`: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.30.3 `config_AM_maximumIcePresence_output_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	<code>maximumIcePresenceOutput</code>
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.317: `config_AM_maximumIcePresence_output_stream`: Name of the stream that the `maximumIcePresence` analysis member should be tied to.

A.30.4 [config_AM_maximumIcePresence_compute_on_startup](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.318: `config_AM_maximumIcePresence_compute_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.30.5 [config_AM_maximumIcePresence_write_on_startup](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.319: `config_AM_maximumIcePresence_write_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.30.6 [config_AM_maximumIcePresence_start_time](#)

Type:	character
Units:	time
Default Value:	0000-00-00.00:00:00
Possible Values:	Timestamp

Table A.320: `config_AM_maximumIcePresence_start_time`: Time to start accumulating ice domain

A.31 [AM_miscellaneous](#)

A.31.1 [config_AM_miscellaneous_enable](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.321: `config_AM_miscellaneous_enable`: If true, ocean analysis member `miscellaneous` is called.

A.31.2 `config_AM_miscellaneous_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dt
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.322: `config_AM_miscellaneous_compute_interval`: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.31.3 `config_AM_miscellaneous_output_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	none
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.323: `config_AM_miscellaneous_output_stream`: Name of the stream that the miscellaneous analysis member should be tied to.

A.31.4 `config_AM_miscellaneous_compute_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.324: `config_AM_miscellaneous_compute_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.31.5 `config_AM_miscellaneous_write_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless

Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.325: `config_AM_miscellaneous_write_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.32 AM_areaVariables

A.32.1 `config_AM_areaVariables_enable`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.326: `config_AM_areaVariables_enable`: If true, ocean analysis member `areaVariables` is called.

A.32.2 `config_AM_areaVariables_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dt
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.327: `config_AM_areaVariables_compute_interval`: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.32.3 `config_AM_areaVariables_output_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	none
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.328: `config_AM_areaVariables_output_stream`: Name of the stream that the `areaVariables` analysis member should be tied to.

A.32.4 `config_AM_areaVariables_compute_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.329: `config_AM_areaVariables_compute_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.32.5 `config_AM_areaVariables_write_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.330: `config_AM_areaVariables_write_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.33 `AM_pondDiagnostics`

A.33.1 `config_AM_pondDiagnostics_enable`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.331: `config_AM_pondDiagnostics_enable`: If true, ocean analysis member `pondDiagnostics` is called.

A.33.2 `config_AM_pondDiagnostics_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dt
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.332: `config_AM_pondDiagnostics_compute_interval`: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.33.3 `config_AM_pondDiagnostics_output_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	none
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.333: `config_AM_pondDiagnostics_output_stream`: Name of the stream that the `pondDiagnostics` analysis member should be tied to.

A.33.4 `config_AM_pondDiagnostics_compute_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.334: `config_AM_pondDiagnostics_compute_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.33.5 `config_AM_pondDiagnostics_write_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.335: `config_AM_pondDiagnostics_write_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.34 `AM_unitConversion`

A.34.1 `config_AM_unitConversion_enable`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.336: `config_AM_unitConversion_enable`: If true, ocean analysis member `unitConversion` is called.

A.34.2 `config_AM_unitConversion_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dt
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.337: `config_AM_unitConversion_compute_interval`: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.34.3 `config_AM_unitConversion_output_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	none
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.338: `config_AM_unitConversion_output_stream`: Name of the stream that the `unitConversion` analysis member should be tied to.

A.34.4 `config_AM_unitConversion_compute_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.339: `config_AM_unitConversion_compute_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.34.5 `config_AM_unitConversion_write_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless

Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.340: `config_AM_unitConversion_write_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.35 `AM_pointwiseStats`

A.35.1 `config_AM_pointwiseStats_enable`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.341: `config_AM_pointwiseStats_enable`: If true, ocean analysis member `pointwiseStats` is called.

A.35.2 `config_AM_pointwiseStats_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dt
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.342: `config_AM_pointwiseStats_compute_interval`: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.35.3 `config_AM_pointwiseStats_output_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	<code>pointwiseStatsOutput</code>
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.343: `config_AM_pointwiseStats_output_stream`: Name of the stream that the `pointwiseStats` analysis member should be tied to.

A.35.4 `config_AM_pointwiseStats_compute_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.344: `config_AM_pointwiseStats_compute_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.35.5 `config_AM_pointwiseStats_write_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.345: `config_AM_pointwiseStats_write_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.36 `AM_iceShelves`

A.36.1 `config_AM_iceShelves_enable`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.346: `config_AM_iceShelves_enable`: If true, ocean analysis member `iceShelves` is called.

A.36.2 `config_AM_iceShelves_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	<code>output_interval</code>
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.347: `config_AM_iceShelves_compute_interval`: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.36.3 `config_AM_iceShelves_output_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	iceShelvesOutput
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.348: `config_AM_iceShelves_output_stream`: Name of the stream that the `iceShelves` analysis member should be tied to.

A.36.4 `config_AM_iceShelves_compute_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.349: `config_AM_iceShelves_compute_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.36.5 `config_AM_iceShelves_write_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.350: `config_AM_iceShelves_write_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.37 `AM_icePresent`

A.37.1 `config_AM_icePresent_enable`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.351: `config_AM_icePresent_enable`: If true, ocean analysis member `icePresent` is called.

A.37.2 `config_AM_icePresent_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dt
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp, 'dt', or 'output_interval'

Table A.352: `config_AM_icePresent_compute_interval`: Timestamp determining how often analysis member computation should be performed.

A.37.3 `config_AM_icePresent_output_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	none
Possible Values:	Any existing stream name or 'none'

Table A.353: `config_AM_icePresent_output_stream`: Name of the stream that the `icePresent` analysis member should be tied to.

A.37.4 `config_AM_icePresent_compute_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.354: `config_AM_icePresent_compute_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up.

A.37.5 `config_AM_icePresent_write_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false

Possible Values:	true or false
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Table A.355: config_AM_icePresent_write_on_startup: Logical flag determining if an analysis member write occurs on start-up.

A.38 AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily

A.38.1 config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_enable

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.356: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_enable: If true, ocean analysis member time series stats is called.

A.38.2 config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_compute_on_startup

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.357: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_compute_on_startup: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up. You likely want this off for this (time series) analysis member because it will accumulate any state prior to time stepping (double counting the last time step).

A.38.3 config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_write_on_startup

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.358: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_write_on_startup: Logical flag determining if an analysis member output occurs on start-up.

A.38.4 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_compute_interval](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dt
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp or 'dt'. This must also be less than or equal to output_interval / 2 (i.e., requires at least two samples in a series).

Table A.359: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_compute_interval: Interval that determines frequency of computation for the time series stats analysis member.

A.38.5 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_output_stream](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	timeSeriesStatsDailyOutput
Possible Values:	An existing stream that will be modified (existing real fields removed and new time series stats versions added) with time series stats outputs. Cannot be 'none', like other analysis members.

Table A.360: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_output_stream: Name of stream the time series stats analysis member will operate on.

A.38.6 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_restart_stream](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	timeSeriesStatsDailyRestart
Possible Values:	A restart stream with state of the time series stats.

Table A.361: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_restart_stream: Name of the restart stream the time series stats analysis member will use to initialize itself if restart is enabled.

A.38.7 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_operation](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	avg

Possible Values:	An operation, where it can be 'avg', 'min', or 'max', 'sum', or 'sos' (sum of squares).
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Table A.362: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_operation`: An operation describing the statistic to apply to the time series for all variables in the output stream, reducing the time dimension.

A.38.8 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_reference_times`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	initial_time
Possible Values:	A list of absolute times or 'initial_time's, separated by ;.

Table A.363: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_reference_times`: A list of absolute times describing when to start accumulating statistics. Each time indicates the start of one time window (time series statistic) per variable, in the output stream (i.e., provide four start times if you want quarterly climatologies, only one time is needed for monthly or daily averages, etc.)

A.38.9 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_duration_intervals`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	repeat_interval
Possible Values:	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s or 'repeat_interval's, separated by ;. Each must be greater than or equal to <code>compute_interval * 2</code> and less than or equal to <code>repeat_interval</code> . <code>duration_intervals</code> less than <code>repeat_intervals</code> allow for repeated statistics within the <code>repeat_interval</code> (i.e., for climatologies)

Table A.364: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_duration_intervals`: A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing how long to accumulate statistics in a time window for each repetition (`repeat_interval`). It has to match the number of start time tokens in `reference_times`.

A.38.10 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_repeat_intervals`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless

Default Value:	reset_interval
Possible Values:	MISSING

Table A.365: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_repeat_intervals`: A list of time durations in d_h:m:s describing the accumulation statistic temporal periodicity (time between beginning to accumulate again after it started - duration_interval describes when to stop after starting/restarting). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.

A.38.11 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_reset_intervals`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	00-00-01_00:00:00
Possible Values:	A list of time durations in d_h:m:s, separated by ;. Ought to be greater than or equal to output_interval (not verified by the analysis member).

Table A.366: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_reset_intervals`: A list of time durations in d_h:m:s describing the statistic reset periodicity (how often to reset/clear/zero the accumulation). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.

A.38.12 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_backward_output_offset`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	00-00-01_00:00:00
Possible Values:	A time interval in YYYY-MM-DD_hh:mm:ss.

Table A.367: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsDaily_backward_output_offset`: Backward offset for file-name timestamps when writing the output stream

A.39 `AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly`

A.39.1 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_enable`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	true
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.368: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_enable`: If true, ocean analysis member time series stats is called.

A.39.2 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_compute_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.369: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_compute_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up. You likely want this off for this (time series) analysis member because it will accumulate any state prior to time stepping (double counting the last time step).

A.39.3 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_write_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.370: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_write_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member output occurs on start-up.

A.39.4 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	dt
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp or 'dt'. This must also be less than or equal to <code>output_interval / 2</code> (i.e., requires at least two samples in a series).

Table A.371: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_compute_interval`: Interval that determines frequency of computation for the time series stats analysis member.

A.39.5 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_output_stream](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	timeSeriesStatsMonthlyOutput
Possible Values:	An existing stream that will be modified (existing real fields removed and new time series stats versions added) with time series stats outputs. Cannot be 'none', like other analysis members.

Table A.372: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_output_stream: Name of stream the time series stats analysis member will operate on.

A.39.6 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_restart_stream](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	timeSeriesStatsMonthlyRestart
Possible Values:	A restart stream with state of the time series stats.

Table A.373: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_restart_stream: Name of the restart stream the time series stats analysis member will use to initialize itself if restart is enabled.

A.39.7 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_operation](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	avg
Possible Values:	An operation, where it can be 'avg', 'min', or 'max', 'sum', or 'sos' (sum of squares).

Table A.374: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_operation: An operation describing the statistic to apply to the time series for all variables in the output stream, reducing the time dimension.

A.39.8 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_reference_times](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	initial_time

Possible Values:	A list of absolute times or 'initial_time's, separated by ;.
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Table A.375: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_reference_times`: A list of absolute times describing when to start accumulating statistics. Each time indicates the start of one time window (time series statistic) per variable, in the output stream (i.e., provide four start times if you want quarterly climatologies, only one time is needed for monthly or daily averages, etc.)

A.39.9 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_duration_intervals`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	repeat_interval
Possible Values:	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s or 'repeat_interval's, separated by ;. Each must be greater than or equal to <code>compute_interval * 2</code> and less than or equal to <code>repeat_interval</code> . <code>duration_intervals</code> less than <code>repeat_intervals</code> allow for repeated statistics within the <code>repeat_interval</code> (i.e., for climatologies)

Table A.376: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_duration_intervals`: A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing how long to accumulate statistics in a time window for each repetition (`repeat_interval`). It has to match the number of start time tokens in `reference_times`.

A.39.10 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_repeat_intervals`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	reset_interval
Possible Values:	MISSING

Table A.377: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_repeat_intervals`: A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing the accumulation statistic temporal periodicity (time between beginning to accumulate again after it started - `duration_interval` describes when to stop after starting/restarting). It has to match the number of tokens in `reference_times`.

A.39.11 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_reset_intervals`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless

Default Value:	00-01-00_00:00:00
Possible Values:	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s, separated by ;. Ought to be greater than or equal to output_interval (not verified by the analysis member).

Table A.378: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_reset_intervals: A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing the statistic reset periodicity (how often to reset/clear/zero the accumulation). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.

A.39.12 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_backward_output_offset](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	00-01-00_00:00:00
Possible Values:	A time interval in YYYY-MM-DD_hh:mm:ss.

Table A.379: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsMonthly_backward_output_offset: Backward offset for file-name timestamps when writing the output stream

A.40 [AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology](#)

A.40.1 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_enable](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.380: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_enable: If true, ocean analysis member time series stats is called.

A.40.2 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_compute_on_startup](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.381: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_compute_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up. You likely want this off for this (time series) analysis member because it will accumulate any state prior to time stepping (double counting the last time step).

A.40.3 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_write_on_startup`

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.382: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_write_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member output occurs on start-up.

A.40.4 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	00-00-00_01:00:00
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp or 'dt'. This must also be less than or equal to <code>output_interval / 2</code> (i.e., requires at least two samples in a series).

Table A.383: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_compute_interval`: Interval that determines frequency of computation for the time series stats analysis member.

A.40.5 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_output_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	<code>timeSeriesStatsClimatologyOutput</code>
Possible Values:	An existing stream that will be modified (existing real fields removed and new time series stats versions added) with time series stats outputs. Cannot be 'none', like other analysis members.

Table A.384: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_output_stream`: Name of stream the time series stats analysis member will operate on.

A.40.6 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_restart_stream](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	timeSeriesStatsClimatologyRestart
Possible Values:	A restart stream with state of the time series stats.

Table A.385: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_restart_stream: Name of the restart stream the time series stats analysis member will use to initialize itself if restart is enabled.

A.40.7 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_operation](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	avg
Possible Values:	An operation, where it can be 'avg', 'min', or 'max', 'sum', or 'sos' (sum of squares).

Table A.386: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_operation: An operation describing the statistic to apply to the time series for all variables in the output stream, reducing the time dimension.

A.40.8 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_reference_times](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	00-03-01_00:00:00;00-06-01_00:00:00;00-09-01_00:00:00;00-12-01_00:00:00
Possible Values:	A list of absolute times or 'initial_time's, separated by ;.

Table A.387: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_reference_times: A list of absolute times describing when to start accumulating statistics. Each time indicates the start of one time window (time series statistic) per variable, in the output stream (i.e., provide four start times if you want quarterly climatologies, only one time is needed for monthly or daily averages, etc.)

A.40.9 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_duration_intervals](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	00-03-00_00:00:00;00-03-00_00:00:00;00-03-00_00:00:00;00-03-00_00:00:00
Possible Values:	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s or 'repeat_interval's, separated by ;. Each must be greater than or equal to compute_interval * 2 and less than or equal to repeat_interval. duration_intervals less than repeat_intervals allow for repeated statistics within the repeat_interval (i.e., for climatologies)

Table A.388: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_duration_intervals: A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing how long to accumulate statistics in a time window for each repetition (repeat_interval). It has to match the number of start time tokens in reference_times.

A.40.10 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_repeat_intervals](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	01-00-00_00:00:00;01-00-00_00:00:00;01-00-00_00:00:00;01-00-00_00:00:00
Possible Values:	MISSING

Table A.389: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_repeat_intervals: A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing the accumulation statistic temporal periodicity (time between beginning to accumulate again after it started - duration_interval describes when to stop after starting/restarting). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.

A.40.11 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_reset_intervals](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	1000-00-00_00:00:00;1000-00-00_00:00:00;1000-00-00_00:00:00;1000-00-00_00:00:00
Possible Values:	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s, separated by ;. Ought to be greater than or equal to output_interval (not verified by the analysis member).

Table A.390: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_reset_intervals: A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing the statistic reset periodicity (how often to reset/clear/zero the accumulation). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.

A.40.12 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_backward_output_offset](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	00-03-00_00:00:00
Possible Values:	A time interval in YYYY-MM-DD_hh:mm:ss.

Table A.391: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsClimatology_backward_output_offset: Backward offset for filename timestamps when writing the output stream

A.41 [AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom](#)

A.41.1 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_enable](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.392: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_enable: If true, ocean analysis member time series stats is called.

A.41.2 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_compute_on_startup](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.393: config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_compute_on_startup: Logical flag determining if an analysis member computation occurs on start-up. You likely want this off for this (time series) analysis member because it will accumulate any state prior to time stepping (double counting the last time step).

A.41.3 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_write_on_startup](#)

Type:	logical
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	false
Possible Values:	true or false

Table A.394: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_write_on_startup`: Logical flag determining if an analysis member output occurs on start-up.

A.41.4 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_compute_interval`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	00-00-00_01:00:00
Possible Values:	Any valid time stamp or 'dt'. This must also be less than or equal to <code>output_interval / 2</code> (i.e., requires at least two samples in a series).

Table A.395: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_compute_interval`: Interval that determines frequency of computation for the time series stats analysis member.

A.41.5 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_output_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	<code>timeSeriesStatsCustomOutput</code>
Possible Values:	An existing stream that will be modified (existing real fields removed and new time series stats versions added) with time series stats outputs. Cannot be 'none', like other analysis members.

Table A.396: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_output_stream`: Name of stream the time series stats analysis member will operate on.

A.41.6 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_restart_stream`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	<code>timeSeriesStatsCustomRestart</code>
Possible Values:	A restart stream with state of the time series stats.

Table A.397: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_restart_stream`: Name of the restart stream the time series stats analysis member will use to initialize itself if restart is enabled.

A.41.7 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_operation](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	avg
Possible Values:	An operation, where it can be 'avg', 'min', or 'max', 'sum', or 'sos' (sum of squares).

Table A.398: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_operation`: An operation describing the statistic to apply to the time series for all variables in the output stream, reducing the time dimension.

A.41.8 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_reference_times](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	initial_time
Possible Values:	A list of absolute times or 'initial_time's, separated by ;.

Table A.399: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_reference_times`: A list of absolute times describing when to start accumulating statistics. Each time indicates the start of one time window (time series statistic) per variable, in the output stream (i.e., provide four start times if you want quarterly climatologies, only one time is needed for monthly or daily averages, etc.)

A.41.9 [config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_duration_intervals](#)

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	repeat_interval
Possible Values:	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s or 'repeat_interval's, separated by ;. Each must be greater than or equal to <code>compute_interval * 2</code> and less than or equal to <code>repeat_interval</code> . <code>duration_intervals</code> less than <code>repeat_intervals</code> allow for repeated statistics within the <code>repeat_interval</code> (i.e., for climatologies)

Table A.400: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_duration_intervals`: A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing how long to accumulate statistics in a time window for each repetition (`repeat_interval`). It has to match the number of start time tokens in `reference_times`.

A.41.10 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_repeat_intervals`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	reset_interval
Possible Values:	MISSING

Table A.401: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_repeat_intervals`: A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing the accumulation statistic temporal periodicity (time between beginning to accumulate again after it started - duration_interval describes when to stop after starting/restarting). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.

A.41.11 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_reset_intervals`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	00-00-07_00:00:00
Possible Values:	A list of time durations in d.h:m:s, separated by ;. Ought to be greater than or equal to output_interval (not verified by the analysis member).

Table A.402: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_reset_intervals`: A list of time durations in d.h:m:s describing the statistic reset periodicity (how often to reset/clear/zero the accumulation). It has to match the number of tokens in reference_times.

A.41.12 `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_backward_output_offset`

Type:	character
Units:	unitless
Default Value:	00-00-01_00:00:00
Possible Values:	A time interval in YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss.

Table A.403: `config_AM_timeSeriesStatsCustom_backward_output_offset`: Backward offset for file-name timestamps when writing the output stream

Appendix B

Variable definitions

Embedded links point to information in chapter [10](#)

B.1 `mesh`

B.1.1 `latCell`

Type:	real
Units:	radians
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % mesh % latCell

Table B.1: `latCell`: Latitude location of cell centers in radians.

B.1.2 `lonCell`

Type:	real
Units:	radians
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % mesh % lonCell

Table B.2: `lonCell`: Longitude location of cell centers in radians.

B.1.3 `xCell`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % xCell

Table B.3: xCell: X Coordinate in cartesian space of cell centers.

B.1.4 [yCell](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % yCell

Table B.4: yCell: Y Coordinate in cartesian space of cell centers.

B.1.5 [zCell](#)

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % zCell

Table B.5: zCell: Z Coordinate in cartesian space of cell centers.

B.1.6 [indexToCellID](#)

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % indexToCellID

Table B.6: indexToCellID: List of global cell IDs.

B.1.7 [latEdge](#)

Type:	real
Units:	radians
Dimension:	nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % mesh % latEdge

Table B.7: latEdge: Latitude location of edge midpoints in radians.

B.1.8 lonEdge

Type:	real
Units:	radians
Dimension:	nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % mesh % lonEdge

Table B.8: lonEdge: Longitude location of edge midpoints in radians.

B.1.9 xEdge

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % mesh % xEdge

Table B.9: xEdge: X Coordinate in cartesian space of edge midpoints.

B.1.10 yEdge

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % mesh % yEdge

Table B.10: yEdge: Y Coordinate in cartesian space of edge midpoints.

B.1.11 `zEdge`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % zEdge

Table B.11: `zEdge`: Z Coordinate in cartesian space of edge midpoints.

B.1.12 `indexToEdgeID`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % indexToEdgeID

Table B.12: `indexToEdgeID`: List of global edge IDs.

B.1.13 `latVertex`

Type:	real
Units:	radians
Dimension:	nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % latVertex

Table B.13: `latVertex`: Latitude location of vertices in radians.

B.1.14 `lonVertex`

Type:	real
Units:	radians
Dimension:	nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % lonVertex

Table B.14: `lonVertex`: Longitude location of vertices in radians.

B.1.15 `xVertex`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % xVertex

Table B.15: `xVertex`: X Coordinate in cartesian space of vertices.

B.1.16 `yVertex`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % yVertex

Table B.16: `yVertex`: Y Coordinate in cartesian space of vertices.

B.1.17 `zVertex`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % zVertex

Table B.17: `zVertex`: Z Coordinate in cartesian space of vertices.

B.1.18 `indexToVertexID`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % indexToVertexID

Table B.18: `indexToVertexID`: List of global vertex IDs.

B.1.19 `cellsOnEdge`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	TWO nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % cellsOnEdge

Table B.19: `cellsOnEdge`: List of cells that straddle each edge.

B.1.20 `nEdgesOnCell`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % nEdgesOnCell

Table B.20: `nEdgesOnCell`: Number of edges that border each cell.

B.1.21 `nEdgesOnEdge`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % nEdgesOnEdge

Table B.21: `nEdgesOnEdge`: Number of edges that surround each of the cells that straddle each edge. These edges are used to reconstruct the tangential velocities.

B.1.22 `edgesOnCell`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	maxEdges nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % edgesOnCell

Table B.22: `edgesOnCell`: List of edges that border each cell.

B.1.23 `edgesOnEdge`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	maxEdges2 nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % edgesOnEdge

Table B.23: `edgesOnEdge`: List of edges that border each of the cells that straddle each edge.

B.1.24 `dvEdge`

Type:	real
Units:	m
Dimension:	nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % dvEdge

Table B.24: `dvEdge`: Length of each edge, computed as the distance between `verticesOnEdge`.

B.1.25 `dcEdge`

Type:	real
Units:	m
Dimension:	nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % dcEdge

Table B.25: `dcEdge`: Length of each edge, computed as the distance between `cellsOnEdge`.

B.1.26 `areaCell`

Type:	real
Units:	m ²
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % areaCell

Table B.26: `areaCell`: Area of each cell in the primary grid.

B.1.27 `areaTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	m ²
Dimension:	nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % areaTriangle

Table B.27: `areaTriangle`: Area of each cell (triangle) in the dual grid.

B.1.28 `edgeNormalVectors`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	R3 nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % edgeNormalVectors

Table B.28: `edgeNormalVectors`: Normal unit vector defined at an edge.

B.1.29 `cellTangentPlane`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	R3 TWO nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % cellTangentPlane

Table B.29: `cellTangentPlane`: The two vectors that define a tangent plane at a cell center.

B.1.30 `localVerticalUnitVectors`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	R3 nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % localVerticalUnitVectors

Table B.30: `localVerticalUnitVectors`: Unit surface normal vectors defined at cell centers.

B.1.31 `cellsOnCell`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	maxEdges nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % mesh % cellsOnCell

Table B.31: `cellsOnCell`: List of cells that neighbor each cell.

B.1.32 `verticesOnCell`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	maxEdges nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % mesh % verticesOnCell

Table B.32: `verticesOnCell`: List of vertices that border each cell.

B.1.33 `verticesOnEdge`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	TWO nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % mesh % verticesOnEdge

Table B.33: `verticesOnEdge`: List of vertices that straddle each edge.

B.1.34 `edgesOnVertex`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	vertexDegree nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % mesh % edgesOnVertex

Table B.34: `edgesOnVertex`: List of edges that share a vertex as an endpoint.

B.1.35 `cellsOnVertex`

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	vertexDegree nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % mesh % cellsOnVertex

Table B.35: `cellsOnVertex`: List of cells that share a vertex.

B.1.36 `kiteAreasOnVertex`

Type:	real
Units:	m ²
Dimension:	vertexDegree nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % mesh % kiteAreasOnVertex

Table B.36: `kiteAreasOnVertex`: Area of the portions of each dual cell that are part of each cell-`sOnVertex`.

B.1.37 `fVertex`

Type:	real
Units:	s ⁻¹
Dimension:	nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % mesh % fVertex

Table B.37: `fVertex`: Coriolis parameter at vertices.

B.1.38 `coeffs_reconstruct`

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	R3 maxEdges nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % mesh % coeffs_reconstruct

Table B.38: coeffs_reconstruct: Coefficients to reconstruct velocity vectors at cells centers.

B.1.39 itimestep

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % mesh % itimestep

Table B.39: itimestep: **MISSING**

B.2 tracers

B.2.1 iceAreaCategory

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % iceAreaCategory

Table B.40: iceAreaCategory: **MISSING**

B.2.2 iceVolumeCategory

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % iceVolumeCategory

Table B.41: iceVolumeCategory: **MISSING**

B.2.3 snowVolumeCategory

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % snowVolumeCategory

Table B.42: snowVolumeCategory: **MISSING**

B.2.4 surfaceTemperature

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % surfaceTemperature

Table B.43: surfaceTemperature: **MISSING**

B.2.5 iceEnthalpy

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % iceEnthalpy

Table B.44: iceEnthalpy: **MISSING**

B.2.6 iceSalinity

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % iceSalinity
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Table B.45: iceSalinity: **MISSING**

B.2.7 snowEnthalpy

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % snowEnthalpy

Table B.46: snowEnthalpy: **MISSING**

B.2.8 iceAge

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % iceAge

Table B.47: iceAge: **MISSING**

B.2.9 firstYearIceArea

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % firstYearIceArea

Table B.48: firstYearIceArea: **MISSING**

B.2.10 levelIceArea

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % levelIceArea

Table B.49: levelIceArea: **MISSING**

B.2.11 levelIceVolume

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % levelIceVolume

Table B.50: levelIceVolume: **MISSING**

B.2.12 pondArea

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % pondArea

Table B.51: pondArea: **MISSING**

B.2.13 pondDepth

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % pondDepth
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Table B.52: pondDepth: **MISSING**

B.2.14 pondLidThickness

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % pondLidThickness

Table B.53: pondLidThickness: **MISSING**

B.2.15 snowScatteringAerosol

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % snowScatteringAerosol

Table B.54: snowScatteringAerosol: **MISSING**

B.2.16 snowBodyAerosol

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % snowBodyAerosol

Table B.55: snowBodyAerosol: **MISSING**

B.2.17 iceScatteringAerosol

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % iceScatteringAerosol

Table B.56: iceScatteringAerosol: **MISSING**

B.2.18 iceBodyAerosol

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % iceBodyAerosol

Table B.57: iceBodyAerosol: **MISSING**

B.2.19 brineFraction

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % brineFraction

Table B.58: brineFraction: **MISSING**

B.2.20 mobileFraction

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % mobileFraction

Table B.59: mobileFraction: **MISSING**

B.2.21 skeletalAlgaeConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % skeletalAlgaeConc

Table B.60: skeletalAlgaeConc: **MISSING**

B.2.22 skeletalDOCConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOC nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % skeletalDOCConc

Table B.61: skeletalDOCConc: **MISSING**

B.2.23 skeletalDICConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDIC nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % skeletalDICConc

Table B.62: skeletalDICConc: **MISSING**

B.2.24 skeletalDONConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDON nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % skeletalDONConc

Table B.63: skeletalDONConc: **MISSING**

B.2.25 skeletalNitrateConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % skeletalNitrateConc

Table B.64: skeletalNitrateConc: **MISSING**

B.2.26 skeletalSilicateConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % skeletalSilicateConc

Table B.65: skeletalSilicateConc: **MISSING**

B.2.27 skeletalAmmoniumConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % skeletalAmmoniumConc

Table B.66: skeletalAmmoniumConc: **MISSING**

B.2.28 `skeletalDMSConc`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % skeletalDMSConc

Table B.67: skeletalDMSConc: **MISSING**

B.2.29 `skeletalDMSPpConc`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % skeletalDMSPpConc

Table B.68: skeletalDMSPpConc: **MISSING**

B.2.30 `skeletalDMSPdConc`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % skeletalDMSPdConc

Table B.69: skeletalDMSPdConc: **MISSING**

B.2.31 `skeletalNonreactiveConc`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % skeletalNonreactiveConc

Table B.70: skeletalNonreactiveConc: **MISSING**

B.2.32 skeletalHumicsConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % skeletalHumicsConc

Table B.71: skeletalHumicsConc: **MISSING**

B.2.33 skeletalParticulateIronConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIron nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % skeletalParticulateIronConc

Table B.72: skeletalParticulateIronConc: **MISSING**

B.2.34 skeletalDissolvedIronConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIron nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % skeletalDissolvedIronConc

Table B.73: skeletalDissolvedIronConc: **MISSING**

B.2.35 verticalAlgaeConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalAlgaeConc

Table B.74: verticalAlgaeConc: **MISSING**

B.2.36 verticalDOCConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalDOCConc

Table B.75: verticalDOCConc: **MISSING**

B.2.37 verticalDICConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalDICConc

Table B.76: verticalDICConc: **MISSING**

B.2.38 verticalDONConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalDONConc

Table B.77: verticalDONConc: **MISSING**

B.2.39 verticalNitrateConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalNitrateConc

Table B.78: verticalNitrateConc: **MISSING**

B.2.40 verticalSilicateConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalSilicateConc

Table B.79: verticalSilicateConc: **MISSING**

B.2.41 verticalAmmoniumConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalAmmoniumConc

Table B.80: verticalAmmoniumConc: **MISSING**

B.2.42 verticalDMSConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalDMSConc

Table B.81: verticalDMSConc: **MISSING**

B.2.43 verticalDMSPpConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalDMSPpConc

Table B.82: verticalDMSPpConc: **MISSING**

B.2.44 verticalDMSPdConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalDMSPdConc

Table B.83: verticalDMSPdConc: **MISSING**

B.2.45 verticalNonreactiveConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalNonreactiveConc

Table B.84: verticalNonreactiveConc: **MISSING**

B.2.46 verticalHumicsConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalHumicsConc

Table B.85: verticalHumicsConc: **MISSING**

B.2.47 verticalParticulateIronConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIronLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalParticulateIronConc

Table B.86: verticalParticulateIronConc: **MISSING**

B.2.48 verticalDissolvedIronConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIronLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalDissolvedIronConc

Table B.87: verticalDissolvedIronConc: **MISSING**

B.2.49 verticalAlgaeSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeSnowLayers nCategories nCells Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalAlgaeSnow

Table B.88: verticalAlgaeSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.50 verticalDOCSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCSnowLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalDOCSnow

Table B.89: verticalDOCSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.51 verticalDICSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICSnowLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalDICSnow

Table B.90: verticalDICSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.52 verticalDONSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONSnowLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalDONSnow

Table B.91: verticalDONSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.53 verticalNitrateSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalNitrateSnow

Table B.92: verticalNitrateSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.54 verticalSilicateSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalSilicateSnow

Table B.93: verticalSilicateSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.55 verticalAmmoniumSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalAmmoniumSnow

Table B.94: verticalAmmoniumSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.56 verticalDMSSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalDMSSnow

Table B.95: verticalDMSSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.57 verticalDMSPpSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalDMSPpSnow

Table B.96: verticalDMSPpSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.58 verticalDMSPdSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalDMSPdSnow

Table B.97: verticalDMSPdSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.59 verticalNonreactiveSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalNonreactiveSnow

Table B.98: verticalNonreactiveSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.60 verticalHumicsSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalHumicsSnow

Table B.99: verticalHumicsSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.61 verticalParticulateIronSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalParticulateIronSnow

Table B.100: verticalParticulateIronSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.62 verticalDissolvedIronSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalDissolvedIronSnow

Table B.101: verticalDissolvedIronSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.63 verticalAlgaeIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeIceLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalAlgaeIce

Table B.102: verticalAlgaeIce: **MISSING**

B.2.64 verticalDOCIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCIceLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalDOCIce

Table B.103: verticalDOCIce: **MISSING**

B.2.65 verticalDICIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICIceLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalDICIce

Table B.104: verticalDICIce: **MISSING**

B.2.66 verticalDONIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONIceLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalDONIce

Table B.105: verticalDONIce: **MISSING**

B.2.67 verticalNitrateIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalNitrateIce

Table B.106: verticalNitrateIce: **MISSING**

B.2.68 verticalSilicateIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalSilicateIce

Table B.107: verticalSilicateIce: **MISSING**

B.2.69 verticalAmmoniumIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalAmmoniumIce

Table B.108: verticalAmmoniumIce: **MISSING**

B.2.70 verticalDMSIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalDMSIce

Table B.109: verticalDMSIce: **MISSING**

B.2.71 verticalDMSPpIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalDMSPpIce

Table B.110: verticalDMSPpIce: **MISSING**

B.2.72 verticalDMSPdIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalDMSPdIce

Table B.111: verticalDMSPdIce: **MISSING**

B.2.73 verticalNonreactiveIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time.levs(:) % tracers % verticalNonreactiveIce

Table B.112: verticalNonreactiveIce: **MISSING**

B.2.74 verticalHumicsIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalHumicsIce

Table B.113: verticalHumicsIce: **MISSING**

B.2.75 verticalParticulateIronIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronIceLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalParticulateIronIce

Table B.114: verticalParticulateIronIce: **MISSING**

B.2.76 verticalDissolvedIronIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronIceLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalDissolvedIronIce

Table B.115: verticalDissolvedIronIce: **MISSING**

B.2.77 verticalAerosolsConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalAerosolsConc

Table B.116: verticalAerosolsConc: **MISSING**

B.2.78 verticalAerosolsSnow

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsSnowLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalAerosolsSnow

Table B.117: verticalAerosolsSnow: **MISSING**

B.2.79 verticalAerosolsIce

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsIceLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalAerosolsIce

Table B.118: verticalAerosolsIce: **MISSING**

B.2.80 verticalSalinity

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers % time_levs(:) % tracers % verticalSalinity

Table B.119: verticalSalinity: **MISSING**

B.3 tracers_aggregate

B.3.1 iceAreaCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % iceAreaCell

Table B.120: iceAreaCell: **MISSING**

B.3.2 iceVolumeCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % iceVolumeCell

Table B.121: iceVolumeCell: **MISSING**

B.3.3 snowVolumeCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % snowVolumeCell

Table B.122: snowVolumeCell: **MISSING**

B.3.4 surfaceTemperatureCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % surfaceTemperatureCell

Table B.123: surfaceTemperatureCell: **MISSING**

B.3.5 iceEnthalpyCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % iceEnthalpyCell

Table B.124: iceEnthalpyCell: **MISSING**

B.3.6 iceSalinityCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % iceSalinityCell

Table B.125: iceSalinityCell: **MISSING**

B.3.7 snowEnthalpyCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % snowEnthalpyCell

Table B.126: snowEnthalpyCell: **MISSING**

B.3.8 iceAgeCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % iceAgeCell

Table B.127: iceAgeCell: **MISSING**

B.3.9 firstYearIceAreaCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % firstYearIceAreaCell

Table B.128: firstYearIceAreaCell: **MISSING**

B.3.10 levelIceAreaCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % levelIceAreaCell

Table B.129: levelIceAreaCell: **MISSING**

B.3.11 levelIceVolumeCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % levelIceVolumeCell

Table B.130: levelIceVolumeCell: **MISSING**

B.3.12 pondAreaCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % pondAreaCell

Table B.131: pondAreaCell: **MISSING**

B.3.13 pondDepthCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % pondDepthCell

Table B.132: pondDepthCell: **MISSING**

B.3.14 pondLidThicknessCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % pondLidThicknessCell

Table B.133: pondLidThicknessCell: **MISSING**

B.3.15 snowScatteringAerosolCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % snowScatteringAerosolCell

Table B.134: snowScatteringAerosolCell: **MISSING**

B.3.16 snowBodyAerosolCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % snowBodyAerosolCell
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Table B.135: snowBodyAerosolCell: **MISSING**

B.3.17 iceScatteringAerosolCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % iceScatteringAerosolCell

Table B.136: iceScatteringAerosolCell: **MISSING**

B.3.18 iceBodyAerosolCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % iceBodyAerosolCell

Table B.137: iceBodyAerosolCell: **MISSING**

B.3.19 brineFractionCell

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % brineFractionCell

Table B.138: brineFractionCell: Grid cell average ratio of brine height to ice thickness

B.3.20 `skeletalAlgaeConcCell`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % skeletalAlgaeConcCell

Table B.139: `skeletalAlgaeConcCell`: **MISSING**

B.3.21 `skeletalDOCConcCell`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOC nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % skeletalDOCConcCell

Table B.140: `skeletalDOCConcCell`: **MISSING**

B.3.22 `skeletalDICConcCell`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDIC nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % skeletalDICConcCell

Table B.141: `skeletalDICConcCell`: **MISSING**

B.3.23 `skeletalDONConcCell`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDON nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % skeletalDONConcCell

Table B.142: skeletalDONConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.24 skeletalNitrateConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % skeletalNitrateConcCell

Table B.143: skeletalNitrateConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.25 skeletalSilicateConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % skeletalSilicateConcCell

Table B.144: skeletalSilicateConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.26 skeletalAmmoniumConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % skeletalAmmoniumConcCell

Table B.145: skeletalAmmoniumConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.27 skeletalDMSConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % skeletalDMSConcCell

Table B.146: skeletalDMSConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.28 skeletalDMSPpConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % skeletalDMSPpConcCell

Table B.147: skeletalDMSPpConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.29 skeletalDMSPdConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % skeletalDMSPdConcCell

Table B.148: skeletalDMSPdConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.30 skeletalNonreactiveConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % skeletalNonreactiveConcCell

Table B.149: skeletalNonreactiveConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.31 skeletalHumicsConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % skeletalHumicsConcCell

Table B.150: skeletalHumicsConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.32 skeletalParticulateIronConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIron nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % skeletalParticulateIronConcCell

Table B.151: skeletalParticulateIronConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.33 skeletalDissolvedIronConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIron nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % skeletalDissolvedIronConcCell

Table B.152: skeletalDissolvedIronConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.34 verticalAlgaeConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeLayers nCells Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalAlgaeConcCell

Table B.153: verticalAlgaeConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.35 verticalDOCConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDOCConcCell

Table B.154: verticalDOCConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.36 verticalDICConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDICConcCell

Table B.155: verticalDICConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.37 verticalDONConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDONConcCell

Table B.156: verticalDONConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.38 verticalNitrateConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalNitrate-ConcCell

Table B.157: verticalNitrateConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.39 verticalSilicateConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalSilicate-ConcCell

Table B.158: verticalSilicateConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.40 verticalAmmoniumConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalAmmonium-ConcCell

Table B.159: verticalAmmoniumConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.41 verticalDMSConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDMSConcCell

Table B.160: verticalDMSConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.42 verticalDMSPpConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers.aggregate % verticalDMSPp-ConcCell

Table B.161: verticalDMSPpConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.43 verticalDMSPdConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers.aggregate % verticalDMSPd-ConcCell

Table B.162: verticalDMSPdConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.44 verticalNonreactiveConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers.aggregate % verticalNonreactiveConcCell

Table B.163: verticalNonreactiveConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.45 verticalHumicsConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalHumicsConcCell

Table B.164: verticalHumicsConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.46 verticalParticulateIronConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIronLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalParticulateIronConcCell

Table B.165: verticalParticulateIronConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.47 verticalDissolvedIronConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIronLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDissolvedIronConcCell

Table B.166: verticalDissolvedIronConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.48 verticalAlgaeSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeSnowLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalAlgaeSnowCell

Table B.167: verticalAlgaeSnowCell: **MISSING**

B.3.49 verticalDOCSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCSnowLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDOCSnow-Cell

Table B.168: verticalDOCSnowCell: **MISSING**

B.3.50 verticalDICSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICSnowLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDICSnow-Cell

Table B.169: verticalDICSnowCell: **MISSING**

B.3.51 verticalDONSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONSnowLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDONSnow-Cell

Table B.170: verticalDONSnowCell: **MISSING**

B.3.52 verticalNitrateSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalNitrateSnowCell

Table B.171: verticalNitrateSnowCell: **MISSING**

B.3.53 verticalSilicateSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalSilicateSnowCell

Table B.172: verticalSilicateSnowCell: **MISSING**

B.3.54 verticalAmmoniumSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalAmmoniumSnowCell

Table B.173: verticalAmmoniumSnowCell: **MISSING**

B.3.55 verticalDMSSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDMSSnowCell

Table B.174: verticalDMSSnowCell: **MISSING**

B.3.56 verticalDMSPpSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers.aggregate % verticalDMSPp-SnowCell

Table B.175: verticalDMSPpSnowCell: **MISSING**

B.3.57 verticalDMSPdSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers.aggregate % verticalDM-SPdSnowCell

Table B.176: verticalDMSPdSnowCell: **MISSING**

B.3.58 verticalNonreactiveSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers.aggregate % verticalNonreactiveSnowCell

Table B.177: verticalNonreactiveSnowCell: **MISSING**

B.3.59 verticalHumicsSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCells Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalHumicsSnowCell

Table B.178: verticalHumicsSnowCell: **MISSING**

B.3.60 verticalParticulateIronSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronSnowLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalParticulateIronSnowCell

Table B.179: verticalParticulateIronSnowCell: **MISSING**

B.3.61 verticalDissolvedIronSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronSnowLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDissolvedIronSnowCell

Table B.180: verticalDissolvedIronSnowCell: **MISSING**

B.3.62 verticalAlgaeIceCell

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ³
Dimension:	nAlgaeIceLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalAlgaeIceCell

Table B.181: verticalAlgaeIceCell: Cell average algal nitrogen for each type and ice bio-grid layer

B.3.63 verticalDOCIceCell

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ³
Dimension:	nDOCIceLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDOCIceCell

Table B.182: verticalDOCIceCell: Cell average dissolved organic carbon for each type and ice bio-grid layer

B.3.64 verticalDICIceCell

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ³
Dimension:	nDICIceLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDICIceCell

Table B.183: verticalDICIceCell: Cell average dissolved inorganic carbon for each type and ice bio-grid layer

B.3.65 verticalDONIceCell

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ³
Dimension:	nDONIceLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDONIceCell

Table B.184: verticalDONIceCell: Cell average dissolved organic nitrogen for each type and ice bio-grid layer

B.3.66 verticalNitrateIceCell

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ³
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCells Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalNitrateIceCell

Table B.185: verticalNitrateIceCell: Cell average nitrate for each ice bio-grid layer

B.3.67 verticalSilicateIceCell

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ³
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalSilicateIceCell

Table B.186: verticalSilicateIceCell: Cell average silicate for each ice bio-grid layer

B.3.68 verticalAmmoniumIceCell

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ³
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalAmmoniumIceCell

Table B.187: verticalAmmoniumIceCell: Cell average ammonium for each ice bio-grid layer

B.3.69 verticalDMSIceCell

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ³
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDMSIceCell

Table B.188: verticalDMSIceCell: Cell average DMS for each ice bio-grid layer

B.3.70 `verticalDMSPpIceCell`

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ³
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDMSPpIceCell

Table B.189: `verticalDMSPpIceCell`: Cell average particulate DMSP for each ice bio-grid layer

B.3.71 `verticalDMSPdIceCell`

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ³
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDMSPdIceCell

Table B.190: `verticalDMSPdIceCell`: Cell average dissolved DMSP for each ice bio-grid layer

B.3.72 `verticalNonreactiveIceCell`

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ³
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalNonreactiveIceCell

Table B.191: `verticalNonreactiveIceCell`: Cell average nonreactive nitrate for each ice bio-grid layer

B.3.73 `verticalHumicsIceCell`

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ³
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalHumicsIceCell

Table B.192: verticalHumicsIceCell: Cell average humic carbon for each ice bio-grid layer

B.3.74 verticalParticulateIronIceCell

Type:	real
Units:	umol/m ³
Dimension:	nPartIronIceLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalParticulateIronIceCell

Table B.193: verticalParticulateIronIceCell: Cell average particulate iron for each type and ice bio-grid layer

B.3.75 verticalDissolvedIronIceCell

Type:	real
Units:	umol/m ³
Dimension:	nDisIronIceLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalDissolvedIronIceCell

Table B.194: verticalDissolvedIronIceCell: Cell average dissolved iron for each type and ice bio-grid layer

B.3.76 verticalAerosolsSnowCell

Type:	real
Units:	mg/m ³
Dimension:	nzAerosolsSnowLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalAerosolsSnowCell

Table B.195: verticalAerosolsSnowCell: Cell average aerosol for each type and snow bio-grid layer

B.3.77 verticalAerosolsIceCell

Type:	real
Units:	mg/m ³
Dimension:	nzAerosolsIceLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalAerosolsIceCell

Table B.196: verticalAerosolsIceCell: Cell average aerosol for each type and ice bio-grid layer

B.3.78 verticalAerosolsConcCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalAerosolsConcCell

Table B.197: verticalAerosolsConcCell: **MISSING**

B.3.79 verticalSalinityCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracers_aggregate % verticalSalinityCell

Table B.198: verticalSalinityCell: **MISSING**

B.4 icestate

B.4.1 iceAreaCellInitial

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % icestate % iceAreaCellInitial

Table B.199: iceAreaCellInitial: **MISSING**

B.4.2 iceAreaCategoryInitial

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % icestate % iceAreaCategoryInitial

Table B.200: iceAreaCategoryInitial: **MISSING**

B.4.3 iceVolumeCategoryInitial

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % icestate % iceVolumeCategoryInitial

Table B.201: iceVolumeCategoryInitial: **MISSING**

B.4.4 iceThicknessCategoryInitial

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % icestate % iceThicknessCategoryInitial

Table B.202: iceThicknessCategoryInitial: **MISSING**

B.4.5 snowVolumeCategoryInitial

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % icestate % snowVolumeCategoryInitial

Table B.203: snowVolumeCategoryInitial: **MISSING**

B.4.6 openWaterArea

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % icestate % openWaterArea

Table B.204: openWaterArea: **MISSING**

B.4.7 iceAreaVertex

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % icestate % iceAreaVertex

Table B.205: iceAreaVertex: **MISSING**

B.4.8 totalMassCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % icestate % totalMassCell

Table B.206: totalMassCell: **MISSING**

B.4.9 totalMassVertex

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % icestate % totalMassVertex

Table B.207: totalMassVertex: **MISSING**

B.5 tracer_tendencies

B.5.1 iceAreaCategoryTend

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_tendencies % iceAreaCategoryTend

Table B.208: iceAreaCategoryTend: **MISSING**

B.5.2 iceVolumeCategoryTend

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_tendencies % iceVolumeCategoryTend

Table B.209: iceVolumeCategoryTend: **MISSING**

B.5.3 snowVolumeCategoryTend

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_tendencies % snowVolumeCategoryTend
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Table B.210: snowVolumeCategoryTend: **MISSING**

B.5.4 surfaceTemperatureTend

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_tendencies % surfaceTemperatureTend

Table B.211: surfaceTemperatureTend: **MISSING**

B.5.5 iceEnthalpyTend

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_tendencies % iceEnthalpyTend

Table B.212: iceEnthalpyTend: **MISSING**

B.5.6 iceSalinityTend

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_tendencies % iceSalinityTend

Table B.213: iceSalinityTend: **MISSING**

B.5.7 snowEnthalpyTend

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_tendencies % snowEnthalpyTend

Table B.214: snowEnthalpyTend: **MISSING**

B.6 tracer_masks

B.6.1 iceAreaCategoryMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % iceAreaCategoryMask

Table B.215: iceAreaCategoryMask: **MISSING**

B.6.2 iceVolumeCategoryMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % iceVolumeCategoryMask

Table B.216: iceVolumeCategoryMask: **MISSING**

B.6.3 snowVolumeCategoryMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % snowVolumeCategoryMask

Table B.217: snowVolumeCategoryMask: **MISSING**

B.6.4 surfaceTemperatureMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % surfaceTemperatureMask

Table B.218: surfaceTemperatureMask: **MISSING**

B.6.5 iceEnthalpyMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % iceEnthalpyMask

Table B.219: iceEnthalpyMask: **MISSING**

B.6.6 iceSalinityMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % iceSalinityMask

Table B.220: iceSalinityMask: **MISSING**

B.6.7 snowEnthalpyMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING

Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % snowEnthalpyMask

Table B.221: snowEnthalpyMask: **MISSING**

B.6.8 iceAgeMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % iceAgeMask

Table B.222: iceAgeMask: **MISSING**

B.6.9 firstYearIceAreaMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % firstYearIceAreaMask

Table B.223: firstYearIceAreaMask: **MISSING**

B.6.10 levelIceAreaMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % levelIceAreaMask

Table B.224: levelIceAreaMask: **MISSING**

B.6.11 levelIceVolumeMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % levelIceVolumeMask

Table B.225: levelIceVolumeMask: **MISSING**

B.6.12 pondAreaMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % pondAreaMask

Table B.226: pondAreaMask: **MISSING**

B.6.13 pondDepthMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % pondDepthMask

Table B.227: pondDepthMask: **MISSING**

B.6.14 pondLidThicknessMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % pondLidThicknessMask

Table B.228: pondLidThicknessMask: **MISSING**

B.6.15 snowScatteringAerosolMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % snowScatteringAerosolMask

Table B.229: snowScatteringAerosolMask: **MISSING**

B.6.16 snowBodyAerosolMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % snowBodyAerosolMask

Table B.230: snowBodyAerosolMask: **MISSING**

B.6.17 iceScatteringAerosolMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % iceScatteringAerosolMask

Table B.231: iceScatteringAerosolMask: **MISSING**

B.6.18 iceBodyAerosolMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % iceBodyAerosolMask

Table B.232: iceBodyAerosolMask: **MISSING**

B.6.19 `brineFractionMask`

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % brineFractionMask

Table B.233: `brineFractionMask`: **MISSING**

B.6.20 `mobileFractionMask`

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % mobileFractionMask

Table B.234: `mobileFractionMask`: **MISSING**

B.6.21 `skeletalAlgaeConcMask`

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % skeletalAlgaeConcMask

Table B.235: `skeletalAlgaeConcMask`: **MISSING**

B.6.22 `skeletalDOCConcMask`

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % skeletalDOCConcMask

Table B.236: skeletalDOCConcMask: **MISSING**

B.6.23 skeletalDICConcMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDIC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % skeletalDICConcMask

Table B.237: skeletalDICConcMask: **MISSING**

B.6.24 skeletalDONConcMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDON nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % skeletalDONConcMask

Table B.238: skeletalDONConcMask: **MISSING**

B.6.25 skeletalNitrateConcMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % skeletalNitrateConcMask

Table B.239: skeletalNitrateConcMask: **MISSING**

B.6.26 skeletalSilicateConcMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING

Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % skeletalSilicateConcMask

Table B.240: skeletalSilicateConcMask: **MISSING**

B.6.27 skeletalAmmoniumConcMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % skeletalAmmoniumConcMask

Table B.241: skeletalAmmoniumConcMask: **MISSING**

B.6.28 skeletalDMSConcMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % skeletalDMSConcMask

Table B.242: skeletalDMSConcMask: **MISSING**

B.6.29 skeletalDMSPpConcMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % skeletalDMSPpConcMask

Table B.243: skeletalDMSPpConcMask: **MISSING**

B.6.30 [skeletalDMSPdConcMask](#)

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % skeletalDMSPdConcMask

Table B.244: skeletalDMSPdConcMask: **MISSING**

B.6.31 [skeletalNonreactiveConcMask](#)

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % skeletalNonreactiveConcMask

Table B.245: skeletalNonreactiveConcMask: **MISSING**

B.6.32 [skeletalHumicsConcMask](#)

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % skeletalHumicsConcMask

Table B.246: skeletalHumicsConcMask: **MISSING**

B.6.33 [skeletalParticulateIronConcMask](#)

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % skeletalParticulateIronConcMask

Table B.247: skeletalParticulateIronConcMask: **MISSING**

B.6.34 skeletalDissolvedIronConcMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % skeletalDissolvedIron-ConcMask

Table B.248: skeletalDissolvedIronConcMask: **MISSING**

B.6.35 verticalAlgaeSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalAlgaeSnow-Mask

Table B.249: verticalAlgaeSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.36 verticalDOCSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalDOCSnow-Mask

Table B.250: verticalDOCSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.37 verticalDICSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % verticalDICSnowMask

Table B.251: verticalDICSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.38 verticalDONSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % verticalDONSnowMask

Table B.252: verticalDONSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.39 verticalNitrateSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % verticalNitrateSnowMask

Table B.253: verticalNitrateSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.40 verticalSilicateSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % verticalSilicateSnowMask

Table B.254: verticalSilicateSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.41 verticalAmmoniumSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalAmmonium-SnowMask

Table B.255: verticalAmmoniumSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.42 verticalDMSSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalDMSSnowMask

Table B.256: verticalDMSSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.43 verticalDMSPpSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalDMSPpSnow-Mask

Table B.257: verticalDMSPpSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.44 verticalDMSPdSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalDMSPdSnowMask
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Table B.258: verticalDMSPdSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.45 verticalNonreactiveSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalNonreactiveSnowMask

Table B.259: verticalNonreactiveSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.46 verticalHumicsSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalHumicsSnowMask

Table B.260: verticalHumicsSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.47 verticalParticulateIronSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalParticulateIronSnowMask

Table B.261: verticalParticulateIronSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.48 verticalDissolvedIronSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % verticalDissolvedIronSnowMask

Table B.262: verticalDissolvedIronSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.49 verticalAlgaeIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % verticalAlgaeIceMask

Table B.263: verticalAlgaeIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.50 verticalDOCIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % verticalDOCIceMask

Table B.264: verticalDOCIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.51 verticalDICIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % verticalDICIceMask

Table B.265: verticalDICIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.52 verticalDONIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalDONIceMask

Table B.266: verticalDONIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.53 verticalNitrateIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalNitrateIceMask

Table B.267: verticalNitrateIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.54 verticalSilicateIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalSilicateIceMask

Table B.268: verticalSilicateIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.55 verticalAmmoniumIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalAmmoniumIceMask

Table B.269: verticalAmmoniumIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.56 verticalDMSIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalDMSIceMask

Table B.270: verticalDMSIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.57 verticalDMSPpIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalDMSPpIceMask

Table B.271: verticalDMSPpIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.58 verticalDMSPdIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalDMSPdIceMask

Table B.272: verticalDMSPdIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.59 verticalNonreactiveIceMask

Type:	integer
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Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % verticalNonreactiveIceMask

Table B.273: verticalNonreactiveIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.60 verticalHumicsIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % verticalHumicsIceMask

Table B.274: verticalHumicsIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.61 verticalParticulateIronIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % verticalParticulateIronIceMask

Table B.275: verticalParticulateIronIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.62 verticalDissolvedIronIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_masks % verticalDissolvedIronIceMask

Table B.276: verticalDissolvedIronIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.63 verticalAerosolsSnowMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalAerosolsSnowMask

Table B.277: verticalAerosolsSnowMask: **MISSING**

B.6.64 verticalAerosolsIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalAerosolsIceMask

Table B.278: verticalAerosolsIceMask: **MISSING**

B.6.65 verticalSalinityMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_masks % verticalSalinityMask

Table B.279: verticalSalinityMask: **MISSING**

B.7 tracer_edge_fluxes

B.7.1 iceAreaCategoryEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING

Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % iceAreaCategoryEdgeFlux

Table B.280: iceAreaCategoryEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.2 iceVolumeCategoryEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % iceVolumeCategoryEdgeFlux

Table B.281: iceVolumeCategoryEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.3 snowVolumeCategoryEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % snowVolumeCategoryEdgeFlux

Table B.282: snowVolumeCategoryEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.4 surfaceTemperatureEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % surfaceTemperatureEdgeFlux

Table B.283: surfaceTemperatureEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.5 iceEnthalpyEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % iceEnthalpyEdgeFlux

Table B.284: iceEnthalpyEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.6 iceSalinityEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % iceSalinityEdgeFlux

Table B.285: iceSalinityEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.7 snowEnthalpyEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % snowEnthalpyEdgeFlux

Table B.286: snowEnthalpyEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.8 iceAgeEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % iceAgeEdgeFlux

Table B.287: iceAgeEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.9 firstYearIceAreaEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % firstYearIceAreaEdgeFlux

Table B.288: firstYearIceAreaEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.10 levelIceAreaEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % levelIceAreaEdge- Flux

Table B.289: levelIceAreaEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.11 levelIceVolumeEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % levelIceVol- umeEdgeFlux

Table B.290: levelIceVolumeEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.12 `pondAreaEdgeFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % pondAreaEdgeFlux

Table B.291: `pondAreaEdgeFlux`: **MISSING**

B.7.13 `pondDepthEdgeFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % pondDepthEdgeFlux

Table B.292: `pondDepthEdgeFlux`: **MISSING**

B.7.14 `pondLidThicknessEdgeFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % pondLidThicknessEdgeFlux

Table B.293: `pondLidThicknessEdgeFlux`: **MISSING**

B.7.15 `snowScatteringAerosolEdgeFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % snowScatteringAerosolEdgeFlux
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Table B.294: snowScatteringAerosolEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.16 snowBodyAerosolEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % snowBodyAerosolEdgeFlux

Table B.295: snowBodyAerosolEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.17 iceScatteringAerosolEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % iceScatteringAerosolEdgeFlux

Table B.296: iceScatteringAerosolEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.18 iceBodyAerosolEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % iceBodyAerosolEdgeFlux

Table B.297: iceBodyAerosolEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.19 `brineFractionEdgeFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % brineFractionEdgeFlux

Table B.298: `brineFractionEdgeFlux`: **MISSING**

B.7.20 `mobileFractionEdgeFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % mobileFractionEdgeFlux

Table B.299: `mobileFractionEdgeFlux`: **MISSING**

B.7.21 `skeletalAlgaeConcEdgeFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % skeletalAlgaeConcEdgeFlux

Table B.300: `skeletalAlgaeConcEdgeFlux`: **MISSING**

B.7.22 `skeletalDOCConcEdgeFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOC nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % skeletalDOC-ConcEdgeFlux
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Table B.301: skeletalDOCConcEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.23 skeletalDICConcEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDIC nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % skeletalDIC-ConcEdgeFlux

Table B.302: skeletalDICConcEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.24 skeletalDONConcEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDON nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % skeletalDONConcEdgeFlux

Table B.303: skeletalDONConcEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.25 skeletalNitrateConcEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % skeletalNitrate-ConcEdgeFlux

Table B.304: skeletalNitrateConcEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.26 `skeletalSilicateConcEdgeFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % skeletalSilicateConcEdgeFlux

Table B.305: `skeletalSilicateConcEdgeFlux`: **MISSING**

B.7.27 `skeletalAmmoniumConcEdgeFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % skeletalAmmoniumConcEdgeFlux

Table B.306: `skeletalAmmoniumConcEdgeFlux`: **MISSING**

B.7.28 `skeletalDMSConcEdgeFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % skeletalDMSConcEdgeFlux

Table B.307: `skeletalDMSConcEdgeFlux`: **MISSING**

B.7.29 `skeletalDMSPpConcEdgeFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % skeletalDMSPp-ConcEdgeFlux
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Table B.308: skeletalDMSPpConcEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.30 skeletalDMSPdConcEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % skeletalDMSPd-ConcEdgeFlux

Table B.309: skeletalDMSPdConcEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.31 skeletalNonreactiveConcEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % skeletalNonreactiveConcEdgeFlux

Table B.310: skeletalNonreactiveConcEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.32 skeletalHumicsConcEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % skeletalHumicsConcEdgeFlux

Table B.311: skeletalHumicsConcEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.33 skeletalParticulateIronConcEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIron nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % skeletalParticulateIronConcEdgeFlux

Table B.312: skeletalParticulateIronConcEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.34 skeletalDissolvedIronConcEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIron nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % skeletalDissolvedIronConcEdgeFlux

Table B.313: skeletalDissolvedIronConcEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.35 verticalAlgaeSnowEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeSnowLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalAlgaeSnowEdgeFlux

Table B.314: verticalAlgaeSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.36 verticalDOCSnowEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCSnowLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalDOC-SnowEdgeFlux
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Table B.315: verticalDOCSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.37 verticalDICSnowEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICSnowLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalDIC-SnowEdgeFlux

Table B.316: verticalDICSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.38 verticalDONSnowEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONSnowLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalDON-SnowEdgeFlux

Table B.317: verticalDONSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.39 verticalNitrateSnowEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalNitrateS-nowEdgeFlux

Table B.318: verticalNitrateSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.40 verticalSilicateSnowEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalSilicateSnowEdgeFlux

Table B.319: verticalSilicateSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.41 verticalAmmoniumSnowEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalAmmoniumSnowEdgeFlux

Table B.320: verticalAmmoniumSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.42 verticalDMSSnowEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalDMSSnowEdgeFlux

Table B.321: verticalDMSSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.43 verticalDMSPpSnowEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalDMSPp-SnowEdgeFlux
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Table B.322: verticalDMSPpSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.44 verticalDMSPdSnowEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalDM-SPdSnowEdgeFlux

Table B.323: verticalDMSPdSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.45 verticalNonreactiveSnowEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalNonreactiveSnowEdgeFlux

Table B.324: verticalNonreactiveSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.46 verticalHumicsSnowEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalHumicsSnowEdgeFlux

Table B.325: verticalHumicsSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.47 [verticalParticulateIronSnowEdgeFlux](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronSnowLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalParticulateIronSnowEdgeFlux

Table B.326: verticalParticulateIronSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.48 [verticalDissolvedIronSnowEdgeFlux](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronSnowLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalDissolvedIronSnowEdgeFlux

Table B.327: verticalDissolvedIronSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.49 [verticalAlgaeIceEdgeFlux](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeIceLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalAlgaeIceEdgeFlux

Table B.328: verticalAlgaeIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.50 [verticalDOCIceEdgeFlux](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCIceLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalDOCIceEdgeFlux
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Table B.329: verticalDOCIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.51 verticalDICIceEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICIceLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalDICIceEdgeFlux

Table B.330: verticalDICIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.52 verticalDONIceEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONIceLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalDONIceEdgeFlux

Table B.331: verticalDONIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.53 verticalNitrateIceEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalNitrateIceEdgeFlux

Table B.332: verticalNitrateIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.54 verticalSilicateIceEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalSilicateIceEdgeFlux

Table B.333: verticalSilicateIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.55 verticalAmmoniumIceEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalAmmoniumIceEdgeFlux

Table B.334: verticalAmmoniumIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.56 verticalDMSIceEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalDMSIceEdgeFlux

Table B.335: verticalDMSIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.57 verticalDMSPpIceEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalDMSPpIceEdgeFlux
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Table B.336: verticalDMSPpIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.58 verticalDMSPdIceEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalDMSPdIceEdgeFlux

Table B.337: verticalDMSPdIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.59 verticalNonreactiveIceEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalNonreactiveIceEdgeFlux

Table B.338: verticalNonreactiveIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.60 verticalHumicsIceEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalHumicsIceEdgeFlux

Table B.339: verticalHumicsIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.61 verticalParticulateIronIceEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronIceLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalParticulateIronIceEdgeFlux

Table B.340: verticalParticulateIronIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.62 verticalDissolvedIronIceEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronIceLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalDissolvedIronIceEdgeFlux

Table B.341: verticalDissolvedIronIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.63 verticalAerosolsSnowEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsSnowLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalAerosolsSnowEdgeFlux

Table B.342: verticalAerosolsSnowEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.64 verticalAerosolsIceEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsIceLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalAerosolsIceEdgeFlux
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Table B.343: verticalAerosolsIceEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.7.65 verticalSalinityEdgeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayers nCategories nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_edge_fluxes % verticalSalinityEdgeFlux

Table B.344: verticalSalinityEdgeFlux: **MISSING**

B.8 tracer_products

B.8.1 iceAreaCategoryProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % iceAreaCategoryProduct

Table B.345: iceAreaCategoryProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.2 iceVolumeCategoryProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % iceVolumeCategoryProduct

Table B.346: iceVolumeCategoryProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.3 snowVolumeCategoryProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % snowVolumeCategoryProduct

Table B.347: snowVolumeCategoryProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.4 surfaceTemperatureProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % surfaceTemperatureProduct

Table B.348: surfaceTemperatureProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.5 iceEnthalpyProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % iceEnthalpyProduct

Table B.349: iceEnthalpyProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.6 iceSalinityProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % iceSalinityProduct
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Table B.350: iceSalinityProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.7 snowEnthalpyProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % snowEnthalpyProduct

Table B.351: snowEnthalpyProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.8 iceAgeProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % iceAgeProduct

Table B.352: iceAgeProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.9 firstYearIceAreaProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % firstYearIceAreaProduct

Table B.353: firstYearIceAreaProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.10 levelIceAreaProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % levelIceAreaProduct

Table B.354: levelIceAreaProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.11 levelIceVolumeProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % levelIceVolumeProduct

Table B.355: levelIceVolumeProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.12 pondAreaProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % pondAreaProduct

Table B.356: pondAreaProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.13 pondDepthProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % pondDepthProduct

Table B.357: pondDepthProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.14 [pondLidThicknessProduct](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % pondLidThicknessProduct

Table B.358: pondLidThicknessProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.15 [snowScatteringAerosolProduct](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % snowScatteringAerosolProduct

Table B.359: snowScatteringAerosolProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.16 [snowBodyAerosolProduct](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % snowBodyAerosolProduct

Table B.360: snowBodyAerosolProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.17 [iceScatteringAerosolProduct](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % iceScatteringAerosolProduct
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Table B.361: iceScatteringAerosolProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.18 iceBodyAerosolProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % iceBodyAerosolProduct

Table B.362: iceBodyAerosolProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.19 brineFractionProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % brineFractionProduct

Table B.363: brineFractionProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.20 mobileFractionProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % mobileFractionProduct

Table B.364: mobileFractionProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.21 `skeletalAlgaeConcProduct`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % skeletalAlgaeConcProduct

Table B.365: `skeletalAlgaeConcProduct`: **MISSING**

B.8.22 `skeletalDOCConcProduct`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % skeletalDOCConcProduct

Table B.366: `skeletalDOCConcProduct`: **MISSING**

B.8.23 `skeletalDICConcProduct`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDIC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % skeletalDICConcProduct

Table B.367: `skeletalDICConcProduct`: **MISSING**

B.8.24 `skeletalDONConcProduct`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDON nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % skeletalDONConcProduct

Table B.368: skeletalDONConcProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.25 skeletalNitrateConcProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % skeletalNitrateConcProduct

Table B.369: skeletalNitrateConcProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.26 skeletalSilicateConcProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % skeletalSilicateConcProduct

Table B.370: skeletalSilicateConcProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.27 skeletalAmmoniumConcProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % skeletalAmmoniumConcProduct

Table B.371: skeletalAmmoniumConcProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.28 skeletalDMSConcProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % skeletalDMSConcProduct

Table B.372: skeletalDMSConcProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.29 skeletalDMSPpConcProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % skeletalDMSPpConcProduct

Table B.373: skeletalDMSPpConcProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.30 skeletalDMSPdConcProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % skeletalDMSPdConcProduct

Table B.374: skeletalDMSPdConcProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.31 skeletalNonreactiveConcProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % skeletalNonreactiveConcProduct

Table B.375: skeletalNonreactiveConcProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.32 skeletalHumicsConcProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % skeletalHumicsConcProduct

Table B.376: skeletalHumicsConcProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.33 skeletalParticulateIronConcProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % skeletalParticulateIronConcProduct

Table B.377: skeletalParticulateIronConcProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.34 skeletalDissolvedIronConcProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % skeletalDissolvedIronConcProduct

Table B.378: skeletalDissolvedIronConcProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.35 verticalAlgaeSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeSnowLayers nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % verticalAlgaeSnow-Product

Table B.379: verticalAlgaeSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.36 verticalDOCSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % verticalDOCSnow-Product

Table B.380: verticalDOCSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.37 verticalDICSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % verticalDICSnow-Product

Table B.381: verticalDICSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.38 verticalDONSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % verticalDONSnow-Product

Table B.382: verticalDONSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.39 verticalNitrateSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalNitrateSnowProduct

Table B.383: verticalNitrateSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.40 verticalSilicateSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalSilicateSnowProduct

Table B.384: verticalSilicateSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.41 verticalAmmoniumSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalAmmoniumSnowProduct

Table B.385: verticalAmmoniumSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.42 verticalDMSSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalDMSSnowProduct

Table B.386: verticalDMSSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.43 verticalDMSPpSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalDMSPp-SnowProduct

Table B.387: verticalDMSPpSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.44 verticalDMSPdSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalDM-SPdSnowProduct

Table B.388: verticalDMSPdSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.45 verticalNonreactiveSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalNonreactiveSnowProduct

Table B.389: verticalNonreactiveSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.46 verticalHumicsSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalHumicsSnowProduct

Table B.390: verticalHumicsSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.47 verticalParticulateIronSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalParticulateIronSnowProduct

Table B.391: verticalParticulateIronSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.48 verticalDissolvedIronSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalDissolvedIronSnowProduct

Table B.392: verticalDissolvedIronSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.49 verticalAlgaeIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalAlgaeIceProduct

Table B.393: verticalAlgaeIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.50 verticalDOCIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalDOCIceProduct

Table B.394: verticalDOCIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.51 verticalDICIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalDICIceProduct

Table B.395: verticalDICIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.52 verticalDONIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalDONIceProduct

Table B.396: verticalDONIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.53 verticalNitrateIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalNitrateIceProduct

Table B.397: verticalNitrateIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.54 verticalSilicateIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalSilicateIceProduct

Table B.398: verticalSilicateIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.55 verticalAmmoniumIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalAmmoniumIceProduct

Table B.399: verticalAmmoniumIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.56 verticalDMSIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalDMSIceProduct

Table B.400: verticalDMSIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.57 verticalDMSPpIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalDMSPpIce-Product

Table B.401: verticalDMSPpIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.58 verticalDMSPdIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalDMSPdIce-Product

Table B.402: verticalDMSPdIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.59 verticalNonreactiveIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_products % verticalNonreactive-IceProduct

Table B.403: verticalNonreactiveIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.60 verticalHumicsIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % verticalHumicsIceProduct

Table B.404: verticalHumicsIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.61 verticalParticulateIronIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % verticalParticulateIronIceProduct

Table B.405: verticalParticulateIronIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.62 verticalDissolvedIronIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % verticalDissolvedIronIceProduct

Table B.406: verticalDissolvedIronIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.63 verticalAerosolsSnowProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % verticalAerosolsSnowProduct

Table B.407: verticalAerosolsSnowProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.64 verticalAerosolsIceProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % verticalAerosolsIceProduct

Table B.408: verticalAerosolsIceProduct: **MISSING**

B.8.65 verticalSalinityProduct

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_products % verticalSalinityProduct

Table B.409: verticalSalinityProduct: **MISSING**

B.9 tracer_triangles

B.9.1 iceAreaCategoryTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % iceAreaCategoryTriangle

Table B.410: iceAreaCategoryTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.2 iceVolumeCategoryTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % iceVolumeCategoryTriangle

Table B.411: iceVolumeCategoryTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.3 snowVolumeCategoryTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % snowVolumeCategoryTriangle

Table B.412: snowVolumeCategoryTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.4 surfaceTemperatureTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % surfaceTemperatureTriangle

Table B.413: surfaceTemperatureTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.5 iceEnthalpyTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % iceEnthalpyTriangle

Table B.414: iceEnthalpyTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.6 iceSalinityTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % iceSalinityTriangle

Table B.415: iceSalinityTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.7 snowEnthalpyTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % snowEnthalpyTri- angle

Table B.416: snowEnthalpyTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.8 iceAgeTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % iceAgeTriangle

Table B.417: iceAgeTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.9 firstYearIceAreaTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % firstYearIceAreaTriangle
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Table B.418: firstYearIceAreaTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.10 levelIceAreaTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % levelIceAreaTriangle

Table B.419: levelIceAreaTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.11 levelIceVolumeTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % levelIceVolumeTriangle

Table B.420: levelIceVolumeTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.12 pondAreaTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % pondAreaTriangle

Table B.421: pondAreaTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.13 pondDepthTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % pondDepthTriangle

Table B.422: pondDepthTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.14 pondLidThicknessTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % pondLidThicknessTriangle

Table B.423: pondLidThicknessTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.15 snowScatteringAerosolTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % snowScatteringAerosolTriangle

Table B.424: snowScatteringAerosolTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.16 snowBodyAerosolTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % snowBodyAerosolTriangle

Table B.425: snowBodyAerosolTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.17 iceScatteringAerosolTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % iceScat- teringAerosolTriangle

Table B.426: iceScatteringAerosolTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.18 iceBodyAerosolTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % iceBodyAerosolTri- angle

Table B.427: iceBodyAerosolTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.19 brineFractionTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % brineFractionTrian- gle

Table B.428: brineFractionTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.20 `mobileFractionTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % mobileFractionTriangle

Table B.429: `mobileFractionTriangle`: **MISSING**

B.9.21 `skeletalAlgaeConcTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % skeletalAlgaeConcTriangle

Table B.430: `skeletalAlgaeConcTriangle`: **MISSING**

B.9.22 `skeletalDOCConcTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOC nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % skeletalDOCConcTriangle

Table B.431: `skeletalDOCConcTriangle`: **MISSING**

B.9.23 `skeletalDICConcTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDIC nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % skeletalDICConcTriangle

Table B.432: skeletalDICConcTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.24 skeletalDONConcTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDON nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % skeletalDONConcTriangle

Table B.433: skeletalDONConcTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.25 skeletalNitrateConcTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % skeletalNitrateConcTriangle

Table B.434: skeletalNitrateConcTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.26 skeletalSilicateConcTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % skeletalSilicateConcTriangle

Table B.435: skeletalSilicateConcTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.27 [skeletalAmmoniumConcTriangle](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % skeletalAmmonium-ConcTriangle

Table B.436: skeletalAmmoniumConcTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.28 [skeletalDMSConcTriangle](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % skeletalDMSConcTriangle

Table B.437: skeletalDMSConcTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.29 [skeletalDMSPpConcTriangle](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % skeletalDMSPp-ConcTriangle

Table B.438: skeletalDMSPpConcTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.30 [skeletalDMSPdConcTriangle](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % skeletalDMSPd-ConcTriangle
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Table B.439: skeletalDMSPdConcTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.31 skeletalNonreactiveConcTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % skeletalNonreactiveConcTriangle

Table B.440: skeletalNonreactiveConcTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.32 skeletalHumicsConcTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % skeletalHumicsConcTriangle

Table B.441: skeletalHumicsConcTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.33 skeletalParticulateIronConcTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIron nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % skeletalParticulateIronConcTriangle

Table B.442: skeletalParticulateIronConcTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.34 `skeletalDissolvedIronConcTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIron nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % skeletalDis- solvedIronConcTriangle

Table B.443: `skeletalDissolvedIronConcTriangle`: **MISSING**

B.9.35 `verticalAlgaeSnowTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeSnowLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalAlgaeSnow- Triangle

Table B.444: `verticalAlgaeSnowTriangle`: **MISSING**

B.9.36 `verticalDOCSnowTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCSnowLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalDOCSnow- Triangle

Table B.445: `verticalDOCSnowTriangle`: **MISSING**

B.9.37 `verticalDICSnowTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING

Dimension:	nDICSnowLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalDICSnow- Triangle

Table B.446: verticalDICSnowTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.38 verticalDONSnowTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONSnowLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalDONSnow- Triangle

Table B.447: verticalDONSnowTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.39 verticalNitrateSnowTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalNitrateSnow- Triangle

Table B.448: verticalNitrateSnowTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.40 verticalSilicateSnowTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalSilicateSnow- Triangle

Table B.449: verticalSilicateSnowTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.41 verticalAmmoniumSnowTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalAmmonium-SnowTriangle

Table B.450: verticalAmmoniumSnowTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.42 verticalDMSSnowTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalDMSSnow-Triangle

Table B.451: verticalDMSSnowTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.43 verticalDMSPpSnowTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalDMSPp-SnowTriangle

Table B.452: verticalDMSPpSnowTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.44 verticalDMSPdSnowTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % verticalDM-SPdSnowTriangle

Table B.453: verticalDMSPdSnowTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.45 verticalNonreactiveSnowTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % verticalNonreactiveSnowTriangle

Table B.454: verticalNonreactiveSnowTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.46 verticalHumicsSnowTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % verticalHumicsSnowTriangle

Table B.455: verticalHumicsSnowTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.47 verticalParticulateIronSnowTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronSnowLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_triangles % verticalParticulateIronSnowTriangle

Table B.456: verticalParticulateIronSnowTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.48 `verticalDissolvedIronSnowTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronSnowLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalDis- solvedIronSnowTriangle

Table B.457: `verticalDissolvedIronSnowTriangle`: **MISSING**

B.9.49 `verticalAlgaeIceTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeIceLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalAlgaeIceTri- angle

Table B.458: `verticalAlgaeIceTriangle`: **MISSING**

B.9.50 `verticalDOCIceTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCIceLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalDOCIceTri- angle

Table B.459: `verticalDOCIceTriangle`: **MISSING**

B.9.51 `verticalDICIceTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICIceLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalDICIceTri- angle

Table B.460: verticalDICIceTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.52 verticalDONIceTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONIceLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalDONIceTri- angle

Table B.461: verticalDONIceTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.53 verticalNitrateIceTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalNitrateIce- Triangle

Table B.462: verticalNitrateIceTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.54 verticalSilicateIceTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalSilicateIceTriangle

Table B.463: verticalSilicateIceTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.55 verticalAmmoniumIceTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalAmmoniumIceTriangle

Table B.464: verticalAmmoniumIceTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.56 verticalDMSIceTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalDMSIceTriangle

Table B.465: verticalDMSIceTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.57 verticalDMSPpIceTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalDMSPpIceTriangle

Table B.466: verticalDMSPpIceTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.58 verticalDMSPdIceTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalDMSPdIce- Triangle

Table B.467: verticalDMSPdIceTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.59 verticalNonreactiveIceTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalNonreactive- IceTriangle

Table B.468: verticalNonreactiveIceTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.60 verticalHumicsIceTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalHumicsIce- Triangle

Table B.469: verticalHumicsIceTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.61 verticalParticulateIronIceTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronIceLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalParticulateIronIceTriangle

Table B.470: verticalParticulateIronIceTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.62 verticalDissolvedIronIceTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronIceLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalDissolvedIronIceTriangle

Table B.471: verticalDissolvedIronIceTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.63 verticalAerosolsSnowTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsSnowLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalAerosolsSnowTriangle

Table B.472: verticalAerosolsSnowTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.64 verticalAerosolsIceTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsIceLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalAerosolsIceTriangle

Table B.473: verticalAerosolsIceTriangle: **MISSING**

B.9.65 verticalSalinityTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayers nCategories nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_triangles % verticalSalinityTriangle

Table B.474: verticalSalinityTriangle: **MISSING**

B.10 tracer_barycenter

B.10.1 iceAreaCategoryBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % iceAreaCategoryBarycenterx

Table B.475: iceAreaCategoryBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.2 iceAreaCategoryBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % iceAreaCategoryBarycentery

Table B.476: iceAreaCategoryBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.3 iceVolumeCategoryBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % iceVolumeCategoryBarycenterx

Table B.477: iceVolumeCategoryBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.4 iceVolumeCategoryBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % iceVolumeCategoryBarycentery

Table B.478: iceVolumeCategoryBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.5 snowVolumeCategoryBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % snowVolumeCategoryBarycenterx

Table B.479: snowVolumeCategoryBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.6 snowVolumeCategoryBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % snowVolumeCategoryBarycentery

Table B.480: snowVolumeCategoryBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.7 surfaceTemperatureBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % surfaceTemperatureBarycenterx

Table B.481: surfaceTemperatureBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.8 surfaceTemperatureBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % surfaceTemperatureBarycentery

Table B.482: surfaceTemperatureBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.9 iceEnthalpyBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % iceEnthalpyBarycenterx

Table B.483: iceEnthalpyBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.10 iceEnthalpyBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % iceEnthalpy-Barycentery

Table B.484: iceEnthalpyBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.11 iceSalinityBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % iceSalinity-Barycenterx

Table B.485: iceSalinityBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.12 iceSalinityBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % iceSalinity-Barycentery

Table B.486: iceSalinityBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.13 snowEnthalpyBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % snowEnthalpyBarycenterx
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Table B.487: snowEnthalpyBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.14 snowEnthalpyBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % snowEnthalpyBarycentery

Table B.488: snowEnthalpyBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.15 iceAgeBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % iceAgeBarycenterx

Table B.489: iceAgeBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.16 iceAgeBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % iceAgeBarycentery

Table B.490: iceAgeBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.17 firstYearIceAreaBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % firstYearIceAreaBarycenterx

Table B.491: firstYearIceAreaBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.18 firstYearIceAreaBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % firstYearIceAreaBarycentery

Table B.492: firstYearIceAreaBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.19 levelIceAreaBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % levelIceAreaBarycenterx

Table B.493: levelIceAreaBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.20 levelIceAreaBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % levelIceAreaBarycentery

Table B.494: levelIceAreaBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.21 levelIceVolumeBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % levelIceVolumeBarycenterx

Table B.495: levelIceVolumeBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.22 levelIceVolumeBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % levelIceVolumeBarycentery

Table B.496: levelIceVolumeBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.23 pondAreaBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % pondAreaBarycenterx

Table B.497: pondAreaBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.24 pondAreaBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % pondAreaBarycenter

Table B.498: pondAreaBarycenter: **MISSING**

B.10.25 pondDepthBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % pondDepthBarycenterx

Table B.499: pondDepthBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.26 pondDepthBarycenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % pondDepthBarycenter

Table B.500: pondDepthBarycenter: **MISSING**

B.10.27 pondLidThicknessBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % pondLidThicknessBarycenterx

Table B.501: pondLidThicknessBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.28 [pondLidThicknessBarycentery](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % pondLidThicknessBarycentery

Table B.502: pondLidThicknessBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.29 [snowScatteringAerosolBarycenterx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % snowScatteringAerosolBarycenterx

Table B.503: snowScatteringAerosolBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.30 [snowScatteringAerosolBarycentery](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % snowScatteringAerosolBarycentery

Table B.504: snowScatteringAerosolBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.31 [snowBodyAerosolBarycenterx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % snowBodyAerosolBarycenterx
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Table B.505: snowBodyAerosolBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.32 snowBodyAerosolBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % snowBodyAerosolBarycentery

Table B.506: snowBodyAerosolBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.33 iceScatteringAerosolBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % iceScatteringAerosolBarycenterx

Table B.507: iceScatteringAerosolBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.34 iceScatteringAerosolBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % iceScatteringAerosolBarycentery

Table B.508: iceScatteringAerosolBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.35 iceBodyAerosolBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % iceBodyAerosolBarycenterx

Table B.509: iceBodyAerosolBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.36 iceBodyAerosolBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % iceBodyAerosolBarycentery

Table B.510: iceBodyAerosolBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.37 brineFractionBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % brineFractionBarycenterx

Table B.511: brineFractionBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.38 brineFractionBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % brineFractionBarycentery
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Table B.512: brineFractionBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.39 [mobileFractionBarycenterx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % mobileFractionBarycenterx

Table B.513: mobileFractionBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.40 [mobileFractionBarycentery](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % mobileFractionBarycentery

Table B.514: mobileFractionBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.41 [skeletalAlgaeConcBarycenterx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalAlgaeConcBarycenterx

Table B.515: skeletalAlgaeConcBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.42 [skeletalAlgaeConcBarycentery](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalAlgaeConcBarycentery

Table B.516: skeletalAlgaeConcBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.43 [skeletalDOCConcBarycenterx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalDOCConcBarycenterx

Table B.517: skeletalDOCConcBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.44 [skeletalDOCConcBarycentery](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalDOCConcBarycentery

Table B.518: skeletalDOCConcBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.45 [skeletalDICConcBarycenterx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDIC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalDIC-ConcBarycenterx
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Table B.519: skeletalDICConcBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.46 skeletalDICConcBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDIC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalDIC-ConcBarycentery

Table B.520: skeletalDICConcBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.47 skeletalDONConcBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDON nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalDONConcBarycenterx

Table B.521: skeletalDONConcBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.48 skeletalDONConcBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDON nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalDONConcBarycentery

Table B.522: skeletalDONConcBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.49 [skeletalNitrateConcBarycenterx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalNitrate-ConcBarycenterx

Table B.523: skeletalNitrateConcBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.50 [skeletalNitrateConcBarycentery](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalNitrate-ConcBarycentery

Table B.524: skeletalNitrateConcBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.51 [skeletalSilicateConcBarycenterx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalSilicate-ConcBarycenterx

Table B.525: skeletalSilicateConcBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.52 [skeletalSilicateConcBarycentery](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalSilicateConcBarycentery
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Table B.526: skeletalSilicateConcBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.53 skeletalAmmoniumConcBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalAmmoniumConcBarycenterx

Table B.527: skeletalAmmoniumConcBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.54 skeletalAmmoniumConcBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalAmmoniumConcBarycentery

Table B.528: skeletalAmmoniumConcBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.55 skeletalDMSConcBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalDMSConcBarycenterx

Table B.529: skeletalDMSConcBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.56 `skeletalDMSConcBarycentery`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalDMSConcBarycentery

Table B.530: `skeletalDMSConcBarycentery`: **MISSING**

B.10.57 `skeletalDMSPpConcBarycenterx`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalDMSPpConcBarycenterx

Table B.531: `skeletalDMSPpConcBarycenterx`: **MISSING**

B.10.58 `skeletalDMSPpConcBarycentery`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalDMSPpConcBarycentery

Table B.532: `skeletalDMSPpConcBarycentery`: **MISSING**

B.10.59 `skeletalDMSPdConcBarycenterx`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalDMSPd-ConcBarycenterx
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Table B.533: skeletalDMSPdConcBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.60 skeletalDMSPdConcBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalDMSPd-ConcBarycentery

Table B.534: skeletalDMSPdConcBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.61 skeletalNonreactiveConcBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalNonreactiveConcBarycenterx

Table B.535: skeletalNonreactiveConcBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.62 skeletalNonreactiveConcBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalNonreactiveConcBarycentery

Table B.536: skeletalNonreactiveConcBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.63 skeletalHumicsConcBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalHumicsConcBarycenterx

Table B.537: skeletalHumicsConcBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.64 skeletalHumicsConcBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalHumicsConcBarycentery

Table B.538: skeletalHumicsConcBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.65 skeletalParticulateIronConcBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalParticulateIronConcBarycenterx

Table B.539: skeletalParticulateIronConcBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.66 skeletalParticulateIronConcBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalParticulateIronConcBarycentery
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Table B.540: skeletalParticulateIronConcBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.67 skeletalDissolvedIronConcBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalDissolvedIronConcBarycenterx

Table B.541: skeletalDissolvedIronConcBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.68 skeletalDissolvedIronConcBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % skeletalDissolvedIronConcBarycentery

Table B.542: skeletalDissolvedIronConcBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.69 verticalAlgaeSnowBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalAlgaeSnowBarycenterx

Table B.543: verticalAlgaeSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.70 verticalAlgaeSnowBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalAlgaeSnowBarycentery

Table B.544: verticalAlgaeSnowBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.71 verticalDOCSnowBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDOCSnowBarycenterx

Table B.545: verticalDOCSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.72 verticalDOCSnowBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDOCSnowBarycentery

Table B.546: verticalDOCSnowBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.73 verticalDICSnowBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDICSnowBarycenterx
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Table B.547: verticalDICSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.74 verticalDICSnowBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDICSnowBarycentery

Table B.548: verticalDICSnowBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.75 verticalDONSnowBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDONSnowBarycenterx

Table B.549: verticalDONSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.76 verticalDONSnowBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDONSnowBarycentery

Table B.550: verticalDONSnowBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.77 [verticalNitrateSnowBarycenterx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalNitrateSnowBarycenterx

Table B.551: verticalNitrateSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.78 [verticalNitrateSnowBarycentery](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalNitrateSnowBarycentery

Table B.552: verticalNitrateSnowBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.79 [verticalSilicateSnowBarycenterx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalSilicateSnowBarycenterx

Table B.553: verticalSilicateSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.80 [verticalSilicateSnowBarycentery](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalSilicateSnowBarycentery
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Table B.554: verticalSilicateSnowBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.81 verticalAmmoniumSnowBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalAmmoniumSnowBarycenterx

Table B.555: verticalAmmoniumSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.82 verticalAmmoniumSnowBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalAmmoniumSnowBarycentery

Table B.556: verticalAmmoniumSnowBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.83 verticalDMSSnowBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDMSSnowBarycenterx

Table B.557: verticalDMSSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.84 verticalDMSSnowBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDMSSnow-Barycentery

Table B.558: verticalDMSSnowBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.85 verticalDMSPpSnowBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDMSPp-SnowBarycenterx

Table B.559: verticalDMSPpSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.86 verticalDMSPpSnowBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDMSPp-SnowBarycentery

Table B.560: verticalDMSPpSnowBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.87 verticalDMSPdSnowBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDM-SPdSnowBarycenterx
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Table B.561: verticalDMSPdSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.88 verticalDMSPdSnowBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDM-SPdSnowBarycentery

Table B.562: verticalDMSPdSnowBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.89 verticalNonreactiveSnowBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalNonreactiveSnowBarycenterx

Table B.563: verticalNonreactiveSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.90 verticalNonreactiveSnowBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalNonreactiveSnowBarycentery

Table B.564: verticalNonreactiveSnowBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.91 verticalHumicsSnowBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalHumicsSnowBarycenterx

Table B.565: verticalHumicsSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.92 verticalHumicsSnowBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalHumicsSnowBarycentery

Table B.566: verticalHumicsSnowBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.93 verticalParticulateIronSnowBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalParticulateIronSnowBarycenterx

Table B.567: verticalParticulateIronSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.94 verticalParticulateIronSnowBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalParticulateIronSnowBarycentery
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Table B.568: verticalParticulateIronSnowBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.95 verticalDissolvedIronSnowBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDissolvedIronSnowBarycenterx

Table B.569: verticalDissolvedIronSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.96 verticalDissolvedIronSnowBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDissolvedIronSnowBarycentery

Table B.570: verticalDissolvedIronSnowBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.97 verticalAlgaeIceBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalAlgaeIceBarycenterx

Table B.571: verticalAlgaeIceBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.98 verticalAlgaeIceBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalAlgaeIceBarycentery

Table B.572: verticalAlgaeIceBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.99 verticalDOCIceBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDOCIceBarycenterx

Table B.573: verticalDOCIceBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.100 verticalDOCIceBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDOCIceBarycentery

Table B.574: verticalDOCIceBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.101 verticalDICIceBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDICIceBarycenterx
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Table B.575: verticalDICIceBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.102 verticalDICIceBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDICIceBarycentery

Table B.576: verticalDICIceBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.103 verticalDONIceBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDONIceBarycenterx

Table B.577: verticalDONIceBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.104 verticalDONIceBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDONIceBarycentery

Table B.578: verticalDONIceBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.105 verticalNitrateIceBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalNitrateIceBarycenterx

Table B.579: verticalNitrateIceBarycenterx: **MISSING****B.10.106 verticalNitrateIceBarycentery**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalNitrateIceBarycentery

Table B.580: verticalNitrateIceBarycentery: **MISSING****B.10.107 verticalSilicateIceBarycenterx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalSilicateIceBarycenterx

Table B.581: verticalSilicateIceBarycenterx: **MISSING****B.10.108 verticalSilicateIceBarycentery**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalSilicateIceBarycentery
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Table B.582: verticalSilicateIceBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.109 verticalAmmoniumIceBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalAmmoniumIceBarycenterx

Table B.583: verticalAmmoniumIceBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.110 verticalAmmoniumIceBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalAmmoniumIceBarycentery

Table B.584: verticalAmmoniumIceBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.111 verticalDMSIceBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDMSIceBarycenterx

Table B.585: verticalDMSIceBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.112 verticalDMSIceBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDMSIceBarycentery

Table B.586: verticalDMSIceBarycentery: **MISSING****B.10.113 verticalDMSPpIceBarycenterx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDMSPpIceBarycenterx

Table B.587: verticalDMSPpIceBarycenterx: **MISSING****B.10.114 verticalDMSPpIceBarycentery**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDMSPpIceBarycentery

Table B.588: verticalDMSPpIceBarycentery: **MISSING****B.10.115 verticalDMSPdIceBarycenterx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDM-SPdIceBarycenterx
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Table B.589: verticalDMSPdIceBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.116 verticalDMSPdIceBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDM-SPdIceBarycentery

Table B.590: verticalDMSPdIceBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.117 verticalNonreactiveIceBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalNonreactiveIceBarycenterx

Table B.591: verticalNonreactiveIceBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.118 verticalNonreactiveIceBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalNonreactiveIceBarycentery

Table B.592: verticalNonreactiveIceBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.119 verticalHumicsIceBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalHumicsIceBarycenterx

Table B.593: verticalHumicsIceBarycenterx: **MISSING****B.10.120 verticalHumicsIceBarycentery**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalHumicsIceBarycentery

Table B.594: verticalHumicsIceBarycentery: **MISSING****B.10.121 verticalParticulateIronIceBarycenterx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalParticulateIronIceBarycenterx

Table B.595: verticalParticulateIronIceBarycenterx: **MISSING****B.10.122 verticalParticulateIronIceBarycentery**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalParticulateIronIceBarycentery
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Table B.596: verticalParticulateIronIceBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.123 verticalDissolvedIronIceBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDissolvedIronIceBarycenterx

Table B.597: verticalDissolvedIronIceBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.124 verticalDissolvedIronIceBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalDissolvedIronIceBarycentery

Table B.598: verticalDissolvedIronIceBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.10.125 verticalAerosolsSnowBarycenterx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalAerosolsSnowBarycenterx

Table B.599: verticalAerosolsSnowBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.126 verticalAerosolsSnowBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalAerosolsSnowBarycentery

Table B.600: verticalAerosolsSnowBarycentery: **MISSING****B.10.127 verticalAerosolsIceBarycenterx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalAerosolsIceBarycenterx

Table B.601: verticalAerosolsIceBarycenterx: **MISSING****B.10.128 verticalAerosolsIceBarycentery**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalAerosolsIceBarycentery

Table B.602: verticalAerosolsIceBarycentery: **MISSING****B.10.129 verticalSalinityBarycenterx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalSalinityBarycenterx
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Table B.603: verticalSalinityBarycenterx: **MISSING**

B.10.130 verticalSalinityBarycentery

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_barycenter % verticalSalinityBarycentery

Table B.604: verticalSalinityBarycentery: **MISSING**

B.11 tracer_reconstruction

B.11.1 iceAreaCategoryCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceAreaCategoryCenter

Table B.605: iceAreaCategoryCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.2 iceAreaCategoryGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceAreaCategoryGradx

Table B.606: iceAreaCategoryGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.3 iceAreaCategoryGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceAreaCategoryGrady

Table B.607: iceAreaCategoryGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.4 iceVolumeCategoryCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceVolumeCategoryCenter

Table B.608: iceVolumeCategoryCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.5 iceVolumeCategoryGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceVolumeCategoryGradx

Table B.609: iceVolumeCategoryGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.6 iceVolumeCategoryGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceVolumeCategoryGrady

Table B.610: iceVolumeCategoryGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.7 snowVolumeCategoryCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % snowVolumeCategoryCenter

Table B.611: snowVolumeCategoryCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.8 snowVolumeCategoryGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % snowVolumeCategoryGradx

Table B.612: snowVolumeCategoryGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.9 snowVolumeCategoryGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % snowVolumeCategoryGrady

Table B.613: snowVolumeCategoryGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.10 `surfaceTemperatureCenter`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % surfaceTemperatureCenter

Table B.614: `surfaceTemperatureCenter`: **MISSING**

B.11.11 `surfaceTemperatureGradx`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % surfaceTemperatureGradx

Table B.615: `surfaceTemperatureGradx`: **MISSING**

B.11.12 `surfaceTemperatureGrady`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % surfaceTemperatureGrady

Table B.616: `surfaceTemperatureGrady`: **MISSING**

B.11.13 `iceEnthalpyCenter`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceEnthalpyCenter
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Table B.617: iceEnthalpyCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.14 iceEnthalpyGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceEnthalpyGradx

Table B.618: iceEnthalpyGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.15 iceEnthalpyGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceEnthalpyGrady

Table B.619: iceEnthalpyGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.16 iceSalinityCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceSalinityCenter

Table B.620: iceSalinityCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.17 iceSalinityGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceSalinity-Gradx

Table B.621: iceSalinityGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.18 iceSalinityGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceSalinity-Grady

Table B.622: iceSalinityGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.19 snowEnthalpyCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % snowEnthalpy-Center

Table B.623: snowEnthalpyCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.20 snowEnthalpyGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % snowEnthalpy-Gradx
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Table B.624: snowEnthalpyGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.21 snowEnthalpyGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % snowEnthalpy-Grady

Table B.625: snowEnthalpyGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.22 iceAgeCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceAgeCenter

Table B.626: iceAgeCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.23 iceAgeGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceAgeGradx

Table B.627: iceAgeGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.24 iceAgeGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceAgeGrady

Table B.628: iceAgeGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.25 firstYearIceAreaCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % firstYearIceAreaCenter

Table B.629: firstYearIceAreaCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.26 firstYearIceAreaGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % firstYearIceAreaGradx

Table B.630: firstYearIceAreaGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.27 firstYearIceAreaGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % firstYearIceAreaGrady

Table B.631: firstYearIceAreaGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.28 levelIceAreaCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % levelIceAreaCenter

Table B.632: levelIceAreaCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.29 levelIceAreaGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % levelIceAreaGradx

Table B.633: levelIceAreaGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.30 levelIceAreaGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % levelIceAreaGrady

Table B.634: levelIceAreaGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.31 levelIceVolumeCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % levelIceVolumeCenter

Table B.635: levelIceVolumeCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.32 levelIceVolumeGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % levelIceVolumeGradx

Table B.636: levelIceVolumeGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.33 levelIceVolumeGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % levelIceVolumeGrady

Table B.637: levelIceVolumeGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.34 pondAreaCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % pondAreaCenter

Table B.638: pondAreaCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.35 `pondAreaGradx`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % pondArea-Gradx

Table B.639: `pondAreaGradx`: **MISSING**

B.11.36 `pondAreaGrady`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % pondArea-Grady

Table B.640: `pondAreaGrady`: **MISSING**

B.11.37 `pondDepthCenter`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % pondDepth-Center

Table B.641: `pondDepthCenter`: **MISSING**

B.11.38 `pondDepthGradx`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % pondDepth-Gradx
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Table B.642: pondDepthGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.39 pondDepthGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % pondDepth-Grady

Table B.643: pondDepthGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.40 pondLidThicknessCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % pondLidThick-nessCenter

Table B.644: pondLidThicknessCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.41 pondLidThicknessGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % pondLidThick-nessGradx

Table B.645: pondLidThicknessGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.42 [pondLidThicknessGrady](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % pondLidThicknessGrady

Table B.646: pondLidThicknessGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.43 [snowScatteringAerosolCenter](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % snowScatteringAerosolCenter

Table B.647: snowScatteringAerosolCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.44 [snowScatteringAerosolGradx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % snowScatteringAerosolGradx

Table B.648: snowScatteringAerosolGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.45 [snowScatteringAerosolGrady](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % snowScatteringAerosolGrady
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Table B.649: snowScatteringAerosolGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.46 snowBodyAerosolCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % snowBodyAerosolCenter

Table B.650: snowBodyAerosolCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.47 snowBodyAerosolGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % snowBodyAerosolGradx

Table B.651: snowBodyAerosolGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.48 snowBodyAerosolGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % snowBodyAerosolGrady

Table B.652: snowBodyAerosolGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.49 iceScatteringAerosolCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceScatteringAerosolCenter

Table B.653: iceScatteringAerosolCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.50 iceScatteringAerosolGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceScatteringAerosolGradx

Table B.654: iceScatteringAerosolGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.51 iceScatteringAerosolGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % iceScatteringAerosolGrady

Table B.655: iceScatteringAerosolGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.52 iceBodyAerosolCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % ice-BodyAerosolCenter
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Table B.656: iceBodyAerosolCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.53 iceBodyAerosolGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % ice-BodyAerosolGradx

Table B.657: iceBodyAerosolGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.54 iceBodyAerosolGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % ice-BodyAerosolGrady

Table B.658: iceBodyAerosolGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.55 brineFractionCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % brineFractionCenter

Table B.659: brineFractionCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.56 `brineFractionGradx`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % brineFractionGradx

Table B.660: `brineFractionGradx`: **MISSING**

B.11.57 `brineFractionGrady`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % brineFractionGrady

Table B.661: `brineFractionGrady`: **MISSING**

B.11.58 `mobileFractionCenter`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % mobileFractionCenter

Table B.662: `mobileFractionCenter`: **MISSING**

B.11.59 `mobileFractionGradx`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % mobileFractionGradx

Table B.663: mobileFractionGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.60 mobileFractionGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % mobileFractionGrady

Table B.664: mobileFractionGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.61 skeletalAlgaeConcCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalAlgaeConcCenter

Table B.665: skeletalAlgaeConcCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.62 skeletalAlgaeConcGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalAlgaeConcGradx

Table B.666: skeletalAlgaeConcGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.63 skeletalAlgaeConcGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalAlgaeConcGrady

Table B.667: skeletalAlgaeConcGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.64 skeletalDOCConcCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDOCConcCenter

Table B.668: skeletalDOCConcCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.65 skeletalDOCConcGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDOCConcGradx

Table B.669: skeletalDOCConcGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.66 skeletalDOCConcGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDOCConcGrady

Table B.670: skeletalDOCConcGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.67 [skeletalDICConcCenter](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDIC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDIC-ConcCenter

Table B.671: skeletalDICConcCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.68 [skeletalDICConcGradx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDIC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDIC-ConcGradx

Table B.672: skeletalDICConcGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.69 [skeletalDICConcGrady](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDIC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDIC-ConcGrady

Table B.673: skeletalDICConcGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.70 [skeletalDONConcCenter](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDON nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDON-ConcCenter

Table B.674: skeletalDONConcCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.71 skeletalDONConcGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDON nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDON-ConcGradx

Table B.675: skeletalDONConcGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.72 skeletalDONConcGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDON nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDON-ConcGrady

Table B.676: skeletalDONConcGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.73 skeletalNitrateConcCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalNitrateConcCenter

Table B.677: skeletalNitrateConcCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.74 [skeletalNitrateConcGradx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalNitrateConcGradx

Table B.678: skeletalNitrateConcGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.75 [skeletalNitrateConcGrady](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalNitrateConcGrady

Table B.679: skeletalNitrateConcGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.76 [skeletalSilicateConcCenter](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalSilicateConcCenter

Table B.680: skeletalSilicateConcCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.77 [skeletalSilicateConcGradx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalSilicateConcGradx

Table B.681: skeletalSilicateConcGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.78 skeletalSilicateConcGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalSilicateConcGrady

Table B.682: skeletalSilicateConcGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.79 skeletalAmmoniumConcCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalAmmoniumConcCenter

Table B.683: skeletalAmmoniumConcCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.80 skeletalAmmoniumConcGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalAmmoniumConcGradx

Table B.684: skeletalAmmoniumConcGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.81 skeletalAmmoniumConcGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalAmmoniumConcGrady

Table B.685: skeletalAmmoniumConcGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.82 skeletalDMSConcCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDMSConcCenter

Table B.686: skeletalDMSConcCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.83 skeletalDMSConcGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDMSConcGradx

Table B.687: skeletalDMSConcGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.84 skeletalDMSConcGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDMSConcGrady

Table B.688: skeletalDMSConcGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.85 `skeletalDMSPpConcCenter`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDM-SPpConcCenter

Table B.689: skeletalDMSPpConcCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.86 `skeletalDMSPpConcGradx`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDM-SPpConcGradx

Table B.690: skeletalDMSPpConcGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.87 `skeletalDMSPpConcGrady`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDM-SPpConcGrady

Table B.691: skeletalDMSPpConcGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.88 `skeletalDMSPdConcCenter`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDM-SPdConcCenter

Table B.692: skeletalDMSPdConcCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.89 skeletalDMSPdConcGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDM-SPdConcGradx

Table B.693: skeletalDMSPdConcGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.90 skeletalDMSPdConcGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDM-SPdConcGrady

Table B.694: skeletalDMSPdConcGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.91 skeletalNonreactiveConcCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalNonreactiveConcCenter

Table B.695: skeletalNonreactiveConcCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.92 skeletalNonreactiveConcGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalNonreactiveConcGradx

Table B.696: skeletalNonreactiveConcGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.93 skeletalNonreactiveConcGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalNonreactiveConcGrady

Table B.697: skeletalNonreactiveConcGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.94 skeletalHumicsConcCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalHumicsConcCenter

Table B.698: skeletalHumicsConcCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.95 skeletalHumicsConcGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalHumicsConcGradx

Table B.699: skeletalHumicsConcGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.96 skeletalHumicsConcGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalHumicsConcGrady

Table B.700: skeletalHumicsConcGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.97 skeletalParticulateIronConcCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalParticulateIronConcCenter

Table B.701: skeletalParticulateIronConcCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.98 skeletalParticulateIronConcGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalParticulateIronConcGradx

Table B.702: skeletalParticulateIronConcGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.99 skeletalParticulateIronConcGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalParticulateIronConcGrady

Table B.703: skeletalParticulateIronConcGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.100 skeletalDissolvedIronConcCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDissolvedIronConcCenter

Table B.704: skeletalDissolvedIronConcCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.101 skeletalDissolvedIronConcGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDissolvedIronConcGradx

Table B.705: skeletalDissolvedIronConcGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.102 skeletalDissolvedIronConcGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % skeletalDissolvedIronConcGrady

Table B.706: skeletalDissolvedIronConcGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.103 verticalAlgaeSnowCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAlgaeSnowCenter

Table B.707: verticalAlgaeSnowCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.104 verticalAlgaeSnowGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAlgaeSnowGradx

Table B.708: verticalAlgaeSnowGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.105 verticalAlgaeSnowGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAlgaeSnowGrady

Table B.709: verticalAlgaeSnowGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.106 verticalDOCSnowCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCSnowLayers nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDOC-SnowCenter

Table B.710: verticalDOCSnowCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.107 verticalDOCSnowGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDOC-SnowGradx

Table B.711: verticalDOCSnowGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.108 verticalDOCSnowGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDOC-SnowGrady

Table B.712: verticalDOCSnowGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.109 verticalDICSnowCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDIC-SnowCenter

Table B.713: verticalDICSnowCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.110 verticalDICSnowGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDIC-SnowGradx

Table B.714: verticalDICSnowGradx: **MISSING****B.11.111 verticalDICSnowGrady**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDIC-SnowGrady

Table B.715: verticalDICSnowGrady: **MISSING****B.11.112 verticalDONSnowCenter**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDON-SnowCenter

Table B.716: verticalDONSnowCenter: **MISSING****B.11.113 verticalDONSnowGradx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDON-SnowGradx

Table B.717: verticalDONSnowGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.114 verticalDONSnowGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDON-SnowGrady

Table B.718: verticalDONSnowGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.115 verticalNitrateSnowCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalNitrateSnowCenter

Table B.719: verticalNitrateSnowCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.116 verticalNitrateSnowGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalNitrateSnowGradx

Table B.720: verticalNitrateSnowGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.117 verticalNitrateSnowGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalNitrateSnowGrady

Table B.721: verticalNitrateSnowGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.118 [verticalSilicateSnowCenter](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalSilicateSnowCenter

Table B.722: verticalSilicateSnowCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.119 [verticalSilicateSnowGradx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalSilicateSnowGradx

Table B.723: verticalSilicateSnowGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.120 [verticalSilicateSnowGrady](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalSilicateSnowGrady

Table B.724: verticalSilicateSnowGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.121 verticalAmmoniumSnowCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAmmoniumSnowCenter

Table B.725: verticalAmmoniumSnowCenter: **MISSING****B.11.122 verticalAmmoniumSnowGradx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAmmoniumSnowGradx

Table B.726: verticalAmmoniumSnowGradx: **MISSING****B.11.123 verticalAmmoniumSnowGrady**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAmmoniumSnowGrady

Table B.727: verticalAmmoniumSnowGrady: **MISSING****B.11.124 verticalDMSSnowCenter**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDMSSnowCenter

Table B.728: verticalDMSSnowCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.125 verticalDMSSnowGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDMSSnowGradx

Table B.729: verticalDMSSnowGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.126 verticalDMSSnowGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDMSSnowGrady

Table B.730: verticalDMSSnowGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.127 verticalDMSPpSnowCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDMSPpSnowCenter

Table B.731: verticalDMSPpSnowCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.128 verticalDMSPpSnowGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDM-SPpSnowGradx

Table B.732: verticalDMSPpSnowGradx: **MISSING****B.11.129 verticalDMSPpSnowGrady**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDM-SPpSnowGrady

Table B.733: verticalDMSPpSnowGrady: **MISSING****B.11.130 verticalDMSPdSnowCenter**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDM-SPdSnowCenter

Table B.734: verticalDMSPdSnowCenter: **MISSING****B.11.131 verticalDMSPdSnowGradx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDM-SPdSnowGradx

Table B.735: verticalDMSPdSnowGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.132 verticalDMSPdSnowGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDM-SPdSnowGrady

Table B.736: verticalDMSPdSnowGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.133 verticalNonreactiveSnowCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalNonre-activeSnowCenter

Table B.737: verticalNonreactiveSnowCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.134 verticalNonreactiveSnowGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalNonre-activeSnowGradx

Table B.738: verticalNonreactiveSnowGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.135 verticalNonreactiveSnowGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalNonre- activeSnowGrady

Table B.739: verticalNonreactiveSnowGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.136 [verticalHumicsSnowCenter](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalHumic- sSnowCenter

Table B.740: verticalHumicsSnowCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.137 [verticalHumicsSnowGradx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalHumic- sSnowGradx

Table B.741: verticalHumicsSnowGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.138 [verticalHumicsSnowGrady](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalHumic- sSnowGrady

Table B.742: verticalHumicsSnowGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.139 verticalParticulateIronSnowCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalParticulateIronSnowCenter

Table B.743: verticalParticulateIronSnowCenter: **MISSING****B.11.140 verticalParticulateIronSnowGradx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalParticulateIronSnowGradx

Table B.744: verticalParticulateIronSnowGradx: **MISSING****B.11.141 verticalParticulateIronSnowGrady**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalParticulateIronSnowGrady

Table B.745: verticalParticulateIronSnowGrady: **MISSING****B.11.142 verticalDissolvedIronSnowCenter**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDissolvedIronSnowCenter

Table B.746: verticalDissolvedIronSnowCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.143 verticalDissolvedIronSnowGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDissolvedIronSnowGradx

Table B.747: verticalDissolvedIronSnowGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.144 verticalDissolvedIronSnowGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDissolvedIronSnowGrady

Table B.748: verticalDissolvedIronSnowGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.145 verticalAlgaeIceCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAlgaeIceCenter

Table B.749: verticalAlgaeIceCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.146 verticalAlgaeIceGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAlgaeIceGradx

Table B.750: verticalAlgaeIceGradx: **MISSING****B.11.147 verticalAlgaeIceGrady**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAlgaeIceGrady

Table B.751: verticalAlgaeIceGrady: **MISSING****B.11.148 verticalDOCIceCenter**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDOCIceCenter

Table B.752: verticalDOCIceCenter: **MISSING****B.11.149 verticalDOCIceGradx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDOCIceGradx

Table B.753: verticalDOCIceGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.150 verticalDOCIceGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDOCIceGrady

Table B.754: verticalDOCIceGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.151 verticalDICIceCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDICIceCenter

Table B.755: verticalDICIceCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.152 verticalDICIceGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDICIceGradx

Table B.756: verticalDICIceGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.153 verticalDICIceGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICELayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDICEGrady

Table B.757: verticalDICEGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.154 **verticalDONIceCenter**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDONIceCenter

Table B.758: verticalDONIceCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.155 **verticalDONIceGradx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDONIceGradx

Table B.759: verticalDONIceGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.156 **verticalDONIceGrady**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDONIceGrady

Table B.760: verticalDONIceGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.157 verticalNitrateIceCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalNitrateIceCenter

Table B.761: verticalNitrateIceCenter: **MISSING****B.11.158 verticalNitrateIceGradx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalNitrateIceGradx

Table B.762: verticalNitrateIceGradx: **MISSING****B.11.159 verticalNitrateIceGrady**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalNitrateIceGrady

Table B.763: verticalNitrateIceGrady: **MISSING****B.11.160 verticalSilicateIceCenter**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalSilicateIceCenter

Table B.764: verticalSilicateIceCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.161 verticalSilicateIceGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalSilicateIceGradx

Table B.765: verticalSilicateIceGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.162 verticalSilicateIceGrady

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalSilicateIceGrady

Table B.766: verticalSilicateIceGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.163 verticalAmmoniumIceCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAmmoniumIceCenter

Table B.767: verticalAmmoniumIceCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.164 verticalAmmoniumIceGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAmmoniumIceGradx

Table B.768: verticalAmmoniumIceGradx: **MISSING****B.11.165 verticalAmmoniumIceGrady**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAmmoniumIceGrady

Table B.769: verticalAmmoniumIceGrady: **MISSING****B.11.166 verticalDMSIceCenter**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDMSIceCenter

Table B.770: verticalDMSIceCenter: **MISSING****B.11.167 verticalDMSIceGradx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDMSIceGradx

Table B.771: verticalDMSIceGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.168 `verticalDMSIceGrady`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDM-SIceGrady

Table B.772: verticalDMSIceGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.169 `verticalDMSPpIceCenter`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDM-SPpIceCenter

Table B.773: verticalDMSPpIceCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.170 `verticalDMSPpIceGradx`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDM-SPpIceGradx

Table B.774: verticalDMSPpIceGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.171 `verticalDMSPpIceGrady`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDM-SPpIceGrady

Table B.775: verticalDMSPpIceGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.172 [verticalDMSPdIceCenter](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDM-SPdIceCenter

Table B.776: verticalDMSPdIceCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.173 [verticalDMSPdIceGradx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDM-SPdIceGradx

Table B.777: verticalDMSPdIceGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.174 [verticalDMSPdIceGrady](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDM-SPdIceGrady

Table B.778: verticalDMSPdIceGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.175 verticalNonreactiveIceCenter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalNonreactiveIceCenter

Table B.779: verticalNonreactiveIceCenter: **MISSING****B.11.176 verticalNonreactiveIceGradx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalNonreactiveIceGradx

Table B.780: verticalNonreactiveIceGradx: **MISSING****B.11.177 verticalNonreactiveIceGrady**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalNonreactiveIceGrady

Table B.781: verticalNonreactiveIceGrady: **MISSING****B.11.178 verticalHumicsIceCenter**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalHumicsIceCenter

Table B.782: verticalHumicsIceCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.179 [verticalHumicsIceGradx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalHumicsIceGradx

Table B.783: verticalHumicsIceGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.180 [verticalHumicsIceGrady](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalHumicsIceGrady

Table B.784: verticalHumicsIceGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.181 [verticalParticulateIronIceCenter](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalParticulateIronIceCenter

Table B.785: verticalParticulateIronIceCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.182 verticalParticulateIronIceGradx

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalParticulateIronIceGradx

Table B.786: verticalParticulateIronIceGradx: **MISSING****B.11.183 verticalParticulateIronIceGrady**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalParticulateIronIceGrady

Table B.787: verticalParticulateIronIceGrady: **MISSING****B.11.184 verticalDissolvedIronIceCenter**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDissolvedIronIceCenter

Table B.788: verticalDissolvedIronIceCenter: **MISSING****B.11.185 verticalDissolvedIronIceGradx**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDissolvedIronIceGradx

Table B.789: verticalDissolvedIronIceGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.186 [verticalDissolvedIronIceGrady](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalDissolvedIronIceGrady

Table B.790: verticalDissolvedIronIceGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.187 [verticalAerosolsSnowCenter](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAerosolsSnowCenter

Table B.791: verticalAerosolsSnowCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.188 [verticalAerosolsSnowGradx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAerosolsSnowGradx

Table B.792: verticalAerosolsSnowGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.189 [verticalAerosolsSnowGrady](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAerosolsSnowGrady

Table B.793: verticalAerosolsSnowGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.190 [verticalAerosolsIceCenter](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAerosolsIceCenter

Table B.794: verticalAerosolsIceCenter: **MISSING**

B.11.191 [verticalAerosolsIceGradx](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAerosolsIceGradx

Table B.795: verticalAerosolsIceGradx: **MISSING**

B.11.192 [verticalAerosolsIceGrady](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalAerosolsIceGrady

Table B.796: verticalAerosolsIceGrady: **MISSING**

B.11.193 `verticalSalinityCenter`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalSalinityCenter

Table B.797: `verticalSalinityCenter`: **MISSING**

B.11.194 `verticalSalinityGradx`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalSalinityGradx

Table B.798: `verticalSalinityGradx`: **MISSING**

B.11.195 `verticalSalinityGrady`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_reconstruction % verticalSalinityGrady

Table B.799: `verticalSalinityGrady`: **MISSING**

B.12 `tracer_conservation`

B.12.1 `iceAreaCategoryCons`

Type:	real
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Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % iceAreaCategoryCons

Table B.800: iceAreaCategoryCons: **MISSING**

B.12.2 iceVolumeCategoryCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % iceVolumeCategoryCons

Table B.801: iceVolumeCategoryCons: **MISSING**

B.12.3 snowVolumeCategoryCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % snowVolumeCategoryCons

Table B.802: snowVolumeCategoryCons: **MISSING**

B.12.4 surfaceTemperatureCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % surfaceTemperatureCons

Table B.803: surfaceTemperatureCons: **MISSING**

B.12.5 iceEnthalpyCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % iceEnthalpyCons

Table B.804: iceEnthalpyCons: **MISSING**

B.12.6 iceSalinityCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % iceSalinityCons

Table B.805: iceSalinityCons: **MISSING**

B.12.7 snowEnthalpyCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % snowEnthalpyCons

Table B.806: snowEnthalpyCons: **MISSING**

B.12.8 iceAgeCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % iceAgeCons

Table B.807: iceAgeCons: **MISSING**

B.12.9 firstYearIceAreaCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % firstYearIceAreaCons

Table B.808: firstYearIceAreaCons: **MISSING**

B.12.10 levelIceAreaCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % levelIceAreaCons

Table B.809: levelIceAreaCons: **MISSING**

B.12.11 levelIceVolumeCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % levelIceVolumeCons

Table B.810: levelIceVolumeCons: **MISSING**

B.12.12 `pondAreaCons`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % pondAreaCons

Table B.811: `pondAreaCons`: **MISSING**

B.12.13 `pondDepthCons`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % pondDepthCons

Table B.812: `pondDepthCons`: **MISSING**

B.12.14 `pondLidThicknessCons`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % pondLidThicknessCons

Table B.813: `pondLidThicknessCons`: **MISSING**

B.12.15 `snowScatteringAerosolCons`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % snowScatteringAerosolCons
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Table B.814: snowScatteringAerosolCons: **MISSING**

B.12.16 snowBodyAerosolCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % snowBodyAerosolCons

Table B.815: snowBodyAerosolCons: **MISSING**

B.12.17 iceScatteringAerosolCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % iceScatteringAerosolCons

Table B.816: iceScatteringAerosolCons: **MISSING**

B.12.18 iceBodyAerosolCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % iceBodyAerosolCons

Table B.817: iceBodyAerosolCons: **MISSING**

B.12.19 [brineFractionCons](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % brineFractionCons

Table B.818: brineFractionCons: **MISSING**

B.12.20 [mobileFractionCons](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % mobileFractionCons

Table B.819: mobileFractionCons: **MISSING**

B.12.21 [skeletalAlgaeConcCons](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % skeletalAlgaeConcCons

Table B.820: skeletalAlgaeConcCons: **MISSING**

B.12.22 [skeletalDOCConcCons](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOC nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % skeletalDOCConcCons

Table B.821: skeletalDOCConcCons: **MISSING**

B.12.23 skeletalDICConcCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDIC nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % skeletalDICConcCons

Table B.822: skeletalDICConcCons: **MISSING**

B.12.24 skeletalDONConcCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDON nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % skeletalDONConcCons

Table B.823: skeletalDONConcCons: **MISSING**

B.12.25 skeletalNitrateConcCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % skeletalNitrateConcCons

Table B.824: skeletalNitrateConcCons: **MISSING**

B.12.26 skeletalSilicateConcCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % skeletalSilicateConcCons

Table B.825: skeletalSilicateConcCons: **MISSING**

B.12.27 skeletalAmmoniumConcCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % skeletalAmmoniumConcCons

Table B.826: skeletalAmmoniumConcCons: **MISSING**

B.12.28 skeletalDMSConcCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % skeletalDMSConcCons

Table B.827: skeletalDMSConcCons: **MISSING**

B.12.29 skeletalDMSPpConcCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % skeletalDMSPpConcCons

Table B.828: skeletalDMSPpConcCons: **MISSING**

B.12.30 skeletalDMSPdConcCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % skeletalDMSPdConcCons

Table B.829: skeletalDMSPdConcCons: **MISSING**

B.12.31 skeletalNonreactiveConcCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % skeletalNonreactiveConcCons

Table B.830: skeletalNonreactiveConcCons: **MISSING**

B.12.32 skeletalHumicsConcCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % skeletalHumicsConcCons

Table B.831: skeletalHumicsConcCons: **MISSING**

B.12.33 skeletalParticulateIronConcCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIron nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % skeletalParticulateIronConcCons

Table B.832: skeletalParticulateIronConcCons: **MISSING**

B.12.34 skeletalDissolvedIronConcCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIron nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % skeletalDissolvedIronConcCons

Table B.833: skeletalDissolvedIronConcCons: **MISSING**

B.12.35 verticalAlgaeSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeSnowLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalAlgaeSnowCons

Table B.834: verticalAlgaeSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.36 verticalDOCSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCSnowLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalDOCSnowCons

Table B.835: verticalDOCSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.37 verticalDICSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICSnowLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time.levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalDICSnowCons

Table B.836: verticalDICSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.38 verticalDONSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONSnowLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time.levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalDONSnowCons

Table B.837: verticalDONSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.39 verticalNitrateSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time.levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalNitrateSnowCons

Table B.838: verticalNitrateSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.40 verticalSilicateSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalSilicateSnowCons

Table B.839: verticalSilicateSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.41 verticalAmmoniumSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalAmmoniumSnowCons

Table B.840: verticalAmmoniumSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.42 verticalDMSSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalDMSSnowCons

Table B.841: verticalDMSSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.43 verticalDMSPpSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalDMSPpSnowCons

Table B.842: verticalDMSPpSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.44 verticalDMSPdSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalDMSPdSnowCons

Table B.843: verticalDMSPdSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.45 verticalNonreactiveSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalNonreactiveSnowCons

Table B.844: verticalNonreactiveSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.46 verticalHumicsSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalHumicsSnowCons

Table B.845: verticalHumicsSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.47 verticalParticulateIronSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronSnowLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalParticulateIronSnowCons

Table B.846: verticalParticulateIronSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.48 verticalDissolvedIronSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronSnowLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalDissolvedIronSnowCons

Table B.847: verticalDissolvedIronSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.49 verticalAlgaeIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeIceLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalAlgaeIceCons

Table B.848: verticalAlgaeIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.50 verticalDOCIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCIceLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalDOCIceCons

Table B.849: verticalDOCIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.51 verticalDICIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICIceLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalDICIceCons

Table B.850: verticalDICIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.52 verticalDONIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONIceLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalDONIceCons

Table B.851: verticalDONIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.53 verticalNitrateIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalNitrateIceCons

Table B.852: verticalNitrateIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.54 verticalSilicateIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalSilicateIceCons

Table B.853: verticalSilicateIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.55 verticalAmmoniumIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalAmmoniumIceCons

Table B.854: verticalAmmoniumIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.56 verticalDMSIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalDMSIceCons

Table B.855: verticalDMSIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.57 verticalDMSPpIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalDMSPpIceCons

Table B.856: verticalDMSPpIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.58 verticalDMSPdIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalDMSPdIceCons

Table B.857: verticalDMSPdIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.59 verticalNonreactiveIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalNonreactiveIceCons

Table B.858: verticalNonreactiveIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.60 verticalHumicsIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalHumicsIceCons

Table B.859: verticalHumicsIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.61 verticalParticulateIronIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronIceLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalParticulateIronIceCons

Table B.860: verticalParticulateIronIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.62 verticalDissolvedIronIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronIceLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalDissolvedIronIceCons

Table B.861: verticalDissolvedIronIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.63 verticalAerosolsSnowCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsSnowLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalAerosolsSnowCons

Table B.862: verticalAerosolsSnowCons: **MISSING**

B.12.64 verticalAerosolsIceCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsIceLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalAerosolsIceCons

Table B.863: verticalAerosolsIceCons: **MISSING**

B.12.65 verticalSalinityCons

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayers nCategories
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_conservation % time_levs(:) % tracer_conservation % verticalSalinityCons
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Table B.864: verticalSalinityCons: **MISSING**

B.13 **tracer_monotonicity**

B.13.1 **iceAreaCategoryLocalMin**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % iceAreaCategoryLocalMin

Table B.865: iceAreaCategoryLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.2 **iceAreaCategoryLocalMax**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % iceAreaCategoryLocalMax

Table B.866: iceAreaCategoryLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.3 **iceVolumeCategoryLocalMin**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % iceVolumeCategoryLocalMin

Table B.867: iceVolumeCategoryLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.4 iceVolumeCategoryLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % iceVolumeCategoryLocalMax

Table B.868: iceVolumeCategoryLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.5 snowVolumeCategoryLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % snowVolumeCategoryLocalMin

Table B.869: snowVolumeCategoryLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.6 snowVolumeCategoryLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % snowVolumeCategoryLocalMax

Table B.870: snowVolumeCategoryLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.7 surfaceTemperatureLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % surfaceTemperatureLocalMin

Table B.871: surfaceTemperatureLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.8 surfaceTemperatureLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % surfaceTemperatureLocalMax

Table B.872: surfaceTemperatureLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.9 iceEnthalpyLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % iceEnthalpyLocalMin

Table B.873: iceEnthalpyLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.10 iceEnthalpyLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % iceEnthalpyLocalMax

Table B.874: iceEnthalpyLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.11 iceSalinityLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % iceSalinityLocalMin

Table B.875: iceSalinityLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.12 iceSalinityLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % iceSalinityLocalMax

Table B.876: iceSalinityLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.13 snowEnthalpyLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % snowEnthalpyLocalMin

Table B.877: snowEnthalpyLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.14 snowEnthalpyLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % snowEnthalpyLocalMax
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Table B.878: snowEnthalpyLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.15 iceAgeLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % iceAgeLocalMin

Table B.879: iceAgeLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.16 iceAgeLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % iceAgeLocalMax

Table B.880: iceAgeLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.17 firstYearIceAreaLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % firstYearIceAreaLocalMin

Table B.881: firstYearIceAreaLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.18 firstYearIceAreaLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % firstYearIceAreaLocalMax

Table B.882: firstYearIceAreaLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.19 levelIceAreaLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % levelIceAreaLocalMin

Table B.883: levelIceAreaLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.20 levelIceAreaLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % levelIceAreaLocalMax

Table B.884: levelIceAreaLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.21 levelIceVolumeLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % levelIceVolumeLocalMin

Table B.885: levelIceVolumeLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.22 levelIceVolumeLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % levelIceVolumeLocalMax

Table B.886: levelIceVolumeLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.23 pondAreaLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % pondAreaLocalMin

Table B.887: pondAreaLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.24 pondAreaLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % pondAreaLocalMax

Table B.888: pondAreaLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.25 pondDepthLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % pondDepthLocalMin

Table B.889: pondDepthLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.26 **pondDepthLocalMax**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % pondDepthLocalMax

Table B.890: pondDepthLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.27 **pondLidThicknessLocalMin**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % pondLidThicknessLocalMin

Table B.891: pondLidThicknessLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.28 **pondLidThicknessLocalMax**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % pondLidThicknessLocalMax

Table B.892: pondLidThicknessLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.29 snowScatteringAerosolLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % snowScatteringAerosolLocalMin

Table B.893: snowScatteringAerosolLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.30 snowScatteringAerosolLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % snowScatteringAerosolLocalMax

Table B.894: snowScatteringAerosolLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.31 snowBodyAerosolLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % snowBodyAerosolLocalMin

Table B.895: snowBodyAerosolLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.32 snowBodyAerosolLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % snow-BodyAerosolLocalMax
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Table B.896: snowBodyAerosolLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.33 iceScatteringAerosolLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % iceScatteringAerosolLocalMin

Table B.897: iceScatteringAerosolLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.34 iceScatteringAerosolLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % iceScatteringAerosolLocalMax

Table B.898: iceScatteringAerosolLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.35 iceBodyAerosolLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % ice-BodyAerosolLocalMin

Table B.899: iceBodyAerosolLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.36 iceBodyAerosolLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % ice- BodyAerosolLocalMax

Table B.900: iceBodyAerosolLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.37 brineFractionLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % brineFraction- LocalMin

Table B.901: brineFractionLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.38 brineFractionLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % brineFraction- LocalMax

Table B.902: brineFractionLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.39 mobileFractionLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % mobileFraction- LocalMin

Table B.903: mobileFractionLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.40 mobileFractionLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % mobileFractionLocalMax

Table B.904: mobileFractionLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.41 skeletalAlgaeConcLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalAlgaeConcLocalMin

Table B.905: skeletalAlgaeConcLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.42 skeletalAlgaeConcLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalAlgaeConcLocalMax

Table B.906: skeletalAlgaeConcLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.43 skeletalDOCConcLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalDOC-ConcLocalMin

Table B.907: skeletalDOCConcLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.44 skeletalDOCConcLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalDOC-ConcLocalMax

Table B.908: skeletalDOCConcLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.45 skeletalDICConcLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDIC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalDIC-ConcLocalMin

Table B.909: skeletalDICConcLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.46 skeletalDICConcLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDIC nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalDIC-ConcLocalMax

Table B.910: skeletalDICConcLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.47 skeletalDONConcLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDON nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalDON-ConcLocalMin

Table B.911: skeletalDONConcLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.48 skeletalDONConcLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDON nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalDON-ConcLocalMax

Table B.912: skeletalDONConcLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.49 skeletalNitrateConcLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalNitrate-ConcLocalMin

Table B.913: skeletalNitrateConcLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.50 skeletalNitrateConcLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalNitrate-ConcLocalMax

Table B.914: skeletalNitrateConcLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.51 skeletalSilicateConcLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalSilicate-ConcLocalMin

Table B.915: skeletalSilicateConcLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.52 skeletalSilicateConcLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalSilicate-ConcLocalMax

Table B.916: skeletalSilicateConcLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.53 skeletalAmmoniumConcLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalAmmoniumConcLocalMin

Table B.917: skeletalAmmoniumConcLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.54 skeletalAmmoniumConcLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalAmmoniumConcLocalMax

Table B.918: skeletalAmmoniumConcLocalMax: **MISSING****B.13.55 skeletalDMSConcLocalMin**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalDMSConcLocalMin

Table B.919: skeletalDMSConcLocalMin: **MISSING****B.13.56 skeletalDMSConcLocalMax**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalDMSConcLocalMax

Table B.920: skeletalDMSConcLocalMax: **MISSING****B.13.57 skeletalDMSPpConcLocalMin**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalDMSP-pConcLocalMin
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Table B.921: skeletalDMSPpConcLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.58 skeletalDMSPpConcLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalDMSP-pConcLocalMax

Table B.922: skeletalDMSPpConcLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.59 skeletalDMSPdConcLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalDMSPd-ConcLocalMin

Table B.923: skeletalDMSPdConcLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.60 skeletalDMSPdConcLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalDMSPd-ConcLocalMax

Table B.924: skeletalDMSPdConcLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.61 skeletalNonreactiveConcLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalNonreactiveConcLocalMin

Table B.925: skeletalNonreactiveConcLocalMin: **MISSING****B.13.62 skeletalNonreactiveConcLocalMax**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalNonreactiveConcLocalMax

Table B.926: skeletalNonreactiveConcLocalMax: **MISSING****B.13.63 skeletalHumicsConcLocalMin**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalHumicsConcLocalMin

Table B.927: skeletalHumicsConcLocalMin: **MISSING****B.13.64 skeletalHumicsConcLocalMax**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	ONE nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalHumicsConcLocalMax

Table B.928: skeletalHumicsConcLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.65 skeletalParticulateIronConcLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalParticulateIronConcLocalMin

Table B.929: skeletalParticulateIronConcLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.66 skeletalParticulateIronConcLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nParticulateIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalParticulateIronConcLocalMax

Table B.930: skeletalParticulateIronConcLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.67 skeletalDissolvedIronConcLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalDissolvedIronConcLocalMin

Table B.931: skeletalDissolvedIronConcLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.68 skeletalDissolvedIronConcLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDissolvedIron nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % skeletalDissolvedIronConcLocalMax

Table B.932: skeletalDissolvedIronConcLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.69 verticalAlgaeSnowLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalAlgaeSnowLocalMin

Table B.933: verticalAlgaeSnowLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.70 verticalAlgaeSnowLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalAlgaeSnowLocalMax

Table B.934: verticalAlgaeSnowLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.71 verticalDOCSnowLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDOC-SnowLocalMin

Table B.935: verticalDOCSnowLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.72 verticalDOCSnowLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDOC-SnowLocalMax

Table B.936: verticalDOCSnowLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.73 verticalDICSnowLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDIC-SnowLocalMin

Table B.937: verticalDICSnowLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.74 verticalDICSnowLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDIC-SnowLocalMax

Table B.938: verticalDICSnowLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.75 verticalDONSnowLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONSnowLayers nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDON-SnowLocalMin

Table B.939: verticalDONSnowLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.76 verticalDONSnowLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDON-SnowLocalMax

Table B.940: verticalDONSnowLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.77 verticalNitrateSnowLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalNitrateSnowLocalMin

Table B.941: verticalNitrateSnowLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.78 verticalNitrateSnowLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalNitrateSnowLocalMax

Table B.942: verticalNitrateSnowLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.79 verticalSilicateSnowLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalSilicateSnowLocalMin

Table B.943: verticalSilicateSnowLocalMin: **MISSING****B.13.80 verticalSilicateSnowLocalMax**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalSilicateSnowLocalMax

Table B.944: verticalSilicateSnowLocalMax: **MISSING****B.13.81 verticalAmmoniumSnowLocalMin**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalAmmoniumSnowLocalMin

Table B.945: verticalAmmoniumSnowLocalMin: **MISSING****B.13.82 verticalAmmoniumSnowLocalMax**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalAmmoniumSnowLocalMax

Table B.946: verticalAmmoniumSnowLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.83 verticalDMSSnowLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDMSSnowLocalMin

Table B.947: verticalDMSSnowLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.84 verticalDMSSnowLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDMSSnowLocalMax

Table B.948: verticalDMSSnowLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.85 verticalDMSPpSnowLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDMSPpSnowLocalMin

Table B.949: verticalDMSPpSnowLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.86 verticalDMSPpSnowLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDMSPp-SnowLocalMax

Table B.950: verticalDMSPpSnowLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.87 [verticalDMSPdSnowLocalMin](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDM-SPdSnowLocalMin

Table B.951: verticalDMSPdSnowLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.88 [verticalDMSPdSnowLocalMax](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDM-SPdSnowLocalMax

Table B.952: verticalDMSPdSnowLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.89 [verticalNonreactiveSnowLocalMin](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalNonre- activeSnowLocalMin

Table B.953: verticalNonreactiveSnowLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.90 [verticalNonreactiveSnowLocalMax](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalNonre- activeSnowLocalMax

Table B.954: verticalNonreactiveSnowLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.91 [verticalHumicsSnowLocalMin](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalHumic- sSnowLocalMin

Table B.955: verticalHumicsSnowLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.92 [verticalHumicsSnowLocalMax](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalHumic- sSnowLocalMax

Table B.956: verticalHumicsSnowLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.93 [verticalParticulateIronSnowLocalMin](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalParticulateIronSnowLocalMin

Table B.957: verticalParticulateIronSnowLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.94 verticalParticulateIronSnowLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalParticulateIronSnowLocalMax

Table B.958: verticalParticulateIronSnowLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.95 verticalDissolvedIronSnowLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDissolvedIronSnowLocalMin

Table B.959: verticalDissolvedIronSnowLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.96 verticalDissolvedIronSnowLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDissolvedIronSnowLocalMax

Table B.960: verticalDissolvedIronSnowLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.97 verticalAlgaeIceLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalAlgaeIceLocalMin

Table B.961: verticalAlgaeIceLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.98 verticalAlgaeIceLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgaeIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalAlgaeIceLocalMax

Table B.962: verticalAlgaeIceLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.99 verticalDOCIceLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDOCIceLocalMin

Table B.963: verticalDOCIceLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.100 verticalDOCIceLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDOCIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDOCIceLocalMax

Table B.964: verticalDOCIceLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.101 verticalDICIceLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDICIceLocalMin

Table B.965: verticalDICIceLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.102 verticalDICIceLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDICIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDICIceLocalMax

Table B.966: verticalDICIceLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.103 verticalDONIceLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDONIceLocalMin

Table B.967: verticalDONIceLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.104 verticalDONIceLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDONIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDON-IceLocalMax

Table B.968: verticalDONIceLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.105 verticalNitrateIceLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalNitrate-IceLocalMin

Table B.969: verticalNitrateIceLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.106 verticalNitrateIceLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalNitrate-IceLocalMax

Table B.970: verticalNitrateIceLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.107 verticalSilicateIceLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalSilicate-IceLocalMin

Table B.971: verticalSilicateIceLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.108 verticalSilicateIceLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalSilicateIceLocalMax

Table B.972: verticalSilicateIceLocalMax: **MISSING****B.13.109 verticalAmmoniumIceLocalMin**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalAmmoniumIceLocalMin

Table B.973: verticalAmmoniumIceLocalMin: **MISSING****B.13.110 verticalAmmoniumIceLocalMax**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalAmmoniumIceLocalMax

Table B.974: verticalAmmoniumIceLocalMax: **MISSING****B.13.111 verticalDMSIceLocalMin**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDMSIce-LocalMin

Table B.975: verticalDMSIceLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.112 verticalDMSIceLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDMSIce-LocalMax

Table B.976: verticalDMSIceLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.113 verticalDMSPpIceLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDMSP-pIceLocalMin

Table B.977: verticalDMSPpIceLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.114 verticalDMSPpIceLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDMSP-pIceLocalMax

Table B.978: verticalDMSPpIceLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.115 verticalDMSPdIceLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDM-SPdIceLocalMin

Table B.979: verticalDMSPdIceLocalMin: **MISSING****B.13.116 verticalDMSPdIceLocalMax**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDM-SPdIceLocalMax

Table B.980: verticalDMSPdIceLocalMax: **MISSING****B.13.117 verticalNonreactiveIceLocalMin**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalNonre-activeIceLocalMin

Table B.981: verticalNonreactiveIceLocalMin: **MISSING****B.13.118 verticalNonreactiveIceLocalMax**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalNonre-activeIceLocalMax

Table B.982: verticalNonreactiveIceLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.119 verticalHumicsIceLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalHumicsIceLocalMin

Table B.983: verticalHumicsIceLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.120 verticalHumicsIceLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalHumicsIceLocalMax

Table B.984: verticalHumicsIceLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.121 verticalParticulateIronIceLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalParticulateIronIceLocalMin

Table B.985: verticalParticulateIronIceLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.122 verticalParticulateIronIceLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nPartIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalParticulateIronIceLocalMax

Table B.986: verticalParticulateIronIceLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.123 verticalDissolvedIronIceLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDissolvedIronIceLocalMin

Table B.987: verticalDissolvedIronIceLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.124 verticalDissolvedIronIceLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nDisIronIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalDissolvedIronIceLocalMax

Table B.988: verticalDissolvedIronIceLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.13.125 verticalAerosolsSnowLocalMin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalAerosolsSnowLocalMin

Table B.989: verticalAerosolsSnowLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.126 verticalAerosolsSnowLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsSnowLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalAerosolsSnowLocalMax

Table B.990: verticalAerosolsSnowLocalMax: **MISSING****B.13.127 verticalAerosolsIceLocalMin**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalAerosolsIceLocalMin

Table B.991: verticalAerosolsIceLocalMin: **MISSING****B.13.128 verticalAerosolsIceLocalMax**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nzAerosolsIceLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalAerosolsIceLocalMax

Table B.992: verticalAerosolsIceLocalMax: **MISSING****B.13.129 verticalSalinityLocalMin**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayers nCategories nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalSalinityLocalMin

Table B.993: verticalSalinityLocalMin: **MISSING**

B.13.130 verticalSalinityLocalMax

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayers nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % tracer_monotonicity % verticalSalinityLocalMax

Table B.994: verticalSalinityLocalMax: **MISSING**

B.14 rotated_mesh

B.14.1 xCellRotate

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % rotated_mesh % xCellRotate

Table B.995: xCellRotate: **MISSING**

B.14.2 yCellRotate

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % rotated_mesh % yCellRotate

Table B.996: yCellRotate: **MISSING**

B.14.3 zCellRotate

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % rotated_mesh % zCellRotate

Table B.997: zCellRotate: **MISSING**

B.14.4 xVertexRotate

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % rotated_mesh % xVertexRotate

Table B.998: xVertexRotate: **MISSING**

B.14.5 yVertexRotate

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % rotated_mesh % yVertexRotate

Table B.999: yVertexRotate: **MISSING**

B.14.6 zVertexRotate

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % rotated_mesh % zVertexRotate

Table B.1000: zVertexRotate: **MISSING**

B.14.7 `xEdgeRotate`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % rotated_mesh % xEdgeRotate

Table B.1001: `xEdgeRotate`: **MISSING**

B.14.8 `yEdgeRotate`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % rotated_mesh % yEdgeRotate

Table B.1002: `yEdgeRotate`: **MISSING**

B.14.9 `zEdgeRotate`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % rotated_mesh % zEdgeRotate

Table B.1003: `zEdgeRotate`: **MISSING**

B.15 `incremental_remap`

B.15.1 `xTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % xTriangle

Table B.1004: `xTriangle`: **MISSING**

B.15.2 `yTriangle`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nQuadPoints nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % yTriangle

Table B.1005: `yTriangle`: **MISSING**

B.15.3 `iCellTriangle`

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % iCellTriangle

Table B.1006: `iCellTriangle`: **MISSING**

B.15.4 `triangleArea`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nTriPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % triangleArea

Table B.1007: `triangleArea`: **MISSING**

B.15.5 `departurePoint`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % departurePoint

Table B.1008: `departurePoint`: **MISSING**

B.15.6 remapEdge

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % remapEdge

Table B.1009: remapEdge: **MISSING**

B.15.7 cellsOnEdgeRemap

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxCellsPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % cellsOnEdgeRemap

Table B.1010: cellsOnEdgeRemap: **MISSING**

B.15.8 edgesOnEdgeRemap

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdgesPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % edgesOnEdgeRemap

Table B.1011: edgesOnEdgeRemap: **MISSING**

B.15.9 xVertexOnCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % xVertexOnCell
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Table B.1012: xVertexOnCell: **MISSING**

B.15.10 [yVertexOnCell](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % yVertexOnCell

Table B.1013: yVertexOnCell: **MISSING**

B.15.11 [xVertexOnEdge](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxVerticesPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % xVertexOnEdge

Table B.1014: xVertexOnEdge: **MISSING**

B.15.12 [yVertexOnEdge](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxVerticesPerEdgeRemap nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % yVertexOnEdge

Table B.1015: yVertexOnEdge: **MISSING**

B.15.13 [transCellToGlobal](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING

Dimension:	R3 R3 nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % transCellToGlobal

Table B.1016: transCellToGlobal: **MISSING**

B.15.14 [transGlobalToCell](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	R3 R3 nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % transGlobalToCell

Table B.1017: transGlobalToCell: **MISSING**

B.15.15 [transVertexToGlobal](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	R3 R3 nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % transVertexToGlobal

Table B.1018: transVertexToGlobal: **MISSING**

B.15.16 [transGlobalToVertex](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	R3 R3 nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % transGlobalToVertex

Table B.1019: transGlobalToVertex: **MISSING**

B.15.17 `transEdgeToGlobal`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	R3 R3 nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % transEdgeToGlobal

Table B.1020: `transEdgeToGlobal`: **MISSING**

B.15.18 `transGlobalToEdge`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	R3 R3 nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % transGlobal- ToEdge

Table B.1021: `transGlobalToEdge`: **MISSING**

B.15.19 `minLengthEdgesOnVertex`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % min- LengthEdgesOnVertex

Table B.1022: `minLengthEdgesOnVertex`: **MISSING**

B.15.20 `xAvgCell`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % xAvgCell

Table B.1023: xAvgCell: **MISSING**

B.15.21 yAvgCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % yAvgCell

Table B.1024: yAvgCell: **MISSING**

B.15.22 xxAvgCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % xxAvgCell

Table B.1025: xxAvgCell: **MISSING**

B.15.23 xyAvgCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % xyAvgCell

Table B.1026: xyAvgCell: **MISSING**

B.15.24 yyAvgCell

Type:	real
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Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % incremental_remap % yyAvgCell

Table B.1027: yyAvgCell: **MISSING**

B.15.25 xxxAvgCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % incremental_remap % xxxAvgCell

Table B.1028: xxxAvgCell: **MISSING**

B.15.26 xxyAvgCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % incremental_remap % xxyAvgCell

Table B.1029: xxyAvgCell: **MISSING**

B.15.27 xyyAvgCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % incremental_remap % xyyAvgCell

Table B.1030: xyyAvgCell: **MISSING**

B.15.28 [yyyAvgCell](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % yyyAvgCell

Table B.1031: yyyAvgCell: **MISSING**

B.15.29 [xxxxAvgCell](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % xxxxAvgCell

Table B.1032: xxxxAvgCell: **MISSING**

B.15.30 [xxxyAvgCell](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % xxxyAvgCell

Table B.1033: xxxyAvgCell: **MISSING**

B.15.31 [xyyyAvgCell](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % xyyyAvgCell

Table B.1034: xyyyAvgCell: **MISSING**

B.15.32 `xyyyAvgCell`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % xyyyAvgCell

Table B.1035: `xyyyAvgCell`: **MISSING**

B.15.33 `yyyyAvgCell`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % yyyyAvgCell

Table B.1036: `yyyyAvgCell`: **MISSING**

B.15.34 `maskEdge`

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nEdges
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % maskEdge

Table B.1037: `maskEdge`: **MISSING**

B.15.35 `maskCell`

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % incremental_remap % maskCell

Table B.1038: `maskCell`: **MISSING**

B.15.36 maskCategoryCell

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % incremental_remap % maskCategoryCell

Table B.1039: maskCategoryCell: **MISSING**

B.15.37 workCategoryCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % incremental_remap % workCategoryCell

Table B.1040: workCategoryCell: **MISSING**

B.16 forcing

B.16.1 nForcingGroupCounter

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % forcing % nForcingGroupCounter

Table B.1041: nForcingGroupCounter: **MISSING**

B.16.2 forcingGroupNames

Type:	text
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nForcingGroupsMax Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % forcing % forcingGroupNames
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Table B.1042: forcingGroupNames: **MISSING**

B.16.3 forcingGroupRestartTimes

Type:	text
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nForcingGroupsMax Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % forcing % forcingGroupRestartTimes

Table B.1043: forcingGroupRestartTimes: **MISSING**

B.17 atmos_coupling

B.17.1 airLevelHeight

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_coupling % airLevelHeight

Table B.1044: airLevelHeight: **MISSING**

B.17.2 airPotentialTemperature

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_coupling % airPotentialTemperature

Table B.1045: airPotentialTemperature: **MISSING**

B.17.3 airTemperature

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % atmos_coupling % airTemperature

Table B.1046: airTemperature: **MISSING**

B.17.4 airSpecificHumidity

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % atmos_coupling % airSpecificHumidity

Table B.1047: airSpecificHumidity: **MISSING**

B.17.5 airDensity

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % atmos_coupling % airDensity

Table B.1048: airDensity: **MISSING**

B.17.6 shortwaveVisibleDirectDown

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % atmos_coupling % shortwaveVisibleDirectDown

Table B.1049: shortwaveVisibleDirectDown: **MISSING**

B.17.7 `shortwaveVisibleDiffuseDown`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_coupling % shortwaveVisibleD-iffuseDown

Table B.1050: `shortwaveVisibleDiffuseDown`: **MISSING**

B.17.8 `shortwaveIRDirectDown`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_coupling % shortwaveIRDirect-Down

Table B.1051: `shortwaveIRDirectDown`: **MISSING**

B.17.9 `shortwaveIRDiffuseDown`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_coupling % shortwaveIRDiffuse-Down

Table B.1052: `shortwaveIRDiffuseDown`: **MISSING**

B.17.10 `longwaveDown`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_coupling % longwaveDown

Table B.1053: longwaveDown: **MISSING**

B.17.11 rainfallRate

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_coupling % rainfallRate

Table B.1054: rainfallRate: **MISSING**

B.17.12 snowfallRate

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_coupling % snowfallRate

Table B.1055: snowfallRate: **MISSING**

B.17.13 uAirVelocity

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_coupling % uAirVelocity

Table B.1056: uAirVelocity: **MISSING**

B.17.14 vAirVelocity

Type:	real
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Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_coupling % vAirVelocity

Table B.1057: vAirVelocity: **MISSING**

B.17.15 [atmosReferenceSpeed10m](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_coupling % atmosReferenceSpeed10m

Table B.1058: atmosReferenceSpeed10m: **MISSING**

B.17.16 [atmosReferenceTemperature2m](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_coupling % atmosReferenceTemperature2m

Table B.1059: atmosReferenceTemperature2m: **MISSING**

B.17.17 [atmosReferenceHumidity2m](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_coupling % atmosReferenceHumidity2m

Table B.1060: atmosReferenceHumidity2m: **MISSING**

B.18 `atmos_forcing`

B.18.1 `windSpeed`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_forcing % windSpeed

Table B.1061: `windSpeed`: **MISSING**

B.18.2 `uAirStress`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_forcing % uAirStress

Table B.1062: `uAirStress`: **MISSING**

B.18.3 `vAirStress`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_forcing % vAirStress

Table B.1063: `vAirStress`: **MISSING**

B.18.4 `shortwaveDown`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_forcing % shortwaveDown
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Table B.1064: shortwaveDown: **MISSING**

B.18.5 cloudFraction

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_forcing % cloudFraction

Table B.1065: cloudFraction: **MISSING**

B.18.6 sensibleTransferCoefficient

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_forcing % sensibleTransferCoefficient

Table B.1066: sensibleTransferCoefficient: **MISSING**

B.18.7 latentTransferCoefficient

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_forcing % latentTransferCoefficient

Table B.1067: latentTransferCoefficient: **MISSING**

B.19 alternative_atmos_forcing

B.19.1 latentHeatFluxCouple

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % alternative_atmos_forcing % latentHeatFluxCouple

Table B.1068: latentHeatFluxCouple: **MISSING**

B.19.2 sensibleHeatFluxCouple

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % alternative_atmos_forcing % sensibleHeatFluxCouple

Table B.1069: sensibleHeatFluxCouple: **MISSING**

B.19.3 surfaceHeatFluxCouple

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % alternative_atmos_forcing % surfaceHeatFluxCouple

Table B.1070: surfaceHeatFluxCouple: **MISSING**

B.19.4 surfaceConductiveFluxCouple

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % alternative_atmos_forcing % surface-ConductiveFluxCouple

Table B.1071: surfaceConductiveFluxCouple: **MISSING**

B.19.5 [airStressForcingU](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % alternative_atmos_forcing % airStress-ForcingU

Table B.1072: airStressForcingU: **MISSING**

B.19.6 [airStressForcingV](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % alternative_atmos_forcing % airStress-ForcingV

Table B.1073: airStressForcingV: **MISSING**

B.20 [ocean_coupling](#)

B.20.1 [seaSurfaceTemperature](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_coupling % seaSurfaceTemperature

Table B.1074: seaSurfaceTemperature: **MISSING**

B.20.2 seaSurfaceSalinity

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_coupling % seaSurfaceSalinity

Table B.1075: seaSurfaceSalinity: **MISSING**

B.20.3 seaFreezingTemperature

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_coupling % seaFreezingTemperature

Table B.1076: seaFreezingTemperature: **MISSING**

B.20.4 freezingMeltingPotential

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_coupling % freezingMeltingPotential

Table B.1077: freezingMeltingPotential: **MISSING**

B.20.5 uOceanVelocity

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_coupling % uOceanVelocity
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Table B.1078: uOceanVelocity: **MISSING**

B.20.6 vOceanVelocity

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_coupling % vOceanVelocity

Table B.1079: vOceanVelocity: **MISSING**

B.20.7 seaSurfaceTiltU

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_coupling % seaSurfaceTiltU

Table B.1080: seaSurfaceTiltU: **MISSING**

B.20.8 seaSurfaceTiltV

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_coupling % seaSurfaceTiltV

Table B.1081: seaSurfaceTiltV: **MISSING**

B.20.9 oceanMixedLayerDepth

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING

Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_coupling % oceanMixedLayerDepth

Table B.1082: oceanMixedLayerDepth: **MISSING**

B.20.10 oceanHeatFluxConvergence

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_coupling % oceanHeatFluxConvergence

Table B.1083: oceanHeatFluxConvergence: **MISSING**

B.20.11 landIceMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_coupling % landIceMask

Table B.1084: landIceMask: **MISSING**

B.20.12 landIceMaskVertex

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_coupling % landIceMaskVertex

Table B.1085: landIceMaskVertex: **MISSING**

B.21 boundary

B.21.1 interiorVertex

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % boundary % interiorVertex

Table B.1086: interiorVertex: **MISSING**

B.21.2 interiorCell

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % boundary % interiorCell

Table B.1087: interiorCell: **MISSING**

B.21.3 interiorEdge

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nEdges Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % boundary % interiorEdge

Table B.1088: interiorEdge: **MISSING**

B.21.4 blockIDout

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % boundary % blockIDout

Table B.1089: blockIDout: **MISSING**

B.22 velocity_solver

B.22.1 dynamicsTimeStep

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % dynamicsTimeStep

Table B.1090: dynamicsTimeStep: **MISSING**

B.22.2 elasticTimeStep

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % elasticTimeStep

Table B.1091: elasticTimeStep: **MISSING**

B.22.3 uVelocity

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % uVelocity

Table B.1092: uVelocity: **MISSING**

B.22.4 vVelocity

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % velocity_solver % vVelocity
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Table B.1093: vVelocity: **MISSING**

B.22.5 uVelocityInitial

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % velocity_solver % uVelocityInitial

Table B.1094: uVelocityInitial: **MISSING**

B.22.6 vVelocityInitial

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % velocity_solver % vVelocityInitial

Table B.1095: vVelocityInitial: **MISSING**

B.22.7 edgeVelocity

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nEdges Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % velocity_solver % edgeVelocity

Table B.1096: edgeVelocity: **MISSING**

B.22.8 normalVectorEdge

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING

Dimension:	TWO maxEdges nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % normalVectorEdge

Table B.1097: normalVectorEdge: **MISSING**

B.22.9 solveStress

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % solveStress

Table B.1098: solveStress: **MISSING**

B.22.10 solveVelocity

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % solveVelocity

Table B.1099: solveVelocity: **MISSING**

B.22.11 solveVelocityPrevious

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % solveVelocityPrevious

Table B.1100: solveVelocityPrevious: **MISSING**

B.22.12 icePressure

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % icePressure

Table B.1101: icePressure: **MISSING**

B.22.13 [stressDivergenceU](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % stressDivergenceU

Table B.1102: stressDivergenceU: **MISSING**

B.22.14 [stressDivergenceV](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % stressDivergenceV

Table B.1103: stressDivergenceV: **MISSING**

B.22.15 [airStressCellU](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % airStressCellU

Table B.1104: airStressCellU: **MISSING**

B.22.16 `airStressCellV`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % airStressCellV

Table B.1105: `airStressCellV`: **MISSING**

B.22.17 `airStressVertexU`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % airStressVertexU

Table B.1106: `airStressVertexU`: **MISSING**

B.22.18 `airStressVertexV`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % airStressVertexV

Table B.1107: `airStressVertexV`: **MISSING**

B.22.19 `uOceanVelocityVertex`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % uOceanVelocityVertex

Table B.1108: `uOceanVelocityVertex`: **MISSING**

B.22.20 `vOceanVelocityVertex`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % vOceanVelocityVertex

Table B.1109: `vOceanVelocityVertex`: **MISSING**

B.22.21 `oceanStressU`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % oceanStressU

Table B.1110: `oceanStressU`: **MISSING**

B.22.22 `oceanStressV`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % oceanStressV

Table B.1111: `oceanStressV`: **MISSING**

B.22.23 `oceanStressCoeff`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % oceanStressCoeff

Table B.1112: oceanStressCoeff: **MISSING**

B.22.24 oceanStressCellU

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % oceanStressCellU

Table B.1113: oceanStressCellU: **MISSING**

B.22.25 oceanStressCellV

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % oceanStressCellV

Table B.1114: oceanStressCellV: **MISSING**

B.22.26 seaSurfaceTiltVertexU

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % seaSurfaceTiltVertexU

Table B.1115: seaSurfaceTiltVertexU: **MISSING**

B.22.27 seaSurfaceTiltVertexV

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING

Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % seaSurfaceTiltVertexV

Table B.1116: seaSurfaceTiltVertexV: **MISSING**

B.22.28 `surfaceTiltForceU`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % surfaceTiltForceU

Table B.1117: surfaceTiltForceU: **MISSING**

B.22.29 `surfaceTiltForceV`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % surfaceTiltForceV

Table B.1118: surfaceTiltForceV: **MISSING**

B.22.30 `totalMassVertexfVertex`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % totalMassVertexfVertex

Table B.1119: totalMassVertexfVertex: **MISSING**

B.22.31 divergence

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % divergence

Table B.1120: divergence: **MISSING**

B.22.32 shear

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % shear

Table B.1121: shear: **MISSING**

B.22.33 dynamicallyLockedCellsMask

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_solver % dynamicallyLocked-CellsMask

Table B.1122: dynamicallyLockedCellsMask: **MISSING**

B.23 velocity_weak

B.23.1 normalVectorPolygon

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO maxEdges nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_weak % normalVectorPolygon

Table B.1123: normalVectorPolygon: **MISSING**

B.23.2 normalVectorTriangle

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	TWO vertexDegree nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_weak % normalVectorTriangle

Table B.1124: normalVectorTriangle: **MISSING**

B.23.3 latCellRotated

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_weak % latCellRotated

Table B.1125: latCellRotated: **MISSING**

B.23.4 latVertexRotated

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_weak % latVertexRotated

Table B.1126: latVertexRotated: **MISSING**

B.23.5 strain11weak

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_weak % strain11weak

Table B.1127: strain11weak: **MISSING**

B.23.6 strain22weak

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_weak % strain22weak

Table B.1128: strain22weak: **MISSING**

B.23.7 strain12weak

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_weak % strain12weak

Table B.1129: strain12weak: **MISSING**

B.23.8 stress11weak

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_weak % stress11weak

Table B.1130: stress11weak: **MISSING**

B.23.9 stress22weak

Type:	real
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Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_weak % stress22weak

Table B.1131: stress22weak: **MISSING**

B.23.10 [stress12weak](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_weak % stress12weak

Table B.1132: stress12weak: **MISSING**

B.23.11 [principalStress1Weak](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_weak % principalStress1Weak

Table B.1133: principalStress1Weak: **MISSING**

B.23.12 [principalStress2Weak](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_weak % principalStress2Weak

Table B.1134: principalStress2Weak: **MISSING**

B.23.13 replacementPressureWeak

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_weak % replacementPressureWeak

Table B.1135: replacementPressureWeak: **MISSING**

B.24 velocity_variational

B.24.1 strain11var

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_variational % strain11var

Table B.1136: strain11var: **MISSING**

B.24.2 strain22var

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_variational % strain22var

Table B.1137: strain22var: **MISSING**

B.24.3 strain12var

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_variational % strain12var

Table B.1138: strain12var: **MISSING**

B.24.4 stress11var

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_variational % stress11var

Table B.1139: stress11var: **MISSING**

B.24.5 stress22var

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_variational % stress22var

Table B.1140: stress22var: **MISSING**

B.24.6 stress12var

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_variational % stress12var

Table B.1141: stress12var: **MISSING**

B.24.7 tanLatVertexRotatedOverRadius

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % velocity_variational % tanLatVertexRotatedOverRadius

Table B.1142: tanLatVertexRotatedOverRadius: **MISSING**

B.24.8 cellVerticesAtVertex

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	vertexDegree nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % velocity_variational % cellVerticesAtVertex

Table B.1143: cellVerticesAtVertex: **MISSING**

B.24.9 basisIntegralsU

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges maxEdges nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % velocity_variational % basisIntegralsU

Table B.1144: basisIntegralsU: **MISSING**

B.24.10 basisIntegralsV

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges maxEdges nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % velocity_variational % basisIntegralsV

Table B.1145: basisIntegralsV: **MISSING**

B.24.11 `basisIntegralsMetric`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges maxEdges nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_variational % basisIntegralsMetric

Table B.1146: `basisIntegralsMetric`: **MISSING**

B.24.12 `basisGradientU`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges maxEdges nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_variational % basisGradientU

Table B.1147: `basisGradientU`: **MISSING**

B.24.13 `basisGradientV`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges maxEdges nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_variational % basisGradientV

Table B.1148: `basisGradientV`: **MISSING**

B.24.14 `principalStress1Var`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_variational % principalStress1Var

Table B.1149: `principalStress1Var`: **MISSING**

B.24.15 `principalStress2Var`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_variational % principal-Stress2Var

Table B.1150: `principalStress2Var`: **MISSING**

B.24.16 `replacementPressureVar`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxEdges nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % velocity_variational % replacement-PressureVar

Table B.1151: `replacementPressureVar`: **MISSING**

B.25 `ridging`

B.25.1 `ridgeConvergence`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridging % ridgeConvergence

Table B.1152: `ridgeConvergence`: **MISSING**

B.25.2 `ridgeShear`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING

Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridging % ridgeShear

Table B.1153: ridgeShear: **MISSING**

B.25.3 [areaLossRidge](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridging % areaLossRidge

Table B.1154: areaLossRidge: **MISSING**

B.25.4 [areaGainRidge](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridging % areaGainRidge

Table B.1155: areaGainRidge: **MISSING**

B.25.5 [iceVolumeRidged](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridging % iceVolumeRidged

Table B.1156: iceVolumeRidged: **MISSING**

B.25.6 [openingRateRidge](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % ridging % openingRateRidge

Table B.1157: openingRateRidge: **MISSING**

B.25.7 [ridgeParticipationFunction](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % ridging % ridgeParticipationFunction

Table B.1158: ridgeParticipationFunction: **MISSING**

B.25.8 [ratioRidgeThicknessToIce](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % ridging % ratioRidgeThicknessToIce

Table B.1159: ratioRidgeThicknessToIce: **MISSING**

B.25.9 [fractionNewRidgeArea](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % ridging % fractionNewRidgeArea

Table B.1160: fractionNewRidgeArea: **MISSING**

B.25.10 `fractionNewRidgeVolume`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridging % fractionNewRidgeVolume

Table B.1161: `fractionNewRidgeVolume`: **MISSING**

B.25.11 `areaLossRidgeCategory`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridging % areaLossRidgeCategory

Table B.1162: `areaLossRidgeCategory`: **MISSING**

B.25.12 `areaGainRidgeCategory`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridging % areaGainRidgeCategory

Table B.1163: `areaGainRidgeCategory`: **MISSING**

B.25.13 `iceVolumeRidgedCategory`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridging % iceVolumeRidgedCategory

Table B.1164: `iceVolumeRidgedCategory`: **MISSING**

B.25.14 raftingIceArea

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridging % raftingIceArea

Table B.1165: raftingIceArea: **MISSING**

B.25.15 raftingIceVolume

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridging % raftingIceVolume

Table B.1166: raftingIceVolume: **MISSING**

B.26 melt_growth_rates

B.26.1 lateralIceMeltFraction

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % melt_growth_rates % lateralIceMelt-Fraction

Table B.1167: lateralIceMeltFraction: **MISSING**

B.26.2 surfaceIceMelt

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % melt_growth_rates % surfaceIceMelt

Table B.1168: surfaceIceMelt: **MISSING**

B.26.3 surfaceIceMeltCategory

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % melt_growth_rates % surfaceIceMelt-Category

Table B.1169: surfaceIceMeltCategory: **MISSING**

B.26.4 basalIceMelt

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % melt_growth_rates % basalIceMelt

Table B.1170: basalIceMelt: **MISSING**

B.26.5 basalIceMeltCategory

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % melt_growth_rates % basalIceMeltCategory

Table B.1171: basalIceMeltCategory: **MISSING**

B.26.6 lateralIceMelt

Type:	real
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Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % melt_growth_rates % lateralIceMelt

Table B.1172: lateralIceMelt: **MISSING**

B.26.7 snowMelt

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % melt_growth_rates % snowMelt

Table B.1173: snowMelt: **MISSING**

B.26.8 snowMeltCategory

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % melt_growth_rates % snowMeltCategory

Table B.1174: snowMeltCategory: **MISSING**

B.26.9 congelation

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % melt_growth_rates % congelation

Table B.1175: congelation: **MISSING**

B.26.10 `congelationCategory`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % melt_growth_rates % congelationCategory

Table B.1176: `congelationCategory`: **MISSING**

B.26.11 `snowiceFormation`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % melt_growth_rates % snowiceFormation

Table B.1177: `snowiceFormation`: **MISSING**

B.26.12 `snowiceFormationCategory`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % melt_growth_rates % snowiceFormationCategory

Table B.1178: `snowiceFormationCategory`: **MISSING**

B.26.13 `snowThicknessChange`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % melt_growth_rates % snowThicknessChange

Table B.1179: snowThicknessChange: **MISSING**

B.26.14 snowThicknessChangeCategory

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % melt_growth_rates % snowThicknessChangeCategory

Table B.1180: snowThicknessChangeCategory: **MISSING**

B.26.15 frazilFormation

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % melt_growth_rates % frazilFormation

Table B.1181: frazilFormation: **MISSING**

B.26.16 frazilGrowthDiagnostic

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % melt_growth_rates % frazilGrowthDiagnostic

Table B.1182: frazilGrowthDiagnostic: **MISSING**

B.27 `atmos_fluxes`

B.27.1 `surfaceHeatFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % <code>atmos_fluxes</code> % <code>surfaceHeatFlux</code>

Table B.1183: `surfaceHeatFlux`: **MISSING**

B.27.2 `surfaceHeatFluxCategory`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % <code>atmos_fluxes</code> % <code>surfaceHeatFluxCategory</code>

Table B.1184: `surfaceHeatFluxCategory`: **MISSING**

B.27.3 `surfaceConductiveFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % <code>atmos_fluxes</code> % <code>surfaceConductiveFlux</code>

Table B.1185: `surfaceConductiveFlux`: **MISSING**

B.27.4 `surfaceConductiveFluxCategory`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % <code>atmos_fluxes</code> % <code>surfaceConductiveFluxCategory</code>

Table B.1186: surfaceConductiveFluxCategory: **MISSING**

B.27.5 longwaveUp

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_fluxes % longwaveUp

Table B.1187: longwaveUp: **MISSING**

B.27.6 sensibleHeatFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_fluxes % sensibleHeatFlux

Table B.1188: sensibleHeatFlux: **MISSING**

B.27.7 sensibleHeatFluxCategory

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % atmos_fluxes % sensibleHeatFluxCategory

Table B.1189: sensibleHeatFluxCategory: **MISSING**

B.27.8 latentHeatFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING

Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % atmos_fluxes % latentHeatFlux

Table B.1190: latentHeatFlux: **MISSING**

B.27.9 latentHeatFluxCategory

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % atmos_fluxes % latentHeatFluxCategory

Table B.1191: latentHeatFluxCategory: **MISSING**

B.27.10 evaporativeWaterFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % atmos_fluxes % evaporativeWaterFlux

Table B.1192: evaporativeWaterFlux: **MISSING**

B.28 ocean_fluxes

B.28.1 oceanFreshWaterFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_fluxes % oceanFreshWaterFlux

Table B.1193: oceanFreshWaterFlux: **MISSING**

B.28.2 oceanSaltFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_fluxes % oceanSaltFlux

Table B.1194: oceanSaltFlux: **MISSING**

B.28.3 oceanHeatFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_fluxes % oceanHeatFlux

Table B.1195: oceanHeatFlux: **MISSING**

B.28.4 oceanShortwaveFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_fluxes % oceanShortwaveFlux

Table B.1196: oceanShortwaveFlux: **MISSING**

B.28.5 oceanFreshWaterFluxArea

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_fluxes % oceanFreshWater-FluxArea

Table B.1197: oceanFreshWaterFluxArea: **MISSING**

B.28.6 oceanSaltFluxArea

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_fluxes % oceanSaltFluxArea

Table B.1198: oceanSaltFluxArea: **MISSING**

B.28.7 oceanHeatFluxArea

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_fluxes % oceanHeatFluxArea

Table B.1199: oceanHeatFluxArea: **MISSING**

B.28.8 oceanShortwaveFluxArea

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_fluxes % oceanShortwave-FluxArea

Table B.1200: oceanShortwaveFluxArea: **MISSING**

B.28.9 oceanHeatFluxIceBottom

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_fluxes % oceanHeatFluxIceBottom
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Table B.1201: oceanHeatFluxIceBottom: **MISSING**

B.29 ocean_atmosphere

B.29.1 airStressOceanU

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_atmosphere % airStressOceanU

Table B.1202: airStressOceanU: **MISSING**

B.29.2 airStressOceanV

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_atmosphere % airStressOceanV

Table B.1203: airStressOceanV: **MISSING**

B.29.3 atmosReferenceTemperature2mOcean

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_atmosphere % atmosReferenceTemperature2mOcean

Table B.1204: atmosReferenceTemperature2mOcean: **MISSING**

B.29.4 [atmosReferenceHumidity2mOcean](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_atmosphere % atmosReferenceHumidity2mOcean

Table B.1205: atmosReferenceHumidity2mOcean: **MISSING**

B.29.5 [albedoVisibleDirectOcean](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_atmosphere % albedoVisibleDirectOcean

Table B.1206: albedoVisibleDirectOcean: **MISSING**

B.29.6 [albedoVisibleDiffuseOcean](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_atmosphere % albedoVisibleDiffuseOcean

Table B.1207: albedoVisibleDiffuseOcean: **MISSING**

B.29.7 [albedoIRDirectOcean](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_atmosphere % albedoIRDirectOcean

Table B.1208: albedoIRDirectOcean: **MISSING**

B.29.8 albedoIRDiffuseOcean

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_atmosphere % albedoIRDiffuseOcean

Table B.1209: albedoIRDiffuseOcean: **MISSING**

B.29.9 longwaveUpOcean

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_atmosphere % longwaveUpOcean

Table B.1210: longwaveUpOcean: **MISSING**

B.29.10 sensibleHeatFluxOcean

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_atmosphere % sensibleHeatFluxOcean

Table B.1211: sensibleHeatFluxOcean: **MISSING**

B.29.11 latentHeatFluxOcean

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_atmosphere % latentHeatFlux-Ocean

Table B.1212: latentHeatFluxOcean: **MISSING**

B.29.12 evaporativeWaterFluxOcean

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ocean_atmosphere % evaporativeWaterFluxOcean

Table B.1213: evaporativeWaterFluxOcean: **MISSING**

B.30 shortwave

B.30.1 dayOfNextShortwaveCalculation

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % dayOfNextShortwaveCalculation

Table B.1214: dayOfNextShortwaveCalculation: **MISSING**

B.30.2 solarZenithAngleCosine

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % solarZenithAngleCosine
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Table B.1215: solarZenithAngleCosine: **MISSING**

B.30.3 albedoVisibleDirectCategory

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % albedoVisibleDirectCategory

Table B.1216: albedoVisibleDirectCategory: **MISSING**

B.30.4 albedoVisibleDiffuseCategory

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % albedoVisibleDiffuseCategory

Table B.1217: albedoVisibleDiffuseCategory: **MISSING**

B.30.5 albedoIRDirectCategory

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % albedoIRDirectCategory

Table B.1218: albedoIRDirectCategory: **MISSING**

B.30.6 albedoIRDiffuseCategory

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % albedoIRDiffuseCategory

Table B.1219: albedoIRDiffuseCategory: **MISSING**

B.30.7 [albedoVisibleDirectCell](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % albedoVisibleDirectCell

Table B.1220: albedoVisibleDirectCell: **MISSING**

B.30.8 [albedoVisibleDiffuseCell](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % albedoVisibleDiffuseCell

Table B.1221: albedoVisibleDiffuseCell: **MISSING**

B.30.9 [albedoIRDirectCell](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % albedoIRDirectCell

Table B.1222: albedoIRDirectCell: **MISSING**

B.30.10 [albedoIRDiffuseCell](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % albedoIRDiffuseCell

Table B.1223: albedoIRDiffuseCell: **MISSING**

B.30.11 [albedoVisibleDirectArea](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % albedoVisibleDirectArea

Table B.1224: albedoVisibleDirectArea: **MISSING**

B.30.12 [albedoVisibleDiffuseArea](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % albedoVisibleDiffuseArea

Table B.1225: albedoVisibleDiffuseArea: **MISSING**

B.30.13 [albedoIRDirectArea](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % albedoIRDirectArea

Table B.1226: albedoIRDirectArea: **MISSING**

B.30.14 [albedoIRDiffuseArea](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % albedoIRDiffuseArea

Table B.1227: albedoIRDiffuseArea: **MISSING**

B.30.15 [shortwaveScalingFactor](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % shortwaveScalingFactor

Table B.1228: shortwaveScalingFactor: **MISSING**

B.30.16 [surfaceShortwaveFlux](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % surfaceShortwaveFlux

Table B.1229: surfaceShortwaveFlux: **MISSING**

B.30.17 [interiorShortwaveFlux](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % interiorShortwaveFlux

Table B.1230: interiorShortwaveFlux: **MISSING**

B.30.18 `penetratingShortwaveFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % penetratingShortwaveFlux

Table B.1231: `penetratingShortwaveFlux`: **MISSING**

B.30.19 `shortwaveLayerPenetration`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayersP1 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % shortwaveLayerPenetration

Table B.1232: `shortwaveLayerPenetration`: **MISSING**

B.30.20 `absorbedShortwaveFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % absorbedShortwaveFlux

Table B.1233: `absorbedShortwaveFlux`: **MISSING**

B.30.21 `absorbedShortwaveSnowLayer`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % shortwave % absorbedShortwaveSnowLayer

Table B.1234: absorbedShortwaveSnowLayer: **MISSING**

B.30.22 [absorbedShortwaveIceLayer](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % absorbedShortwaveIceLayer

Table B.1235: absorbedShortwaveIceLayer: **MISSING**

B.30.23 [bareIceAlbedoCategory](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % bareIceAlbedoCategory

Table B.1236: bareIceAlbedoCategory: **MISSING**

B.30.24 [snowAlbedoCategory](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % snowAlbedoCategory

Table B.1237: snowAlbedoCategory: **MISSING**

B.30.25 [pondAlbedoCategory](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING

Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % pondAlbedoCategory

Table B.1238: pondAlbedoCategory: **MISSING**

B.30.26 bareIceAlbedoCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % bareIceAlbedoCell

Table B.1239: bareIceAlbedoCell: **MISSING**

B.30.27 snowAlbedoCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % snowAlbedoCell

Table B.1240: snowAlbedoCell: **MISSING**

B.30.28 pondAlbedoCell

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % pondAlbedoCell

Table B.1241: pondAlbedoCell: **MISSING**

B.30.29 effectivePondAreaCategory

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % effectivePondAreaCategory

Table B.1242: effectivePondAreaCategory: **MISSING**

B.30.30 [effectivePondAreaCell](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % effectivePondAreaCell

Table B.1243: effectivePondAreaCell: **MISSING**

B.30.31 [snowFractionCategory](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % shortwave % snowFractionCategory

Table B.1244: snowFractionCategory: **MISSING**

B.31 [drag](#)

B.31.1 [airOceanDragCoefficientRatio](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % drag % airOceanDragCoefficientRatio

Table B.1245: airOceanDragCoefficientRatio: **MISSING**

B.31.2 oceanDragCoefficient

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % drag % oceanDragCoefficient

Table B.1246: oceanDragCoefficient: **MISSING**

B.31.3 oceanDragCoefficientSkin

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % drag % oceanDragCoefficientSkin

Table B.1247: oceanDragCoefficientSkin: **MISSING**

B.31.4 oceanDragCoefficientFloe

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % drag % oceanDragCoefficientFloe

Table B.1248: oceanDragCoefficientFloe: **MISSING**

B.31.5 oceanDragCoefficientKeel

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % drag % oceanDragCoefficientKeel

Table B.1249: oceanDragCoefficientKeel: **MISSING**

B.31.6 `airDragCoefficient`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % drag % airDragCoefficient

Table B.1250: `airDragCoefficient`: **MISSING**

B.31.7 `airDragCoefficientSkin`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % drag % airDragCoefficientSkin

Table B.1251: `airDragCoefficientSkin`: **MISSING**

B.31.8 `airDragCoefficientFloe`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % drag % airDragCoefficientFloe

Table B.1252: `airDragCoefficientFloe`: **MISSING**

B.31.9 `airDragCoefficientPond`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % drag % airDragCoefficientPond

Table B.1253: `airDragCoefficientPond`: **MISSING**

B.31.10 `airDragCoefficientRidge`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % drag % airDragCoefficientRidge

Table B.1254: `airDragCoefficientRidge`: **MISSING**

B.31.11 `dragFreeboard`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % drag % dragFreeboard

Table B.1255: `dragFreeboard`: **MISSING**

B.31.12 `dragIceSnowDraft`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % drag % dragIceSnowDraft

Table B.1256: `dragIceSnowDraft`: **MISSING**

B.31.13 `dragRidgeHeight`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % drag % dragRidgeHeight

Table B.1257: `dragRidgeHeight`: **MISSING**

B.31.14 `dragRidgeSeparation`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % drag % dragRidgeSeparation

Table B.1258: `dragRidgeSeparation`: **MISSING**

B.31.15 `dragKeelDepth`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % drag % dragKeelDepth

Table B.1259: `dragKeelDepth`: **MISSING**

B.31.16 `dragKeelSeparation`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % drag % dragKeelSeparation

Table B.1260: `dragKeelSeparation`: **MISSING**

B.31.17 `dragFloeLength`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % drag % dragFloeLength

Table B.1261: `dragFloeLength`: **MISSING**

B.31.18 dragFloeSeparation

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % drag % dragFloeSeparation

Table B.1262: dragFloeSeparation: **MISSING**

B.32 ponds

B.32.1 pondFreshWaterFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ponds % pondFreshWaterFlux

Table B.1263: pondFreshWaterFlux: **MISSING**

B.32.2 pondSnowDepthDifference

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ponds % pondSnowDepthDifference

Table B.1264: pondSnowDepthDifference: **MISSING**

B.32.3 pondLidMeltFluxFraction

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % ponds % pondLidMeltFluxFraction
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Table B.1265: pondLidMeltFluxFraction: **MISSING**

B.33 aerosols

B.33.1 atmosAerosolFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % aerosols % atmosAerosolFlux

Table B.1266: atmosAerosolFlux: **MISSING**

B.33.2 oceanAerosolFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAerosols nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % aerosols % oceanAerosolFlux

Table B.1267: oceanAerosolFlux: **MISSING**

B.33.3 aerosolMassExtinctionCrossSection

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSpectralIntervals maxAerosolType
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % aerosols % aerosolMassExtinction-CrossSection

Table B.1268: aerosolMassExtinctionCrossSection: **MISSING**

B.33.4 aerosolSingleScatterAlbedo

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSpectralIntervals maxAerosolType
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % aerosols % aerosolSingleScatterAlbedo

Table B.1269: aerosolSingleScatterAlbedo: **MISSING**

B.33.5 aerosolAsymmetryParameter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSpectralIntervals maxAerosolType
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % aerosols % aerosolAsymmetryParameter

Table B.1270: aerosolAsymmetryParameter: **MISSING**

B.33.6 modalMassExtinctionCrossSection

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSpectralIntervals nModall
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % aerosols % modalMassExtinctionCrossSection

Table B.1271: modalMassExtinctionCrossSection: **MISSING**

B.33.7 modalSingleScatterAlbedo

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSpectralIntervals nModall
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % aerosols % modalSingleScatterAlbedo

Table B.1272: modalSingleScatterAlbedo: **MISSING**

B.33.8 modalAsymmetryParameter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSpectralIntervals nModal1
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % aerosols % modalAsymmetryParameter

Table B.1273: modalAsymmetryParameter: **MISSING**

B.33.9 modalBCabsorptionParameter

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nSpectralIntervals nModal1 nModal2
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % aerosols % modalBCabsorptionParameter

Table B.1274: modalBCabsorptionParameter: **MISSING**

B.34 biogeochemistry

B.34.1 newlyFormedIce

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % newlyFormedIce

Table B.1275: newlyFormedIce: **MISSING**

B.34.2 rayleighCriteriaReal

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING

Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % rayleighCriteriaReal

Table B.1276: rayleighCriteriaReal: **MISSING**

B.34.3 [atmosBioFluxes](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % atmosBioFluxes

Table B.1277: atmosBioFluxes: **MISSING**

B.34.4 [atmosIceBioFluxes](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % atmosIceBioFluxes

Table B.1278: atmosIceBioFluxes: **MISSING**

B.34.5 [snowIceBioFluxes](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % snowIceBioFluxes

Table B.1279: snowIceBioFluxes: **MISSING**

B.34.6 [atmosBlackCarbonFlux](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxBCType nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % atmosBlackCarbon-Flux

Table B.1280: atmosBlackCarbonFlux: **MISSING**

B.34.7 [atmosDustFlux](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxDustType nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % atmosDustFlux

Table B.1281: atmosDustFlux: **MISSING**

B.34.8 [oceanBioFluxes](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m2/s
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanBioFluxes

Table B.1282: oceanBioFluxes: Tracers are ordered: diatom nitrogen, smallPlankton nitrogen, phaeocystis nitrogen, nitrate, polysaccharid carbon, lipid carbon, ammonium, silicate, DMSPp, DMSPd, DMS, Nonreactive nitrate, Protein nitrogen, dissolved iron in umol/m2/s, particulate iron in umol/m2/s, humic carbon, black carbon1 in mg/m2/s, black carbon2 in mg/m2/s, dust1 in mg/m2/s, dust2 in mg/m2/s, dust3 in mg/m2/s, dust4 in mg/m2/s

B.34.9 [oceanBioConcentrations](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m3
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % oceanBioConcentrations
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Table B.1283: oceanBioConcentrations: Tracers are ordered: diatom nitrogen, smallPlankton nitrogen, phaeocystis nitrogen, nitrate, polysaccharid carbon, lipid carbon, ammonium, silicate, DMSPp, DMSPd, DMS, Nonreactive nitrate, Protein nitrogen, dissolved iron in umol/m3, particulate iron in umol/m3, humic carbon, black carbon1 in mg/m3, black carbon2 in mg/m3, dust1 in mg/m3, dust2 in mg/m3, dust3 in mg/m3, dust4 in mg/m3

B.34.10 oceanAlgaeConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxAlgaeType nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % oceanAlgaeConc

Table B.1284: oceanAlgaeConc: **MISSING**

B.34.11 oceanDOCConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxDOCType nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % oceanDOCConc

Table B.1285: oceanDOCConc: **MISSING**

B.34.12 oceanDICConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxDICType nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % oceanDICConc

Table B.1286: oceanDICConc: **MISSING**

B.34.13 oceanDONConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxDONType nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanDONConc

Table B.1287: oceanDONConc: **MISSING**

B.34.14 oceanNitrateConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanNitrateConc

Table B.1288: oceanNitrateConc: **MISSING**

B.34.15 oceanSilicateConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanSilicateConc

Table B.1289: oceanSilicateConc: **MISSING**

B.34.16 oceanAmmoniumConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanAmmonium-Conc

Table B.1290: oceanAmmoniumConc: **MISSING**

B.34.17 [oceanDMSConc](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanDMSConc

Table B.1291: oceanDMSConc: **MISSING**

B.34.18 [oceanDMSPConc](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanDMSPConc

Table B.1292: oceanDMSPConc: **MISSING**

B.34.19 [oceanHumicsConc](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanHumicsConc

Table B.1293: oceanHumicsConc: **MISSING**

B.34.20 [oceanParticulateIronConc](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxIronType nCells Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % oceanParticulateIronConc

Table B.1294: oceanParticulateIronConc: **MISSING**

B.34.21 oceanDissolvedIronConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxIronType nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % oceanDissolvedIronConc

Table B.1295: oceanDissolvedIronConc: **MISSING**

B.34.22 oceanZAerosolConc

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxAerosolType nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % oceanZAerosolConc

Table B.1296: oceanZAerosolConc: **MISSING**

B.34.23 oceanAlgaeFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxAlgaeType nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % oceanAlgaeFlux

Table B.1297: oceanAlgaeFlux: **MISSING**

B.34.24 oceanDOCFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxDOCType nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanDOCFlux

Table B.1298: oceanDOCFlux: **MISSING**

B.34.25 oceanDICFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxDICType nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanDICFlux

Table B.1299: oceanDICFlux: **MISSING**

B.34.26 oceanDONFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxDONType nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanDONFlux

Table B.1300: oceanDONFlux: **MISSING**

B.34.27 oceanNitrateFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanNitrateFlux

Table B.1301: oceanNitrateFlux: **MISSING**

B.34.28 oceanSilicateFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanSilicateFlux

Table B.1302: oceanSilicateFlux: **MISSING****B.34.29 oceanAmmoniumFlux**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanAmmonium-Flux

Table B.1303: oceanAmmoniumFlux: **MISSING****B.34.30 oceanDMSFlux**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanDMSFlux

Table B.1304: oceanDMSFlux: **MISSING****B.34.31 oceanDMSPpFlux**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanDMSPpFlux

Table B.1305: oceanDMSPpFlux: **MISSING**

B.34.32 oceanDMSPdFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanDMSPdFlux

Table B.1306: oceanDMSPdFlux: **MISSING****B.34.33 oceanHumicsFlux**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanHumicsFlux

Table B.1307: oceanHumicsFlux: **MISSING****B.34.34 oceanParticulateIronFlux**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxIronType nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % oceanParticulateIronFlux

Table B.1308: oceanParticulateIronFlux: **MISSING****B.34.35 oceanDissolvedIronFlux**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxIronType nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % oceanDissolvedIronFlux
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Table B.1309: oceanDissolvedIronFlux: **MISSING**

B.34.36 oceanDustIronFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % oceanDustIronFlux

Table B.1310: oceanDustIronFlux: **MISSING**

B.34.37 bioTracerShortwave

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nShortwaveBio nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % bioTracerShortwave

Table B.1311: bioTracerShortwave: **MISSING**

B.34.38 bioPorosity

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP2 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % bioPorosity

Table B.1312: bioPorosity: **MISSING**

B.34.39 bioTemperature

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP2 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % bioTemperature

Table B.1313: bioTemperature: **MISSING**

B.34.40 **bioShortwaveFlux**

Type:	real
Units:	W/m ²
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % bioShortwaveFlux

Table B.1314: bioShortwaveFlux: Shortwave radiative flux on the vertical biology grid per category

B.34.41 **bioShortwaveFluxCell**

Type:	real
Units:	W/m ²
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % bioShortwaveFlux-Cell

Table B.1315: bioShortwaveFluxCell: Averaged cell shortwave radiative flux on the vertical biology grid

B.34.42 **bioDiffusivity**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % bioDiffusivity

Table B.1316: bioDiffusivity: **MISSING**

B.34.43 bioPermeability

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1 nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % bioPermeability

Table B.1317: bioPermeability: **MISSING**

B.34.44 zSalinityFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % zSalinityFlux

Table B.1318: zSalinityFlux: **MISSING**

B.34.45 zSalinityGDFlux

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % zSalinityGDFlux

Table B.1319: zSalinityGDFlux: **MISSING**

B.34.46 zSalinityFluxCat

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % zSalinityFluxCat

Table B.1320: zSalinityFluxCat: **MISSING**

B.34.47 `zSalinityGDFluxCat`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % zSalinityGDFlux-Cat

Table B.1321: `zSalinityGDFluxCat`: **MISSING**

B.34.48 `darcyVelocityBio`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % darcyVelocityBio

Table B.1322: `darcyVelocityBio`: **MISSING**

B.34.49 `brineTopChange`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % brineTopChange

Table B.1323: `brineTopChange`: **MISSING**

B.34.50 `brineBottomChange`

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % brineBottomChange
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Table B.1324: brineBottomChange: **MISSING**

B.34.51 **zSalinityIceDensity**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % zSalinityIceDensity

Table B.1325: zSalinityIceDensity: **MISSING**

B.34.52 **peakVerticalAlgalConc**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nAlgae nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % peakVerticalAlgalConc

Table B.1326: peakVerticalAlgalConc: **MISSING**

B.34.53 **netSpecificAlgalGrowthRate**

Type:	real
Units:	1/s
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % netSpecificAlgalGrowthRate

Table B.1327: netSpecificAlgalGrowthRate: Specific algal growth rate per grid cell

B.34.54 verticalNitrogenLosses

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP3 nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % verticalNitrogenLosses

Table B.1328: verticalNitrogenLosses: **MISSING**

B.34.55 netNitrateUptake

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ² /d
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % netNitrateUptake

Table B.1329: netNitrateUptake: Total rate of nitrate uptake by algae weighted by ice area

B.34.56 netAmmoniumUptake

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ² /d
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % netAmmoniumUptake

Table B.1330: netAmmoniumUptake: Total rate of ammonium uptake by algae weighted by ice area

B.34.57 primaryProduction

Type:	real
Units:	mg carbon/m ² /d
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % primaryProduction

Table B.1331: primaryProduction: Average total primary production in a grid cell

B.34.58 [totalSkeletalAlgae](#)

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % totalSkeletalAlgae

Table B.1332: totalSkeletalAlgae: **MISSING**

B.34.59 [totalVerticalBiologyIce](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m2
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % totalVerticalBiologyIce

Table B.1333: totalVerticalBiologyIce: Tracers are ordered: diatom nitrogen, smallPlankton nitrogen, phaeocystis nitrogen, nitrate, polysaccharid carbon, lipid carbon, ammonium, silicate, DMSPp, DMSPd, DMS, Nonreactive nitrate, Protein nitrogen, dissolved iron in umol/m2, particulate iron in umol/m2, humic carbon, black carbon1 in mg/m2, black carbon2 in mg/m2, dust1 in mg/m2, dust2 in mg/m2, dust3 in mg/m2, dust4 in mg/m2

B.34.60 [totalVerticalBiologySnow](#)

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m2
Dimension:	nZBGCTracers nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % totalVerticalBiologySnow

Table B.1334: totalVerticalBiologySnow: Tracers are ordered: diatom nitrogen, smallPlankton nitrogen, phaeocystis nitrogen, nitrate, polysaccharid carbon, lipid carbon, ammonium, silicate, DMSP_p, DMSP_d, DMS, Nonreactive nitrate, Protein nitrogen, dissolved iron in umol/m², particulate iron in umol/m², humic carbon, black carbon1 in mg/m², black carbon2 in mg/m², dust1 in mg/m², dust2 in mg/m², dust3 in mg/m², dust4 in mg/m²

B.34.61 totalVerticalSalinity

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % totalVerticalSalinity

Table B.1335: totalVerticalSalinity: **MISSING**

B.34.62 totalChlorophyll

Type:	real
Units:	mg/m ²
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % totalChlorophyll

Table B.1336: totalChlorophyll: Ice integrated chlorophyll concentration per cell

B.34.63 totalNitrate

Type:	real
Units:	mmol/m ³
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % biogeochemistry % totalNitrate

Table B.1337: totalNitrate: Ice integrated nitrate concentration per cell

B.34.64 netBrineHeight

Type:	real
Units:	m
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % netBrineHeight

Table B.1338: netBrineHeight: Cell average brine height

B.34.65 biologyGrid

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP2
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % biologyGrid

Table B.1339: biologyGrid: **MISSING****B.34.66 interfaceBiologyGrid**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nBioLayersP1
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % interfaceBiology-Grid

Table B.1340: interfaceBiologyGrid: **MISSING****B.34.67 verticalGrid**

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayersP1
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % verticalGrid

Table B.1341: verticalGrid: **MISSING**

B.34.68 interfaceGrid

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayersP1
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % interfaceGrid

Table B.1342: interfaceGrid: **MISSING**

B.34.69 verticalShortwaveGrid

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayersP1
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % verticalShortwave-Grid

Table B.1343: verticalShortwaveGrid: **MISSING**

B.34.70 carbonToNitrogenRatioAlgae

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxAlgaeType
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % carbonToNitrogen-RatioAlgae

Table B.1344: carbonToNitrogenRatioAlgae: **MISSING**

B.34.71 carbonToNitrogenRatioDON

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	maxDONTtype
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % biogeochemistry % carbonToNitrogen-RatioDON
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Table B.1345: carbonToNitrogenRatioDON: **MISSING**

B.35 initial

B.35.1 initialSalinityProfile

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayersP1 nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % initial % initialSalinityProfile

Table B.1346: initialSalinityProfile: **MISSING**

B.35.2 initialMeltingTemperatureProfile

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nIceLayersP1 nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % initial % initialMeltingTemperature-Profile

Table B.1347: initialMeltingTemperatureProfile: **MISSING**

B.35.3 categoryThicknessLimits

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCategoriesP1
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % initial % categoryThicknessLimits

Table B.1348: categoryThicknessLimits: **MISSING**

B.36 regions

B.36.1 regionCellMasks

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nRegions nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % regions % regionCellMasks

Table B.1349: regionCellMasks: **MISSING**

B.36.2 regionVertexMasks

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nRegions nVertices
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % regions % regionVertexMasks

Table B.1350: regionVertexMasks: **MISSING**

B.36.3 regionNames

Type:	text
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nRegions
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % regions % regionNames

Table B.1351: regionNames: **MISSING**

B.37 diagnostics

B.37.1 xtime

Type:	text
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % diagnostics % xtime
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Table B.1352: xtime: **MISSING**

B.37.2 simulationStartTime

Type:	text
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % diagnostics % simulationStartTime

Table B.1353: simulationStartTime: **MISSING**

B.37.3 daysSinceStartOfSim

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % diagnostics % daysSinceStartOfSim

Table B.1354: daysSinceStartOfSim: **MISSING**

B.37.4 meltOnset

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % diagnostics % meltOnset

Table B.1355: meltOnset: **MISSING**

B.37.5 freezeOnset

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING

Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % diagnostics % freezeOnset

Table B.1356: freezeOnset: **MISSING**

B.37.6 iceAreaTendencyTransport

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % diagnostics % iceAreaTendencyTransport

Table B.1357: iceAreaTendencyTransport: **MISSING**

B.37.7 iceVolumeTendencyTransport

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % diagnostics % iceVolumeTendencyTransport

Table B.1358: iceVolumeTendencyTransport: **MISSING**

B.37.8 iceAgeTendencyTransport

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % diagnostics % iceAgeTendencyTransport

Table B.1359: iceAgeTendencyTransport: **MISSING**

B.37.9 iceAreaTendencyThermodynamics

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % diagnostics % iceAreaTendencyThermodynamics

Table B.1360: iceAreaTendencyThermodynamics: **MISSING**

B.37.10 iceVolumeTendencyThermodynamics

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % diagnostics % iceVolumeTendencyThermodynamics

Table B.1361: iceVolumeTendencyThermodynamics: **MISSING**

B.37.11 iceAgeTendencyThermodynamics

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % diagnostics % iceAgeTendencyThermodynamics

Table B.1362: iceAgeTendencyThermodynamics: **MISSING**

B.37.12 freezingMeltingPotentialInitial

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blocklist % diagnostics % freezingMeltingPotentialInitial
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Table B.1363: freezingMeltingPotentialInitial: **MISSING**

B.37.13 timeAverageTestVariable

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % diagnostics % timeAverageTestVariable

Table B.1364: timeAverageTestVariable: **MISSING**

B.38 testing_system_test

B.38.1 testArrayRegression

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % testing_system_test % testArrayRegression

Table B.1365: testArrayRegression: **MISSING**

B.38.2 testArrayParallelism

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % testing_system_test % testArrayParallelism

Table B.1366: testArrayParallelism: **MISSING**

B.38.3 testArrayRestartability

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % testing_system_test % testArrayRestartability

Table B.1367: testArrayRestartability: **MISSING**

B.39 pointLocations

B.39.1 pointCellGlobalID

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nPoints
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % pointLocations % pointCellGlobalID

Table B.1368: pointCellGlobalID: List of global cell IDs in point set.

B.39.2 pointCellLocalID

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nPoints
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % pointLocations % pointCellLocalID

Table B.1369: pointCellLocalID: List of local cell IDs in point set.

B.39.3 indexToPointCellLocalID

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nPoints

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % pointLocations % indexToPointCellLocalID

Table B.1370: indexToPointCellLocalID: Index to list of local cell IDs in point set.

B.39.4 [pointVertexGlobalID](#)

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nPoints
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % pointLocations % pointVertexGlobalID

Table B.1371: pointVertexGlobalID: List of global vertex IDs in point set.

B.39.5 [pointVertexLocalID](#)

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nPoints
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % pointLocations % pointVertexLocalID

Table B.1372: pointVertexLocalID: List of local vertex IDs in point set.

B.39.6 [indexToPointVertexLocalID](#)

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nPoints
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % pointLocations % indexToPointVertexLocalID

Table B.1373: indexToPointVertexLocalID: Index to list of local vertex IDs in point set.

B.39.7 pointNames

Type:	text
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nPoints
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % pointLocations % pointNames

Table B.1374: pointNames: The names of each point.

B.39.8 pointGroupNames

Type:	text
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nPointGroups
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % pointLocations % pointGroupNames

Table B.1375: pointGroupNames: The names of each point group.

B.39.9 nPointsInGroup

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nPointGroups
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % pointLocations % nPointsInGroup

Table B.1376: nPointsInGroup: The number of points in each point group.

B.39.10 pointsInGroup

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	maxPointsInGroup nPointGroups
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % pointLocations % pointsInGroup

Table B.1377: pointsInGroup: The indices of each point in a each group.

B.39.11 **xPoint**

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nPoints
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % pointLocations % xPoint

Table B.1378: xPoint: X Coordinate in cartesian space of point locations.

B.39.12 **yPoint**

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nPoints
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % pointLocations % yPoint

Table B.1379: yPoint: Y Coordinate in cartesian space of point locations.

B.39.13 **zPoint**

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	nPoints
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % pointLocations % zPoint

Table B.1380: zPoint: Z Coordinate in cartesian space of point locations.

B.39.14 **latPoint**

Type:	real
Units:	radians
Dimension:	nPoints
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % pointLocations % latPoint

Table B.1381: latPoint: Latitude of point locations.

B.39.15 lonPoint

Type:	real
Units:	radians
Dimension:	nPoints
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % pointLocations % lonPoint

Table B.1382: lonPoint: Longitude of point locations.

B.40 highFrequencyOutputAM

B.40.1 iceAreaCellCategory1

Type:	real
Units:	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % highFrequencyOutputAM % iceArea-CellCategory1

Table B.1383: iceAreaCellCategory1: area of ice in category 1

B.41 temperaturesAM

B.41.1 iceTemperature

Type:	real
Units:	degrees C
Dimension:	nIceLayers nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % temperaturesAM % iceTemperature

Table B.1384: iceTemperature: Ice layer temperature

B.41.2 snowTemperature

Type:	real
Units:	degrees C
Dimension:	nSnowLayers nCategories nCells Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % temperaturesAM % snowTemperature

Table B.1385: snowTemperature: snow layer temperature

B.42 regionalStatisticsAM

B.42.1 uVelocityCell

Type:	real
Units:	m/s
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % regionalStatisticsAM % uVelocityCell

Table B.1386: uVelocityCell: U ice velocity on cells

B.42.2 vVelocityCell

Type:	real
Units:	m/s
Dimension:	nCells
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % regionalStatisticsAM % vVelocityCell

Table B.1387: vVelocityCell: V ice velocity on cells

B.42.3 totalIceArea

Type:	real
Units:	km ²
Dimension:	nRegions Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % regionalStatisticsAM % totalIceArea

Table B.1388: totalIceArea: Total sea-ice area by region

B.42.4 `totalIceExtent`

Type:	real
Units:	km ²
Dimension:	nRegions Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % regionalStatisticsAM % totalIceExtent

Table B.1389: `totalIceExtent`: Total sea-ice extent by region

B.42.5 `totalIceVolume`

Type:	real
Units:	km ³
Dimension:	nRegions Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % regionalStatisticsAM % totalIceVolume

Table B.1390: `totalIceVolume`: Total sea-ice volume by region

B.42.6 `totalSnowVolume`

Type:	real
Units:	km ³
Dimension:	nRegions Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % regionalStatisticsAM % totalSnowVolume

Table B.1391: `totalSnowVolume`: Total snow volume by region

B.42.7 `totalKineticEnergy`

Type:	real
Units:	J
Dimension:	nRegions Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % regionalStatisticsAM % totalKineticEnergy

Table B.1392: totalKineticEnergy: Total kinetic energy by region

B.42.8 rmsIceSpeed

Type:	real
Units:	m/s
Dimension:	nRegions Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % regionalStatisticsAM % rmsIceSpeed

Table B.1393: rmsIceSpeed: RMS ice speed by region

B.42.9 averageAlbedo

Type:	real
Units:	—
Dimension:	nRegions Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % regionalStatisticsAM % averageAlbedo

Table B.1394: averageAlbedo: Average albedo by region

B.42.10 maximumIceVolume

Type:	real
Units:	km ²
Dimension:	nRegions Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % regionalStatisticsAM % maximumIceVolume

Table B.1395: maximumIceVolume: Maximum sea-ice volume by region

B.42.11 maximumIceVolumeLocked

Type:	real
Units:	km ²

Dimension:	nRegions Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % regionalStatisticsAM % maximumIceVolumeLocked

Table B.1396: maximumIceVolumeLocked: Maximum sea-ice volume by region for dynamically locked cells

B.42.12 maximumIceVolumeNotLocked

Type:	real
Units:	km ²
Dimension:	nRegions Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % regionalStatisticsAM % maximumIceVolumeNotLocked

Table B.1397: maximumIceVolumeNotLocked: Maximum sea-ice volume by region for non-dynamically locked cells

B.42.13 maximumIcePressure

Type:	real
Units:	kN/m
Dimension:	nRegions Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % regionalStatisticsAM % maximumIcePressure

Table B.1398: maximumIcePressure: Maximum sea-ice pressure by region

B.42.14 maximumIceSpeed

Type:	real
Units:	m/s
Dimension:	nRegions Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % regionalStatisticsAM % maximumIceSpeed

Table B.1399: maximumIceSpeed: Maximum sea-ice speed by region

B.43 `ridgingDiagnosticsAM`

B.43.1 `levelIceAreaAverage`

Type:	real
Units:	–
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridgingDiagnosticsAM % levelIceAreaAverage

Table B.1400: `levelIceAreaAverage`: level ice cell fraction

B.43.2 `ridgedIceAreaAverage`

Type:	real
Units:	–
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridgingDiagnosticsAM % ridgedIceAreaAverage

Table B.1401: `ridgedIceAreaAverage`: ridged ice cell fraction

B.43.3 `levelIceVolumeAverage`

Type:	real
Units:	–
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridgingDiagnosticsAM % levelIceVolumeAverage

Table B.1402: `levelIceVolumeAverage`: level ice cell volume

B.43.4 `ridgedIceVolumeAverage`

Type:	real
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Units:	–
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % ridgingDiagnosticsAM % ridgedIceVolumeAverage

Table B.1403: ridgedIceVolumeAverage: ridged ice cell volume

B.44 conservationCheckAM

B.44.1 performConservationPrecompute

Type:	integer
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % conservationCheckAM % performConservationPrecompute

Table B.1404: performConservationPrecompute: **MISSING**

B.45 conservationCheckEnergyAM

B.45.1 initialEnergy

Type:	real
Units:	J
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % conservationCheckEnergyAM % initialEnergy

Table B.1405: initialEnergy: Total initial energy of ice and snow

B.45.2 finalEnergy

Type:	real
Units:	J
Dimension:	Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckEnergyAM % finalEnergy

Table B.1406: finalEnergy: Total final energy of ice and snow

B.45.3 energyChange

Type:	real
Units:	J
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckEnergyAM % energyChange

Table B.1407: energyChange: Total energy change of ice and snow during time step

B.45.4 netEnergyFlux

Type:	real
Units:	W
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckEnergyAM % netEnergyFlux

Table B.1408: netEnergyFlux: Net energy flux to ice

B.45.5 absoluteEnergyError

Type:	real
Units:	J
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckEnergyAM % absoluteEnergyError

Table B.1409: absoluteEnergyError: Absolute energy conservation error

B.45.6 `relativeEnergyError`

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckEnergyAM % relativeEnergyError

Table B.1410: `relativeEnergyError`: Relative energy conservation error

B.45.7 `accumulatedSurfaceHeatFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckEnergyAM % accumulatedSurfaceHeatFlux

Table B.1411: `accumulatedSurfaceHeatFlux`: **MISSING**

B.45.8 `accumulatedOceanHeatFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckEnergyAM % accumulatedOceanHeatFlux

Table B.1412: `accumulatedOceanHeatFlux`: **MISSING**

B.45.9 `accumulatedFreezingPotential`

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent

Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckEnergyAM % accumulatedFreezingPotential
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Table B.1413: accumulatedFreezingPotential: **MISSING**

B.45.10 accumulatedSnowfallHeat

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckEnergyAM % accumulatedSnowfallHeat

Table B.1414: accumulatedSnowfallHeat: **MISSING**

B.45.11 accumulatedLatentHeat

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckEnergyAM % accumulatedLatentHeat

Table B.1415: accumulatedLatentHeat: **MISSING**

B.46 conservationCheckMassAM

B.46.1 initialMass

Type:	real
Units:	kg
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckMassAM % initial-Mass

Table B.1416: initialMass: Total initial mass of ice and snow

B.46.2 `finalMass`

Type:	real
Units:	kg
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckMassAM % final-Mass

Table B.1417: `finalMass`: Total final mass of ice and snow

B.46.3 `massChange`

Type:	real
Units:	kg
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckMassAM % mass-Change

Table B.1418: `massChange`: Total mass change of ice and snow during time step

B.46.4 `netMassFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	kg/s
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckMassAM % net-MassFlux

Table B.1419: `netMassFlux`: Net mass flux to ice

B.46.5 `absoluteMassError`

Type:	real
Units:	kg
Dimension:	Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % conservationCheckMassAM % absoluteMassError

Table B.1420: absoluteMassError: Absolute mass conservation error

B.46.6 [relativeMassError](#)

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % conservationCheckMassAM % relativeMassError

Table B.1421: relativeMassError: Relative mass conservation error

B.46.7 [accumulatedRainfallRate](#)

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % conservationCheckMassAM % accumulatedRainfallRate

Table B.1422: accumulatedRainfallRate: **MISSING**

B.46.8 [accumulatedSnowfallRate](#)

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % conservationCheckMassAM % accumulatedSnowfallRate

Table B.1423: accumulatedSnowfallRate: **MISSING**

B.46.9 `accumulatedEvaporation`

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckMassAM % accumulatedEvaporation

Table B.1424: `accumulatedEvaporation`: **MISSING**

B.46.10 `accumulatedFreshWater`

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckMassAM % accumulatedFreshWater

Table B.1425: `accumulatedFreshWater`: **MISSING**

B.46.11 `accumulatedFrazilWater`

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckMassAM % accumulatedFrazilWater

Table B.1426: `accumulatedFrazilWater`: **MISSING**

B.47 `conservationCheckSaltAM`

B.47.1 `initialSalt`

Type:	real
Units:	kg
Dimension:	Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckSaltAM % initial-Salt

Table B.1427: initialSalt: Total initial salt of ice and snow

B.47.2 finalSalt

Type:	real
Units:	kg
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckSaltAM % finalSalt

Table B.1428: finalSalt: Total final salt of ice and snow

B.47.3 saltChange

Type:	real
Units:	kg
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckSaltAM % saltChange

Table B.1429: saltChange: Total salt change of ice and snow during time step

B.47.4 netSaltFlux

Type:	real
Units:	kg/s
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckSaltAM % netSalt-Flux

Table B.1430: netSaltFlux: Net salt flux to ice

B.47.5 `absoluteSaltError`

Type:	real
Units:	kg
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckSaltAM % absoluteSaltError

Table B.1431: `absoluteSaltError`: Absolute salt conservation error

B.47.6 `relativeSaltError`

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckSaltAM % relativeSaltError

Table B.1432: `relativeSaltError`: Relative salt conservation error

B.47.7 `accumulatedOceanSaltFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckSaltAM % accumulatedOceanSaltFlux

Table B.1433: `accumulatedOceanSaltFlux`: **MISSING**

B.47.8 `accumulatedFrazilSaltFlux`

Type:	real
Units:	None
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % conservationCheckSaltAM % accumulatedFrazilSaltFlux

Table B.1434: accumulatedFrazilSaltFlux: **MISSING**

B.48 geographicalVectorsAM

B.48.1 uVelocityGeo

Type:	real
Units:	m/s
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % geographicalVectorsAM % uVelocity-Geo

Table B.1435: uVelocityGeo: True eastwards ice velocity

B.48.2 vVelocityGeo

Type:	real
Units:	m/s
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % geographicalVectorsAM % vVelocity-Geo

Table B.1436: vVelocityGeo: True northwards ice velocity

B.48.3 stressDivergenceUGeo

Type:	real
Units:	N/m ²
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % geographicalVectorsAM % stressDivergenceUGeo

Table B.1437: stressDivergenceUGeo: True eastwards stress divergence

B.48.4 `stressDivergenceVGeo`

Type:	real
Units:	N/m ²
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % geographicalVectorsAM % stressDivergenceVGeo

Table B.1438: `stressDivergenceVGeo`: True northwards stress divergence

B.48.5 `airStressVertexUGeo`

Type:	real
Units:	N/m ²
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % geographicalVectorsAM % airStressVertexUGeo

Table B.1439: `airStressVertexUGeo`: True eastwards sea ice-air stress

B.48.6 `airStressVertexVGeo`

Type:	real
Units:	N/m ²
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % geographicalVectorsAM % airStressVertexVGeo

Table B.1440: `airStressVertexVGeo`: True northwards sea ice-air stress

B.48.7 `oceanStressUGeo`

Type:	real
Units:	N/m ²
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % geographicalVectorsAM % oceanStressUGeo

Table B.1441: oceanStressUGeo: True eastwards sea ice-ocean stress

B.48.8 oceanStressVGeo

Type:	real
Units:	N/m ²
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % geographicalVectorsAM % oceanStressVGeo

Table B.1442: oceanStressVGeo: True northwards sea ice-ocean stress

B.48.9 surfaceTiltForceUGeo

Type:	real
Units:	N/m ²
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % geographicalVectorsAM % surfaceTilt- ForceUGeo

Table B.1443: surfaceTiltForceUGeo: True eastwards sea surface tilt stress

B.48.10 surfaceTiltForceVGeo

Type:	real
Units:	N/m ²
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % geographicalVectorsAM % surfaceTilt- ForceVGeo

Table B.1444: surfaceTiltForceVGeo: True northwards sea surface tilt stress

B.48.11 uOceanVelocityVertexGeo

Type:	real
Units:	m/s
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % geographicalVectorsAM % uOceanVelocityVertexGeo

Table B.1445: uOceanVelocityVertexGeo: True eastwards ocean velocity

B.48.12 vOceanVelocityVertexGeo

Type:	real
Units:	m/s
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % geographicalVectorsAM % vOceanVelocityVertexGeo

Table B.1446: vOceanVelocityVertexGeo: True northwards ocean velocity

B.49 loadBalanceAM

B.49.1 nCellsProcWithSeaIce

Type:	integer
Units:	—
Dimension:	nProcs Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % loadBalanceAM % nCellsProcWithSeaIce

Table B.1447: nCellsProcWithSeaIce: Number of cells with sea ice present per processor

B.49.2 nCellsProc

Type:	integer
Units:	—
Dimension:	nProcs
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % loadBalanceAM % nCellsProc

Table B.1448: nCellsProc: Number of cells per processor

B.50 maximumIcePresenceAM

B.50.1 maximumIcePresence

Type:	integer
Units:	–
Dimension:	nMonths nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % maximumIcePresenceAM % maximumIcePresence

Table B.1449: maximumIcePresence: Maximum extent of sea-ice for the simulation divided by months

B.51 miscellaneousAM

B.51.1 bulkSalinity

Type:	real
Units:	ppt
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % miscellaneousAM % bulkSalinity

Table B.1450: bulkSalinity: Bulk salinity of ice in a cell

B.51.2 broadbandAlbedo

Type:	real
Units:	–
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % miscellaneousAM % broadbandAlbedo

Table B.1451: broadbandAlbedo: snow/sea ice broadband albedo

B.51.3 coriolisStressVertexU

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % miscellaneousAM % coriolisStressVertexU

Table B.1452: coriolisStressVertexU: Coriolis stress in U direction

B.51.4 coriolisStressVertexV

Type:	real
Units:	MISSING
Dimension:	nVertices Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % miscellaneousAM % coriolisStressVertexV

Table B.1453: coriolisStressVertexV: Coriolis stress in V direction

B.52 areaVariablesAM

B.52.1 snowfallRateInitialArea

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % areaVariablesAM % snowfallRateInitialArea

Table B.1454: snowfallRateInitialArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.52.2 rainfallRateInitialArea

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time

Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % areaVariablesAM % rainfallRateInitialArea

Table B.1455: rainfallRateInitialArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.52.3 absorbedShortwaveFluxInitialArea

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % areaVariablesAM % absorbedShortwaveFluxInitialArea

Table B.1456: absorbedShortwaveFluxInitialArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.52.4 latentHeatFluxInitialArea

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % areaVariablesAM % latentHeatFluxInitialArea

Table B.1457: latentHeatFluxInitialArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.52.5 sensibleHeatFluxInitialArea

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % areaVariablesAM % sensibleHeatFluxInitialArea

Table B.1458: sensibleHeatFluxInitialArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.52.6 [longwaveUpInitialArea](#)

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % areaVariablesAM % longwaveUpInitialArea

Table B.1459: longwaveUpInitialArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.52.7 [evaporativeWaterFluxInitialArea](#)

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % areaVariablesAM % evaporativeWaterFluxInitialArea

Table B.1460: evaporativeWaterFluxInitialArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.52.8 [surfaceHeatFluxInitialArea](#)

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % areaVariablesAM % surfaceHeatFluxInitialArea

Table B.1461: surfaceHeatFluxInitialArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.52.9 [surfaceConductiveFluxInitialArea](#)

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % areaVariablesAM % surfaceConductiveFluxInitialArea

Table B.1462: surfaceConductiveFluxInitialArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.52.10 [surfaceHeatFluxCategoryInitialArea](#)

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % areaVariablesAM % surfaceHeatFlux-CategoryInitialArea

Table B.1463: surfaceHeatFluxCategoryInitialArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.52.11 [surfaceConductiveFluxCategoryInitialArea](#)

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % areaVariablesAM % surfaceConductiveFluxCategoryInitialArea

Table B.1464: surfaceConductiveFluxCategoryInitialArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.52.12 [latentHeatFluxCategoryInitialArea](#)

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % areaVariablesAM % latentHeatFlux-CategoryInitialArea

Table B.1465: latentHeatFluxCategoryInitialArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.52.13 [sensibleHeatFluxCategoryInitialArea](#)

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % areaVariablesAM % sensibleHeatFlux-CategoryInitialArea

Table B.1466: sensibleHeatFluxCategoryInitialArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.53 pondDiagnosticsAM

B.53.1 meltPondArea

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % pondDiagnosticsAM % meltPondArea

Table B.1467: meltPondArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.53.2 meltPondAreaFinalArea

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % pondDiagnosticsAM % meltPondArea-FinalArea

Table B.1468: meltPondAreaFinalArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.53.3 meltPondDepth

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % pondDiagnosticsAM % meltPond-Depth

Table B.1469: meltPondDepth: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.53.4 meltPondDepthFinalArea

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % pondDiagnosticsAM % meltPond-DepthFinalArea

Table B.1470: meltPondDepthFinalArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.53.5 meltPondLidThickness

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % pondDiagnosticsAM % melt-PondLidThickness

Table B.1471: meltPondLidThickness: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.53.6 meltPondLidThicknessFinalArea

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % pondDiagnosticsAM % melt-PondLidThicknessFinalArea

Table B.1472: meltPondLidThicknessFinalArea: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.53.7 meltPondDepthCategory

Type:	real
Units:	UNITS HERE
Dimension:	nCategories nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % pondDiagnosticsAM % meltPond-DepthCategory

Table B.1473: meltPondDepthCategory: DESCRIPTION HERE

B.54 iceShelvesAM

B.54.1 iceAreaOverIceShelves

Type:	real
Units:	—
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % iceShelvesAM % iceAreaOverIceShelves

Table B.1474: iceAreaOverIceShelves: Total ice area present where ice shelves exist

B.55 icePresentAM

B.55.1 icePresent

Type:	real
Units:	—
Dimension:	nCells Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blacklist % icePresentAM % icePresent

Table B.1475: icePresent: 1.0 if ice present, 0.0 if ice not present

B.56 timeSeriesStatsAM

B.56.1 timeSeriesStatsOneString

Type:	text
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Units:	unitless
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % timeSeriesStatsAM % timeSeriesStatsOneString

Table B.1476: timeSeriesStatsOneString: **MISSING**

B.56.2 timeSeriesStatsOneInteger

Type:	integer
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % timeSeriesStatsAM % timeSeriesStatsOneInteger

Table B.1477: timeSeriesStatsOneInteger: **MISSING**

B.56.3 timeSeriesStatsOneReal

Type:	real
Units:	unitless
Dimension:	Time
Persistence:	persistent
Location in code:	domain % blocklist % timeSeriesStatsAM % timeSeriesStatsOneReal

Table B.1478: timeSeriesStatsOneReal: **MISSING**